

THE BUSINESS CASE FOR CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY:
CAN LUXURY AND FASHION BRANDS BE SUSTAINABLE FROM CONSUMER
PERSPECTIVE?

NINA VUKAS

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted before for any other academic award.

Nina Vukas

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Abstract

Purpose - Luxury fashion managers need to have a better understanding of the factors that can foster and hamper sustainable luxury and fashion consumption in order to design advanced product and marketing strategies, communicate brand sustainability attributes without inducing undesirable effects and address corporate social responsibility (CSR) implementation strategically. It is necessary for reaping the financial benefits of social responsibility investments and building long-lasting relationships with ethically mindful and responsible luxury fashion consumers.

Design/methodology - Using the convenience and voluntary response sampling methods, 453 survey responses were collected online from self-reported luxury fashion consumers. Data were analysed using the softwares SmartPLS 4 and SPSS 29 to test and evaluate the relationships between the variables in the study.

Findings - The findings of this study indicate that consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability and perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability negatively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

This study proposes that consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands are the strongest predictor of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands, followed by consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands, awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability and expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability. Consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands differ based on gender in a way that male and female consumers have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than gender-neutral consumers.

Implications - The findings of this study provide theoretical contributions to the academic literature on corporate social responsibility and academic knowledge on sustainable consumer behaviour in a luxury fashion context. The findings can help managers to improve their decision-making in designing and marketing sustainable luxury fashion brands.

Originality/value - This study is among the first to follow an integrative approach in studying sustainable consumer behaviour in the context of luxury fashion. This study is the first to examine the link between the dimensions of sustainability and luxury fashion marketing based on measuring consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability and linking them with consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The study is the first to examine how consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

Keywords: Sustainability, sustainable and circular luxury fashion brands, consumer research

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1. Overview

This chapter discusses the rationale for studying corporate social responsibility and conducting research on corporate social responsibility in the luxury and fashion industry from the consumer's perspective and the background and the purpose of the study. The chapter presents the research questions and objectives of the study and the structure of the thesis.

1.2. Rationale for Studying Corporate Social Responsibility

In the contemporary global business environment, companies regardless of their size and the industry in which they operate are not spared from public condemnation and scandals because of their unethical behaviour (Schiopoiu Burlea, Nastase and Dobrea, 2013). However, as a potential source of the company's competitiveness, corporate social responsibility has become a controversial issue for researchers and practitioners (Garriga and Melé, 2004; Porter and Kramer, 2006). The academic literature and business practice have not provided convincing evidence if companies can ameliorate their competitiveness by implementing social responsibility policies or if the competitiveness of an organisation leads to success in social responsibility performance (Wagner and Schaltegger, 2003; Reinhardt and Stavins, 2010). The prevalent discussion among scholars is whether companies have an ethical duty to succeed in corporate social responsibility performance or companies' engagement in corporate social responsibility should be used instrumentally for maximising profits (Carroll, 1999; Masaka, 2008; Spitzbeck, 2013; Hamidu, Haron and Amran, 2015).

Proponents of corporate social responsibility argue that ignoring social responsibility generates adverse influences on the company's long-term profitability, competitiveness and power. As Davis' (1960) Iron Law of Responsibility suggests, companies that avoid to behave responsibly are likely to lose power and profits allowed by society in the long run (Carroll, 1999). The contemporary social responsibility field has been influenced by Porter and Kramer's (2006) principle of creating shared value, which implies that maintaining long-term competitiveness necessitates the accomplishment of both economic and social success (Moon *et al.*, 2011; Bakan, 2015). This is reflected in the emerging practice of

investors to make decisions on purchasing stock in financial markets based on profitability and social responsibility, which indicates the importance of addressing the interests and expectations of various stakeholders in resource allocation decisions (Ioannou and Serafeim, 2015). Economic and social goals are not deemed opposite in the long run but the nature of the interrelation between corporate social responsibility and economic performance remains vague (Vilanova, Lozano and Arenas, 2009).

It has been argued that consumers are the most powerful stakeholder group for boosting or preventing sustainable development because of having the power to decide or refuse to purchase products and services provided by truly sustainable and transparent companies (Morrison and Bridwell, 2011; Raczkowski, Sulkowski and Fijalkowska, 2016). Consumers' positive attitudes towards social responsibility are seldom transformed into sustainable consumption (Newhouse, 1990; Dembkowski and Hanmer-Lloyd, 1994; Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002; White, Habib and Hardisty, 2019). Because of driving consumers' behaviours, consumers' emotions, motives, opinions, expectations, perceptions, judgements and attitudes are as important as their purchase intentions, loyalty or word of mouth (Shrum, McCarty and Lowrey, 1995; Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004; Du, Bhattacharya and Sen, 2007; Du, Bhattacharya and Sen, 2010; Silverman, 2011). Accordingly, consumers' views on corporate social responsibility should be regarded as momentous in examining factors that can encourage more responsible business operations (Lantos, 2001; Lee and Shin, 2010; Servera-Francés and Piqueras-Tomás, 2019).

1.3. Rationale for Studying Corporate Social Responsibility in the Luxury and Fashion Industry

A new market for sustainable fashion has been developing through raising consumers' awareness of the exigency of solving social responsibility problems in the global fashion supply chain prompted by the ubiquitous activism regarding fashion brands' failure to improve transparency on conducting their business operations and environmental and social initiatives. Studies on sustainable fashion highlighted the manufacturing side of the emerging market. Scarce consumer research in the field put emphasis on finding solutions for excessive consumption rather than a holistic understanding of sustainable fashion as part of the slow fashion movement (Fletcher, 2010; Niinimäki, 2010; Niinimäki and Hassi, 2011; Henninger, Alevizou and Oates, 2016; Lundblad and Davies, 2016).

The fashion industry has a negative reputation in terms of human, labour and animal rights and it is regarded as one of the most polluting industries globally (Garcia-Torres, Rey-Garcia and Albareda-Vivo, 2017; White, Nielsen and Valentini, 2017). Garment workers are even forced to work in unsafe conditions, which is best manifested by the collapse of the Rana Plaza building in 2013 when more than a thousand workers died and over two thousand people were seriously injured in Bangladesh. This tragedy showed the magnitude of impacts created by the fashion industry and it became a reminder and symbol that the fashion industry needs thorough social responsibility reforms (Rutter, Armstrong and Cano, 2017).

The legitimacy theory of corporate social responsibility explains that companies engage in corporate social responsibility to legitimise their business in society. Social responsibility engagement is often manifested as responsiveness to unfavourable events in order to alleviate the adverse effects of ignoring social responsibility on profitability and as compliance with other companies' social responsibility practices (Branco and Rodrigues, 2008). The luxury fashion brand Dolce and Gabbana came under the spotlight concerning the accusations of racism and disrespect towards Chinese culture caused by inadequate advertising, which led to boycotting the brand in China and Hong Kong and it negatively influenced the company's long-term profitability (Galvan, 2018). The luxury fashion company Burberry got a considerable deal of public attention because of incinerating overflow inventory to protect the brand's exclusivity through the prevention of selling products to 'the wrong people'. The company announced to stop this practice because consumers decided to boycott Burberry for such wastefulness while the members of the UK Parliament demanded from the British government to prohibit such practices (Lieber, 2018). In accordance with the institutional theory of corporate social responsibility, different forces within the institutional environment influence companies to acknowledge their responsibilities and be accountable for the consequences of their business operations (Campbell, 2007).

According to Changing Markets Foundation, which is a campaigning organisation for disclosing corporate behaviours, most fashion brands in Europe and the UK do not provide trustworthy information on how to reduce the harmful effects of their activities on the environment and society. Fashion brands commonly utilise misleading and greenwashing sustainability marketing by making false sustainability claims and promises in order to profit from consumers' concerns for the environment and social betterment. For example,

the luxury brand Burberry has been called out to be among fashion brands that lack transparency and have failed to provide credible evidence to verify their sustainability labels and claims (Ho, 2021). Fashion companies are under investigation for misleading sustainable marketing and the fashion brand Hennes and Mauritz has been recently sued for greenwashing and false sustainability credentials. It is likely that this case can be a watershed moment that will have a decisive influence on the direction of socially responsible actions within the fashion industry (Wicker, 2022). It can be argued that luxury and fashion companies cannot longer disregard corporate social responsibility in managing and performing their business activities to earn profits (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015; Henninger *et al.*, 2017).

Conducting research on corporate social responsibility in the fashion and luxury industry is also important considering a significant role that these industries have in the British and world economy. The luxury sector in the UK has achieved incredibly robust growth in the last several years. In contrast to high-street fashion brands, the growth of British luxury brands is not dependent on British consumers because the demand for luxury brands is global and international consumers are a high-spending segment of the British luxury market (Dirvanauskas, 2020).

Asian markets, especially China and India, are regarded as the main growth drivers of the global luxury market. During the Coronavirus outbreak that occurred in 2020, luxury stores were closed firstly in China and then in the rest of the world (Hopkins, 2020). The recovery of high-end luxury brands has been intensified and luxury sales have been returning to the pre-pandemic levels and in some cases even above (Van Dam and Long, 2021).

It has been estimated that the global luxury customer base has exceeded four hundred million consumers (D'Arpizio *et al.*, 2019). Luxury companies used to be small niche businesses that offered very expensive products only to an upscale clientele. Nowadays, the luxury industry is a fast-growing global industry that targets different market segments, which has intensified research interest in this sector (Okonkwo, 2009; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

The fashion industry generates huge annual global revenues and provides hundred of millions of jobs for workers globally. Overall fashion consumption is predicted to continue to experience exponential growth and create high environmental and social costs (Op De

Beeck, 2018). The luxury fashion industry is one of the fastest-growing industries globally that reaps extremely high revenues and profits worth billions (Cabigiosu, 2020).

The growth of the luxury fashion industry illustrates the metamorphosis from haute couturiers to global large companies that offer ready-to-wear clothes and accessories with different levels of luxury (Crane, 1997). Some scholars emphasise that luxury fashion brands can open the way for environmental and social reforms and progress in the whole fashion industry because sustainability can be in alignment with the true qualities of luxury, such as outstanding quality, durability, longevity and even rarity with regard to the need for the responsible use of natural resources necessary for the generation of the most valuable materials directly from the natural environment (Joy *et al.*, 2012; Godart and Seong, 2014; Ranfagni and Ozuem, 2022).

1.4. Background and Purpose of the Study

The business case for corporate social responsibility is defined as ‘the bottom-line financial and other reasons for businesses pursuing CSR strategies and policies’ (Carroll and Shabana, 2010, p. 85). The fruitfulness of implementing corporate social responsibility has been primarily appraised by examining the link between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Research indicates a positive and negative link between corporate social responsibility and financial performance in different industries and research contexts (Herremans, Akathaporn and Mcinnes, 1993; Orlitzky, Schmidt and Rynes, 2003; Alshehhi, Nobanee and Khare, 2018; Busch and Friede, 2018). In a luxury context, a negative link between corporate social responsibility and financial performance has been reported (Sipilä *et al.*, 2021).

Companies have been pressured to endure costly corporate social responsibility improvements in the production side of their business. However, the economic benefits of corporate social responsibility investments remain uncertain if socially responsible production is not endorsed by responsible consumption (Smith, Palazzo and Bhattacharya, 2010; Saricam and Okur, 2019). Prior research has shown that consumers are still reluctant to purchase sustainable luxury products (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). It is believed that ethical hardliners represent only a niche market in the luxury fashion industry (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013; Beckham and Voyer, 2014; Henninger *et al.*, 2017).

Because of the significance of consumers for revenue streams, maximising profitability and strengthening market value, a pivotal function in examining the business case for corporate social responsibility has been assigned to marketing researchers (Maignan and Ferrell, 2004; Pelozo and Shang, 2011). Developing a sustainable economy and society is not possible without socially conscious consumers and responsible consumption (Hansen and Schrader, 1997). In this regard, it is worthwhile to illuminate the problem of the business case for corporate social responsibility from the consumer's point of view in the luxury and fashion industry (Carroll and Shabana, 2010; Beckham and Voyer, 2014).

Research has shown that cause-related marketing can have positive effects on luxury consumer outcomes and be beneficial for both luxury brands and charitable organisations (Gupta and Pirsch, 2006; Boenigk and Schuchardt, 2013; Hagtvedt and Patrick, 2016). It has been proposed that luxury products with an environmental claim may evoke favourable consumer reactions when personal benefits reflecting the social status of the consumer are highlighted in their promotion rather than global environmental benefits (Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman, 2013).

However, communicating social responsibility may stimulate lower brand evaluations in comparison to when the luxury brand does not promote socially responsible initiatives. A self-enhancement concept of luxury brands may not be perceived as congruent with self-transcendence values associated with corporate social responsibility (Torelli, Monga and Kaikati, 2012). Consumers are likely to perceive the sophistication of luxury brands in a low fit with corporate social responsibility (Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019). Consumers tend to perceive luxury as a sector without the overuse of natural resources and unethical practices, which demonstrates the problem of the fallacy of clean luxury (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012). Prior research has indicated that the perceived incompatibility between luxury and sustainability is higher for consumers who define luxury as high price, rarity, exclusivity and hedonism than for consumers who define luxury as high quality (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Luxury brands face the problem of how to pursue corporate social responsibility and be perceived as sustainable without generating detrimental consequences (Bhardwaj and Bedford, 2017; Sipilä *et al.*, 2021).

A few studies examined consumer behaviour in the field of sustainable luxury fashion. Achabou and Dekhili (2013) report luxury fashion consumers' negative perceptions of using recycling in the manufacturing of clothes (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013). Janssen *et al.* (2014) argue that the perceived contradiction between luxury and corporate social responsibility is especially strong in fashion because of the ephemeral nature of clothes in comparison to enduring luxury goods (Janssen *et al.*, 2014). Beckham and Voyer (2014) suggest that consumers perceive eco-labelled luxury fashion goods unfavourably because sustainability reduces the degree of the luxuriousness of such goods (Beckham and Voyer, 2014). Adigüzel and Donato (2021) propose that consumers are likely to have more favourable evaluations toward upcycled than non-sustainable luxury and fashion because of increased pride as well as toward upcycled than recycled luxury and fashion because of increased pride and greater novelty (Adigüzel and Donato, 2021).

A few studies examined the meanings that consumers assign to second-hand luxury fashion goods and identified ecological and ethical awareness among the drivers of buying and selling those goods (Turunen and Leipämaa-Leskinen, 2015; Kessous and Valette-Florence, 2019; Turunen, Cervellon and Carey, 2020). Henninger *et al.* (2017) propose that consumers do not need to value sustainability in their luxury fashion purchases in spite of declaring to have moral values and concerns about business practices and being aware of the pollution problem and unjust relationships in the luxury and fashion supply chain (Henninger *et al.*, 2017).

Success in pursuing corporate social responsibility in luxury and fashion is therefore significantly dependent on the understanding of the factors that shape consumers' sustainable behaviour. The purpose of this study is to facilitate convergence in the understanding of the drivers and constraints of sustainable luxury and fashion consumption. Up to the present time, to my knowledge, no coherent model or theory exists to guide the understanding of the growth of sustainable luxury fashion from consumer perspective. The understanding of the socially responsible luxury fashion consumer helps comprehend how to make the manufacturing of luxury fashion products more responsible and promote sustainable luxury fashion consumption (Carroll and Shabana, 2010; Beckham and Voyer, 2014; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

1.5. Research Questions and Objectives of the Study

The research questions of the study are:

1. Do consumers perceive a contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability?
2. What are consumers' views on sustainable luxury fashion?
3. What are the key drivers of sustainable luxury fashion from consumer perspective?

The research objectives of the study are:

1. To identify consumers' views and behaviours regarding sustainable luxury fashion brands
2. To identify the critical factors that can stimulate the growth of sustainable luxury fashion brands from consumer perspective.

1.6. Structure of the Thesis

Chapter 1 introduced this thesis by explaining the rationale for conducting research in the field of corporate social responsibility and sustainable luxury and fashion. It specified the background and purpose of the study and the research questions and objectives of the study.

Chapter 2 explores the nature and evolution of the concept of corporate social responsibility and theories on corporate social responsibility. This chapter discusses the concepts of luxury and fashion and theories on sustainable luxury and fashion with focus on consumer behaviour. The chapter presents the testable hypotheses and the conceptual and theoretical framework of the study, forming the base of the research.

Chapter 3 addresses the research design and strategy of the study, the philosophical assumptions underlying the study and the justification for using the quantitative, explanatory and deductive research method for testing the hypotheses and answering the research questions of the study. This chapter presents the overview, design and scale of the survey questionnaire and the sampling method and procedure of the study. The measures undertaken for minimising errors in conducting the research are elucidated. The validity and reliability of the pilot study's data are tested and interpreted. The followed procedures to satisfy the principles of research ethics and integrity are explained.

Chapter 4 represents the presentation and interpretation of the results of the main study. The characteristics of the sample are described. The validity and reliability of the main study's data are tested and interpreted. The hypotheses are tested and the results are reported and interpreted.

Chapter 5 discusses the results of the study by connecting the findings with the research questions and prior theories on corporate social responsibility and sustainable luxury and fashion. The managerial implications, theoretical contributions and limitations of the study and the suggestions for future research are discussed.

Chapter 6 is the conclusion in which the findings are summarised and briefly discussed following the research questions and objectives of the study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1. Overview

The first opening section in the literature review chapter explains the purpose of the literature review in research and the literature review methodology for this study. The next section encompasses the review of the meaning, significance and development of the corporate social responsibility concept and theories in the field of corporate social responsibility. After presenting the section on the conceptualisation of luxury and fashion and their link with sustainability, the literature review chapter discusses the findings of studies relevant for the research problem underlying this thesis, that is, managing corporate social responsibility implementation in luxury fashion and promoting sustainable luxury fashion consumption without triggering adverse consequences.

2.2. Literature Review and its Purpose

The literature review has the aim to help researchers to understand the academic literature on the topic of interest and integrate the achievements in prior research with the need for further research in order to fill in the research gaps. By establishing the theoretical basis for research and the standards for comparing the findings of studies relevant for the research problem, the literature review points to the scope and limitations of results and the ambiguities and inconsistencies within existing knowledge regarding the selected topic.

The literature review proposes a new perspective for the research problem in accordance with the most recent stage of theory development (Hart, 1998; Boote and Beile, 2005).

2.2.1. Literature Review Methodology for the Thesis

Researching the academic literature for this thesis started with running the words and phrases related to the research topic through academic search engines. Academia Education, Emerald Insight, Google Scholar, JSTOR, Research Gate, SAGE Journals, Science Direct, Springer Link, Taylor and Francis and Wiley Online Library were the main academic search engines used for identifying the applicable literature for this study. In order to create a comprehensive list of the writings relevant for the research topic, the titles of sources were initially checked by Google Scholar to get the information on the number of citations.

An initial list of the academic publications for this study was modified during writing the thesis by adding more novel and important papers for the research topic. The papers published in academic journals prevailed in writing the thesis based on the need to obtain a wide collection of research findings, knowledge developments and future directions in the research field. The Table 2.1 represents the list of the academic journals along with the number of the publications used for writing the thesis while the Table 2.2 refers to the list of the authors of the seminal conceptual texts and key texts used in writing this paper. The Table 2.3 is the summary of the most productive key papers for the research problem with the following details: author(s), source/journal, citations, keywords, research methodology, sample and findings. The last update on the number of citations was on the 16th September 2024.

Table 2.1: List of Academic Journals

Academic journal/s	Number of publications
<i>Journal of Business Ethics</i>	31
<i>Journal of Business Research</i>	18
<i>Journal of Marketing</i>	17
<i>Sustainability</i>	16
<i>Journal of Consumer Research</i>	15
<i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>	13
<i>Academy of Management Review, Journal of Brand Management, Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management</i>	10
<i>Business Horizons, Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management</i>	8
<i>Business Ethics Quarterly, Business and Society, Journal of Marketing Research, Journal of Product and Brand Management, Strategic Management Journal</i>	7
<i>Academy of Management Journal, International Journal of Market Research, International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management, Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science</i>	6
<i>Corporate Communications: An International Journal, European Journal of Marketing, Harvard Business Review, International Journal of Consumer Studies, Journal of Consumer Marketing</i>	5
<i>Journal of Applied Psychology, Journal of Corporate Citizenship, Journal of Marketing Management</i>	4
<i>Advances in Consumer Research, European Business Review, European Management Journal, International Journal of Management Reviews, Journal of Consumer Affairs, Journal of Consumer Behaviour, Journal of Consumer Policy, Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, Social Responsibility Journal, Sustainable Development</i>	3

Academic journal/s	Number of publications
<p><i>Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal, Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education, Business Strategy and the Environment, California Management Review, Cleaner and Responsible Consumption, Decision Sciences, Economic Research, Economy Transdisciplinarity Cognition, Educational Researcher, Fashion Practice, Field Methods, Frontiers in Psychology, Heliyon, Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine, International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility, International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing, International Marketing Review, International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research, Journal of Advertising, Journal of Business Logistics, Journal of Consumer Psychology, Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science, Journal of Management Studies, Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice, Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, Journal of Public Policy and Marketing, Journal of Retailing, Long Range Planning, Management Decision, Marketing Intelligence and Planning, Marketing Letters, Marketing Science, Operations Management Research, Psychological Bulletin, Psychology and Marketing, Psychological Methods, Public Opinion Quarterly, Public Relations Review, Qualitative Market Research, Quality and Quantity, Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Tourism Management</i></p>	2

Academic journal/s	Number of publications
<p><i>Academic Medicine, Academy of Marketing Science Review, Accountability in Research, Accounting, Organisations and Society, Addictive Behaviour, Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research, Administrative Science Quarterly, Advances in Developing Human Resources, AIP Conference Proceedings, American Economic Review, American Journal of Agricultural Economics, American Journal of Evaluation, American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy, American Journal of Mathematics and Statistics, American Psychologist, American Statistician, Annals of Cardiac Anaesthesia, Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics, Annual Review of Psychology, Applied Mathematical Modelling, Arab Economic and Business Journal, Asia Pacific Journal of Management, Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics, Asian Journal of Sustainability and Social Responsibility, Australasian Marketing Journal, BMC Public Health, British Journal of Management, British Medical Journal, Business and Management Review, Business and Professional Ethics Journal, Business Research, Business Research Quarterly, Business Strategy Review, California Review Management, Central European Business Review, CIRP Annals, Competition Forum, Contemporary Sociology, Cornell International Law Journal, Corporate Ownership and Control, Corporate Reputation Review, Critical Perspectives on Accounting, Current Directions in Psychological Science, Daffodil International University Journal of Business and Economics, Ecological Economics, Ecological Indicators, Economic Journal, Educational Communication and Technology, Educational and Psychological Measurement, Electronic Journal of Business Ethics and Organisation Studies, Ekonomski vjesnik/Econviews-Review of Contemporary Business, Entrepreneurship and Economic Issues, Environmental Education Research, European Journal of Management and Business Economics, European Journal of Research Methods for the Behavioural and Social Sciences, Europe's Journal of Psychology, Evidence-Based Nursing, Fashion and Textiles, Fashion Theory, Financial Management, Food Quality and Preference</i></p>	1

Academic journal/s	Number of publications
<p><i>Geoforum, Greener Management International, Hofstra Labor and Employment Law Journal, Human Relations, Human Reproduction, Indian Journal of Corporate Governance, Indian Journal of Urology, Industrial Management and Data Systems, Information Management and Business Review, Innovation in Aging, Innovative Marketing, International Business Review, International Journal of Academic Research in Management, International Journal of Academic Value Studies, International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Applied Sciences, International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences, International Journal of Contemporary Management, International Journal of English Studies, International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research, International Journal of Environmental and Ecological Engineering, International Journal of Forecasting, International Journal of Hospitality Management, International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction, International Journal of Intercultural Relations, International Journal of Logistics: Research and Applications, International Journal of Medical Education, International Journal of Multivariate Data Analysis, International Journal of Nursing Studies, International Journal of Operations and Production Management, International Journal of Organisational Analysis, International Journal of Production Economics, International Journal of Research, International Journal of Research in Marketing, International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation, International Journal of Social Science Research, International Journal of Strategic Communication, International Marketing and Management of Innovations: International Scientific E-Journal, International Review of Management and Business Research, Jornal Brasileiro de Pneumologia, Journal of Accounting Research, Journal of Advertising Research, Journal of Applied Business Research, Journal of Clinical Nursing, Journal of Communication Management, Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication, Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology, Journal of Consumer Culture, Journal of Critical Care Medicine, Journal of Current Issues and Research in Advertising, Journal of Economic Education</i></p>	1

Academic journal/s	Number of publications
<p><i>Journal of Economic Psychology, Journal of Education and Practice, Journal of Educational and Social Research, Journal of Environmental Education, Journal of Environmental Sustainability, Journal of Euromarketing, Journal of Experimental Social Psychology, Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care, Journal of Global Responsibility, Journal of Indian Orthodontic Society, Journal of Innovation Economics and Management, Journal of Intercultural Management, Journal of International and Area Studies, Journal of International Business Ethics, Journal of Management Research, Journal of Marketing Communications, Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness, Journal of Marketing Strategies, Journal of Measurement and Evaluation in Education and Psychology, Journal of Nonprofit and Public Sector Marketing, Journal of Organisational Behaviour, Journal of Political Economy, Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, Journal of Social Entrepreneurship, Journal of Surgical Research, Journal of Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology, Journal of the Textile Institute, Journal of Usability Studies, Journal of World Business, Korean Journal of Anesthesiology, Law and Society Review, Luxury Research, Management Science, Management Science Letters, Marketing Bulletin, Marketing Theory, Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, MIS Quarterly, Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development, National Forum of Educational Administration and Supervision Journal, Natural Science, Neurology, New York Times Magazine, Nonprofit Management and Leadership, Open Journal of Business and Management, Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes, Organisational Dynamics, Organisation and Environment, Organisation Studies, Oxford Review of Economic Policy, Pace International Law Review, Physical Review Physics Education Research, Poetics, Preventing Chronic Disease, Problems of Education in the 21st Century, Procedia Economics and Finance, Procedia-Social and Behavioural Sciences, Project Management Journal, Psicothema, Psychological Review, Psychology, Psychology and Health, Psychometrika, Qualitative Research Journal</i></p>	1

Academic journal/s	Number of publications
<i>Qualitative Research in Organisations and Management: An International Journal, Quarterly Journal of Economics, Research Methods in Applied Linguistics, Resources, Conservation and Recycling, Science and Education, Semiotica, Social Enterprise Journal, South African Journal of Education, Stata Journal, Statistical Methods in Medical Research, Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal, Sustainability Science, Symphonia, Theoretical and Applied Economics, Total Quality Management, Virtual Reality, Waste Management and Research</i>	1

Table 2.2: Seminal Conceptual Texts and Key Papers

Seminal Conceptual Texts
<p>Aaker (1997), Ajzen (1991), Ajzen (2011), Anderson and Cunningham (1972), Auger <i>et al.</i> (2003), Aupperle, Carroll and Hatfield (1985), Bagwell and Bernheim (1996), Balmer (2001), Barone, Miyazaki and Taylor (2000), Bearden, Netemeyer and Teel (1989), Berman <i>et al.</i> (1999), Bernheim (1994), Bhattacharya, Korschun and Sen (2009), Brakus, Schmitt and Zarantonello (2009), Brammer, Brooks and Pavelin (2006), Brammer and Pavelin (2006), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Brown and Dacin (1997), Burke and Logsdon (1996), Campbell (2007), Carroll (1979), Carroll (1991), Carroll (1999), Carroll (2015), Carroll (2016), Carroll and Shabana (2010), Carter and Ellram (1992), Cochran and Wood (1984), Crane and Matten (2016), Dahlsrud (2008), Davis (1973), De George (1987), Delmas and Burbano (2011), Dhar and Wertebroch (2000), Du, Bhattacharya and Sen (2007), Du, Bhattacharya and Sen (2010), Eastman, Goldsmith and Flynn (1999), Fionda and Moore (2009), Frederick (1994), Freedman and Fraser (1966), Freeman (1994), Friedman (1970), Garriga and Melé (2004), Gray and Balmer (1998), Greenwald and Banaji (1995), Griffin and Mahon (1997), Gutman (1982), Han, Nunes and Drèze (2010), Hirschman and Holbrook (1982), Holbrook and Hirschman (1982), Jensen (2002), Joyner and Payne (2002), Kapferer and Bastien (2009a), Kapferer and Bastien (2009b), Kapferer and Bastien (2017), Keller (2013), Kollmuss and Agyeman (2002), Lantos (2001), Lee (2008), Leibenstein (1950), Levy (1959), Mackey, Mackey and Barney (2007), Maignan and Ferrell (2004), Matten and Moon (2008), McWilliams and Siegel (2000), Menon and Menon (1997), Milne and Gray (2013), Nueno and Quelch (1998), Orlitzky, Schmidt and Rynes (2003), Pelozo and Shang (2011), Pomeroy and Dolnicar (2009), Porter and Kramer (2002), Porter and Kramer (2006), Roberts (1996a), Rogers and Tibben-Lembke (2011), Schlegelmilch, Bohlen and Diamantopoulos (1996), Schwartz and Carroll (2003), Sen and Bhattacharya (2001), Sethi (1979), Sharma and Vredenburg (1998), Sheth, Newman and Gross (1991), Smith and Colgate (2007), Sproles and Kendall (1986), Swanson (1995), Tynan, McKechnie and Chhuon (2010), Van Riel and Balmer (1997), Vigneron and Johnson (1999), Vigneron and Johnson (2017), Vilanova, Lozano and Arenas (2009), Waddock and Graves (1997), Wartick and Cochran (1985), Webster (1975), White, Habib and Hardisty (2019), Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels (2009), Wright and Ferris (1997), Yoon, Giirhan-Canli and Schwarz (2006), Zaltman (2003), Zeithaml (1988)</p>

Key Texts

Achabou and Dekhili (2013), Adigüzel and Donato (2021), Amatulli *et al.* (2018), Armstrong *et al.* (2016), Barone, Miyazaki and Taylor (2000), Beckham and Voyer (2014), Bhattacharya and Sen (2004), Boenigk and Schuchardt (2013), Boulstridge and Carrigan (2000), Carrigan and Attalla (2001), Cervellon (2013), Cervellon and Shammass (2013), Costa Pinto *et al.* (2019), Creyer and Ross (1996), Creyer and Ross (1997), Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai (2012), Dominguez and Bhatti (2022), Drumwright (1996), Ellen, Webb and Mohr (2006), Folkes and Kamins (1999), Goworek *et al.* (2012), Griskevicius, Tybur and Van den Bergh (2010), Hagtvedt and Patrick (2016), Han *et al.* (2017), Henninger *et al.* (2017), Henninger, Bürklin and Niinimäki (2019), Janssen *et al.* (2014), Janssen, Vanhamme and Leblanc (2017), Joergens (2006), Kapferer and Michaut (2014), Kapferer and Michaut (2015), Karpova *et al.* (2022), Kessous and Valette-Florence (2019), Kim, Jung and Lee (2021), Lee, Zailani and Rahman (2020), McGoldrick and Freestone (2008), Morgan and Birtwistle (2009), Niinimäki (2010), Podnar and Golob (2007), Sen and Bhattacharya (2001), Sipilä *et al.* (2021), Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman (2013), Sung *et al.* (2020), Torelli, Monga and Kaikati (2012), Turunen, Carey and Cervellon (2020), Turunen and Leipämaa-Leskinen (2015), Turunen and Pöyry (2019), Vehmas *et al.* (2018), Weber, Lynes and Young (2017), Yoon, Giirhan-Canli and Schwarz (2006)

Table 2.3: Details and Findings of the Most Productive Key Papers

Author(s) / Source/ Journal / Citations / Key words / Research methodology / Sample	Findings
Creyer and Ross (1996) / <i>Marketing Letters</i> / 344 / Ethical and unethical corporate behaviour, consumer behaviour / Experimental research / University undergraduate students	Ethical corporate behaviour is not likely to be rewarded by paying a premium price but unethical corporate behaviour cannot be unnoticed. Consumers are likely to pay lower prices for unethically sourced products. Consumers are not likely to reward an ethical company by choosing to buy its products over competitors' products but they are significantly less likely to choose products offered by unethical companies. The negative consequences of companies' unethical deeds can be neutralised by undertaking new ethical actions.
Drumwright (1996) / <i>Journal of Marketing</i> / 1250 / Corporate social responsibility, cause- related marketing / Qualitative interviews / Managers from companies and agencies pursuing cause-related marketing	The key factors for companies' success in advertising with a social agenda are: company-cause compatibility, long-term commitment to cause-related marketing, strong affinity for the cause among key stakeholders, developing close relationships with the cause community, carefully created advertising messages, using multiple brands to support the cause and supporting a smaller number of causes. When the business and the cause share a common market segment, consumers' perceptions of the motives underlying the campaign are more positive. Social campaigns with mixed objectives are effective for accomplishing company-oriented objectives, for example, employees' motivation and communicating the company's mission, which neutralises disappointments if the economic objectives of campaigns have not been satisfied to the highest degree. Consumers perceive cause-related marketing either as a marketing strategy for increasing sales and maximising profitability or as endeavours to contribute to community wellbeing.

<p>Creyer and Ross (1997) / <i>Journal of Consumer Marketing</i> / 2149 / Ethical and unethical corporate behaviour, consumer behaviour / Survey questionnaire / Parents of pupils in one public elementary school in the USA</p>	<p>Ethics has become an important matter for consumers when making purchase decisions. Consumers are willing to pay higher prices for ethical products and they want to pay lower prices for unethical products.</p>
<p>Barone, Miyazaki and Taylor (2000) / <i>Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science</i> / 1836 / Corporate social responsibility, cause-related marketing, consumer behaviour / Experimental research / Undergraduate business students</p>	<p>The major considerations for marketing managers in cause-related projects are related to consumers' perceptions of the motives behind cause-related marketing and to what extent consumers are willing to exchange the company's sponsorship of social causes for lower quality and/or higher price.</p>
<p>Boulstridge and Carrigan (2000) / <i>Journal of Communication Management</i> / 1040 / Corporate social responsibility, ethics, consumer behaviour, attitude-behaviour gap / Focus groups / Managers, university students, manual workers and pensioners (two groups - under and over 35 years old, heterogeneous in gender)</p>	<p>Consumers' low corporate social responsibility awareness is explained by the lack of information on companies' social responsibility. Consumers tend to develop interest in corporate social responsibility only if corporate behaviour affects them personally. Consumers are sceptical about companies' motives for using cause-related marketing to support charity. Although consumers believe that the business sector needs to be accountable for social betterment, they do not involve information on ethical or unethical corporate behaviour in their purchase decisions. Quality, price and brand familiarity are more important in consumer purchase decisions. More information on corporate social responsibility would not change consumer purchase decisions drastically. A minority of consumers admitted that their increased knowledge of unethical corporate behaviour might affect their purchase decisions. Paying a price premium for ethical products is perceived unfavourably.</p>

<p>Carrigan and Attalla (2001) / <i>Journal of Consumer Marketing</i> / 3042 / Corporate social responsibility, ethical consumer behaviour, attitude-behaviour gap / Focus groups / University educated participants (18-25 years old, gender groups)</p>	<p>Consumers had low corporate social responsibility awareness. Although participants were familiar with the unethical activities of a few big companies, they continued to buy their products. Participants' awareness of ethical corporate behaviour was negligible. The postulation that consumers are more influenced by information on unethical corporate behaviour than information on ethical corporate behaviour was not supported by this research. There was a low level of consumers' interest in searching for more information on corporate behaviour. Consumers were mostly concerned with animal rights. They justified it with their feelings of helplessness because of the non-existence of economic and legal conditions and cultural norms for social responsibility improvements in host countries. Participants were not willing to pay more for corporate social responsibility but they had positive attitudes towards paying a premium price for products sourced without animal suffering. Participants acknowledged that their hypothetical strong buying power might lead to paying more for high-quality products manufactured in an ethical way. However, there was an obvious gap between consumers' ethical attitudes or purchase intentions of ethical products and consumers' actual ethical actions. Consumers based their purchase decisions on value, brand image, price and fashion trends. Respondents were not willing to boycott unethical brands or reward ethical corporate behaviour. Some respondents perceived companies with poor corporate social responsibility records as ethical because of their success in profit maximisation and providing employment opportunities in developing countries. Consumers' scepticism about companies' motives for corporate social responsibility was found. Gender did not influence attitudes towards ethical corporate behaviour.</p>
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<p>Bhattacharya and Sen (2004) / <i>California Management Review</i> / 4076 / Corporate social responsibility, cause-related marketing, consumer behaviour / Mixed methods research - experiments, surveys, focus groups, in-depth interviews / Participants from the general population and university undergraduate and postgraduate business students</p>	<p>Consumers are more sensitive to information on negative corporate behaviour than information on positive corporate behaviour. Consumers are willing to tolerate socially responsible companies' sporadic irresponsible activities. Consumers may become attached to companies undertaking for consumers important corporate social responsibility activities and become loyal to such companies. Through the consumer-company identification, consumers are likely to have positive word of mouth on responsible brands. Certain companies' corporate social responsibility efforts may evoke and strengthen consumers' feelings of well-being. Economic goals and objectives are perceived as the drivers of companies' engagement in cause-related marketing. Cause-related marketing is perceived more approvingly when the for-profit company is a company with a good reputation. When the sponsoring company has a bad reputation and the nature of the company's business is closely connected with the cause, consumers are sceptical about the purpose of undertaking cause-related marketing actions. Companies proactively engaged in corporate social responsibility are perceived more favourably than companies that adopt a preventive social responsibility strategy. Small companies engaging in corporate social responsibility and local operations are perceived more positively. Consumers are not willing to pay a price premium for the manufacturing of products in a more socially responsible way and to accept a compromise between social responsibility and product quality. Consumers' low corporate social responsibility awareness and extrinsic social responsibility attributions hamper the rise of responsible consumption.</p>
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<p>Ellen, Webb and Mohr (2006) / <i>Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science</i> / 2450 / Corporate social responsibility, cause-related marketing, corporate associations, corporate reputation / Open-ended questions, experimental survey / University students (age and gender groups, most employed, ethnically diverse); random sample of university staff (age, gender and income groups, ethnically diverse)</p>	<p>The majority of participants perceived cause-related initiatives as companies' efforts to simultaneously generate sales and support the cause. Consumers perceive campaigns undertaken to sincerely help others more positively than campaigns as a respond to the pressure of stakeholders. A high fit between the business and the social agenda is perceived more positively. A shorter commitment in supporting the cause is not desirable because consumers are likely to perceive cause-related marketing as responding to stakeholders' pressures. Consumers' attributions of the company's motives for corporate social responsibility significantly affect their purchase intentions. Purchase intentions are lower if corporate social responsibility attributions are egoistic and stakeholder driven and higher when social responsibility attributions are values driven and strategic.</p>
<p>Joergens (2006) / <i>Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management</i> / 996 / Ethics, ethical fashion consumption / Method triangulation - focus groups, email survey questionnaire / Participants from Germany and England aged 18-26</p>	<p>Consumers' purchase behaviour is not influenced by fashion brands' environmental and social records. Consumers are sceptical about fashion brands' corporate social responsibility engagement. Consumers believe that it is not possible to eliminate or mitigate unethical practices in the global apparel supply chain because of different social norms and the lack of regulations in developing countries. It makes consumers more concerned with animal rights. The harmful effects of hazardous chemicals used in the manufacturing of clothes on the environment and apparel workers' health seem to be irrelevant for consumers. Consumers care about ethics only when ethical actions affect their own health. Respondents had low corporate social responsibility awareness in fashion and they believed that there was the lack of the media coverage of corporate social responsibility in fashion. Participants were not willing to pay a premium for ethically sourced clothing but they had positive attitudes towards buying ethical fashionable clothes at comparable prices in the future.</p>

<p>Yoon, Giirhan-Canli and Schwarz (2006) / <i>Journal of Consumer Psychology</i> / 2020 / Corporate social responsibility, corporate reputation, consumers' attributions of corporate social responsibility / Experimental research / Undergraduate students</p>	<p>The effectiveness of using a corporate social responsibility appeal in selling products is mediated by the perceived sincerity of companies' corporate social responsibility motives. The company's image and reputation can be improved through corporate social responsibility only if consumers perceive the sincere motives behind corporate social responsibility. Consumers' distrust in corporate credibility reduces the effectiveness of using social responsibility as a differentiating factor in the market.</p>
<p>McGoldrick and Freestone (2008) / <i>International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research</i> / 147 / Ethical consumption, consumers' willingness to pay a premium for ethics / Focus groups, Zaltman metaphor elicitation technique, email questionnaires / Participants recruited from a data consumer base (age and gender groups from all regions in the UK)</p>	<p>Consumers are willing to pay the highest premium for ethically sourced food, which may indicate that consumers are likely to develop interest in the ethical aspects of products if ethical corporate behaviour affects them directly. Consumers are not willing to pay a high premium for ethically manufactured garments.</p>

<p>Morgan and Birtwistle (2009) / <i>International Journal of Consumer Studies</i> / 798 / Sustainability, fashion, recycling, textile, consumers / Method triangulation - focus groups, interviews, survey questionnaire / Female fashion consumers (aged 17-25 in focus groups and 27-57 in interviews; age, marital status and education groups in a survey)</p>	<p>Young fashion consumers had low awareness of the environmental aspects of the fashion industry and they were uninformed about the need for textile and clothes recycling. They believed that their low awareness of sustainability in fashion was a result of the insufficient media coverage of the sustainability aspects of the fashion industry. Their used clothes were mostly donated to charities, which was determined by convenience. A small quantity of their used garments was handed in for recycling and thrown for landfilling. Some participants practised clothes swapping and selling garments on the second-hand market. Older fashion consumers used their clothes as long as they were wearable. Some level of consumers' awareness of clothing disposal options was identified but it was not correlated with their attitude to perform textile waste management through recycling.</p>
<p>Griskevicius, Tybur and Van den Bergh (2010) / <i>Journal of Personality and Social Psychology</i> / 2852 / Consumer behaviour, costly signalling, altruism, environmental conservation, status competition / Experiments / Students at a public university</p>	<p>Less luxurious green products may be evaluated as more desirable than more luxurious and equally priced traditional products if possessing such products affects consumers' social status. When consumers do shopping publicly in stores, they may be likely to choose less luxurious green products over more luxurious and equally priced non-green products. When consumers purchase online, it is likely that they choose luxury non-green products rather than green and less luxurious products. When the factor of price was involved, social motives influenced participants to choose more expensive green products over low-priced non-green products.</p>
<p>Niinimäki (2010) / <i>Sustainable Development</i> / 859 / Ethical fashion, consumer behaviour / Survey questionnaire / Consumers in Finland recruited online (mostly females and students under 35 years old)</p>	<p>Highly socially conscious and committed fashion consumers, which are a market niche, follow their own tenets of sustainability in their clothing purchases, which can be more important than aesthetics and creativity in fashion or personal identity expressed through clothes. Most participants responded positively concerning the idea of buying durable and high-quality clothes to support sustainable development in the future.</p>

<p>Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai (2012) / <i>Journal of Business Ethics</i> / 560 / Ethical consumers, luxury and commodity purchases / Survey questionnaire with structured and open-ended questions / Participants approached on the main streets in two towns in the UK and selected on the basis of socio-economic quotas (age, gender, income and education)</p>	<p>The quantitative findings show that satisfaction achieved in past purchases, quality and convenience have the most significant influence on consumers' purchase decisions for both luxury and commodity products. The quality of a brand connected with prestige is more relevant in luxury purchases than in commodity purchases. Ethics is a less significant criterion in luxury purchases than in commodity purchases. The qualitative findings indicate consumers' low awareness of ethics in luxury and consumers' fallacy of clean luxury. Consumers' low awareness of ethics in luxury is a result of the lack of information on the ethical aspects of luxury and the lack of available ethical luxury products. Consumers' fallacy of clean luxury stemmed from their beliefs that the manufacturing of luxury products is almost without any environmental impacts and unethical behaviours but such beliefs were not substantiated by any rationale or example in support of clean and ethical luxury. Respondents assumed that luxury companies operate predominantly in the Western world without creating significant environmental and social impacts. Paying a premium for luxury was evaluated negatively. Participants believed that any premium paid for ethics in luxury would not be distributed for solving environmental and social problems in the global supply chain. The separation fallacy between ethics and business leads consumers to think that ethical products cost more than their traditional counterparts. The irregularity of luxury purchases prevents consumers to search for more information on ethical luxury. Participants believed that they can make contributions to help developing countries only through their regular purchases of ethical commodity products. Luxury is perceived as a sector that cannot make a positive and real change in improving working conditions and producing less waste in the global supply chain.</p>
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<p>Goworek <i>et al.</i> (2012) / <i>International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management</i> / 323 / Sustainable clothing, clothing retailers, consumer behaviour / Focus groups, diary tasks and workshops / Respondents recruited by on-street interviewers in three towns in the UK</p>	<p>Participants showed low awareness of the sustainability aspects of clothing. Participants acknowledged that they were willing to adopt more sustainable practices concerning reducing energy waste through washing clothes at lower temperatures but their willingness to purchase sustainable clothes remained weak. Participants were interested in gaining more information on the sustainability impacts of clothes and the availability of facilities for recycling.</p>
<p>Torelli, Monga and Kaikati (2012) / <i>Journal of Consumer Research</i> / 522 / Corporate social responsibility, luxury, brand concepts / Experimental research / Consumer panel and university undergraduate students in the USA</p>	<p>The idea of brand concepts is essential for the understanding of consumers' reactions to corporate social responsibility. A self-transcendence concept of corporate social responsibility reflected in altruistic and intrinsic concerns for the welfare of others is not in harmony with a self-enhancement concept of luxury brands that puts emphasis on self-centred values. This conflict triggers disfluency in processing social information, especially when there is no concrete information on companies' social responsibility efforts. The study stresses the importance of making the distinction between advertising corporate social responsibility in an abstract and concrete way.</p>
<p>Achabou and Dekhili (2013) / <i>Journal of Business Research</i> / 538 / Sustainability, luxury, textile, recycling, consumer behaviour / Survey questionnaire / Affluent French participants (gender, profession, income and consumption level groups)</p>	<p>Luxury brands' environmental behaviours do not have an important role in consumers' purchase decisions. Recycling is perceived positively in terms of ecology but the introduction of recycling in the manufacturing of luxury clothes is perceived negatively. Recycling is perceived positively for the product packaging in luxury. Using organic cotton in the manufacturing of luxury garments is perceived positively. Some participants perceived recycling as luxury brands' marketing strategy for maximising profits. Females and occasional consumers are less sceptical about the usage of recycled fabrics in the manufacturing of luxury clothes.</p>

<p>Boenigk and Schuchardt (2013) / <i>International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing</i> / 71 / Cause-related marketing, luxury, consumer attitudes and purchase intentions / Experimental research / Actual luxury consumers and students at a prestigious business school in Germany (age, gender and income groups)</p>	<p>Consumers' purchase intentions of luxury brands are likely to be higher when luxury brands apply a low-pricing strategy in cause-related marketing campaigns and when donations are high. High donations are in a positive relation with the perceived sincerity of the luxury company's motives to help philanthropic activities. The combination of high-priced luxury and high donations appears to prompt consumers' scepticism about the motives for luxury companies' cause-related marketing activities.</p>
<p>Cervellon (2013) / <i>International Journal of Market Research</i> / 147 / Luxury, sustainability, philanthropy, consumer behaviour / Semiotics, focus groups / Actual luxury consumers in a few opulent European towns, females</p>	<p>Participants expected that luxury brands follow sustainability in the following realms: philanthropy, controlling pollution, protecting and conserving biodiversity and soil, preserving and nurturing natural resources through waste management practices and improving labour and consumer rights (for example, promoting anti-discriminatory practices at work and dealing with the problem of anorexic models and bulimia). The dichotomy between discreet and conspicuous brands reflects the difference between ascribed and achieved luxury and status in society. When a brand has the status of ascribed luxury, it is relevant to include the principles of sustainability in the mission and vision of the brand and along the supply chain. Ascribed luxury symbolises inaccessible luxury associated with local and slow manufacturing, craftsmanship, the use of precious, natural and rare materials for higher added value, highly skilled workforce, heraldic tradition, timelessness and vintage value and sponsoring art. Brands with the status of achieved luxury are not naturally perceived as compatible with sustainability. Achieved luxury is related to conspicuous luxury consumption, highly visible brand markings and mass production. It is expected that these brands support environmental and social causes.</p>

<p>Cervellon and Shammas (2013) / <i>Journal of Corporate Citizenship</i> / 147 / Conspicuous consumption, luxury, sustainability, consumer behaviour / Zaltman metaphor elicitation technique, semi-structured interviewing / Luxury consumers recruited from upper-middle class (four samples - UK, Canada, Italy, France; males and females aged 23-60)</p>	<p>The values related to sustainable luxury in mature markets are: eco-centred values (ecological and social responsiveness), socio-cultural values (conspicuousness, heritage and belonging to a social class) and individual, ego-centred values (guilt-free satisfaction, health, hedonism and quality). In Italy and France, the individual drivers of sustainable luxury consumption may be dominant. In Canada and the UK, collective values are likely to have a decisive influence on luxury consumers' sustainable buying behaviour. Some luxury values can be increased through pursuing sustainability in luxury, such as high quality and conspicuousness. Other values are created through sustainable luxury, for example, ecological and social sensitivity, health and guilt-free satisfaction. For French and Italian interviewees, conspicuous consumption can be achieved through purchasing sustainable luxury products. Canadian consumers do not perceive sustainability as a source of the prestige of a brand. Conspicuousness is only expressed in purchasing expensive luxury goods and high-end brands to signal social status. Conspicuous consumption for Canadians and British does not evoke guilt. Luxury purchases are rewards for hard work and achieved results. In Canada, sustainable luxury is seen as a way for nurturing and protecting nature rather than through the cultural heritage of the country. French consumers associate sustainable luxury with everlastingness, vintage collections and goods that can increase in value over time. Italian consumers are focused on know-how and craftsmanship. In the UK, France and Italy, sustainable luxury products are perceived as beneficial for health.</p>
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<p>Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman (2013) / <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> / 137 / Environmental claim, eco-labels, luxury product, utilitarian product, consumer behaviour / Experimental research / Consumers of utilitarian and luxury products (age, gender, education, income and family status groups)</p>	<p>The perceived functionality of a utilitarian product can be improved through eco-labelling. This strategy is more effective when environmental claims put emphasis on global environmental benefits. In a luxury context, consumers perceive eco-labelling more positively if eco-labels highlight personal benefits, such as social status and self-indulgence.</p>
<p>Beckham and Voyer (2014) / <i>Advances in Consumer Research</i> / 139 / Sustainable luxury, sustainable luxury fashion, implicit and explicit consumer attitudes / Mixed-methods research - Go/No-Go Association Task, survey experiment, focus group / Female participants (aged 16-51; 17-66; 21-25)</p>	<p>Participants' implicit attitudes towards sustainable luxury were negative. In the context of high-street brands, participants' attitudes towards sustainable luxury were positive. Participants' explicit attitudes towards using eco-labelling in luxury fashion were negative, that is, sustainable luxury fashion goods were perceived as less luxurious than unlabelled luxury fashion goods. Eco-labelling does not influence consumers' decisions on how much to pay for luxury fashion. More expensive luxury fashion goods are perceived as more luxurious. The high quality and durability of materials used to manufacture luxury goods are not perceived as the natural characteristics and sources of sustainability in luxury. The perceived conceptual contradiction between luxury and sustainability was identified. Participants were of the opinion that luxury shoppers are not likely to purchase sustainable luxury because of their high need to signal status to society. Luxury purchases reflecting consumers' obsession with status symbols were evaluated negatively while purchasing luxury based on consumers' internal propensities was perceived positively. Participants mostly gave positive personal opinions on sustainable luxury but they were sceptical about luxury brands' credibility in communicating their conformity with sustainability.</p>

<p>Janssen <i>et al.</i> (2014) / <i>Journal of Business Ethics</i> / 287 / Corporate social responsibility, luxury, consumers, ephemerality, scarcity / Experimental research / French female participants interested in luxury and selected on websites from students and the general population (age groups)</p>	<p>The ephemerality and scarcity dimensions of luxury influence consumers' perceptions of the congruence between luxury and corporate social responsibility. It affects consumers' attitudes towards products promoting corporate social responsibility. When luxury products are enduring, scarce products are likely to be perceived as more socially responsible than widely available products, which creates more positive attitudes towards scarce luxury products. For scarce luxury products, enduring products are likely to be perceived as more socially responsible than ephemeral products such as clothes, which creates more positive attitudes towards enduring luxury products. The perceived congruence between luxury and corporate social responsibility is lowest for ephemeral products, which causes difficulties in positioning those products as socially responsible in the market.</p>
<p>Kapferer and Michaut (2014) / <i>Journal of Brand Management</i> / 360 / Luxury, sustainability, consumer behaviour / Survey questionnaire / Self-reported luxury consumers in France (age, gender, income and sustainable development sensibility and behaviour groups)</p>	<p>Consumers do not take sustainability into account when purchasing luxury products and they perceive a high contradiction between luxury and sustainability based on their perceptions of luxury as a symbol of social inequalities and superficiality. The luxury industry is perceived as a sector with a low level of ignoring responsible business standards. Participants' cognition of the unethical aspects of luxury supply chains, such as animal cruelty and sweatshops, was followed by a shock. Consumers expect local supply chains and craftsmanship to be restored to luxury.</p>
<p>Kapferer and Michaut (2015) / <i>Luxury Research Journal</i> / 243 / Luxury, sustainability, consumer behaviour / Survey research / Actual luxury consumers in France (age, gender, income and the first important luxury attribute groups)</p>	<p>Consumers mostly do not care about sustainability when purchasing luxury brands. Luxury is evaluated as a sector that should be exemplary in following sustainability. Consumers who define luxury as superior quality perceive a lower contradiction between luxury and sustainability than consumers who define luxury based on rarity, high price, exclusivity and hedonism. The majority of young consumers perceive a high contradiction between luxury and sustainability. The majority of older consumers do not perceive a contradiction between luxury and sustainability. Sustainability is perceived as a new dimension of quality.</p>

<p>Turunen and Leipämaa-Leskinen (2015) / <i>Journal of Product and Brand Management</i> / 285 / Second-hand and vintage luxury fashion, meanings, consumer behaviour, circularity / Qualitative interviews / Finnish female participants</p>	<p>Second-hand luxury fashion accessories are perceived as more affordable, timeless and unique products in comparison to products offered on the mass luxury market. Purchasing second-hand luxury fashion products represents wise investments for consumers, allowing them to profit from the monetary resale value of those products in the future. Consumers purchase second-hand luxury because it represents a more sustainable choice. Second-hand luxury fashion products symbolise nostalgia for the originality of luxury and the craftsmanship of the past. Investing in second-hand luxury poses the risk of inauthenticity and purchasing counterfeits.</p>
<p>Hagtvedt and Patrick (2016) / <i>Journal of Retailing</i> / 122 / Cause-related marketing, luxury, consumer attitudes and purchase intentions / Experimental research / Undergraduate students (gender groups), participants recruited by Amazon Mechanical Turk (gender and income groups)</p>	<p>Luxury companies' cause-related activities increase consumers' purchase intentions of luxury products. Consumers are more likely to choose a luxury brand over a value-for-money brand at the point of sale when the luxury brand corroborates with charity. It is explained by the guilt-reduction mechanism rather than the perceived compatibility between the luxury brand and the cause. Guilt associated with luxury purchases decreases with donating to charity and leads to higher purchase intentions towards luxury brands.</p>

<p>Han <i>et al.</i> (2017) / <i>Sustainability in fashion: A cradle to upcycle approach</i> / 113 / Fashion, sustainability, upcycling, circular economy, circulation / Semi-structured interviews / Experts involved in sustainable practices in fashion in the UK</p>	<p>Quality, price, style and design are the major factors of consumers' purchase intentions in fashion while sustainability is of secondary importance. Consumers have low awareness of sustainability in fashion or they do not want to consider the harmful effects of excessive fashion consumption on the environment. Triggering consumers' guilt because of their prior consumption habits is not likely to have a far-reaching effect on consumers' positive attitude change towards more sustainable consumption in fashion. Consumers prefer concrete and engaging stories about constructive sustainability changes and innovations within fashion, such as clean technologies and how sustainable fashion products are actually manufactured, for example, how high-quality and stylish garments are produced through upcycling. Consumers expect upcycled fashion brands to provide exclusivity, limited editions and original and unique designs. Fashion brands lack transparency in communicating sustainability practices. Social media and in-store dialogue are the most used channels for promoting sustainable clothing. Purchasing second-hand clothes is perceived as unattractive. Consumers' psychological barriers to accept second-hand clothes are related to, for example, the perceived poor hygienic condition of second-hand textiles or difficulties in signalling social status in comparison to when purchasing new fashion products.</p>
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<p>Henninger <i>et al.</i> (2017) / <i>Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management</i> / 69 / Luxury fashion, consumer typology, purchase motivators / Semi-structured interviews, focus groups / Chinese consumers of luxury fashion in the UK (purposeful sampling based on satisfying the requirement of being a luxury fashion consumer in the UK and part of the Chinese middle class; age group under 35, female and male participants)</p>	<p>Chinese consumers have high awareness of sustainability issues in the global luxury fashion supply chain. They mainly associated sustainability with environmental protection. The influence of sustainability on people's well-being emerged as a new dimension of sustainability. Some participants believed that luxury should be the leading sector in sustainability engagement. Because of charging price premiums, the luxury industry is expected to be highly responsible for tackling environmental and social problems. Sustainability has become a crucial feature of luxury fashion, which is based on the longevity and durability of materials used for the manufacturing of high-quality luxury fashion products. Others emphasised that sustainability cannot be matched with luxury because of their conceptual differences. In purchasing luxury fashion products, the more important criteria than sustainability are: uniqueness, quality, rarity, self-indulgence and social influence. A consumer group that emerged from the study are indulgers who ignore sustainability in their luxury fashion purchases in spite of being aware of sustainability in the luxury fashion supply chain.</p>
<p>Janssen, Vanhamme and Leblanc (2017) / <i>Journal of Business Research</i> / 144 / Corporate social responsibility, luxury, brand conspicuousness, self-identity, consumer research / Experimental survey research / Online participants interested in luxury goods (age and gender groups, 68.5% self-declared luxury consumers)</p>	<p>Consumers' attitudes towards responsible luxury are influenced by brand conspicuousness. Consumers perceive socially responsible efforts more favourably when a luxury brand follows an inconspicuous branding strategy rather than a conspicuous branding strategy. Conspicuous brands are less relevant for consumers with a modest self-identity. Consumers with an extravagant self-identity are less influenced by the branding strategy of the luxury brand than consumers with a modest self-identity, that is, extravagant consumers are likely to have purchase interest in all luxury products to express their identity, regardless of if luxury products are conspicuously branded or not.</p>

<p>Weber, Lynes and Young (2017) / <i>International Journal of Consumer Studies</i> / 208 / Textile waste management, sustainability, consumer behaviour / Survey research / Online participants recruited among residents in Ontario, which is a province with the largest amount of residential waste in Canada (age, gender, income and the type of residence groups)</p>	<p>Consumers with a high fashion index are more likely to perform textile waste management through reselling, recycling and swapping than consumers with a low fashion index. Donating garments for both types of consumers is dependent on the availability of donation locations and convenience. Consumers with a high fashion index produce more textile waste because of driving the majority of fashion purchases but they have a lower rate of disposing textile waste than consumers with a low fashion index. Consumers with a low fashion index choose to dispose clothes rather than to donate clothes to charities, which is based on a perceived low value of their thrown clothes.</p>
<p>Amatulli <i>et al.</i> (2018) / <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> / 198 / Corporate social responsibility, luxury marketing, status consumption, conspicuous consumption / Experimental research / Workers and undergraduate students in a large city in Europe; respondents randomly chosen in a luxury mall; respondents recruited using Amazon Mechanical Turk (gender and age groups)</p>	<p>Luxury brands' philanthropic and legal corporate social responsibility activities are perceived as more visible and noticeable and more related to status and conspicuous luxury consumption than company-internal social responsibility initiatives. Consumers purchasing luxury mainly for enhancing social status and signalling wealth are likely to be more attracted by luxury products that communicate legal and philanthropic corporate social responsibility than company-internal social responsibility.</p>

<p>Vehmas <i>et al.</i> (2018) / <i>Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management</i> / 367 / Sustainability, circular clothes, circular economy, recycling, consumer behaviour, communication in circular and sustainable fashion / Interviews, discussions on an online platform and workshops / Consumers recruited from the general public (aged 16-78, males and females); project partners; communication, marketing and textile professionals in Finland</p>	<p>Consumers perceive circular clothes positively but they expect circular clothing to have the same qualities as clothing made from virgin fabrics and luxury clothes, such as comfort, colour fastness, outstanding quality and longevity. Consumers are interested to learn how working conditions have been improved in the fashion supply chain. They are willing to know how their more sustainable consumption choices could reduce environmental impacts created by the manufacturing of clothes. Consumers are interested to obtain more concrete information about the new look of old recycled clothes. They accept humour in fashion brands' sustainability communication based on actual sustainability improvements. However, it seems that having more information on sustainability in fashion does not significantly affect their purchase decisions. More effective communication is necessary to increase consumers' awareness of sustainability in fashion. It is necessary to promote sustainable fashion in a more attractive and interesting way to induce consumers' positive attitudes towards sustainable fashion.</p>
<p>Costa Pinto <i>et al.</i> (2019) / <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> / 52 / Luxury brands, corporate social responsibility, brand ethicality, brand personality, consumer identity goals / Experiments / Participants recruited from an online panel and undergraduate students (gender and age groups)</p>	<p>Participants perceived a sincere brand personality to be more ethical and less luxurious while a sophisticated brand personality was perceived as highly luxurious and less ethical. The influence of brand personality on brand ethicality is dependent on identity goals. Consumers with salient social identity goals perceive luxury brands as less ethical and they prefer corporate social responsibility activities that accentuate the interests of wider society for sincere brands and the interests of consumers for sophisticated brands. For consumers with strong personal identity goals, the influence of brand personality on their brand evaluations is weaker.</p>

<p>Henninger, Bürklin and Niinimäki (2019) / <i>Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management</i> / 123 / Clothes swapping, collaborative consumption, consumer behaviour / In-depth interviewing, participant observations / Attendees at swap-shop events in the UK, Finland and Germany, females dominant</p>	<p>Consumers are looking for high-quality and vintage fashion products at swap-shop events. Participants felt proud because of sharing clothes with others. The organisers of swap-shop events regarded uncertainty in supplying and low stock of fashion products as the major barriers for a more productive usage of this kind of sustainable consumption.</p>
<p>Kessous and Valette-Florence (2019) / <i>Journal of Business Research</i> / 188 / Second-hand luxury, first-hand luxury, conspicuous consumption / Album On Line technique, online questionnaires / Female and mostly highly educated consumers in France; gender and age groups</p>	<p>Purchasing brand-new products arises from luxury consumers' desire for status signalling, obtaining power and possessing high-quality products. Consumers purchase second-hand luxury to increase social status, gain financial benefits, reduce global warming and possess vintage goods. Second-hand luxury purchases may be stimulated by consumers' desire to search for unique goods that represent the original pieces or symbols of luxury collections or consumers' feelings of nostalgia reflected in respect for brand heritage when searching for vintage luxury goods.</p>
<p>Turunen and Pöyry (2019) / <i>International Journal of International Studies</i> / 143 / Luxury, second-hand luxury and fashion, luxury fashion accessories, consumer behaviour, shopping styles / Semi-structured interviews / Female participants from Finland (25-40 years old)</p>	<p>Second-hand luxury fashion has become more significant for consumers who put emphasis on the high quality, longevity and durability of materials used for the manufacturing of luxury fashion products. Consumers are interested in monetary resale value and they have quality, price-per-quality and brand consciousness. Consumers who want to purchase second-hand luxury fashion do not necessarily perceive themselves as the end-users of products. Luxury fashion consumers who value second-hand used products may be very cognised of the quality and aged condition of products. Luxury fashion consumers who search for unused products on the second-hand market have high price-per-quality awareness.</p>

<p>Sung <i>et al.</i> (2020) / <i>Fashion Practice</i> / 27 / Fashion, sustainability, sustainable business, production, design and consumption, upcycling, consumer research / Semi-structured interviews / Consumers (gender and age groups) and practitioners</p>	<p>The problems for UK material suppliers relate to the lack of the inflow of materials for upcycling, low financial support, low juridical support, complex and confusing legislation, the negative influence of recession on business growth and low companies' awareness of the need for donating textile waste to suppliers. Upcycling designers and producers face the problem of the sourcing and circulation of materials for upcycling, the lack of space for storing textiles, the lack of equipment and paying high salaries for skilled workforce. Promoting fashion goods made of upcycled textile, connecting with consumers interested in those goods and building brand reputation are the biggest problems in marketing. Retailers were of the opinion that it is difficult to create effective messages to promote upcycled fashion goods because of consumers' low awareness of upcycling, find consumers for upcycled fashion and effectively use social media to promote upcycled fashion. Consumers have low awareness of and unfavourable views on upcycling and upcycled fashion goods. This is based on the limited availability of high-quality upcycled fashion goods and the lack of the media coverage of upcycled fashion.</p>
<p>Sipilä <i>et al.</i> (2021) / <i>Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science</i> / 66 / Sustainability, luxury, extrinsic corporate social responsibility attributions, company-internal corporate social responsibility, consumer research / Secondary data and experimental research / A sample of luxury companies; luxury and non-luxury consumers, students (gender and age groups)</p>	<p>The influence of corporate social responsibility on luxury companies' financial performance is negative. In contrast to non-luxury settings, extrinsic social responsibility attributions are higher when consumers have received information on a luxury product's corporate social responsibility proposition than when corporate social responsibility information is not received at the point of purchase. In addition to the probability that consumers' extrinsic corporate social responsibility attributions may be evoked at the point of purchase, extrinsic social responsibility attributions are likely to be deepened when consumers think carefully about the motives behind luxury brands' corporate social responsibility efforts. Luxury brands can reduce the negative effects of extrinsic corporate social responsibility attributions on consumer loyalty by accentuating company-internal initiatives in corporate social responsibility communication, for example, employee satisfaction, which is based on luxury brands' dependence on fine craftsmanship. Promoting luxury brands framed as sustainable more than as exclusive may induce lowering extrinsic corporate social responsibility attributions.</p>

<p>Adigüzel and Donato (2021) / <i>Journal of Business Research</i> / 63 / Upcycled and recycled products, luxury, novelty, circular economy, consumer research / Experimental research / Self-reported luxury consumers recruited by Amazon Mechanical Turk (gender and age groups)</p>	<p>Consumers are likely to evaluate upcycled luxury goods more positively than traditional luxury goods when they feel proud to contribute to sustainable development. Consumers are likely to have higher purchase intentions of luxury brands that offer upcycled goods than luxury brands that offer recycled goods through pride and novelty. In comparison to existing luxury brands, consumers perceive upcycled goods by new luxury brands as more compatible with sustainable production when their environmental concerns are increased, which increases consumers' purchase intentions of upcycled goods versus recycled goods.</p>
<p>Karpova <i>et al.</i> (2022) / <i>Sustainability</i> / 8 / Clothes swapping, collaborative consumption / Ethnographic research / Females from the USA</p>	<p>Safety swapping risk relates to consumers' concern for the condition of clothing. Self-esteem or vulnerability swapping risk relates to consumers' fear that clothes offered for swapping could be rejected. Clothes swapping along with other forms of collaborative sustainable consumption have the potential to satisfy consumers' needs of the highest importance in Maslow's hierarchy of needs, that is, personal development, self-esteem and sustainability. However, belonging to the same social group and the psychological fit of clothes in terms of swappers' similar clothing styles are the necessary prerequisites for the success of this form of sustainable consumption.</p>

2.3. Defining and Evolution of the Corporate Social Responsibility Concept

2.3.1. Early Corporate Social Responsibility Concept

The corporate social responsibility concept was originated by Sheldon (1924) who related corporate social responsibility to the company's accountability in funding the prosperity of society parallel with maximising its profits (Yang and Guo, 2014). In the 1930s, the discussion on the purpose of the corporation was opened by proposing two contrary theories about the relationship between the corporation and society (Von Stange, 1994).

Berle and Means (1932) asked an important question: Do managers really act for the interests of shareholders in light of dispersed ownership and the separation between ownership and control in the corporation? (Panda and Leepsa, 2017). Berle and Means

(1932) argued that the interests of shareholders may be jeopardised by the concentration of economic power in management with possible adverse effects on economic activities and resource allocation. Any engagement in activities not profitable for shareholders should not be accepted, including corporate social responsibility initiatives. However, Dodd (1932), who was an advocate of consumer and labour rights and interests, stressed that corporations perform business operations and transactions because the law provides it and companies should voluntarily engage in social responsibility (Windsor, 2001). In the 1950s, Berle (1954) changed his argument on the purpose of the corporation by involving the interests of shareholders and the whole community (Von Stange, 1994).

2.3.2. Ethically Oriented Corporate Social Responsibility Concept

In Western countries, the 1950s and 1960s were the beginning of the modern era of corporate social responsibility in which business operations were under public scrutiny stimulated by the expansion of the social movements. The concept of ethically oriented corporate social responsibility was prevailing in the 1950s and 1960s and philanthropic contributions were dominant in promoting social welfare (Cochran, 2007; Hamidu, Haron and Amran, 2015; Latapi Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir, 2019).

The initial definition of corporate social responsibility was proposed by Bowen (1953) who defined it as ‘the obligations of businessmen to pursue those policies, to make those decisions, or to follow those lines of action which are desirable in terms of the objectives and values of our society’ (Bowen, 2013, p. 6). The idea of corporate citizenship was prognosticated by McGuire (1963) who argued that the responsibility of companies is not restricted only to economic and legal goals yet the company should act in a morally responsible way as a good citizen. In the late 1960s and the early 1970s, the business sector was confronted with different stakeholders’ expectations as a consequence of the raising power of the social movements on labour, consumers’ and women’s rights and ecology that resulted in government regulation (Carroll, 1999).

The 1970s were a stage in the development of the corporate social responsibility concept in which the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance was more emphasised but the ethical corporate social responsibility concept was more influential (Yang and Guo, 2014). This is evident, for example, in the suggestion of Heald (1970) that the philanthropic domain of corporate social responsibility was of the greatest

importance for managerial considerations. It is worth to mention Eilbert and Parker (1973) whose research was one of the early studies that investigated the types and importance of social responsibility activities in relation to organisational issues, such as organisational structure and financial planning and budgeting (Carroll, 1999).

Friedman (1970), the Noble Prize winning economist, vigorously argued that the only legal and social responsibility of the company is to maximise profits for its owners while investments in costly corporate social responsibility activities may cause the decline of innovations and competitiveness and even liquidations and closures (Hou and Li, 2014). The author introduced a narrowly defined concept of corporate social responsibility in his epochal essay "A Friedman doctrine: The social responsibility of business is to increase its profits" published for The New York Times. As stated by Friedman (1970), 'in a free-enterprise, private-property system, a corporate executive is an employee of the owners of the business' having 'direct responsibility to his employers' (Friedman, 1970, p. 123).

In the 1970s, Sethi (1975) introduced the concept of corporate social responsiveness and corporate social performance (Cochran, 2007). The emergence of the social responsiveness concept reflects the need for following a proactive approach in responding to the pressures of society. Social responsiveness is a phase in implementing social responsibility policies when companies, for example, prevent pollution. The concept of corporate social performance implies that the company practically responds to corporate social responsibility problems, encompassing corporate social responsibility, social responsiveness and social issues management (Sethi, 1979). Manne and Wallich (1972) stressed a voluntary nature of corporate social responsibility. However, it is difficult to recognise purely voluntary social responsibility engagement because of implementing social responsibility policies as a respond to the pressures of society (Carroll, 1979).

Kassarjian (1971) studied consumers' reactions to the introduction of a new environmentally friendly product and found that consumers were willing to pay a premium price for social responsibility (Kassarjian, 1971). Anderson and Cunningham (1972) stressed that socially responsible consumers are likely to be professionally, financially and educationally fulfilled, more unprejudiced, open-minded and cosmopolitan, less concerned with their position within a social hierarchy and more connected with the values, needs and social relationships of their community. The authors demonstrated that consumer corporate social responsibility awareness can be the foundation for market segmentation

(Anderson and Cunningham, 1972). This is in line with the suggestion of Kelly (1971) that market segmentation on the basis of consumers' corporate social responsibility concerns and practices was an emerging phenomenon (Kelly, 1971).

Webster (1975) highlighted that the socially conscious consumer is aware of corporate social responsibility issues and the need for combating environmental deterioration and supporting social progress through socially responsible purchases. The socially conscious consumer is likely to be a female, have a higher income and purchase ethical products in order to benefit the community (Webster, 1975). Brooker (1976) found that high self-actualisation is of high importance for consumers who declared themselves to be socially responsible (Brooker, 1976).

One of the influential authors in the 1970-s was Frederick (1978) who praised the social responsiveness concept in terms of its usefulness in stimulating research on the link between the corporation and society and the identification of factors that prevent companies to proactively respond to the requirements of society. However, the corporate social responsiveness concept does not clarify the meaning of corporate social responsibility and the nature of the relationship between the corporation and society. It does not define social betterment, social priorities and criteria for social performance. The theory of social responsiveness is a static conception without much consideration of how to anticipate social change and values for companies to follow in building the capacity to proactively respond to environmental and social pressures (Frederick, 1994).

Carroll (1979) introduced the model of corporate social responsibility which breaks the company's responsibilities towards society into the economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic responsibilities (Carroll, 1979). Carroll's (1979) model has become the most popular framework for theorists and empirical researchers in discussing and investigating corporate social responsibility, although the model has been criticised. For example, the model does not address the possibility of resolving the conflicting relationship between the economic and ethical domain of corporate social responsibility, that is, between maximising profitability and sweatshop working conditions (Crane and Matten, 2016).

2.3.3. Business Oriented Corporate Social Responsibility Concept

Jones (1980) opened a new stage in the development of the concept by suggesting that corporate social responsibility should be understood as the managerial process of decision-making on corporate behaviour. In other words, the operationalisation of the idea of corporate social responsibility was confirmed through developing new frameworks, techniques and models for assessing the effectiveness of corporate social responsibility engagement (Latapi Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir, 2019). For example, Cochran and Wood (1984) explored the link between corporate social responsibility and financial performance using the reputation index method for measuring social responsibility (Cochran and Wood, 1984).

Freeman's (1984) stakeholder theory puts forward the idea of satisfying the interests of all important stakeholders equally because the managerial understanding of how different stakeholder groups interact in the value creation process can positively influence corporate value and competitiveness (Freeman, 2010; Freeman and Dmytriiev, 2017). It became more evident that the growth of the corporation could not be accelerated by considering only the interests of shareholders (Mainardes, Alves and Raposo, 2011). Drucker (1984) emphasised that the responsibility of the company is undoubtedly to strengthen its economic position. Social responsibility initiatives should be regarded as the stimuli for business opportunities in management decision-making (Wartick and Cochran, 1985).

In 1991, Carroll presented his model as the pyramid of corporate social responsibility (Carroll, 1991). A study by Wang and Dewhirst (1992) reveals that boards of directors considered consumers and government the most important stakeholders, followed by shareholders, employees and society (Wang and Dewhirst, 1992). Donaldson and Preston (1995) explained that the managerial aspect of stakeholder theory is related to the practice of examining the link between stakeholder management and planned and desired results, such as profit maximisation, reputation, market share, stability and growth. The normative aspect of stakeholder theory is associated with interpreting the purpose of the corporation based on following ethical norms in considering the interests of all stakeholders (Donaldson and Preston, 1995).

Burke and Logsdon (1996) were the first scholars who attempted to assess the strategic advantages of the company's corporate social responsibility engagement (Latapi Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir, 2019). The scholars explained that following a strategic approach to corporate social responsibility implementation means that social responsibility is incorporated into the mission and goals of the business and utilised to create its competitive advantages over rivals in the long-run. The company responds to anticipated and emerging corporate social responsibility problems on a voluntary basis and uses effective tools to communicate its corporate social responsibility initiatives to its stakeholders (Burke and Logsdon, 1996). Jones and Wicks (1999) recommended the convergence of the instrumental and normative elements of stakeholder theory through formulating a theory that aims to prove 'how managers can create morally sound approaches to business and make them work' (Jones and Wicks, 1999, p. 206).

The prevalence of the business oriented concept of corporate social responsibility in the academic literature in the 1990s reflects the intensified institutionalisation of corporate social responsibility through integrating corporate social responsibility policies into companies' business frameworks and practices. Corporate social responsibility issues, such as resource depletion, consumer rights, working conditions and workforce diversity, were already involved into the managerial decision-making process. The strategic reconciliation between corporate social responsibility and maximising profits was discussed in terms of how the strategic implementation of corporate social responsibility strengthens the economic position of companies and it resulted in the emergence of the concept of the business case for corporate social responsibility (Carroll, 2015).

2.3.4. Sustainable Development and Corporate Sustainability

During the 1980s, public concern about pollution reached a very high level, which brought the concept of sustainable development on the scene. One of the most important events that happened as a consequence of the need for taking serious actions regarding protecting the environment was the establishment of the World Commission on Environment and Development as a sub-organisation of the United Nations in 1983. The commission is commonly called the Brundtland Commission because it was 'chaired by the Norwegian Prime Minister Gro Harlem Brundtland' (Latapi Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir, 2019, p. 7). Sustainable development is defined by Brundtland Commission (1987) as 'development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the

ability of future generations to meet their needs' (United Nations General Assembly, 1987 cited in Gimenez, Sierra and Rodon, 2012, p. 150). Dyllick and Hockerts (2002) define corporate sustainability as 'meeting the needs of a firm's direct and indirect stakeholders (such as shareholders, employees, clients, pressure groups, communities, etc.), without compromising its ability to meet the needs of future stakeholders' (Dyllick and Hockerts, 2002, p. 131).

The concept of sustainability evolved from a narrow concept of ecological sustainability to a tridimensional concept that incorporates the economic, ecological and social aspects of business in society. Since the Earth Summit or the Rio Conference, which is the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, 'the environmental (ecological), economic, and social dimensions' are recognised as the three facets of sustainable development, although the definition of sustainability provided by the Brundtland Commission (1983) did not specify this ternary classification (Lehtonen, 2004, p. 200).

2.3.4.1. Corporate Social Responsibility in the Globalised Economy

Because the globalisation of the world was intensified in the 1990s, corporate social responsibility became a growing international phenomenon. Managers in modern corporations deal with the problem of performing business operations in different business environments with conflicting social responsibility pressures (Carroll, 2015).

Crane and Matten (2016) explain the significance of the ongoing process of globalisation for the evolution of corporate social responsibility theory and practice by pointing at the role of multinational corporations:

'They are accused of exploiting workers in developing countries, destroying the environment, and, by abusing their economic power, engaging developing countries in a so-called "race to the bottom". However true these accusations are in practice, there is no doubt that globalisation is the most current and demanding arena in which corporations have to define and legitimatise "the rights and wrongs" of their behaviour' (Crane and Matten, 2016, p. 18).

Although corporate behaviour can be by some means regulated through enforceable laws and shared norms, multinational corporations perform in a highly unregulated context on a global scale, which provides the space for ignoring corporate social responsibility (Gond, Palazzo and Basu, 2009). Nevertheless, a raising number of companies adopt in principle or true commitments to corporate social responsibility because of a high media risk of tarnishing corporate reputation and the possible adverse effects of ignoring social responsibility on profitability (Sharma *et al.*, 2018).

2.3.5. Strategic Corporate Social Responsibility Concept in the New Millennium

In the 2000s, a notable contribution to the debate on corporate social responsibility came from Lantos (2001) who emphasised that a strategic approach is inseparable from managing and implementing corporate social responsibility (Latapi Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir, 2019). Lantos (2001) supports Friedman's (1970) theory of social responsibility by arguing that contributing to social betterment can be part of strategic plans only if it results in profit maximisation. The author proposes that ethical corporate social responsibility should be the compulsory dimension of social responsibility toward stakeholders, which involves, for example, fair labour practices and ethically sourced materials. The philanthropic domain of corporate social responsibility is not a justifiable corporate activity, that is, it is not a pertinent choice for the achievement of the strategic goals of profit-oriented organisations, although the author praises charitable donations and other good deeds without harming the principal-agent relationship (Lantos, 2001).

On the other hand, Porter and Kramer (2002) believe that corporate philanthropy can be a source of competitive advantages based on applying a strategic and focused approach. For example, improving education in the local community can boost companies' competitiveness because it creates more competent and skilful human resources. Porter and Kramer (2002) criticise the ineffective practice of using corporate philanthropy for promoting the company's image through cause-related marketing without developing capabilities to compete with rivals (Porter and Kramer, 2002).

Some authors draw attention to the importance of considering the society-corroding effects of corporate giving. Namely, corporate philanthropy may cause adverse effects on social progress if local governments and civil society organisations become passive in dealing with corporate social responsibility problems because of relying on charitable donations

(Rasche *et al.*, 2008; Gond, Palazzo and Basu, 2009). Likewise, corporate philanthropy may have negative effects on society through generating the effect of compliance without pressure, which implies that the user of a charitable donation is likely to comply with the requests of the donor without pressure (Freedman and Fraser, 1966; Palazzo and Richter, 2005).

A good example of the harmful effects of corporate giving is the practice of the tobacco industry to grant scientific research directed towards proving the neutral effects of smoking on human health, which is encapsulated in the following quote:

‘When the tobacco industry realised that the studies proving the health damages of tobacco consumption were becoming a threat to their very existence, they started to foster research that cast doubt upon the addictive character of nicotine and research that associated lung cancer with anything but smoking’ (Palazzo and Richter, 2005, p. 389).

2.3.5.1. Concept of Shared Value

Porter and Kramer’s (2006) view on creating shared value indicates that a strategic approach to managing corporate social responsibility should provide the effective identification of social responsibility initiatives that create value for the business sector and society. Corporate social responsibility activities and projects need to be selected on the basis of their potential to generate the greatest shared value, that is, to strengthen a company’s competitiveness and improve the economic benefits and social betterment of the communities in which the company performs its business (Porter and Kramer, 2006).

2.3.5.2. Explicit and Implicit Corporate Social Responsibility

Matten and Moon (2008) explain explicit corporate social responsibility as the company’s strategic, intentional and voluntary engagement in addressing important corporate social responsibility issues. Initiatives within explicit social responsibility refer to, for example, charitable donations for remedying natural disasters or improving labour rights and working conditions in supply chains considering the expectations of stakeholders. Implicit corporate social responsibility relates to the company’s response to the institutional environment in satisfying the mandatory requirements of society. Initiatives within implicit

social responsibility refer to, for example, mandatory obligations towards employees. The European model of corporate social responsibility is more implicit in accordance with the functioning of the coordinated market economies (Matten and Moon, 2008).

2.3.6. Corporate Citizenship Concept of Corporate Social Responsibility

The idea of corporate citizenship indicates that the enterprise should perform and operate in a morally acceptable manner just as a good, responsible and respectable citizen behaves (Carroll, 1999; Garriga and Melé, 2004). The corporation is considered an artificial entity and it is possible to draw a parallel between the corporation and the citizen as they both have certain rights and responsibilities in a society in which they exist, behave or operate. In contrast, corporate social responsibility opponents use Friedman's (1970) arguments to discuss the untenability of the tenet that the company is morally responsible for its performance and actions (Crane and Matten, 2016).

Friedman (1970) explained that only human beings have a voluntary moral responsibility for their behaviour, praising only altruistic givings coming from the corporation's owners or executives based on donating their own money. The corporation as an artificial person 'may have artificial responsibilities, but "business" as a whole cannot be said to have responsibilities, even in this vague sense' (Friedman, 1970, p. 123). Directors and managers have their fiduciary duties to act in the best interest of the owner of the company who employs them, that is, to defend the owner's assets, investments and profits. Corporations, although owned by shareholders, exist independently of them because shareholders' liability is limited to the amount they invested in their company, which means that 'shareholders are not responsible for the debts or damages caused by the corporation' (Crane and Matten, 2016, p. 46). According to Friedman (1970), voluntary contributions to social betterment mean that, for example, the corporation should 'refrain from increasing the price of the product in order to contribute to the social objective of preventing inflation, even though a price increase would be in the best interests of the corporation' (Friedman, 1970, p. 123).

2.3.7. Micro and Macro Approach to Corporate Social Responsibility

A macro approach to corporate social responsibility incorporates the world-culture paradigm and institutional theory in the understanding of the concept (Buendía-Martínez and Carrasco Monteagudo, 2020). The world-culture model of corporate social responsibility emphasises that the company is a constituent of the globalised economy, which causes that the company adopts social responsibility policies (Shamir, 2011).

A micro approach to corporate social responsibility is about the role of corporate governance in pursuing social responsibility. Corporate social responsibility becomes a constitutive part of the company's business framework and culture as a result of different pressures from the external environment (Schultz and Wehmeier, 2010).

2.3.7.1. Implementing Corporate Social Responsibility in the Global Supply Chain

The implementation of corporate social responsibility policies in the supply chains of multinational corporations has been obstructed by the influence of ethical relativism and the absence of a strong and democratic regulatory framework and organised protest groups in developing countries. Criticism on the unethical behaviour of multinational corporations is more apparent in the developed world than in host developing countries. The cost reduction strategy has been successfully applied by multinational corporations because Third World governments supported by international organisations have given priority to economic growth rather than social responsibility implementation while governments in Western countries have not considerably succeeded in regulating multinational corporations' activities (Boström and Micheletti, 2016).

It is considered that neither universalism nor relativism can offer a framework for intercultural dialogue on solving the child labour problem or any other social responsibility issue in the developing world. By positing that a set of common moral norms could be relevant for all cultures, universalism ignores the fact that different cultures cannot offer the same understanding of universality. Relativism implies that each culture has its own ethical norms incomparable with the ethical norms of other cultures. According to a constructivist approach to intercultural ethics, communication on criticising existing ethical norms is indispensable for the formulation of more appropriate ethical norms as the base for solving environmental and social problems in the globalised world (Evanoff, 2004).

Third World countries need to pass a stage in their socio-economic development in which enacted and enforced legislation will prevent and eliminate child labour and sweatshops and combat hazardous pollution. It is necessary to develop a democratic process of dialogue and compromise in which different parties should work on improving labour, working and ecology standards in developing countries and it could improve implementing corporate social responsibility policies in the global supply chain (Hindman and Smith, 1999; D'Avolio, 2004).

2.3.8. Consumer-driven Model of Corporate Social Responsibility

Claydon (2013) introduced the model of consumer-driven corporate responsibility as a result of the criticism of corporate social responsibility models, primarily the model of the pyramid of corporate social responsibility. The pyramid model of corporate social responsibility posits that the company's economic performance is the foundation for its corporate social responsibility engagement without emphasising that profit maximisation is also dependent on fulfilling the legal, ethical and philanthropic corporate social responsibilities. Claydon (2013) argues that the model of consumer-driven corporate responsibility is beneficial for the company and its stakeholders. The satisfaction of consumers' demands for corporate social responsibility improves brand reputation and boosts consumer base and profits. The requirements of stakeholders and the environment are satisfied and the company's value is increased (Claydon, 2013).

The Table 2.4. summarises the development of the corporate social responsibility concept in the academic literature from 1920 until the present time with the contributions of the relevant authors in the field. It shows inconsistency in defining corporate social responsibility and mirrors an ongoing practice of not finding an agreement on how to use social responsibility to achieve greater profits and increase competitiveness. Dahlsrud (2008) emphasises that it is necessary to develop a better understanding of 'how CSR is socially constructed in a specific context and how to take this into account when business strategies are developed' (Dahlsrud, 2008, p. 6). Corporate social responsibility initiatives are driven by a myriad of factors, including the industry and social environment in which companies operate (Porter and Kramer, 2006) as well as consumers' motivations and willingness to support companies' corporate social responsibility engagement (Morrison and Bridwell, 2011; Claydon, 2013).

Table 2.4: Evolution of the Corporate Social Responsibility Concept

Period	Authors	References
1920-1949	Sheldon (1924) argued that the responsibility of companies is profit maximisation and social welfare.	Yang and Guo (2014)
	Berle and Means (1932) believed that the responsibility of directors and managers is only maximising shareholder wealth.	Panda and Leepsa (2017)
	Dodd (1932) indicated that the company's responsibility is enhancing both economic position and social responsibility.	Von Stange (1994)
1950-1969	Bowen (1953) proposed the initial definition of corporate social responsibility as an ethical concept and recommended that large corporations implement corporate social responsibility policies.	Bowen (1953), Carroll (1999)
	Berle (1954) recognised that the corporation has the responsibilities toward shareholders and society.	Von Stange (1994)
	Drucker (1954) argued that the company has the basic responsibility to maximise profits but also to contribute to social progress and stability.	Joyner and Payne (2002)
	Heald (1957) believed that the company's purpose is to enhance economic performance and social betterment.	Chakraborty (2015)
	Frederic (1960) suggested that the production of goods and services and the usage of economic resources and workforce should be done with the aim of benefiting society and not only for the interests of the owners of companies.	Carroll (1999)
	Davis (1960) introduced his Iron Law of Responsibility and indicated that corporate social responsibility investments bring positive returns in the long run.	Morrison and Bridwell (2011)
	McGuire (1963) foreshadowed the idea of corporate citizenship and defined corporate social responsibility in terms of the company's responsibilities that exceed the economic and legal obligations.	Carroll (1999)
	Davis and Blomstrom (1966) defined corporate social responsibility considering companies' interests and the interests of different parties affected by business operations.	Carroll (1999)
	Walton (1967) emphasised the importance of companies' voluntary engagement in corporate social responsibility and readiness to endure high costs for social responsibility implementation.	Morrison and Bridwell (2011)
1970-1979	Heald (1970) explained that corporate philanthropy was the dominant managerial concern.	Carroll (1999)
	Friedman (1970) argued that corporate social responsibility is solely profit maximisation.	Friedman (1970)
	Johnson (1971) indicated that strong companies with high profits can successfully pursue social responsibility.	Carroll (1999)

	Anderson and Cunningham (1972) studied the characteristics of socially conscious consumers and highlighted that consumers' corporate social responsibility awareness can be the basis for market segmentation.	Anderson and Cunningham (1972)
	Manne (1972) argued that companies have the responsibilities beyond the economic responsibility. The financial benefits of corporate social responsibility investments cannot be easily measured because it is complicated to make the distinction between business costs declared to have been made for social purpose and actual costs made for enhancing the well-being of society.	Carroll (1999), Morrison and Bridwell (2011)
	Davis (1973) emphasised that corporate social responsibility goes beyond the minimal legal responsibilities.	Davis (1973)
	Sethi (1975) drew attention to the concept of corporate social responsiveness and corporate social performance.	Sethi (1975)
	Webster (1975) defined socially responsible consumers as individuals who are aware of corporate social responsibility and buy ethically sourced products to help protect the environment and support social betterment.	Webster (1975)
	Brooker (1976) emphasised that socially responsible behaviour allows consumers to self-actualise, that is, to realise their full potential.	Brooker (1976)
	Frederick (1978) explained that the managerial dimension of corporate social responsibility started to take prevalence over the ethical dimension of corporate social responsibility.	Frederick (1994)
	Carroll (1979) interpreted corporate social responsibility as the company's economic, legal, ethical and discretionary or philanthropic responsibilities.	Carroll (1979)
1980-1989	Jones (1980) explained that corporate social responsibility is pursued through the managerial process of decision-making. The author put emphasis on the operationalisation of corporate social responsibility.	Latapi Agudelo, Jóhannsdóttir and Davídsdóttir (2019)
	Cochran and Wood (1984) discussed the social performance and financial performance relationship. There is no strong support for the link between social responsibility and financial performance.	Cochran and Wood (1984)
	Drucker (1984) proposed that corporate social responsibility is profit maximisation and social responsibility initiatives can be used to increase profits.	Wartick and Cochran (1985)
	Freeman (1984) argued that the company needs to satisfy the interest of multiple stakeholder groups.	Freeman (2010)

	Aupperle, Carroll and Hatfield (1985) indicated that there is no relationship between social responsibility and profitability.	Aupperle, Carroll and Hatfield (1985)
	Wartick and Cochran (1985) introduced the model of the evolution of corporate social responsibility. Corporate social responsibility incorporates the economic responsibility, the public responsibility, social responsiveness and social issues management.	Wartick and Cochran (1985)
	Brundtland Commission (1987) defined sustainable development.	Gimenez, Sierra and Rodon (2012)
	Epstein (1987) stressed that corporate social responsibility should be understood in terms of the enterprise's social responsiveness and utilising business ethics in managing social responsibility problems to achieve desirable outcomes for the interests of stakeholders.	Carroll (1999)
1990-1999	Carroll (1991) presented his corporate social responsibility model as the pyramid of corporate social responsibility.	Carroll (1991)
	Meznar, Chrisman and Carroll (1991) discussed different business strategies in terms of pursuing the sole purpose of profit maximisation or engaging in corporate social responsibility based on increasing social benefits and/or reducing social costs.	Meznar, Chrisman and Carroll (1991)
	Wang and Dewhirst (1992) asserted that directors and managers considered the interests of consumers and government highly relevant for satisfying organisational goals.	Wang and Dewhirst (1992)
	Donaldson and Preston (1995) discussed the managerial and normative aspects of stakeholder theory.	Donaldson and Preston (1995)
	Burke and Logsdon (1996) explained the concept of strategic corporate social responsibility and the benefits of using a strategic approach to social responsibility for creating competitive advantages in the long run.	Burke and Logsdon (1996)
	Elkington (1998) coined the concept of the triple bottom line which relates to people, planet and profit. It suggests that the company can achieve positive financial results by supporting social progress and implementing environmentally friendly policies.	González-Rodríguez, Díaz-Fernández and Simonetti (2015)
	Sharma and Vredenburg (1998) advocated following a strategic proactive approach in responding to environmental and social pressures that in return strengthens competitiveness.	Sharma and Vredenburg (1998)
	Jones and Wicks (1999) stressed the relevance of merging the instrumental and normative dimensions of stakeholder theory.	Jones and Wicks (1999)

	Woodward-Clyde (1999) regarded corporate social responsibility as a contract between business and society which allows companies to operate. In return, companies need to comply with the environmentally and socially acceptable standards of behaviour.	Dahlsrud (2008)
2000s	Lantos (2001) argued that corporate social responsibility implementation may be beneficial only if it contributes to the company's only possible purpose of maximising profits.	Lantos (2001)
	The European Commission (2001) defined corporate social responsibility considering companies' involvement in ecology, social issues and stakeholders on a voluntary basis.	Dahlsrud (2008)
	Jensen (2002) indicated that the wider adoption of stakeholder theory in managing business practices causes the reduction of social welfare based on inappropriate resource allocation decisions.	Jensen (2002)
	Porter and Kramer (2002) stressed the importance of using a strategic and focused approach to corporate philanthropy to create competitive advantages in the long run.	Porter and Kramer (2002)
	Schwartz and Carroll (2003) introduced the three-domain model of corporate social responsibility as an attempt to allow the possibility of subsuming the philanthropic domain of corporate social responsibility under the economic or ethical dimension, which is based on the reasoning that philanthropic initiatives can have different motives.	Schwartz and Carroll (2003)
	Porter and Kramer (2006) proposed the concept of shared value for the company and society.	Porter and Kramer (2006)
	Silberhorn and Warren (2007) indicated that corporate social responsibility has become a strategic business practice. However, it is questionable if this trend will continue to grow to the extent that supports the development of a truly circular economy and sustainable society.	Silberhorn and Warren (2007)
	Matten and Moon (2008) explained the distinction between explicit corporate social responsibility in liberal economies and implicit corporate social responsibility in coordinated economies.	Matten and Moon (2008)
	Claydon (2013) offered the model of consumer-driven corporate social responsibility. The model highlights that satisfying consumers' social responsibility demands is the base for the effective use of social responsibility and maximising profits.	Claydon (2013)

2.3.9. Link between Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainability

The phenomenon of corporate social responsibility has been described by different terms, such as 'social issues management, public policy and business, stakeholder management, corporate accountability' as well as 'corporate citizenship and corporate sustainability' (Garriga and Melé, 2004, p. 51). When discussing corporate behaviour and the responsibilities of companies towards society and the environment, the concept of corporate social responsibility and the concept of corporate sustainability have been used individually or in a combination. For example, Van Den Brink and Van Der Woerd (2004) as well as Camilleri (2017) use the term corporate sustainability and responsibility (Van Den Brink and Van Der Woerd, 2004; Camilleri, 2017) while Van Marrewijk (2003) uses the term corporate sustainability/corporate social responsibility (Van Marrewijk, 2003).

In the past, corporate social responsibility was predominantly discussed in terms of integrating social concerns with companies' business performance and relationships with stakeholders, such as equitable labour practices, human welfare and philanthropy (Keijzers, 2002). The environmental dimension was not explicitly emphasised in the early definitions of corporate social responsibility, although environmental issues are involved in social responsibility (Carroll, 1999). Environmental concerns were treated as a subgroup of social issues by some authors (Graves and Waddock, 1994; Agle, Mitchell and Sonnenfeld, 1999).

The environmental impacts of business operations are regarded as a crucial part of contemporary corporate social responsibility (Uddin, Tarique and Hassan, 2008). Dahlsrud (2008) emphasises that the environmental and social responsibilities are equally involved in explaining the concept of social responsibility (Dahlsrud, 2008). A considerable body of the academic literature discusses the environmental dimension of corporate social responsibility (Rahman and Post, 2012; Rashid, Rahman and Khalid, 2014) and sustainability (Goodland, 1995; Morelli, 2011; Moldan, Janoušková and Hák, 2012). Likewise, the academic literature has paid increasing attention to the explanation of the social dimension of sustainability (Hutchins and Sutherland, 2008; Dempsey *et al.*, 2011; Vallance, Perkins and Dixon, 2011) and the integration of the economic, environmental and social dimensions of sustainability (Kaptein and Wempe, 2001; Lehtonen, 2004; Schüz, 2012). As it has been proposed by academics and practitioners, satisfying the sustainable development goals requires following economic, ecological and social standards and

principles in performing business, which is very much like what the concept of corporate social responsibility indicates (Montiel, 2008).

The convergence of corporate social responsibility and corporate sustainability is also evident in academic research. For example, Janssen, Vanhamme and Leblanc (2017) measured consumers' corporate social responsibility beliefs by the use of sustainability indicators. The statements used refer to the credibility of a brand's sustainability claim, fit with sustainability and environmental responsibility (Janssen, Vanhamme and Leblanc, 2017). Kim *et al.* (2015) measured consumers' perceptions of sustainability on the basis of the statements related to providing social activities for local communities, making social contributions, caring about human rights, hiring local people, serving social responsibility as well as corporate transparency in business management, corporate governance, corporate accountability, using green technologies and investing for environmental protection (Kim *et al.*, 2015).

The concept of corporate social responsibility, following Carroll's (1991) model, proposes the crucial role of the economic responsibility in fulfilling other pillars of social responsibility. The legal, ethical and philanthropic dimensions of social responsibility supplement the primary motive of the business sector to deliver desired products for society and to make profits by selling those products, which allows adding value, that is, benefiting companies' stakeholders (Carroll, 1991). Similarly, Bansal (2005) explains the economic dimension of corporate sustainability as value creation, which implies that the goal of economic prosperity is reflected in achieving strong financial performance, enhancing shareholders' equity and dividends, creating more jobs, providing good salaries and professional improvements for workers and executives and delivering products for consumers. However, Bansal (2005) emphasises that the complementarity between the economic, environmental and social responsibilities is necessary to follow sustainability (Bansal, 2005) while the concept of corporate social responsibility regards the economic, environmental and social pillars as independent (Garavan and McGuire, 2010).

It has been argued that corporate social responsibility transcends corporate sustainability because the concept of sustainability contributes to the social responsibility discussion. Corporate sustainability is therefore an extension of corporate social responsibility and a specific way of approaching the concept of social responsibility (Garavan and McGuire, 2010). According to this view, corporate social responsibility is a very broad and

comprehensive concept which involves various issues related to the responsibilities of the corporation to deliver economic, environmental and social benefits to its stakeholders and follow the sustainable development goals (Garriga and Melé, 2004; De Bakker, Groenewegen and Hond, 2005).

Although the standardised definition of corporate social responsibility has not been proposed (Carroll, 1999; Montiel, 2008), as Dahlsrud (2008) explains, the existing definitions of corporate social responsibility have in common that they encompass the economic, environmental, social, stakeholder and voluntariness dimensions (Dahlsrud, 2008). This is in line with the suggestion of Van Marrewijk (2003) that the economic, environmental and social pillars of sustainability can be translated into corporate social responsibility followed by companies as a holistic approach and a long-term strategy in interacting with various stakeholders and contributing to sustainable development on a voluntary basis (Van Marrewijk, 2003).

The integration of the economic, environmental and social dimensions into the concept of sustainable development formed the foundation for the generally accepted definitions of corporate social responsibility in international organisations, such as OECD, Commission of the European Communities and International Business Leaders Forum (Lehtonen, 2004). The definition of corporate social responsibility provided by Commission of the European Communities (2001) stands out as the definition with the highest frequency counts from Google (Dahlsrud, 2008).

In this paper, I widely use the term corporate social responsibility to refer to a business approach that companies use to address sustainability challenges and contribute to sustainable development by fulfilling their economic, environmental and social responsibilities towards their stakeholders on a voluntary basis. I adopt the definition of corporate social responsibility provided by Commission of the European Communities (2001) which relates corporate social responsibility to 'a concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns in their business operations and in their interaction with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis' (Commission of the European Communities, 2001 cited in Dahlsrud, 2008, p. 7).

2.3.10. Connecting Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainability with Business Ethics

Any discussion on corporate social responsibility and sustainability always involves the concept of ethics. Following corporate social responsibility and sustainability involves ethical matters and requires that companies make ethical business decisions (Crane and Matten, 2016; Torelli, 2021). Fisher and Lovell (2006) explain that ethics is about doing good deeds while morality is concerned with justice in terms of preventing wrong deeds and making restitutions when immoral acts have been done (Fisher and Lovell, 2006). Crane and Matten (2016) write that ethics is related to 'the study of morality and the application of reason to elucidate specific rules and principles that determine morally acceptable courses of action' while ethical theories refer to 'the codifications of these rules and principles' (Crane and Matten, 2016, p. 8).

The link between business ethics and corporate social responsibility has not been clarified in the academic literature. Bowen (1953), who is often referred as the father of corporate social responsibility, stressed that business morality is a synonym for social responsibility (Bowen, 2013). The concept of business ethics and the concept of corporate social responsibility are used as synonyms, although the concept of business ethics is often limited to philosophical theories about the understanding of morality while the concept of corporate social responsibility has been explained by different theories, including ethical theories, such as normative stakeholder theory and sustainable development, or instrumental theories, such as shareholder theory, shared value theory and cause-related marketing (Carroll, 1999; Garriga and Melé, 2004).

Citing Crane and Matten (2016) again, business ethics is concerned with 'the study of business situations, activities, and decisions where issues of right and wrong are addressed' and it is basically related to 'issues not covered by law, or where there is no definite consensus on whether something is right or wrong' (Crane and Matten, 2016, pp. 5-6). De George (1987) emphasised that any ethical theory, such as utilitarian, deontological, teleological or virtue ethics, does not offer a comprehensive framework for dealing with complex ethical issues in performing business. The field of business ethics is an established field which requires an interdisciplinary approach to study the ethical dimensions of decision-making in organisations. According to De George (1987), business ethics is a broad concept that incorporates corporate social responsibility and ethics in business (De George, 1987).

Weller (2020) found that senior managers believe that corporate social responsibility is a part of business ethics (Weller, 2020) while Brunk (2012) discovered that consumers think that ethical corporate behaviour relates to behaving in a socially responsible way (Brunk, 2012). Gheraia, Saadaoui and Abdelli (2019) conclude that 'both corporate social responsibility and business ethics are part of the other' (Gheraia, Saadaoui and Abdelli, 2019, p. 2026).

Ferrell *et al.* (2019) addressed the link between business ethics and corporate social responsibility by studying consumer brand attitudes towards corporate social responsibility and business ethics. Regarding measuring consumers' expectations for companies' corporate social responsibility, the authors used the statements about supporting communities, including sustainability information for all stakeholders, supporting employee diversity and providing fair return on investors. Measuring consumers' expectations for companies' ethical behaviour involved the statements about engaging in bribery, being transparent in stakeholder engagement and engaging in misleading or deceptive conduct with consumers (Ferrell *et al.*, 2019).

In academic research, however, business ethics and corporate social responsibility are more often used as the overlapping construct. Joyner and Payne (2002) treated business ethics as the ethical responsibilities within Carroll's (1979) model of corporate social responsibility when addressing the link between values, corporate social responsibility and business ethics and their possible links with financial performance (Joyner and Payne, 2002). Furthermore, researchers examining consumers' ethical behaviour commonly utilise ethics scales for measuring consumers' beliefs on corporate behaviour and business practices associated with both corporate social responsibility and business ethics (Vitell and Muncy, 2005). White, MacDonnell and Ellard (2012) examined consumers' ethical behaviour and used the term Fairtrade products when referring to ethical products (White, MacDonnell and Ellard, 2012). Sierra *et al.* (2017) employed corporate social responsibility measures for evaluating the customer perceived ethicality of a brand and it was appraised by the use of the statements about if the brand is socially responsible and environmentally responsible as well as if the brand creates new jobs, supports good causes and contributes to society (Sierra *et al.*, 2017). For evaluating the brand's perceived ethicality, Costa Pinto *et al.* (2019) used the statements about being ethical, socially responsible, socially conscious and sustainable (Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019).

Being sustainable implies that the company's corporate social responsibility engagement reflects its true dedication to sustainable development. Acting in an environmentally responsible way requires that the company contributes to environmental sustainability without violating the social pillar of sustainability. Corporate behaviour that involves labour exploitation and abuse in supply chains cannot be regarded as sustainable or ethical (Torelli, 2021).

The fundamental economic responsibilities of business organisations are often in conflict with their ethical responsibilities. Satisfying the economic dimension of social responsibility is threatened by developing environmentally friendly production processes, purchasing costly clean technologies and improving workers' well-being. However, maximising profitability by violating the environmental and social aspects of business cannot be considered sustainable or ethical (Crane and Matten, 2016).

2.3.11. Future of Corporate Social Responsibility

Business organisations will continue to face the pressure of their constituencies to act beyond satisfying the economic responsibilities and obeying the law. Current trends in responding to environmental and social problems contradict the scenario that corporate social responsibility will be embraced by profit-oriented companies to a great extent. The trend of social entrepreneurship will continue to grow based on the need to find new solutions for social responsibility problems (Carroll, 2015).

The new crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic has left devastating effects on the global economy and poor social consequences. Under these conditions, social enterprises have the challenging opportunities to address social issues for which the private and public sector cannot offer solutions (Buendía-Martínez and Carrasco Monteagudo, 2020).

2.3.12. Link between Corporate Social Responsibility and Social Entrepreneurship

Emerging from Davis' (1960) Iron Law of Responsibility, legitimacy theory argues that companies search for legitimacy through satisfying their responsibilities within a social contract between business and society, which is common for both corporate social responsibility and social entrepreneurship (Adler, Mansi and Pandey, 2018; Palakshappa and Grant, 2018). Legitimacy is associated with 'a judgment of resource-holding audiences about the acceptability, desirability, or appropriateness of an organisation' (Überbacher, 2014, p. 667).

In comparison to organisations with clearly defined market goals, which are profit oriented companies that use corporate social responsibility for increasing their competitive advantages and profits, social enterprises face the problem of attaining legitimacy from different audiences with whom they interact because of the opposite nature of profit and social goals (Agrawal and Hockerts, 2013; Park and Bae, 2020).

The emergence of social enterprise is commonly described as 'a businesslike contrast to the traditional nonprofit organisation' (Dart, 2004, p. 411) and 'a natural extension of CSR' (Buendía-Martínez and Carrasco Monteagudo, 2020, p. 14). A separation line between social responsibility and social entrepreneurship is the social mission of social entrepreneurship (Petrella and Richez-Battesti, 2014).

Both concepts involve sustainability. As already discussed in this paper, corporate social responsibility and sustainability are nowadays used individually or in a combination. It is evident in the practice of many companies to publish non-financial reports as corporate social responsibility or corporate sustainability reports (Pirnea, Olaru and Moisa, 2011). Social mission, sustainability and environmentalism appear to be equally important for social entrepreneurship (Weerawardena and Mort, 2006).

2.4. Research in the Corporate Social Responsibility Field

2.4.1. Prevailing Research Approach in the Corporate Social Responsibility Field

Rather than investigating how companies can implement, perform and manage corporate social responsibility in order to increase their competitiveness and maximise returns on social responsibility investments, the discussion on if companies should utilise a normative or instrumental approach to social responsibility was dominant in the academic literature. This practice has the root in the lack of consistency in defining corporate social responsibility and no agreement on if economic and social goals can be joined in the long run without substantial compromises (Bhattacharya, Korschun and Sen, 2009).

2.4.2. Corporate Social Responsibility and Company Performance

The business case for corporate social responsibility refers to the idea that the implementation of social responsibility policies should generate positive organisational outcomes (Bhattacharya, Korschun and Sen, 2009). One of the main challenges for theorists and practitioners is the lack of the understanding of how implementing corporate social responsibility influences competitiveness. The responsibility competitiveness paradox implies that maximising profits is in conflict with voluntary engagement in enhancing the well-being of society (Vilanova, Lozano and Arenas, 2009).

Studies suggest that implementing different corporate social responsibility initiatives can have a positive effect on the accounting or market value of firm performance in various sectors (Waddock and Graves, 1997; Berman *et al.*, 1999; Mackey, Mackey and Barney, 2007; Cho, Chung and Young, 2019). A curvilinear relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance has been indicated by some studies, proposing that social contributions and maximising financial performance may be complementary in the long run (Barnett and Salomon, 2006; Maqbool and Bakr, 2019). Many studies, however, demonstrated a negative link between corporate social responsibility and financial performance, which implicates that implementing social responsibility practices causes considerable costs for companies and forgoing competitive advantages in favour of rivals. This suggests that financially strong companies are likely to endure additional high costs for solving social and environmental problems (Wright and Ferris, 1997; Mittal, Sinha and Singh, 2008; Makni, Francoeur and Bellavance, 2009).

2.4.2.1. Challenges in Assessing the Social and Financial Performance Link

Contradictory, incomplete and unclear findings on the link between corporate social responsibility and organisational performance are not significantly helpful for managers in developing the understanding of how social responsibility should be managed to ensure long-term competitive advantages (Griffin and Mahon, 1997; Vilanova, Lozano and Arenas, 2009). Circumstances influencing the link between social and financial performance remain unexplained by reporting results rather than processes. Most studies on the influence of social responsibility on firm performance miss to incorporate the cause and effect model (Wagner and Schaltegger, 2003; Rodriguez-Fernandez, 2016).

The deficiencies of studies investigating the link between corporate social and financial performance arise because of the problem of how to measure social responsibility and financial performance. Information on corporate social responsibility is mainly non-financial with a minimum of reporting standardisation. The voluntary nature of corporate social responsibility reporting additionally exacerbates the problem (Galant and Cadez, 2017). The problem is which method to use to measure corporate social responsibility performance, the reputation index or the content analysis method (Milne and Adler, 1999; Cravens, Oliver and Ramamoorti, 2003). The measurement of financial performance is challenged by the practice of using different values in studies, that is, financial and market values (Lev and Zarowin, 1999; McWilliams and Siegel, 2000).

Studies examining the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance are commonly based on small samples, observation periods are short, companies vary in size, they are exposed to different business risks and industry effects need to be taken into account. The inadequate consideration of different factors affecting the relationship between corporate social responsibility and economic results could diminish or exaggerate positive findings on the link (Herremans, Akathaporn and McInnes, 1993).

2.4.3. Long-term Competitiveness

Managers need to be knowledgeable about the influence of corporate social responsibility initiatives on competitiveness and how to communicate those initiatives to stakeholders to achieve competitive advantages. Long-term competitiveness is not guaranteed only by positive financial performance because competitiveness, as explained by Porter and Kramer (2002), is dependent on 'the productivity with which companies can use labor, capital, and natural resources to produce high-quality goods and services' (Porter and Kramer, 2002, p. 3). Porter (1998) stressed that competitiveness is embodied in satisfying consumers' needs and wishes and the capability of a company to apprehend, create and capture a great proportion of high value delivered to consumers in competitive markets (Porter, 1998). Following Kay (2006), competitiveness connects the company's characteristic abilities with confronting and outperforming competition in markets based on building and sustaining the effective relationships with its stakeholders imbued with trust (Kay, 2006). Madhani (2012) emphasises the importance of intangible assets in driving sustainable competitive advantages, such as brand equity, reputation, relationships and research and development (Madhani, 2012).

2.4.4. Corporate Social Responsibility and Corporate Reputation

Marketing research has been mostly concerned with the link between corporate social responsibility and corporate reputation. Bianchi, Bruno and Sarabia-Sanchez (2019) propose that consumer perceived corporate social responsibility positively affects brand image and consumer satisfaction while satisfaction positively affects brand loyalty. Brand loyalty is a positive antecedent of consumer purchase intention and corporate reputation (Bianchi, Bruno and Sarabia-Sanchez, 2019). Walsh *et al.* (2009) demonstrated that consumer trust and satisfaction positively affect corporate reputation which has a positive effect on consumer loyalty and word of mouth (Walsh *et al.*, 2009). Consumer satisfaction and loyalty are routinely employed as the predictors of future business potential (Eskildsen and Kristensen, 2008). Brand satisfaction, loyalty and trust are the crucial elements of brand value because companies yield predictable revenues and profits from satisfied and loyal consumers while brand trust helps companies to retain satisfied and loyal consumers (Aaker, 1996). Positive word of mouth strongly influences consumer choices and it is regarded as a more powerful marketing tool than the traditional forms of marketing (Silverman, 2001).

Corporate image relates to 'the immediate mental picture that audiences have of an organisation' (Gray and Balmer, 1998, p. 697) while 'reputation, as the reciprocal of image, is treated as feedback from others concerning the credibility of an organisation's self-definition' (Whetten and Mackey, 2002, p. 400). A related concept to corporate image and reputation is the concept of corporate identity, which is commonly defined in terms of 'an organisation's unique characteristics which are rooted in the behaviour of members of the organisation' (Van Riel and Balmer, 1997, p. 341). Concern for stakeholders and related communication in a highly faceted way are the ground for distinguishing corporate identity from traditional brand marketing (Balmer and Gray, 1999; Balmer, 2001).

It has been argued that during economic uncertainty the market value of reputable companies is decreased significantly less than the market value of companies with a lower reputation index (Jones, Jones and Little, 2000). However, research suggests that social responsibility performance, although positively associated with corporate reputation, can negatively affect financial performance (Brammer, Brooks and Pavelin, 2006). Moreover, reputation can be tarnished if the congruence between environmental performance and environmental problems has not been recognised (Brammer and Pavelin, 2006).

Reputation research has mostly followed a multiple-stakeholder approach, although consumers are a stakeholder group directly accountable for revenue and profit creation that appears to be increasingly responsive to environmental and social issues (Walsh *et al.*, 2009). Research suggests that corporate reputation has become an important consideration for consumers but not a prime concern in their purchase decisions (Boulstridge and Carrigan, 2000). Page and Fearn (2005) stressed that consumers welcome ethical brands if quality and price are not compromised but their personally important factors are dominant in their purchase decisions (Page and Fearn, 2005).

Yoon, Giirhan-Canli and Schwarz (2006) emphasise that success in communicating corporate social responsibility is dependent on the perceived sincerity of the motives for corporate social responsibility (Yoon, Giirhan-Canli and Schwarz, 2006). Carrigan and Attalla (2001) found that companies' corporate social responsibility efforts may evoke consumers' untoward attributions of the motives behind corporate social responsibility induced by the lack of credibility in corporate social responsibility communication. Consumers were not highly aware of corporate social responsibility but they had high interest in animal rights because of feeling helpless regarding the possibility of making

steady progress in improving working conditions in supply chains. It appeared that the probability of actual responsible consumption was very low (Carrigan and Attalla, 2001).

Brown and Dacin (1997) showed that the company's good reputation built upon corporate ability associations influences product evaluations more significantly than the company's reputation developed on the basis of corporate social responsibility associations (Brown and Dacin, 1997). Sen and Bhattacharya (2001) indicate that consumers are more responsive to information on negative corporate social responsibility records than information on positive social responsibility records. Implementing corporate social responsibility at the strategic level requires from managers to choose initiatives that correspond to the needs of the most relevant consumer segments among a variety of social responsibility initiatives (Sen and Bhattacharya, 2001).

Creyer and Ross (1996) argue that consumers are not willing to reward ethical corporate behaviour by paying a price premium for ethical products but they want products manufactured and sourced in an unethical way to be low-priced (Creyer and Ross, 1996). Creyer and Ross (1997) found that consumers may be willing to pay a higher price for ethical companies' products to reward ethical corporate behaviour and they are likely to pay less for unethical companies' products to discipline unethical corporate behaviour (Creyer and Ross, 1997).

Folkes and Kamins (1999) report that consumers' positive attitudes towards ethical companies are enhanced by a superior product attribute. The effect is stronger when the company proactively engages in ethical behaviour than when the company just abstains from unethical actions. The company's ethical engagement has little influence on consumers' attitudes when a product has inferior attributes (Folkes and Kamins, 1999).

2.4.5. Limited Research Approach to Corporate Social Responsibility

Marketing research in the corporate social responsibility field has been commonly conducted by employing simplified measures and focused on the limited dimensions of social responsibility by examining either the environmental domain of social responsibility or cause-related marketing. The reason for using such an approach to study corporate social responsibility by marketing researchers is probably 'the scarcity of comprehensive

conceptual frameworks originating from the marketing discipline' (Maignan and Ferrell, 2004, p. 5).

In filling in the gap on how consumers perceive and evaluate different corporate social responsibility attributes, Marquina and Morales (2012), for instance, stress that promoting the environmental attribute of a product may be more effective than putting accent on fair labour practices in communicating social responsibility, which seems to be contextually determined. Likewise, consumers are willing to pay a higher price for product quality than for responsible environmental behaviours (Marquina and Morales, 2012).

2.4.5.1. Environmental Corporate Social Responsibility

Among studies examining environmental corporate social responsibility, Menon and Menon (1997) discussed the notion of an enviropreneurial marketing strategy, which relates to applying the idea of cause-related marketing in promoting environmental protection. The emergence of the concept is a response to the pressures of the growing ecological movements and the advancement of environmental regulatory frameworks. Nevertheless, as this study indicates, companies do not incorporate an environmentally-sensitive approach into their marketing strategy and business model, although companies in traditionally polluting sectors have a strategic precondition to increase their competitiveness based on investing in environmentally friendly initiatives (Menon and Menon, 1997).

2.4.5.2. Cause-related Marketing

A few marketing studies investigated if consumers are likely to choose brands involved in cause-related marketing. Barone, Miyazaki and Taylor (2000) argue that the influence of cause-related marketing on the consumer's choice depends on the level of the perceived compromise between support for the social cause and lower quality and/or higher price and on the perceived motivation for cause-related marketing engagement (Barone, Miyazaki and Taylor, 2000). Drumwright (1996) points that social campaigns encompass both economic and social objectives but consumers tend to perceive cause-related marketing to be driven by profit maximisation or as true endeavours for social betterment (Drumwright, 1996).

Ellen, Webb and Mohr (2006) found that consumers believe that corporate social responsibility efforts are driven by both profit maximisation and community wellbeing. Consumers perceive engaging in social responsibility unfavourably if it is done to respond to the pressures of stakeholders (Ellen, Webb and Mohr, 2006). Bhattacharya and Sen (2004) propose that consumers may have tolerant and approving attitudes towards the sponsoring company's involvement in cause-related marketing initiatives because of maximising profits. There should be a satisfactory level of the congruence between the company's business and the participating cause. Cause-related marketing is perceived less favourably when the for-profit company is a company with a tarnished reputation that supports the cause closely linked to its business (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004). Grau and Folse (2007) draw attention to the question of how to engage less motivated consumers to support causes. The scholars proposed that less-involved consumers are likely to be attracted by communication that emphasises the local impact and positive outcome of cause-related campaigns (Grau and Folse, 2007).

Different perceived motives behind cause-related marketing are the ground for generating arguments for and against using charitable donations as a marketing tool, making corporate advertising with a social dimension the most controversial marketing approach. Critics argue that it is the antithesis of ethics because the purpose of profit-oriented enterprises is to maximise the wealth of their owners, which is in conflict with the aim of charitable and social activities to contribute to social prosperity. The problem arising is if the different interests can be harmonised without great compromises (Berglind and Nakata, 2005).

2.4.6. Corporate Social Responsibility Labelling

In responding to environmental and social pressures, eco-labelling emerged as a marketing tool to alleviate the advancement of sustainable consumption in various industries. Eco-labelling has become a marketing differentiating strategy used for targeting socially conscious fashion consumers (Choudhury, 2015). The development of labelling initiatives and schemes is a result of the negotiation about adopting sustainability practices between non-governmental organisations and trade associations on one side and companies on the other side, although the end-consumer demand for eco-labelling is actually low (Gulbrandsen, 2006).

It has been argued that communicating production and ecological standards behind the labels is an effective way to improve brand image and reputation and an opportunity to create auspicious prices. However, the infrequency of promotion campaigns, high certification costs and confusion that eco-labelling creates for consumers are regarded as the factors that impede the successful usage of this marketing strategy (Atănăsoaie, 2013).

2.4.7. Corporate Social Responsibility Reporting

Companies can use corporate social responsibility or sustainability reports to signal how they respond to environmental and social pressures. However, the fruitfulness of using corporate social responsibility disclosures for augmenting competitiveness is under intense scrutiny (Wagner and Schaltegger, 2003). It is believed that companies' corporate social responsibility reporting deviates from their actual corporate social responsibility performance (Cochran and Wood, 1984; Morhardt, Baird and Freeman, 2002; Cooper and Owen, 2007). Accordingly, corporate social responsibility reporting is characterised as companies' endeavours to fulfil their responsibilities to obtain legitimacy in society (Castelló and Lozano, 2011).

A study of corporate social responsibility disclosures by Stratling (2007) indicates that companies in general do not follow a strategic approach to corporate social responsibility to increase their competitive advantages and profitability. Social responsibility disclosures mirror companies' efforts to legitimise their existence in society (Stratling, 2007). Mahoney *et al.* (2013) report that companies that issue standalone social responsibility reports have stronger social responsibility ratings than companies that do not issue those reports (Mahoney *et al.*, 2013). Milne and Gray (2013) explain that many important corporate social responsibility issues connected with business operations are commonly not included in social responsibility reports, for example, unethical advertising or increased consumer spending. Although communicating sustainability, companies do not address many issues relevant for sustainable development, such as ecological footprints and social equity (Milne and Gray, 2013). Standardisation, emphasis on content and stakeholder specificity have been proposed as the important issues that need to be addressed for ameliorating credibility and understandability in corporate social responsibility reporting (Lock and Seele, 2016).

Lee, Cruz and Shankar (2018) developed a model which proposes that companies reap profits based on employing a greenwashing strategy when the market is not informed. Consumers' increased corporate social responsibility awareness may decrease greenwashing practices but it would not certainly stimulate the business sector to act more responsibly because of the high expenditure of implementing social responsibility policies in the supply chain. In this regard, subventions and partnership agreements with corporations seem to be a more realistic strategy for governments to control greenwashing, which gives support to Friedman's (1970) belief that governments are the stakeholders responsible for social betterment (Lee, Cruz and Shankar, 2018).

As emphasised by Friedman (1970), the allocation of the business' resources for social responsibility purposes is an example of the principal-agent problem that generates the need for funding social responsibility projects by governments, which is encapsulated in the following quotation:

'This is the basic reason why the doctrine of "social responsibility" involves the acceptance of the socialist view that political mechanisms, not market mechanisms, are the appropriate way to determine the allocation of scarce resources to alternative uses' (Friedman, 1970, p. 124).

2.5. Defining Luxury

2.5.1. Relativity of the Concept of Luxury

Because luxury is a subjective and multidimensional concept, an integrative approach to defining luxury should be applied. The relativity of the luxury concept is the most cited reason for the absence of a universal definition of luxury in the academic literature (Dryl, 2014). The relativity of luxury products can be analysed from different angles. Regional relativity is explained by the difference between a low value of a widely available good in some parts of the world and a luxury status of the same good in another areas because of its rarity (Heine, 2012). For example, the luxury brand Chanel may be perceived as mass for some consumer segments in the developed world while it is perceived as luxurious in the emerging markets (Dryl, 2014).

Temporal relativity is related to the influence of time, social trends and technology advancement on a change in the public perception of the symbols of luxury. The process is also reversible because goods regarded as ordinary in the past have become luxury. For example, 'natural flax, handmade shoes or down comforters' may be perceived as luxurious goods because they are 'nowadays replaced by artificial textiles and mass production' (Kasztalska, 2017, p. 78). Economic relativity implies that the perception of luxury is dependent on an individual's buying power or a stage in the economic development of a particular country (Heine, 2012). For example, affordable clothes and accessories offered by luxury brands can be perceived as luxurious by consumers with low incomes while consumers with high buying power can consider them mass and ordinary. Likewise, consumers in East European countries were not once a target luxury market, which has been changed on the basis of the development of their economies and the higher incomes of their citizens and residents (Dryl, 2014).

Situational relativity is expressed in the fact that a luxurious good can lose its attribution of brilliancy if it is used to satisfy the basic human needs. However, the same product may still be perceived as luxurious if it is used rarely. A product can be perceived as luxurious, ordinary or necessary depending on how consumers approach it in different situations (Kemp, 1998; Dryl, 2014). Cultural relativity relates to the perception of luxury shaped by cultural factors (Heine, 2012). For example, what is regarded as a luxury good in the Western world may be perceived as standard and even unacceptable and worthless in other parts of the world (Urkmez and Wagner, 2015). Every social and cultural group and subculture has 'a different kind of luxury, which means that a Cartier is no luxury in some cases where a television is highly exclusive in other cases' (Mortelmans, 2005, p. 497). Some authors argue that the most conspicuous product categories have the potential to develop the status of independence in relation to the influence of culture on the perceptions of luxury (Urkmez and Wagner, 2015).

The perceptions of luxury are simultaneously highly individual as the desirability of luxury goods vary among the members of the same cultural group based on their different awareness of luxury symbols. For example, a fashion item offered by some iconic luxury brand may produce the contradictory perceptions of luxury between different consumer groups whose members have been raised in the same culture. A brand-name fashion garment may be perceived as luxurious, desirable and prestigious as well as decadent,

valueless and extravagant depending on consumers' age and education (Kasztalska, 2017).

2.5.2. Economic Theory of Luxury

The economic theory of luxury accentuates the criterion of utility in distinguishing between utilitarian and luxury products (Besley, 1989). Consumers balance between fulfilling their essential needs and indulging in non-essential luxury goods and services that often has hedonic motivations (Kivetz and Simonson, 2002). A strictly economic conception of luxury implies that luxury products have the highest price and quality relationship in the market without involving 'the notion of an absolute minimum threshold', which indicates that luxury is explained by 'the price differential between luxury products and products with comparable functions' rather than the absolute price (Kapferer, 1996, p. 252).

2.5.3. Concept of Relative Consumption in Luxury

As one of the founders of neoclassical economics, Marshall (1890) proposed that the production, pricing and consumption of products are defined by the supply and demand model and consumers make purchase decisions based on assessing the utility of a product (Sheth, Newman and Gross, 1991). Superfluousness, however, cannot be always regarded as the determining feature of luxury. For instance, possessing an iPad may be perceived as unnecessary but it may not create the perception of luxuriousness. The value of a luxury brand emphasises 'social, psychological or other similar benefits' (Turunen, 2018, p. 47). Rational choice theory does not explain luxury purchases that are often driven by intangible and symbolic attributes (Kapferer, 2017).

The last decades witnessed the revival of academic interest in the concept of relative consumption. Duesenberry's (1949) relative spending hypothesis implies that consumption is dependent on prices and consumers' incomes as well as consumers' desire to achieve a position in the community that defines consumption norms (Sanders, 2010). Veblen (1899) introduced the concept of conspicuous consumption, which explains that the aim of achieving a high level of social status stimulates individuals to consume distinctly conspicuous goods and services (Bagwell and Bernheim, 1996). One side of luxury consumption, especially relevant for the emerging markets, is 'demonstration of success (luxury for others)' while 'indulging in one's pleasure (luxury for self)' is likely to be

dominant in luxury consumption in developed Western countries (Kapferer and Bastien, 2009b, p. 321).

The influence of reference groups in consumption was initially discussed by Bourne (1957) who pointed out that purchased products need to be noticed by others to affect consumer brand decisions (Bearden and Etzel, 1982). When purchasing the most visible luxury products, for example, designer clothes and cars, consumers are susceptible to social influence to the highest degree (Husic and Cicic, 2009). Based on purchasing and using luxury products, consumers knowingly or subconsciously endeavour to enhance their self-concept and feel that they belong to significant others within value-expressive reference groups (Bearden, Netemeyer and Teel, 1989; Dubois and Laurent, 1996; Vigneron and Johnson, 2017).

2.5.4. Types of Luxury Consumers

Leibenstein (1950) stressed the importance of distinguishing between the Veblen effect, the bandwagon or demonstration effect and the snob effect for the understanding of luxury consumption (Leibenstein, 1950). The relevance of the Veblen effect for luxury marketing is nicely explained by the reasoning of a luxury marketing manager published in *The Economist* (1993), 'If we halved the price of all our products, we would double our sales for six months and then we would sell nothing' (*The Economist*, 1993 cited in Bagwell and Bernheim, 1996, p. 349). In other words, the rise of a luxury product's price results in growing consumption among consumers who gain satisfaction and status from the fact that only few other consumers possess it (Kastanakis and Balabanis, 2012).

The bandwagon effect in luxury consumption means that the demand for certain luxury brands and products is increased because of their popularity (Leibenstein, 1950). Consumers purchasing luxuries because of their popularity create social status by associating with the lifestyle of the majority of luxury consumers and separating from less opulent consumers. The demand for certain luxury brands and products is enhanced because influential status groups purchase those luxuries. Snobbism in luxury consumption occurs when consumers discontinue to purchase luxuries already popular among others to display their uniqueness (Kastanakis and Balabanis, 2014). Although different intentions and goals influence snobs and followers to purchase luxuries, the

fundamental motive of luxury consumption is the magnification of an individual's self-concept (Dubois and Duquesne, 1993).

The introvert hedonic consumer seeks for luxury goods and services that ensure 'more experiential consumption, fun, pleasure, and excitement' (Dhar and Wertenbroch, 2000, p. 60). The perfectionist luxury consumer is engrossed with 'the very best quality in products' (Sproles and Kendall, 1986, p. 271). Vigneron and Johnson (1999) explained that the high price of luxury products for status-oriented consumers demonstrates prestige while snobbish consumers associate it with exclusivity. The perfectionist luxury consumer perceives price as supportive evidence for the quality attribute of a product. Preoccupied with searching for pleasure that can induce positive emotions, hedonist consumers put less emphasis on price. Bandwagon luxury consumption is driven by the popularity of a product and also less influenced by price as a signal of prestige consumption. Vigneron and Johnson (1999) use the term luxury when referring to the top category of prestige brands (Vigneron and Johnson, 1999).

Some authors regard status and conspicuous luxury consumption as the same type of consumer behaviour. Others argue that status consumption is about signalling high status and wealth to society while conspicuous consumption is about signalling high social status, wealth and enhanced image to significant others. In conspicuous consumption, comparisons with others are more important and noticeable (Bernheim, 1994; Eastman, Goldsmith and Flynn, 1999; O'Cass and Frost, 2002).

The categorisations of luxury consumers in essence reflect the luxury consumer's expressions of self, that is, a prevailing social or signalling approach in luxury consumption or a predominant personal orientation in luxury purchases. A sharp border between the expressions of self does not need to exist yet they can coexist in the mind of an individual luxury consumer (Aaker and Lee, 2001; Truong, 2010).

Han, Nunes and Drèze (2010) draw attention to the phenomenon of inconspicuous luxury by proposing the concept of brand prominence, which refers to 'the conspicuousness of a brand's mark or logo on a product' (Han, Nunes and Drèze, 2010, p. 15). Inconspicuous luxury occurs as new luxury. The turn towards inconspicuous consumption is happening because of luxury brands' dilution, that is, the diminished ability of traditional luxury brands to signal social status as a result of losing their original value. Accordingly, luxury

consumers desire craftsmanship aimed at perfection in quality and sophistication and subtlety in design in order to develop a new sense of belonging within a narrowly defined social class (Eckhardt, Belk and Wilson, 2015).

By connecting consumers' preference for conspicuously or discreetly branded luxury goods with consumers' need to associate with or disassociate from a particular consumer group, Han, Nunes and Drèze (2010) identified four types of luxury consumers: patricians, parvenus, poseurs and proletarians (Han, Nunes and Drèze, 2010). This classification of consumer buying behaviour in luxury reflects the separation between accessible and inaccessible luxury taking into account the democratisation of luxury and the emergence of inconspicuous luxury consumption (De Barnier, Falcy and Valette-Florence, 2012). The characteristics of patricians, parvenus, poseurs and proletarians are described in the Table 2.5. The Table 2.6 represents the summary of the incentives and motives for luxury purchases that reflect the types of consumer behaviour in luxury.

Table 2.5: Types of Luxury Consumers

Type of consumer	Main characteristics
Patricians	Very affluent consumers who buy quiet luxury goods to connect with other patricians rather than to separate from other types of consumers. Subtle signals are used to connect with other patricians. Luxury brands with visible logos are not desirable.
Parvenus	Consumers who choose luxury goods with loud, visible marks to promote social status and associate themselves with other affluent consumers and disassociate from consumers with lower buying power.
Poseurs	Consumers who do not have enough money to readily afford original luxury goods. They purchase counterfeit luxury goods to satisfy their need for brand status, that is, communicating social status by the brand.
Proletarians	Consumers who are not interested in signalling social status based on purchasing luxury goods.

Based on: Han, Nunes and Drèze (2010)

Table 2.6: Incentives and Motives for Luxury Purchases

Incentive/motive	Meaning	References
Hedonism	Purchasing luxury is stimulated by consumers' wish for indulgence. These consumers want to experience joy and pleasure from luxury purchases.	Holbrook and Hirschman (1982); Bardhi and Arnould (2005); Cardoso and Pinto (2010); Amatulli, De Angelis and Donato (2019)
Conspicuousness	Consumers purchase luxury to demonstrate wealth, impress others and enhance social status.	Wang and Griskevicius (2014)
Snob effect	Luxury purchases are a way for distinguishing from the majority of consumers and gaining dissociative status. These consumers have a strong need for exclusiveness and uniqueness arising from their self-expressive aims; they prefer limited editions.	Amaldoss and Jain (2008); Kastanakis and Balabanis (2014)
Bandwagon	Purchasing popular luxury brands and products arises from a consumer's desire to associate with the wealthy lifestyle of influential luxury consumers and dissociate from less opulent consumers. Focus is on conformity; the influence of celebrities that purchase certain luxury brands and products is important for triggering the demand for those brands and products.	Kastanakis and Balabanis (2014)
Quality	Purchasing luxury is based on a consumer's need to possess high-quality products.	Sproles and Kendall (1986); Vigneron and Johnson (1999)
Self-identity	The underlying motivation force for different types of luxury purchases is a consumer's self-enhancement. Consumers build their self-identity by purchasing luxury brands and products that are in alignment with their self-image.	Dubois and Duquesne (1993)

Self-gift giving	Luxury purchases allow consumers to satisfy their dreams and fantasies based on gaining symbolic benefits. Consumers purchase luxury goods and services to reward themselves for success and achievements and lift mood after disappointments.	Bardhi and Arnould (2005); Tsai (2005); Heath, Tynan and Ennew (2011)
Sociality	Socially oriented luxury purchases are the reflection of an individual's interdependent self.	Eastman, Goldsmith and Flynn (1999); Kapferer and Bastien (2009b); Ackerman and Chung (2012); Bahri-Ammari, Coulibaly and Mimoun (2020)

2.5.5. Luxury Brands

It is relevant to clarify the meaning of luxury brands surrounded by affordable luxury and premium brands. Luxury brands from an economic perspective are defined as 'those whose ratio of functional utility to price is low while the ratio of intangible and situational utility to price is high' (Nueno and Quelch, 1998, p. 62). A variety of the definitions of luxury brands have been offered to explain the characteristics of luxury brands. For example, Tynan, McKechnie and Chhuon (2010) define luxury brands as 'high quality, expensive and non-essential products and services that appear to be rare, exclusive, prestigious, and authentic and offer high levels of symbolic and emotional/hedonic values through customer experiences' (Tynan, McKechnie and Chhuon, 2010, p. 1158). Following Dubois, Laurent and Czellar (2001), luxury brands are often associated with outstanding quality, high price, heritage, uniqueness, beauty, scarcity and exceeding necessary (Christodoulides, Michaelidou and Li, 2009). The characteristics of luxury brands explained by the prominent authors in the field are summarised in the Table 2.7, which helps to understand the essence of luxury brands.

Table 2.7: Characteristics of Luxury Brands

Authors	Characteristics of luxury brands
Nueno and Quelch (1998)	High quality, slow manufacturing, perfect craftsmanship, recognisable great design and style, product excellence and emotional appeal, association with a country of origin, uniqueness, global reputation, exclusivity, the creator's values and personality.
Okonkwo (2007)	Strong brand image, differentiation, high quality, craftsmanship, innovation, premium price, exclusivity.
Fionda and Moore (2009)	Brand name and identity, luxury communication strategy, outstanding product quality, craftsmanship and innovation, brand signature, iconic products, prestige price, exclusivity, luxury heritage, luxury distribution, luxury organisational culture.
Kapferer and Bastien (2009a); Kapferer and Bastien (2009b)	Premium quality, rarity, high price, beauty, perfection, exclusivity, history, art, uniqueness, handmade, distinctiveness, symbolic value, status, culture.
Keller (2017)	Prestige, premium price, high quality, happy and pleasant experiences in purchasing and consumption, intangible brand associations and aspirational image, rich heritage, symbolic value, brand name and tangible brand elements, secondary associations from related popular personalities and prestigious events, association with a country of origin, controlled distribution, brand architecture management, legal protection.

2.5.5.1. Exclusivity of Luxury Brands

The price and quality relationship is the foundation for distinguishing between luxury brands and premium brands that are the expensive alternatives for commodity products. The high price of premium brands reflects their excellent quality, high functional value and first-class performance in satisfying utilitarian needs (Heine, 2012). Because the high price of luxury brands is related to their intangible values, such as prestige, exclusivity and heritage, it can be associated more with brand value rather than product quality, although luxury brands possess outstanding quality (Kapferer and Bastien, 2017; Turunen, 2018). The intangible value of luxury brands allows the avoidance of commoditisation that is common for most growth industries when competing products become indistinguishable (Kapferer, 2017). Because of communicating symbolic attributes, luxury brands by charging premiums do not compromise consumer demand (Seo and Buchanan-Oliver, 2015).

Kapferer and Bastien (2009a) explain that classic and premium brands compete by product positioning while luxury brands are unsurpassed and incomparable:

‘When it comes to luxury, being unique is what counts, not any comparison with a competitor. Luxury is the expression of a taste, of a creative identity, of the intrinsic passion of a creator; luxury makes the bold statement “this is what I am”, not “that depends” - which is what positioning implies’ (Kapferer and Bastien, 2009a, p. 62).

2.5.5.2. Desirability of Luxury through Authenticity, Scarcity and Rarity

Traditionally, Central Europe is the origin of luxury fashion brands and a ‘Made in France’ etiquette, for example, is considered ‘a key cue for high-quality craftsmanship’ (Turunen, 2018, p. 43). Because outsource manufacturing decreases consumers’ perceptions of the genuineness of a brand, some luxury fashion brands have recently reshored some parts of their production operations from developing countries back to the headquarters country to restore their authenticity (Robinson and Hsieh, 2016). Brand authenticity is commonly interpreted as ‘a subjective evaluation of genuineness ascribed to a brand by consumers’ (Napoli *et al.*, 2014, p. 1091). The rarity principle in luxury indicates that ‘in order to maintain prestige, luxury brands must sustain high levels of awareness and tightly controlled brand diffusion to enhance exclusivity’ (Phau and Prendergast, 2020, p. 122).

Product scarcity is ensured by limiting supply, that is, making it difficult to buy a particular luxury product, which was the case with Louis Vuitton handbags (Vigneron and Johnson, 2017). However, the mass-production of Louis Vuitton handbags nowadays illustrates that luxury does not need to be absolutely based on consumers' perceptions of scarcity (Turunen, 2018).

Managers in the luxury industry face the problem of the distribution paradox of luxury marketing, which suggests that the growth of luxury business based on increased sales reduces the perceptions of exclusivity and rarity (Berthon *et al.*, 2009). Maintaining rarity and exclusivity in luxury is achieved through limited brand diffusion and product lines, controlled prices, consumer selection, media coverage and lasting originality (Kapferer and Valette-Florence, 2016).

2.5.5.3. Measuring the Level of Luxury

Vigneron and Johnson (2004) developed a framework for measuring the perceived level of the luxury of a single brand based on categorising the motives for luxury into two basic groups. The personal perceptions of luxury encompass hedonist and extended self motives for luxury while the non-personal perceptions of luxury relate to quality, uniqueness and conspicuousness. A high level of the brand's luxuriousness based on using this scale corresponds to the perceived highest degree of the personal and non-personal dimensions of luxury (Vigneron and Johnson, 2017). Vigneron and Johnson's (2004) scale has been regarded as the most complete scale for distinguishing between high-level and low-level luxury brands (Turunen, 2018). In comparison to comparative processing, however, the evaluation of a single brand may have the limitation reflected in the risk of generating greater brand evaluations, suggesting that it is questionable if the highest result on all luxury dimensions means that the brand in fact has the highest luxury level (Posavac *et al.*, 2004).

Marketing can influence consumers' perceptions of luxuriousness. For example, De Beers is a company that succeeded in creating consumers' long-term perceptions of diamonds as important luxurious goods. The company's marketing strategy was triumphal in designing and communicating the idea of true romance behind diamond jewellery as the intangible attribute of the physical good. The success of this company shows how a unique

and well-designed marketing strategy can convince consumers that certain types of luxury products are highly desirable (Bergenstock and Maskulka, 2001).

2.5.6. Consumer Value

The common conceptualisation of consumer brand value is done on the basis of Zeithaml's (1988) definition (France *et al.*, 2020), which indicates that consumer perceived value is 'a tradeoff of give and get components' and it represents 'a higher level concept than quality' (Zeithaml, 1988, p. 14). Consumer value is associated with 'the perceived personal relevance of the choice alternatives', which suggests that 'consumers are likely to select those choice alternatives that are seen as more useful for their needs' (Reynolds and Olson, 1983, p. 8). Perceived value can be related to emotional benefits for consumers (Young and Feigen, 1975) and other abstract product attributes, for example, novelty, uniqueness and social value (Geistfeld, Sproles and Badenhop, 1977; Sheth, Newman and Gross, 1991).

With regard to the importance of consumer value in marketing, Gutman (1982) explained the means-end chain concept:

'A means-end chain is a model that seeks to explain how a product or service selection facilitates the achievement of desired end states...The means-end chain concept offers marketing managers a way to position products by associating means (the physical aspects of products) with advertising that seeks to tie the consumption of products to the achievement of desired ends (valued states)' (Gutman, 1982, p. 60).

It is worth to mention Levitt's (1960) concept of marketing myopia, which indicates that a nearsighted approach to marketing is more focused on the production side of business than consumers. When Harvard Business Review reprinted the article "Marketing Myopia" in 2004, the concept was connotated as 'the most influential marketing idea of the past half century' (Smith, Drumwright and Gentile, 2010, p. 4). As Levitt (2004) stated, 'sustained growth depends on how broadly you define your business - and how carefully you gauge your customers' needs' (Levitt, 2004, p. 138). Holbrook (2002) stresses that the notion of interactive consumer value reconciles the product and marketing orientations in

conducting business because of postulating that the qualities of a product can be translated into consumer value through consumer experiences (Holbrook, 2002).

Many brands offer a combination of functional, experiential and symbolic values to consumers and consumer behaviour in general reflects balancing between more and less important values (Park, Jawarski, and MacInnis, 1986). This is in line with the suggestion of Keller (2013) that brand associations comprised of brand attributes and brand benefits lead to brand values within the structure of a means-end chain. Brand attributes refer to 'descriptive features that characterise a product', brand benefits are related to 'the personal value and meaning attached to product attributes' while values are associated with 'stable and enduring personal goals or motivations' (Keller, 2013, p. 92).

2.5.6.1. Functional, Experiential and Symbolic Luxury Value

Berthon *et al.* (2009) explain that the main dimensions of luxury brands are: functional, material or objective value, experiential or individual value and symbolic or social value. The functionality of luxury brands is about the purpose for which luxury products are made. For example, famous luxury fashion brands were initially established as the manufacturers of clothes of exceptional quality and functionality (Berthon *et al.*, 2009). The experiential or hedonic dimension of luxury is related to consumers' shopping and consumption experiences derived from the brand (Smith and Colgate, 2007). The term brand experience was introduced by Brakus, Schmitt and Zarantonello (2009) as 'subjective, internal consumer responses (sensations, feelings, and cognitions) and behavioural responses evoked by brand-related stimuli that are part of a brand's design and identity, packaging, communications, and environments' (Brakus, Schmitt and Zarantonello, 2009, p. 53).

Gardner and Levy (1955) emphasised that managers need to have a better understanding of 'the social and psychological nature of products' (Gardener and Levy, 1955 cited in Meenaghan, 1995, p. 26), which means that 'people buy products not only for what they can do, but also for what they mean' (Levy, 1959, p. 118). The symbolic characteristics of luxury products are crucial in brand selection because 'consumers imbue a product with a subjective meaning that supplements the concrete attributes it possesses' (Hirschman and Holbrook, 1982, p. 94). The symbolic attributes of luxury products are commonly

associated with satisfying consumers' needs for 'self-enhancement, role position, group membership, or ego-identification' (Smith and Colgate, 2007, p. 8).

2.5.6.2. Ethics Value in Luxury

Smith (1999) highlights the importance of ethics consumer value associated with boycotts that are the pro-democracy demonstrations of consumers' environmental and social concerns. An alternative concept of ethics consumer value suggests that it is questionable whether ethics value has been adequately designed as a high purchasing driver. That is to say, ethical altruism through promoting limited consumption and rationing does not fit the standard marketing transaction between the company and consumers based on the exchange of values. Balancing between functional, experiential or symbolic value versus ethics value in luxury may be seen as contradictory based on this view (Smith, 1999).

However, Green and Peloza (2011) explain that consumer choice behaviour in relation to corporate social responsibility purchases is influenced by three value drivers: functional, emotional and social. In a luxury and fashion context, functional value may be a motive for involving social responsibility in purchase decisions when brands' social responsibility credentials are associated with slow manufacturing and higher quality. Emotional value relates to 'warm glow', that is, emotional satisfaction that consumers experience when purchasing products with social responsibility claims and supporting the cause they care about. Consumers' choices in luxury and fashion are driven by social value in terms of satisfying relevant social norms based on group membership, which indicates that socially responsible purchases need to be socially approved. Value received from social responsibility needs to be complementary to overall value that consumers receive from luxury and fashion brands (Green and Peloza, 2011).

2.5.6.2.1. Sustainability or Ethical Branding

Although conflicting findings on social responsibility considerations in consumer purchase decisions were reported (Creyer and Ross, 1997; Boulstridge and Carrigan, 2000; Carrigan and Attalla, 2001), a rich body of the academic literature indicates that sustainability or ethical branding is essential for making a positive change in any marketplace. Consumers are nowadays more sophisticated and socially concerned and they consider companies' social responsibility performance more seriously in comparison

to the late 20th century (Fan, 2005; Pomeroy and Johnson, 2009; Raczkowski, Sulkowski and Fijalkowska, 2016).

Previous research mostly sought to explore the status-seeking drivers of luxury brand consumption (Han, Nunes and Drèze, 2010), the benefits of consuming luxury brands that are not entirely driven by searching for social status, such as conspicuousness (Wang and Griskevicius, 2014), bandwagon and snob effects (Kastanakis and Balabanis, 2014), as well as the benefits of personally oriented luxury consumption in terms of self-directed hedonism, self-gift giving and conformity with internal self (Tsai, 2005). However, the limitation of the prior theories of luxury is omitting to propose how following socially responsible principles in branding decisions creates added value for the luxury company and its stakeholders (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015; Amatulli *et al.*, 2018). By adding how sustainability affects consumer behaviour in luxury fashion, this study contributes to addressing this gap.

The term brand reflects brand elements, such as logo, name, design, symbol or slogan as well as functional, emotional and social values, and it can be applied at the product and company level. Alwi, Ali and Nguyen (2017) explain that ethical branding relates to the process of strengthening the identity of a company with ethics in order to develop an ethical image of the brand in consumers' mind. Effective ethical brand positioning requires connecting with the target market in a unique and authentic way in order to deliver value that the brand brings to the audience. The ethical brand transcends the product and profitability because it acts ethically in accepting its economic, social and environmental responsibilities. The ethical brand offers sustainable products and services and does not hurt the environment, people and animals. Ethical marketing communicates these values to stakeholders with honesty, transparency and integrity (Alwi, Ali and Nguyen, 2017).

Sustainability or ethical branding has become a new paradigm that companies need to meet because irresponsible corporate behaviour is likely to tarnish corporate reputation with possible adverse effects on profitability (Fan, 2005; García de los Salmones Sánchez and Pérez Ruiz, 2018). Singh, Iglesias and Batista-Foguet (2012) argue that the perceived ethicality of a brand is positively related to brand affect, brand trust and brand loyalty, which is likely to increase profitability (Singh, Iglesias and Batista-Foguet, 2012). Luxury fashion brands can therefore reap benefits based on using sustainability brand communication and positioning. Among the functional areas of business, it is mostly

expected from marketing to effectively use its tools and strategies to help develop sustainable products and business practices (Sagar, Singh and Agrawal, 2006). These suggestions support the research model of this study.

2.6. Corporate Social Responsibility in the Luxury and Fashion Industry

2.6.1. Link between Social and Financial Performance in the Luxury Industry

A negative link between corporate social responsibility and financial performance has been reported by Sipilä *et al.* (2021) who carried out a longitudinal research project to analyse the link using secondary data based on a big sample of luxury companies. The researchers chose sales revenue growth as the measure of financial performance because this indicator is mostly directly related to consumer purchase behaviour. Brand value growth was employed as an alternative dependent variable in the complementary analysis (Sipilä *et al.*, 2021).

2.6.2. Significance of Corporate Social Responsibility for Luxury and Fashion Brands

Luxury brands have implemented corporate social responsibility policies and disclosed social responsibility information in order to respond to the growing hard-hitting activist groups' campaigns and concerns (Sipilä *et al.*, 2021). Many luxury brands have adopted ethical codes as the guidelines of principles and best practices for conducting their business operations with honesty and integrity (Henninger *et al.*, 2017). The importance of corporate social responsibility in the luxury fashion industry is reflected in a range of social responsibility issues that managers need to deal with, such as anorexic models, animal rights, poor labour standards, ecology, scarce resources, recycling, upcycling, counterfeits and so forth (Hennigs *et al.*, 2013).

Karaosman, Brun and Morales-Alonso (2015) examined corporate social responsibility disclosures in the luxury fashion industry and found that energy consumption, recycling and packaging are mostly represented in luxury fashion brands' social responsibility or sustainability reports, followed by disclosures on waste and emissions and supplier management. The authors suggest that reporting on sustainable water resources management, material sourcing and use and biodiversity should be improved because of the importance of these issues for the functioning of luxury business (Karaosman, Brun

and Morales-Alonso, 2015). Luxury brands are expected to give back to nature because the high-end quality of luxury is heavily dependent on the gifts of nature. The quality of luxury products may be jeopardised by climate change and resource scarcity, putting luxury brands at business continuity risks (Winston, 2016).

2.6.3. Link between Sustainability, Luxury and Fashion

Fashion refers to 'temporary cyclical phenomena adopted by consumers for a particular time and situation' (Sproles, 1981, p. 116). The fashion sector is characterised by 'short product life cycles, high volatility and low predictability of product demand' (Macchion, Danese and Vinelli, 2015, p. 15). The antithesis between luxury fashion and sustainability may stem from the core meaning of luxury fashion as repetitive change at the highest degree (Godart and Seong, 2014). Luxury is intrinsically related to indulgence, ostentation and extravagance, which is opposite to the idea of corporate social responsibility expressed in environmental protection and social betterment, justice and equality (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013).

Luxury and fashion share the similarity in 'the need for social differentiation' but luxury lasts forever or for a very long period of time in contrast to fashion that is ephemeral (Godart and Seong, 2014, p. 15). It has been argued that luxury values, such as high quality, timelessness, durability and first-class craftsmanship, can be the excellent foundation for the coexistence of luxury and sustainability. In this regard, Joy *et al.* (2012) contend that luxury brands could help in solving social responsibility problems in the whole fashion industry (Joy *et al.*, 2012). This extends the view of Heath and Potter (2004) that an opportunity for sustainable luxury may arise from the potential of a postmodern version of the Veblen effect. Namely, luxury consumers as countercultural rebels searching for status may adopt the elitist cultural practices of purchasing premium sustainable brands in opposing conventional consumer behaviour (Thompson and Coskuner-Balli, 2007). Likewise, the longevity currency and scarcity of luxury goods makes them desirable for trading on the flourishing second-hand luxury market (Carrigan, Moraes and McEachern, 2013).

Sustainability has been adopted and communicated by a few leading luxury fashion brands and a group of ethically minded couture fashion designers. A positive influence on developing sustainability in fashion may come from initiatives such as the establishment of

the Ethical Fashion Forum in 2006, which is a non-governmental organisation with the mission to promote ethical practices in the fashion industry (Carrigan, Moraes and McEachern, 2013).

An aggravating circumstance for intensifying sustainability in luxury fashion may be the recent massification of luxury fashion brands through supplying broader market segments with entry-level products (Athwal *et al.*, 2019). By combining high perceived prestige value with moderate premium prices, new masstige positioning strategies are employed to attract middle-class and young consumers with less expensive and non-rare luxury goods (Truong, McColl and Kitchen, 2009; Kapferer and Michaut, 2014).

Others argue that luxury is not about demonstrating wealth anymore yet about outstanding craftsmanship and sustainable development, ethics and inclusiveness (Frank, 2020). The term new luxury relates to 'affordability, mass-market proliferation, the divorce of status and class, and availability in the mass market, ideally without undermining a brand's luxury status' (Eckhardt, Belk and Wilson, 2015, p. 809).

2.6.3.1. Sustainable or Ethical Fashion

According to Mintel, which is a UK and global market research company, ethical fashion or eco-fashion encompasses: ethical, eco and organic clothing. Ethical clothing refers to clothes that are manufactured considering the environmental and social impacts of fashion companies' business operations, that is, the positive and negative effects of the manufacturing and trading of fashion products on the environment and people involved in that process. Eco clothing refers to clothes manufactured in an environmentally friendly manner, including organic textiles and sustainable materials, such as hemp and vegan leather and non-textiles, for example, fabrics made from recycled plastic bottles. Eco clothing also includes second-hand and vintage clothes as well as clothes made from recycled and upcycled textiles and other materials that are re-used in a way that helps protect the environment but not necessarily grown in accordance with organic agricultural standards. Organic clothing refers to clothes made from materials that are grown sustainably and with minimum pollution. It involves arrangements such as Fairtrade in fashion, which is the global movement aimed to help achieve fair wages and good conditions for farmers and workers in developing countries and fair prices for their products (Carey and Cervellon, 2014).

2.6.4. Sustainability along the Supply Chain in the Luxury and Fashion Industry

Scarce research shows that small and medium enterprises in the luxury and fashion industry are more concerned with economic survival and growth than how to progress in implementing corporate social responsibility policies and increasing supply chain transparency (Towers, Perry and Chen, 2013; Carrigan *et al.*, 2017). Yang, Han and Lee (2017) proposed the value creation mechanism for following sustainability in the supply chain of luxury fashion. Luxury fashion companies should increase efficiency in their business operations through waste resource management, reduce pollution, disclose information on raw materials used in the manufacturing of their products and their footprints, monitor their environmental impacts and develop cooperative relationships with non-governmental organisations that help in sustainability implementation. The cases for research in the study were Stella McCartney and its parent company Kering, which are the examples of enterprises that successfully merge luxury and sustainability (Yang, Han and Lee, 2017).

Porter's (1985) value chain concept indicates the creation of consumer value through companies' basic and supporting activities (Porter, 1998). The contemporary value chain concept is regarded as a complex process and system of the exchanges of values between the company and its constituencies concerning addressing environmental and social problems (Hartman and Stafford, 1998). Logistics is traditionally defined as 'the process of planning, implementing and controlling the efficient flow and storage of goods, services and related information as they travel from point of origin to point of consumption' (Stock, Greis and Kasarda, 1998, p. 45).

In academic research and managerial practice, the forward supply chain and logistic management has had prevalence over the reverse flow of supply chain that starts to appear as the research field and a business practice for following sustainability (Rogers and Tibben-Lembke, 2001; Bernon and Cullen, 2007). Existing empirical research on reverse logistics has accentuated the economic and environmental dimensions of social responsibility. It has been argued that reverse logistics is a strategy that can positively influence different socially responsible practices, for example, health and safety and employment practices (Sarkis, Helms and Hervani, 2010).

One of the earliest definitions of the reverse flow of supply chain was given by Murphy and Poist (1989) who defined it as 'the movement of goods from a consumer towards a producer in a channel of distribution' (Murphy and Poist, 1989 cited in Rogers and Tibben-Lembke, 2001, p. 129). Carter and Ellram (1992) defined reverse logistics more specifically as 'the process whereby companies can become more environmentally efficient through recycling, reusing, and reducing the amount of materials used' (Carter and Ellram, 1992, p. 85).

Hvass (2014) explains that economic factors and corporate citizenship are the basic driving forces behind fashion companies' engagement in reverse logistics. Currently, legal pressure on fashion companies to consider the end-of-life aspects of their products is low. Economic forces stimulate fashion companies to enter the reverse flow of supply chains if it brings lower costs, new consumer segments and increased revenues and profitability. Corporate citizenship implies that companies need to consider the goals of sustainable development when entering and performing within the reverse flow of supply chains (Hvass, 2014).

Polonsky, Carlson and Fry (2003) emphasise the importance of considering the benefits of marketing exchanges between the company and its stakeholders as well as the harming influences of those exchanges on different parties in the network (Polonsky, Carlson and Fry, 2003). A course in corporate social responsibility research in luxury and fashion is related to the problem of how to avoid or decrease harmful influences that take place in the luxury and fashion supply chain (Kunz, May and Schmidt, 2020). For example, Carrigan, Moraes and McEachern (2013) explain that the British Fur Trade Association creates harm in the pre-production and production phase of the supply chain by advocating the use of real fur. It is justified with the claim that real fur is more sustainable because the manufacturing of artificial fur uses non-renewable and polluting resources (Carrigan, Moraes and McEachern, 2013).

A study by Dominguez and Bhatti (2022) shows how luxury and fashion brands could be sustainable and profitable based on rescuing products from landfill, transforming discarded waste through fine craftsmanship into topnotch products and donating to charities. Elvis and Kresse is a successful brand that designs and manufactures outstanding luxury fashion accessories through the transformation of wasted fire hoses and leather and donates half of its profits to charities (Dominguez and Bhatti, 2022).

2.6.4.1. Upcycling and Recycling

Upcycling relates to a creative process of remanufacturing and upgrading waste materials (Singh *et al.*, 2019). Upcycling is regarded as a more sustainable practice than recycling in which materials are wasted to a certain extent (Wilson, 2016). Using upcycled textile in the manufacturing of fashion goods does not imply shattering that is common for textile recycling (Bridgens *et al.*, 2018). Different making techniques can be used in the fashion industry to creatively transform textile waste into new materials, for example, 'needle-punch felting, knitting, stitching and weaving' (Keith and Silies, 2015, p. 1056).

One of the recycling techniques in the fashion industry is shredding, which results in the decomposition of textiles into fibres that can be of high and low grade. Low grade shoddy, as it is named, cannot be recycled into virgin fabrics like high quality shoddy, finishing as filling materials that are landfilled or incinerated after their lifespan. This indicates that recycling can contribute to environmental sustainability but recycling techniques are not absolutely sustainable. Recycling is only a more favourable practice to deal with fashion waste than landfilling and incineration (Keith and Silies, 2015). The value of recycling is currently reduced to downcycling when 'materials lose value as they circulate through industrial systems' (Braungart, McDonough and Bollinger, 2007, p. 4).

In the fashion industry, the prices of recycled materials are directly influenced by the cost of clothing recycling. The recycling system is based on donations to decrease the cost of recycled fibers because 'the price of regenerated fibers is 30% higher than that of native fiber' (Yan, 2019, p. 305). A negligible percentage of donated and discarded clothes are actually recycled into new garments within the reverse flow of the textile supply chain. Instead, unsold and end-of-life clothes are commonly landfilled and incinerated (House of Commons, 2019). The second-hand clothing system is not effective in tackling the problem of huge fashion waste because donated and discarded garments are dispatched to poor countries rather than truly recycled (Martinko, 2016; Delap, 2019). A considerable proportion of the population in the Third World is dependent on second-hand clothing imports from the developed world. Critics noticed that these trends negatively influence the textile industry in developing countries. However, these practices create jobs for the second-hand industry in those countries (Piribauer and Bartl, 2019).

Pollution caused by the fashion industry mainly does not come from waste landfills and incineration. Endeavours to boost recycling and reduce the use of raw materials in the textile manufacturing process should not be reflected in the practice of ignoring unsustainable practices in other parts of the textile supply chain. Addressing sustainability problems in the fashion industry requires a broader approach. The manufacturing process in the fashion industry generates environmental impacts through the employment of toxic technologies and chemicals and the usage of the great volumes of energy, air and water (House of Commons, 2019). The production of natural fabrics requires the extensive usage of water and pesticides while synthetic fabrics use non-renewable resources. Environmental degradation is also caused by high transportation costs due to the outsourcing of different activities in the manufacturing of garments and accessories within the scattered global fashion supply chain (Caniato *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, the dyeing process in the fashion industry exploits the enormous amounts of water and generates great liquid effluents that pollute the environment because of containing toxins and chemicals (De Souza, Peruzzo and De Souza, 2008). It has been estimated that effluent wastewater after dyeing in the textile and printing industry is 'the main source of pollution problem in recent time' (Mia *et al.*, 2019, p. 221). Nevertheless, textile recycling within the reverse logistics of the fashion supply chain is an important challenge and potential for making the industry more sustainable. In comparison to traditional recycling, the so-called circular economy with a network-based business model of companies, could bring benefits by connecting transportation capacities with warehouses and workforce to tackle the acute problem of fashion waste (Yan, 2019).

Therefore, addressing sustainability in fashion should put accent on delivering products created for the environment based on considering different environmentally friendly practices, such as delivering durable products and materials, using energy-efficient and non-toxic technologies, reducing chemicals in manufacturing, environmental labelling, package reusing and refilling, reducing or eliminating packaging, second-hand fashion, vintage practices, upcycling and so forth (Hartman and Stafford, 1998). It has been estimated that fibre production per year will be significantly increased to reach over a hundred million tonnes in the upcoming years while little has been done on extending the lifespan of fashion products. Without new consumption patterns, it will have far-reaching harmful effects on the environment (Piribauer and Bartl, 2019).

2.6.5. Consumer Research in the Field of Sustainable Luxury and Fashion

Based on using an experimental research design, Boenigk and Schuchardt (2013) and Hagtvedt and Patrick (2016) found that cause-related marketing can be a beneficial cooperative strategy for both luxury companies and charitable organisations. The effect of an association with charity on purchase intentions is essentially explained by the mechanism of guilt reduction (Boenigk and Schuchardt, 2013; Hagtvedt and Patrick, 2016). An experimental study by Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman (2013) indicates that communicating messages on the environmental benefits of utilitarian products by the use of eco-labels enhances the perceived functionality of those products. The effectiveness of using eco-labelling on consumers' evaluations of utilitarian products is reinforced by promoting environmental protection at the global level. In contrast, eco-labelled luxury products may be perceived positively if eco-labels highlight benefits related to consumers' self-interested reasons, for example, improved health because of reduced pollution and social recognition based on adopting environmentally sustainable behaviours (Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman, 2013).

The findings of an experimental research project by Amatulli *et al.* (2018) suggest that communicating the philanthropic and legal dimensions of corporate social responsibility increases consumers' willingness to purchase sustainable luxury brands more than communicating the economic and ethical dimensions of corporate social responsibility. Luxury brands promoting initiatives within the external domains of corporate social responsibility are perceived as more luxurious. The effect is stronger for high status and conspicuous luxury consumption than for self-oriented luxury consumption (Amatulli *et al.*, 2018). Based on experiments, Sipilä *et al.* (2021) report that assigning extrinsic corporate social responsibility attributions to luxury brands can damage consumer loyalty. These negative effects can be alleviated if luxury companies communicate company-internal social responsibility initiatives, for example, employee satisfaction, rather than philanthropic social responsibility. Luxury is significantly dependent on superb craftsmanship while philanthropy can be perceived as conflicting with the concept of luxury. Likewise, corporate social responsibility efforts can be more beneficial if the luxury brand's framing strategy accentuates sustainability more than exclusivity because it reduces extrinsic corporate social responsibility attributions (Sipilä *et al.*, 2021).

By the use of the Go/No-Go Association Task technique, Beckham and Voyer (2014) examined consumers' implicit attitudes towards sustainable luxury and found that consumers do not readily match luxury with sustainability. When luxury brands were evaluated in the context of high-street brands, participants in the study matched luxury brands with sustainability (Beckham and Voyer, 2014). Implicit attitudes relate to 'introspectively unidentified (or inaccurately identified) traces of past experience that mediate favourable or unfavourable feeling, thought, or action toward social objects' (Greenwald and Banaji, 1995, p. 8). In contrast to implicit attitudes that reflect consumers' automatic evaluations, explicit attitudes are associated with 'more thoughtful or deliberative responding' (Rudman, 2004, p. 79). An experimental survey study within this research project showed that consumers perceive eco-labelled luxury fashion products as less luxurious. A follow-up focus group discussion supported the finding that eco-labelling makes luxury fashion products less luxurious and discovered that consumers may not perceive luxury as essentially sustainable because of its excellent quality and durability (Beckham and Voyer, 2014).

Based on using the focus groups research method and wear tests, Cao *et al.* (2014) examined and evaluated consumers' willingness to use garments that can change their function, fit and style, which was based on the idea of extending the utility of products. Participants in the study had positive views on using adaptable apparel (Cao *et al.*, 2014). Adaptable design was introduced by Gu, Hashemian and Nee (2002) who recommended that creating products adaptable in design and/or production could be more beneficial than recycling in reducing excessive consumption and saving resources. The reason is that adaptable design as a sustainable design guide allows the usage of one adaptable product through replacing multiple products. Recycling, however, implies using returned fabrics and clothes for producing new garments in the early phases of the product supply chain (Gu, Hashemian and Nee, 2002).

A mixed methods study by Morgan and Birtwistle (2009) reveals that consumers lack awareness of the environmental aspects of the fashion industry and the need for recycling within the industry, which is believed to be a consequence of poor media coverage (Morgan and Birtwistle, 2009). A qualitative multi-method study by Vehmas *et al.* (2018) reports that consumers approve the usage of recycled textile waste in the manufacturing of new clothes. The study indicates that consumers could be willing to purchase garments made of recycled fabrics if they were well acquainted with recycling practices in the textile

industry and had concrete and attractive information on transforming textile waste into new high-quality clothes (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018). However, an experimental study by Achabou and Dekhili (2013) indicates a negative link between consumers' perceptions of luxury garments and the usage of recycled fabrics in the manufacturing of those goods while using organic fabrics and sustainable product packaging in luxury was evaluated positively (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013).

A survey study conducted by Niinimäki (2010) proposes that the majority of fashion consumers do not involve social responsibility information in their purchase decisions. However, consumers are willing to invest in high-quality and durable clothes in the future to give their contributions to combating pollution and global warming. It is well known that consumers show their own identity and distinctiveness through clothes. Niinimäki (2010) argues that for highly ethically motivated and committed fashion consumers, which are still a minor consumer group in the market, ethical fashion purchases are more than the expression of their personal identity. Purchasing clothes for ethical hardliners is a kind of applying 'their own ideology in their appearance' (Niinimäki, 2010, p. 159).

Based on using the focus group research method, Goworek *et al.* (2012) found a low level of consumers' awareness of the sustainability aspects of clothing. Some participants had interest in gaining more information on sustainability in fashion, textile waste management and the availability of facilities to act in a more sustainable manner. After the focus group discussion, participants had home diary tasks in which they showed their willingness to adopt more sustainable practices, which indicates that consumers' increased environmental awareness may evoke consumers' positive attitudes towards certain pro-sustainable behaviours. The information and discussion from the focus group influenced participants to reduce energy consumption through laundering. However, a small number of participants indicated that they were willing to change their purchase behaviour by reducing the quantity of clothes and purchasing sustainably assured clothes. Retailers were perceived as having no sincere motives in promoting and selling sustainable clothes (Goworek *et al.*, 2012).

In a survey study, Weber, Lynes and Young (2017) found that fashion consumers have a lower rate of disposing textile waste than non-fashion consumers. Consumers with high interest in fashion are more willing to manage textile waste through recycling, swapping and reselling than non-fashion consumers (Weber, Lynes and Young, 2017). By the

employment of in-depth interviews and observations, Henninger, Bürklin and Niinimäki (2019) examined the potential of swapping clothes between consumers for addressing the problem of textile waste and promoting sustainability. The findings indicate that consumers are mostly concerned with the quality and availability of clothes while stock shortage is the main problem for the organisers of swap-shop events (Henninger, Bürklin and Niinimäki, 2019).

Based on conducting interviews with consumers and practitioners, Sung *et al.* (2020) suggest that currently a negligible minority of consumers perceive upcycled fashion goods positively. The majority of consumers in the study had low awareness of upcycling business practices in fashion (Sung *et al.*, 2020). An experimental study by Adıgüzel and Donato (2021) signifies that consumers have higher purchase intentions of upcycled than recycled luxury goods through greater novelty and increased pride. When consumers' environmental concerns are increased, upcycled goods offered by new luxury brands are perceived as more congruent with sustainable production in comparison to existing luxury brands. Consumers are likely to perceive upcycled luxury goods more favourably than non-sustainable luxury goods through increased pride (Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021).

Based on using the focus group and survey questionnaire methods, Joergens (2006) found that consumers' decisions on buying clothes are not influenced by ethics. Participants in the study expressed negative attitudes towards and cynicism about fashion brands' corporate social responsibility efforts. Consumers are more interested in animal rights than labour and human rights in the fashion supply chain due to being aware that Western companies adapt their business operations to moral and working conditions in the developing world. Although the eventuality of eco-fashion consumption was very low, the future potential of buying ethical fashion was recognised among participants. The findings suggest that consumers are not willing to pay ethical clothes at higher prices in comparison to the prices of non-ethical garments (Joergens, 2006). A survey study by McGoldrick and Freestone (2008) indicates consumers' positive attitudes toward paying a small premium for ethically manufactured clothes (McGoldrick and Freestone, 2008).

A survey study by Kapferer and Michaut (2014) suggests that consumers are not likely to value sustainability in their luxury purchases. However, consumers expect the localisation of supply chains and craftsmanship to be the most important luxury values, which are the values that can be in coexistence with sustainable development. Consumers perceive

luxury as a cleaner and more responsible sector than other industries and they have low awareness of sustainability in luxury (Kapferer and Michaut, 2014).

Based on conducting multiple surveys, Kapferer and Michaut (2015) found that consumers do not involve sustainability in their luxury purchases. The perceived contradiction between luxury and sustainability is lower for consumers who define luxury as high quality and higher for consumers who define luxury as rarity, high price, exclusivity and hedonism. Consumers think about luxury as a reminder of wealth inequalities and superficial lifestyle. Although consumers perceive luxury and sustainability as contradictory, they expect luxury brands to demonstrate strong sustainability performance and deliver it as a dimension of quality (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). An experimental survey study by Dekhili, Achabou and Alharbi (2019) suggests that sustainability information can have a negative influence on the perceived quality of luxury products among consumers in developing countries. This is explained by a low level of sustainability awareness and a stronger social comparison orientation in luxury, which indicates that shallow luxury values, such as status and prestige, are more important for consumers in developing countries (Dekhili, Achabou and Alharbi, 2019).

An experimental survey study by Janssen *et al.* (2014) proposes that consumers perceive the lowest compatibility between luxury and corporate social responsibility for ephemeral luxury goods such as apparel. Consumers are likely to evaluate enduring luxury goods as more socially responsible if those goods are scarce (Janssen *et al.*, 2014).

Based on administering a survey with structured and open-minded questions, Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai (2012) found that ethics is a less important factor in luxury purchases than in commodity markets. Consumers consider both ethical commodity and luxury products more expensive than their non-ethical alternatives, which reflects the separation fallacy between business and ethics. In contrast to commodity purchases, consumers believe that luxury brands cannot contribute to solving social responsibility problems in the global supply chain. Consumers perceive the manufacturing and sourcing of luxury products with scarcely any negative environmental or social influence. In contrast to consumers' interest to obtain ethical information on commodity products based on purchasing those products on a regular base, the irregularity of purchasing luxury products causes that consumers are not willing to make efforts to find more information on the ethical aspects of luxury. Consumers believe that there is the lack of information on social responsibility in luxury

and luxury companies neglected promotional efforts to establish themselves as visible ethical brands in the market (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012).

Cervellon and Shammass (2013) used an exploratory research approach to study the drivers of luxury consumption in different cultures (Canada, UK, Italy and France). Respondents in this study in general associated sustainable luxury with ecology, philanthropy, belonging, conspicuousness, national identity, guilt-free consumption, high quality and hedonism. Consumers in all samples perceived luxury goods as sustainable based on their exceptional quality and durability and meticulousness in luxury manufacturing. It is worth to mention that French and Italian participants considered that sustainable luxury goods have a higher level of hedonic value in comparison to their traditional counterparts. However, a few interviewees were of the opinion that sustainability decreases the hedonic value of goods that have a special position in luxury, for example, couture within the luxury fashion industry (Cervellon and Shammass, 2013).

Based on using the semiotic and focus group research methods, Cervellon (2013) draws attention to the importance of consumers' perceptions of sustainability in relation to the type of luxury. Although consumers expect that brands offering mass luxury support environmental and social causes, achieved luxury cannot be perceived as intrinsically compatible with sustainability. Brands representing ascribed luxury are expected to have a sustainability mission and vision and shape their business model in accordance with the sustainable development goals. The qualities of ascribed luxury, such as operating locally, slow production, limited editions, using rare, natural and exceptional materials, outstanding designs, craftsmanship and timelessness, are perceived as more compatible with sustainable development (Cervellon, 2013).

An experimental study by Griskevicius, Tybur and Van den Bergh (2010) indicates that status consumption may be compatible with altruism. The findings of this study contradict a traditional approach which connects consumers' motivation for luxury purchases with signalling wealth. This study showed that consumers may relinquish highly luxurious products and turn to less luxurious sustainable products only if such a behaviour can be observed by others and affect their reputation. When the factor of price was included, social motives influenced consumers to choose a more expensive green luxury product over a less expensive non-green luxury product. The study demonstrated that status

motives can be a driver of sustainable consumption, which can be used in promoting sustainable products (Griskevicius, Tybur and Van den Bergh, 2010).

An experimental study by Torelli, Monga and Kaikati (2012) suggests that consumers may perceive self-enhancement values promoted by luxury brands as incompatible with self-transcendence values associated with corporate social responsibility. This perceived contradiction may create unfavourable brand evaluations, brand dilution and brand equity erosion in the short-term based on processing disfluency and experiencing vague discontent. These effects are stronger when corporate social responsibility is promoted in an abstract way (Torelli, Monga and Kaikati, 2012).

Based on collected experimental survey data, Janssen, Vanhamme and Leblanc (2017) report that consumers have more positive corporate social responsibility attitudes towards a responsible luxury brand that follows an inconspicuous branding strategy in comparison to a responsible luxury brand that follows a conspicuous branding strategy. This supports the idea that the social norms of modesty and self-sacrifice do not match conspicuousness (Janssen, Vanhamme and Leblanc, 2017). Based on using an experimental research design, Costa Pinto *et al.* (2019) propose that promoting corporate social responsibility can be detrimental for luxury brands because consumers perceive luxury brands as highly linked to a sophisticated brand personality, which is characterised by glamour and high social status and perceived as less ethical. However, it is recommended that luxury companies communicate corporate social responsibility by highlighting the interests of consumers, for example, health benefits associated with sustainable luxury products (Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019).

Based on administering a questionnaire and conducting focus groups interviews, Armstrong *et al.* (2016) found that fashion consumers may perceive use-oriented product-service systems, such as swapping, renting and clothing consultancy, as more favourable than product-oriented product-service systems, such as repair, redesign and customisation. The positive evaluation of use-oriented product-service systems was based on participants' wish to reduce their current scale of consumption and to act economically (Armstrong *et al.*, 2016).

An ethnographic study by Karpova *et al.* (2022) examined the phenomenon of temporary clothes swapping in consumers' real-life environments. Karpova *et al.* (2022) take the stance that temporary clothes swapping may be pivotal in a gradual transition from excessive fashion consumerism to circular and sustainable fashion consumption because of having the elements of both possession and non-possession of clothes. Namely, the impossibility to possess garments and accessories appears to be a stumbling block to consumers in embracing the idea of collaborative consumption in light of the fact that purchasing fashion goods is greatly impacted by emotional motives. However, it is not possible to perform this sustainable practice on a mass scale due to the perceived risk of contamination and the problem of belonging to different social groups (Karpova *et al.*, 2022).

Based on using semi-structured interviewing, Turunen and Pöyry (2019) found that resale value has become a new important dimension of luxury fashion consumers' shopping style parallel with quality, price-per-quality and brand awareness. Consumers in this study held the view that used luxury fashion products reflect the highest quality of materials used in their manufacturing and perfect craftsmanship. These consumers search for a luxury product that is priced based on its high quality, they have brand consciousness and they believe that the second-hand market unveils the real value of a brand. The findings of this study suggest the likelihood of a shift in luxury fashion consumers' motives, values and behaviours from donating and throwing to reselling products (Turunen and Pöyry, 2019).

A semi-structured qualitative study by Turunen and Leipämaa-Leskinen (2015) revealed that combating overconsumption and animal suffering and finding timeless and unique goods different from brand-new and mass-produced goods with loud logos stimulate consumers to purchase second-hand luxury fashion, although it is basically driven by resale value awareness (Turunen and Leipämaa-Leskinen, 2015). A mixed-method study by Kessous and Valette-Florence (2019) indicates that consumers purchase first-hand luxury to signal status, demonstrate power and possess high-quality products. The drivers of purchasing second-hand luxury are rooted in consumers' wish to get recognition within a social class that was formerly elusive, ecological awareness, expectations to gain financial gains through reselling products, feelings of nostalgia when searching for vintage products and desire to find unique products (Kessous and Valette-Florence, 2019). Based on using the in-depth interviewing technique, Turunen, Cervellon and Carey (2020) found that the most important motives for trading on the second-hand luxury market are associated with

consumers' desire to gain high social status or to contribute to the growth of a circular economy based on extending the product life cycle (Turunen, Cervellon and Carey, 2020).

Based on administering semi-structured interviews with professionals involved in sustainable fashion design practices, Han *et al.* (2017) explored marketing communication strategies and techniques used by upcycled and sustainable fashion brands in reaching consumers most likely to purchase their products. The findings of this study show that social media has become the major marketing technique for targeting socially conscious and responsible fashion consumers. The second most used marketing strategy for targeting consumers likely to engage in socially responsible consumption by fashion brands is in-store dialogue (Han *et al.*, 2017).

2.6.5.1. Market Segmentation and the Characteristics of Socially Responsible Consumers

A myriad of studies generated conflicting findings on the utility of demographic indicators for identifying consumers who are more likely to make purchases in support of corporate social responsibility (Auger *et al.*, 2003; Lee, 2008; McGoldrick and Freestone, 2008; Luchs and Mooradian, 2012; Furman, Maison and Sekścińska, 2020). For example, Balderjahn (1988) indicates that socially responsible consumption is likely to vary directly with socio-economic status (Balderjahn, 1988). Roberts (1996a) suggests that females, older and higher educated consumers are more likely to engage in ecologically conscious behaviour. There is a negative relationship between income and ecologically conscious consumption, which shows that the market for corporate social responsibility related products has been enlarging and attracting different segments of society (Roberts, 1996a).

It has been argued that psychographic variables, such as lifestyle, personality characteristics, values and attitudes, can be more useful than demographics for market segmentation because of indicating why consumers purchase products (Narang, 2010). Accordingly, certain personality features could be emphasised in companies' marketing media efforts when advertising socially responsible products. Fraj and Martinez (2006) propose that companies should target conscientious and open-minded individuals with extrovert personality when promoting products with a social responsibility proposition (Fraj and Martinez, 2006). Similarly, Song and Kim (2018) explain that the socially responsible consumer is likely to have the personality traits of openness, conscientiousness and bravery as well as to be highly efficient and self-controlled (Song and Kim, 2018).

Prosocial motivations and behaviours can be examined through dispositional and situational outcomes. Based on the use of a personality dispositional approach to prosocial behaviour, Basil and Weber (2006) discovered that consumers concentrated on values perceive socially responsible behaviour as an internal normative requirement. Individuals concerned with how they appear to others evaluate social responsibility efforts positively because it is regarded as a socially desirable behaviour, which may be applied in promoting corporate social responsibility in fashion (Basil and Weber, 2006).

The phenomenon of the situational specificity of behaviour indicates that the effect of personality traits on behaviour is stronger if an individual is reminded on his/her personality traits in a certain situation (Kraut, 1973). It can be used in communicating corporate social responsibility to reinforce the effect of a personality trait on motivating socially responsible purchases. However, the amount of the variation in consumer behaviour explained by personality indicators in studies is commonly small (Basil and Weber, 2006). Likewise, there is a weak correlation between socio-demographic variables and consumer behaviour, showing that consumers' purchase interest in products is more driven by other factors, such as attitudes, quality, price, value, brand familiarity, trends, snobbery, convenience and so forth (Roberts, 1996a; Roberts, 1996b). Schlegelmilch, Bohlen and Diamantopoulos (1996) conclude that 'attitudes are the most consistent predictor of pro-environmental purchasing behaviour' (Schlegelmilch, Bohlen and Diamantopoulos, 1996, p. 51).

It is possible to distinguish between consumers who choose to reduce consumption, consumers who prefer to recycle, repair and reuse products and consumers who prioritise second-hand and vintage products (Zamwel, Sasson-Levy and Ben-Porat, 2014; Athwal *et al.*, 2019). McDonald, Oates and Alevizou (2016) identified three segments of green consumers: selectors who are focused on a specific green activity/activities, translators who are passive in adopting responsible behaviours and exceptors who are actively motivated to choose to behave responsibly but sometimes they allow themselves deviations from green standards (McDonald, Oates and Alevizou, 2016). Henninger *et al.* (2017) used this typology as a framework for investigating consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion and identified indulgers as the fourth consumer type. These consumers purchase luxury fashion products only to satisfy their personal wishes and needs, regardless of if luxury fashion products are sourced sustainably or not (Henninger *et al.*, 2017).

Kapferer and Michaut's (2014) study formed a three-part luxury market segmentation that involves 'luxury buyers who are quite critical and even guilty, those who say they have no idea and those for whom luxury carries no harm' (Kapferer and Michaut, 2014, p. 11). Carrigan and Attalla's (2001) categorisation of consumer behaviour, which is done on the basis of consumers' ethical awareness and willingness to purchase ethical products, recognises four types of consumers: 'cynical and disinterested', 'confused and uncertain', 'caring and ethical' and 'oblivious' consumers (Carrigan and Attalla, 2001, pp. 572-573). The characteristics of these consumer groups are described in the Table 2.8.

Table 2.8: Market Segmentation Based on Consumers' Ethical Awareness and Willingness to Purchase Ethical Products

Cynical and disinterested consumer	Consumers who have information on companies' ethical behaviour but they do not have trust in the motives behind companies' social responsibility efforts, which creates their low purchase intentions towards ethical products.
Confused and uncertain consumer	Consumers who hesitate to buy ethical products because of lacking clear and concrete information on corporate behaviour, although they are willing to purchase ethical products.
Caring and ethical consumer	Consumers who are motivated to reward ethical companies and discriminate unethical companies but they may be selective in making their ethical judgements.
Oblivious consumer	Consumers who are not aware of or not concerned with ethics and do not involve information on corporate behaviour in their purchase decisions.

Based on: Carrigan and Attalla (2001)

2.7. Theoretical Background and Hypotheses

The theoretical framework of this study is based on the theory of planned behaviour, which is the most frequently applied model for explaining and predicting behaviour in different research realms and industries. For example, the theory of planned behaviour was used to explain and predict consumer purchasing behaviour concerning counterfeit apparel goods (Kozar and Marcketti, 2011), green consumer behaviour in the hotel industry (Bashir *et al.*, 2019) and sustainable consumer behaviour regarding electronic products (Sheoran and Kumar, 2022). In a luxury context, there is the lack of research on the antecedents of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable brands (Olšanová *et al.*, 2022).

The theory of planned behaviour posits that a conscious and deliberate behavioural intention is influenced by attitudes, subjective norms or other potential determinants and it has a decisive effect on human social behaviour. As an extension of the theory of reasoned action, the theory of planned behaviour includes perceived behavioural control as an additional determinant of intentions, as illustrated in the Figure 2.1 below (Ajzen, 1991; Ajzen, 2011).

Figure 2.1: Theory of Planned Behaviour

Source: Adapted from Ajzen (1991, p. 182)

A useful theoretical framework for this research is Carroll's (1991) model of corporate social responsibility, which provides the systematisation of the domains of corporate social responsibilities. Carroll's (1991) model is considered 'a leading paradigm of CSR in the social issues in management field' (Schwartz and Carroll, 2003, p. 504). The model argues that the company's economic and legal responsibilities are required by society, the

company's ethical responsibilities are expected by society and the company's philanthropic responsibilities are desirable by society (Carroll, 1991). For example, Safi (2013) used Carroll's (1991) model of corporate social responsibility to explore if consumers consider companies' initiatives within the economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic domains of social responsibility in their purchase decisions (Safi, 2013). Pino *et al.* (2016) used Carroll's (1991) model of corporate social responsibility to study how consumers' perceptions of genetically modified food producers' corporate social responsibility initiatives influence consumers' attitudes and purchase intentions towards this type of food (Pino *et al.*, 2016). In a luxury context, there is scarce research on how consumers respond to different corporate social responsibility domains and initiatives (Amatulli *et al.*, 2018). The model is presented in the Figure 2.2 below.

Figure 2.2: Carroll's (1991) Model of Corporate Social Responsibility

Source: Adapted from Carroll (1991, p. 42)

The literature review draws attention to the following critical factors that can affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands: consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability, awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability, perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands and gender. This study aims to facilitate the understanding of if there is a significant relationship between these factors and consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The study measures the direct influence of the variables on consumers' purchase intentions, which has not been explored in a luxury fashion context. The term direct effect means to quantify the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable without the inclusion of a third hypothetical variable (Buis, 2010).

2.7.1. Relation between Consumers' Perceived Contradiction between Luxury Fashion and Sustainability and Purchase Intention of Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brands

Sustainable luxury fashion brand is a luxury fashion brand which is committed to environmental and social issues and brings sustainable products to consumers (Carey and Cervellon, 2014). Consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability refers to the degree to which consumers believe that luxury fashion and sustainability are contradictory (Pickens, 2005; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

Ajzen (1991) writes that 'behavioural intentions are indications of a person's readiness to perform a behaviour' (Ajzen, 2011, p. 1122). Purchase intention, following Spears and Singh (2004), is 'an individual's conscious plan to make an effort to purchase a brand' (Spears and Singh, 2004, p. 56). In this study, consumers' purchase intention of sustainable luxury fashion brands refers to consumers' self-reported willingness to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands (Ajzen, 2011; Hung *et al.*, 2011).

Kapferer and Michaut (2014) explain that consumers are possibly aware of the contradiction between luxury and sustainability and consumers are not likely to include sustainability in their luxury purchases. Consumers perceive luxury and sustainability as contradictory because of linking luxury with social stratification and superficiality rather than thinking about unsustainable practices within the luxury industry. This indicates that luxury brands have promoted sustainability without highlighting that true and deep luxury

values can be in alignment with sustainable development, such as high quality, durability, longevity, credibility and transparency (Kapferer and Michaut, 2014).

Beckham and Voyer (2014) suggest that the perceived contradiction between luxury and sustainability is likely to cause consumers' unwillingness to purchase sustainable luxury brands. Participants in Beckham and Voyer's (2014) study were of the opinion that sustainable luxury goods bring lower prestige to their owners, i.e., 'the people who normally buy from Gucci would not be inclined to buy sustainable shoes...I think it takes away the "special factor" for that market' (Beckham and Voyer, 2014, p. 248). Based on the established conceptual link between luxury and sustainability, it is logical to assume that consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability is negatively related to consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H1: Consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability negatively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands such that the higher perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability, the lower purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

2.7.2. Relation between Consumers' Awareness of Luxury Fashion Brands' Sustainability and Purchase Intention of Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brands

In this study, consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability refers to consumers' knowledge of luxury fashion brands' sustainability activities and principles when purchasing sustainable luxury fashion brands (Olšánová *et al.*, 2022). Carrigan and Attalla (2001) argue that consumers do not involve information on unethical corporate behaviour in their purchase decisions, although consumers have some awareness of unethical business operations, i.e., 'most people think, there is not much I can do about it, so why bother?' (Carrigan and Attalla, 2001, p. 569). Henninger *et al.* (2017) suggest that indulgers ignore sustainability information in their luxury purchases, in spite of being aware that all luxury products are not sourced sustainably, i.e., 'I get easily attracted by limited editions and some special collections that made of leather and fur and I will totally forget to think where the leather comes from' (Henninger *et al.*, 2017, pp. 426-428). Kapferer and Michaut (2014) found that consumers have low awareness of the sustainability aspects of the luxury industry (Kapferer and Michaut, 2014). Similarly, Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai

(2012) report that consumers have low awareness of ethical issues in luxury and available ethical luxury products. Because of the lack of information on the ethical aspects of luxury, consumers foster mistaken beliefs about clean and ethical luxury (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012).

In Lee and Shin's (2010) study, consumers' awareness of corporate social contribution and local community contribution activities significantly positively impacted their purchase intentions. Consumers' awareness of corporate environmental contribution activities had little effect on their purchase intentions. The study indicates the importance of how the results of corporate social responsibility activities have been delivered to consumers. Likewise, consumers have interest in for them particularly good socially responsible activities and to buy products from companies that excel in delivering those activities (Lee and Shin, 2010). This reflects the suggestion of Mohr, Webb and Harris (2001) that consumers' increased awareness of social responsibility and companies' records on social responsibility is likely to positively affect consumers' socially responsible behaviour (Mohr, Webb and Harris, 2001).

Suki Suki and Azman (2016) demonstrate that there is a significant and positive relationship between consumers' awareness of green marketing and consumers' purchase intentions (Suki Suki and Azman, 2016). Sharma *et al.* (2018) found that consumers' corporate social responsibility awareness has a significant and positive impact on consumers' purchase intentions of the retail product (Sharma *et al.*, 2018). Olšanová *et al.* (2022) report a significant and positive relationship between consumers' awareness of luxury brands' socially responsible activities and consumers' purchase intentions of luxury brands (Olšanová *et al.*, 2022). This study anticipates finding a positive relationship between consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability and consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability positively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands such that the higher awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, the higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

2.7.3. Relation between Consumers' Expectation for Luxury Fashion Brands' Sustainability and Purchase Intention of Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brands

In this study, consumers' expectation for luxury fashion brands' sustainability refers to the degree to which consumers believe that luxury fashion brands will comply with policies within the legal and ethical, social and environmental domains of sustainability (Pickens, 2005; Ng, 2022). Kapferer and Michaut (2015) propose that consumers have high latent expectations about luxury brands' dedication to sustainability, although they mostly do not consider sustainability in their luxury purchases (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Marin and Ruiz (2007) explain that consumers may respond negatively to brands and products if their expected contribution to environmental protection and social betterment has not been made (Marin and Ruiz, 2007). Reynolds and Ceranic (2007) argue that individuals' moral identity and judgements affect their moral behaviour (Reynolds and Ceranic, 2007) while Choi and Winterich (2013) demonstrate that consumers' moral identity impacts their brand attitudes and prosocial behaviour. Accordingly, consumers' moral identity can be induced when corporate social responsibility expectations are met and it can positively affect their attitudes and intentions towards ethical brands (Choi and Winterich, 2013). Ng (2022) proposes that consumers' expectations for social enterprises' corporate social responsibility significantly positively affect their attitudes and purchase intentions towards social enterprise products (Ng, 2022).

Creyer and Ross (1997) indicate that consumers' expectations for the ethicality of corporate behaviour are a significant predictor of consumers' willingness to reward an ethical company or punish an unethical company by purchasing behaviour (Creyer and Ross, 1997). Podnar and Golob (2007) extended the work of Creyer and Ross (1997) using Carroll's (1991) model of corporate social responsibility to study how consumers' corporate social responsibility expectations affect consumers' willingness to pay a premium for the socially responsible company's products and consumers' willingness to be loyal to the socially responsible company. In Podnar and Golob's (2007) study, consumers' expectations for the ethical and philanthropic corporate social responsibility were significantly positively related to consumers' support of companies' socially responsible behaviour (Podnar and Golob, 2007). Within the fashion industry, Lin, Wang and Yang (2023) report that consumers' expectations for fashion brands' socially responsible practices significantly positively predict consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable fashion brands (Lin, Wang and Yang, 2023). This study anticipates finding a positive

relationship between consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability and consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability (H3a. expectations for legal and ethical sustainability, H3b. expectations for social sustainability and H3c. expectations for environmental sustainability) positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands such that the higher expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, the higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

2.7.4. Relation between Consumers' Attitude towards Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brands and Purchase Intention of Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brands

The theory of planned behaviour accepts attitude as the main determinant of behavioural intention and defines it as 'the degree to which a person has a favourable or unfavourable evaluation or appraisal of the behaviour in question' (Ajzen, 1991, p. 188). Mitchell and Olson (1981) define attitude towards the brand as 'an individual's internal evaluation of an object such as a branded product' (Mitchell and Olson, 1981, p. 318). In this study, consumers' attitude towards sustainable luxury fashion brands refers to the degree to which consumers have a favourable or unfavourable evaluation of purchasing sustainable luxury fashion brands (Ajzen, 1991; Lee, Zailani and Rahman, 2020).

De Pelsmacker, Driesen and Rayp (2005) found the inconsistency between consumers' positive attitudes towards purchasing Fairtrade coffee and consumers' willingness to pay a price premium for Fairtrade coffee (De Pelsmacker, Driesen and Rayp, 2005). However, Lee and Yun (2015) and Yazdanpanah and Forouzani (2015) report that consumers are likely to purchase organic food, which is a type of eco-friendly food, because of their positive attitudes towards purchasing such food (Lee and Yun, 2015; Yazdanpanah and Forouzani, 2015). Lee, Zailani and Rahman (2020) argue that consumers purchase social enterprise products because they have positive attitudes towards such products (Lee, Zailani and Rahman, 2020).

Kapferer and Michaut (2015) concluded that consumers are less likely to purchase sustainable luxury products based on measuring consumers' attitudes towards involving sustainability in their luxury purchases (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Salem and Chaichi (2018) found that consumers' attitudes towards luxury fashion products significantly positively affect consumers' purchase intentions towards luxury fashion products and their willingness to pay a premium price for such products (Salem and Chaichi, 2018). Rausch and Kopplin (2021) report a significant and positive relationship between consumers' attitudes and purchase intentions towards sustainable clothes (Rausch and Kopplin, 2021). This study anticipates finding a positive relationship between consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands and consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands such that the higher attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, the higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

2.7.5. Relation between Consumers' Attribution for Luxury Fashion Brands' Intrinsic Sustainability and Purchase Intention of Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brands

Corporate social responsibility attribution, according to Bhattacharya and Sen (2004), refers to 'causal reasoning consumers engage in when trying to understand a company's CSR activities' (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004, p. 14). In this study, consumers' attribution for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability refers to the degree to which consumers believe that luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability because they have genuine concern for sustainability (Vlachos, Panagopoulos and Rapp, 2013).

Kim and Lee (2012) explain that consumers tend to attribute both public-serving and firm-serving motives to companies' corporate social responsibility and consumers are willing to accept that the main purpose of business are firm-serving motives. Accordingly, assuring consumers of the business' intrinsic corporate social responsibility might be more important in generating consumers' willingness to support corporate social responsibility related purchases (Kim and Lee, 2012). This is in line with the suggestion of Bhattacharya and Sen (2004) that consumers develop positive attitudes towards companies with genuine commitments to social responsibility (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004). Moreover, as

Parguel, Benoît-Moreau and Larceneux (2011) indicate, consumers' perceptions of intrinsic social responsibility significantly positively impact their corporate brand evaluations (Parguel, Benoît-Moreau and Larceneux, 2011).

In Ellen, Webb and Mohr's (2006) study, consumers' attributions for egoistic and stakeholder driven corporate social responsibility significantly negatively predicted consumers' purchase intentions while consumers' attributions for values driven and strategic corporate social responsibility significantly positively predicted consumers' purchase intentions (Ellen, Webb and Mohr, 2006). Ellen, Webb and Mohr's (2006) egoistic, stakeholder driven and strategic corporate social responsibility motivations closely correspond to extrinsic corporate social responsibility. Values driven corporate social responsibility motivations are closely aligned with intrinsic corporate social responsibility (Vlachos, Panagopoulos and Rapp, 2013). Ginder, Kwon and Byun (2021) found a significant and negative relationship between consumers' attributions for extrinsic corporate social responsibility and purchase intentions. The relationship between consumers' attributions for intrinsic corporate social responsibility and purchase intentions was significantly positive (Ginder, Kwon and Byun, 2021). This study anticipates finding a positive relationship between consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability and consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands such that the higher attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability, the higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

2.7.6. Relation between Consumers' Perceived Value of Circular Luxury Fashion Brands and Purchase Intention of Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brands

A circular economy approach within the fashion industry indicates creating a closed-loop system in which products are designed, produced and utilised with the aim to minimise landfill waste, reduce environmental impacts and save resources (Brydges, 2021). Circular fashion appears to be the main attempt in addressing sustainability issues in the fashion supply chain based on using practices that keep materials and products in use as long as

possible, such as recycling, upcycling and resale programmes (Carey and Cervellon, 2014; Jimenez-Fernandez, Aramendia-Muneta and Alzate, 2023).

Zeithaml (1988) defines perceived value as 'the consumer's overall assessment of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is received and what is given' (Zeithaml, 1988, p. 14). A multidimensional approach to perceived value implies that the multiple dimensions of value have different influences on consumer choice in different situations. Sheth, Newman and Gross (1991) classified perceived value into five dimensions: "functional value, social value, emotional value, epistemic value, and conditional value" (Sheth, Newman and Gross, 1991, p. 160). Based on Sheth, Newman and Gross' (1991) theory of consumption values, Kim, Jung and Lee (2021) propose that emotional, social and epistemic values in combination with environmental value reflect the basic dimensions of consumers' perceived value of circular fashion products. Functional value was excluded from their analysis because consumers might hypothesise that circular fashion products have lower durability and quality based on using discarded materials in their manufacturing, that is, it was considered a risk factor. Conditional value was not involved in their analysis because it does not have relevance for explaining general consumer buying behaviour (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021).

In line with the suggestion of Kim, Jung and Lee (2021), this study employs emotional, social, epistemic and environmental values as the dimensions of consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands. Therefore, consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands refers to the degree to which consumers have a favourable or unfavourable evaluation of the emotional, social, epistemic and environmental values of circular luxury fashion brands (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021).

Emotional value refers to 'the perceived utility acquired from an alternative's capacity to arouse feelings or affective states' (Sheth, Newman and Gross, 1991, p. 161). Consumers perceive high emotional value when they experience joy and reduce stress by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands. Consumers can feel happy and proud when they contribute to environmental protection based on purchasing circular luxury fashion brands (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Adıgüzel and Donato (2021) propose that consumers are likely to evaluate upcycled luxury more positively than traditional luxury because of feeling proud to behave sustainably (Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021).

Social value refers to ‘the perceived utility acquired from an alternative’s association with one or more specific social groups’ (Sheth, Newman and Gross, 1991, p. 161). Consumers obtain high social value if they evaluate that buying and possessing circular luxury fashion brands help them to enhance their self-concept and social status in the community (Sweeney and Soutar, 2001). Chi (2015) argues that consumers might perceive that buying and wearing environmentally friendly apparel help them to gain social acceptance and impress significant others (Chi, 2015).

Epistemic value refers to ‘the perceived utility acquired from an alternative’s capacity to arouse curiosity, provide novelty, and/or satisfy a desire for knowledge’ (Sheth, Newman and Gross, 1991, p. 162). Consumers perceive high epistemic value if circular luxury fashion brands are novel, unique and rare (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). According to Adıgüzel and Donato (2021), consumers are likely to evaluate upcycled luxury more positively than recycled luxury through novelty, which increases consumers’ purchase intentions of upcycled luxury brands (Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021). Research indicates that second-hand luxury fashion shopping is driven by searching for unique and rare products that are not available on the mass market (Turunen and Leipämaa-Leskinen, 2015; Kessous and Valette-Florence, 2019).

Environmental value captures the perceived utility derived from the environmental impacts of a product. Consumers receive high environmental value if they perceive that circular luxury fashion brands are capable to provide greater environmental benefits in comparison to other luxury fashion brands (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Following Hussain, Saleem and Soomro (2023), consumers’ purchase intentions of sustainable fashion brands might be prompted because of their belief that circular fashion brands advance the usage of recycling and upcycling practices through sustainable supply chain management in order to protect the natural environment (Hussain, Saleem and Soomro, 2023).

Kim, Jung and Lee (2021) suggest that consumers’ perceived emotional, social, epistemic and environmental values of circular fashion products significantly positively affect consumers’ circular fashion product attitudes, which has a significant positive effect on consumers’ purchase intentions towards such products (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Yu and Lee (2018) report that there is a significant positive impact of consumers’ perceived green, emotional and aesthetic values of overall upcycled products on consumers’ attitudes and purchase intentions towards such products (Yu and Lee, 2018). Lou *et al.* (2022)

demonstrate that consumers' emotional, social, perceived quality and green values significantly positively impact consumers' purchase intentions of second-hand luxury products (Lou *et al.*, 2022). Hussain, Saleem and Soomro (2023) indicate that consumers' environmental, emotional and social values significantly positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of circular fashion products (Hussain, Saleem and Soomro, 2023). This study anticipates finding a positive relationship between consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands and consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: Consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands (H6a. perceived emotional value, H6b. perceived social value, H6c. perceived epistemic value and H6d. perceived environmental value) positively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands such that the higher perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands, the higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

2.7.7. Relation between Consumers' Gender and Purchase Intention of Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brands

It has been suggested that animal welfare, environmental impacts and ethical wages in the fashion industry are more important for females than males (Gazzola *et al.*, 2020) and women perceive recycling in luxury fashion more positively than men (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013). The influence of gender on purchase intentions towards sustainable luxury fashion brands has not been explored. Within the fashion industry, Dangelico, Alvino and Fraccascia (2022) report that consumers' purchase intentions of garments made of organic materials are significantly influenced by gender. Females, in comparison to males, have higher purchase intentions of garments made of organic materials and females are more willing to pay a premium price for such garments (Dangelico, Alvino and Fraccascia, 2022). Outside the luxury and fashion industry, Han, Hsu and Lee (2009) found that females are more likely to pay a premium for green hotels than males (Han, Hsu and Lee, 2009). Matic and Puh (2016) demonstrate that gender has a significant influence on consumers' purchase intentions of green or natural cosmetic products, that is, women have higher willingness to purchase such cosmetics than men (Matic and Puh, 2016). This study anticipates that females are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands than males. The following hypothesis is proposed:

H7: Females have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than males.

The Figure 2.3 represents the research model of the study, showing the variables and the relationships to be explored. The model examines how consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability, awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability, perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands and gender affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

Figure 2.3: Research Model of the Study

Source: Author's contribution based on the academic literature

2.8. Summary

The review of the evolution of the corporate social responsibility concept in this chapter demonstrated the generation of a variety of theories that can be associated with an instrumental perspective and normative perspective to corporate social responsibility. The instrumental theory of corporate social responsibility reflects the relevance of business reasons for companies' social responsibility engagement. It is a more realistic application

of the social responsibility concept in business with regard to the fact that the business sector exists for lucrative purposes. The normative theory of corporate social responsibility suggests the consideration of ethical reasons for pursuing social responsibility by involving the interests of all stakeholder groups. It is a less feasible scenario of social responsibility based on the objective reasoning that businesses' involvement in social responsibility cannot be guided exclusively by moral judgments and arguments in the capitalistic economic and political system. It is also practically difficult to consider the requirements of a multiplicity of stakeholders when making decisions on implementing social responsibility policies, which leads the managerial process to focus on the interests of the most relevant stakeholders for the goals of the organisation (Carroll, 1999; Masaka, 2008; Crane and Matten, 2016).

Studies on the corporate social responsibility and firm performance link yielded competing and variable findings (Cho, Chung and Young, 2019; Maqbool and Bakr, 2019). Circumstances explaining the relationship between corporate social and financial performance remain unexplained, leaving managers uncertain if social responsibility performance is an indispensable condition for competitiveness or competitiveness is a prerequisite for socially responsible behaviour (Griffin and Mahon, 1997; Vilanova, Lozano and Arenas, 2009; Rodriguez-Fernandez, 2016).

The role of marketing researchers is to provide market recommendations for the business case for corporate social responsibility. The business sector is pressured by the activist movements to advance corporate social responsibility implementation in supply chains that without socially responsible consumption cannot be justified (Maignan and Ferrell, 2004; Pelozo and Shang, 2011). The link between corporate social responsibility initiatives and socially responsible consumption seems to be a paradox that needs further examination to determine how companies should use and communicate corporate social responsibility without enduring adverse effects (Reinhardt and Stavins, 2010).

Marketing research in the field of corporate social responsibility has been focused on the link between corporate social responsibility and corporate image and reputation (Walsh *et al.*, 2009; Bianchi, Bruno and Sarabia-Sanchez, 2019). It has become increasingly difficult to ignore the influence of corporate social responsibility on consumer perceived value and loyalty, which has been neglected in marketing research (Shin and Thai, 2015; Servera-Francés and Piqueras-Tomás, 2019).

A holistic approach to investigating consumers' perceptions of different corporate social responsibility domains and activities is a missing link (Maignan and Ferrell, 2004). Research on the influence of the environmental and philanthropic domains of corporate social responsibility on consumer choice has not generated definite findings (Drumwright, 1996; Menon and Menon, 1997; Barone, Miyazaki and Taylor, 2000). Research on communicating corporate social responsibility via social responsibility disclosures and eco-labelling is in an initial phase (Stratling, 2007; Atănăsoaie, 2013). More studies are necessary to understand the gap between consumers' social responsibility attitudes and purchase intentions and actual socially responsible actions (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004; White, Habib and Hardisty, 2019).

A negative link between corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance has been identified in a luxury context (Sipilä *et al.*, 2021). Prior research indicated that promoting and motivating responsible consumption is challenging for luxury brands because social responsibility is not highly important in luxury purchase decisions (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012; Kapferer and Michaut, 2014). This is manifested in luxury fashion markets to a great degree because of the industry's short product life cycle and a deliberately conveyed self-enhancement image of luxury fashion brands. However, high quality, durability and craftsmanship in luxury have been emphasised as the favourable qualities for the development of sustainable luxury (Joy *et al.*, 2012; Torelli, Monga and Kaikati, 2012; Godart and Seong, 2014; Nash, Ginger and Cartier, 2016; Henninger *et al.*, 2017).

Very little research has been done about consumers' views on different corporate social responsibility domains and activities in luxury (Amatulli *et al.*, 2018; Sipilä *et al.*, 2021). There has been the lack of research on consumers' attitudes towards textile waste managing practices and circular clothes, i.e., swapping and reusing, recycling, upcycling, reselling and donating (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013; Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021; Karpova *et al.*, 2022).

Additional research is needed to examine the matter of the fallacy of clean luxury and the perceived contradiction between luxury and sustainability in different luxury settings. Consumers' low awareness of corporate social responsibility and unfavourable corporate social responsibility attributions in luxury indicate the need for more studies on developing

effective strategies for communicating socially responsible initiatives in luxury (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012; Han *et al.*, 2017).

Research has been focused on examining consumers' perceptions, attitudes and behaviours regarding brand-new sustainable luxury while consumers' interest in second-hand luxury as an opportunity for boosting sustainable consumption has received less attention (Turunen and Pöyry, 2019). It has been emphasised that luxury brands cannot ignore sustainability and consumers are a stakeholder group that have high expectations regarding luxury brands' sustainability efforts (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Luxury and fashion brands need to use sustainability branding as a marketing and business practice to demonstrate their environmental and social engagement (Alwi, Ali and Nguyen, 2017). Corporate reputation is likely to be damaged by irresponsible corporate behaviour with possible negative effects on profitability (Fan, 2005; García de los Salmones Sánchez and Pérez Ruiz, 2018).

The testable hypotheses for this study were developed based on the review of previous findings, the identified gaps in knowledge and the need for the further consideration of consumer behaviour in the field of sustainable luxury and fashion. Carroll's (1991) model of corporate social responsibility has been proposed as the theoretical framework of the study, which is an effective managerial framework for evaluating the relevance of different corporate social responsibility domains and activities for consumers (Carroll, 1991). The need to develop a better understanding of the factors that affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands justifies the employment of the theory of planned behaviour as the theoretical framework of the study (Ajzen, 1991; Ajzen, 2011).

Chapter 3: Research Methodology and Design

3.1. Overview

This chapter in the introductory section defines academic research and science and explains the importance of a methodological fit among the elements of this research project. The chapter discusses the philosophical assumptions and the research strategy underlying this study, the research methods for collecting and analysing data and the followed procedures necessary to ensure the rigour and robustness of the findings in order to answer the research questions of the study and contribute to knowledge development.

3.2. Concept of Research and Methodological Fit

Scientific research, citing Kerlinger (1973), implies ‘a systematic, controlled, empirical and critical investigation of hypothetical propositions about the presumed relations among natural phenomena’ (Kerlinger, 1973, p. 11). Science, following Bhattacharjee (2012), is ‘a systematic and organised body of knowledge in any area of inquiry that is acquired using “the scientific method”’ (Bhattacharjee, 2012, p. 1). Research is a planned, systematic and organised process of the collection, analysis and interpretation of data directed towards the advancement of science through enhancing the comprehension of the topic of interest for scholars and practitioners (Leedy and Ormrod, 2005).

In the knowledge development process for this thesis, the literature review formed the base for identifying the research gaps in the field of corporate social responsibility and in the context of sustainable luxury and fashion with accent on consumer behaviour. The research design of this study is a plan for conducting research in order to answer the research questions of the study and succeed in theoretical contributions to the fields of corporate social responsibility and consumer behaviour as well as practical contributions concerning the managerial understanding of consumers’ views and intentions with regard to the idea of sustainable luxury fashion. Introduced by Edmondson and McManus (2007), methodological fit is ‘internal consistency among elements of a research project’ and it plays a crucial role for the effective theoretical and practical contributions of research studies, encompassing ‘research question, prior work, research design and theoretical contribution’ (Edmondson and McManus, 2007, p. 1155).

3.3. Research Design

Research design is related to ‘the overarching plan for the collection, measurement and analysis of data’ (Gray, 2018, p. 132). Following Crotty (1998), designing this study considers the essential components of any research process: epistemological assumptions, theoretical perspective, research methodology and methods (Crotty, 1998). Epistemological assumptions influence the adoption of a research methodology and research method/methods for answering the research questions of a study by shaping the ways of acquiring and communicating knowledge and eventually determining ‘what tests and criteria must be involved in order to establish knowledge’ (Hitchcock and Hughes, 1995, p. 19). The choice of employing positivism as the theoretical philosophical

foundation of this study is in accordance with finding answers to the research questions based on following a quantitative research strategy, that is, the usage of the survey questionnaire method for collecting data and statistical tests for testing the hypotheses (Crotty, 1998).

3.4. Research Philosophical Assumptions

Research philosophy portrays 'a system of beliefs and assumptions about the development of knowledge' (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p. 130). Crotty (1998) explained that the concept of ontology relates to 'the study of being' while epistemology is concerned with 'what it means to know' (Crotty, 1998, p. 10). The consideration of the philosophical assumptions of ontology and epistemology is essential for the understanding of the research field and how to fill in the research gaps (Tekin and Kotaman, 2013; Žukauskas, Vveinhardt and Andriukaitienė, 2018).

The initial stage of the research design for this study is the justification for using the objectivist and positivist philosophical perspective on the phenomenon under study. Objectivism argues that social phenomena exist separately from the researcher and the reality of the social world cannot be altered by the constructions of social actors (Burrell and Morgan, 1979; Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Hatch and Cunliffe, 2013; Yucel, 2018).

As an objectivist research perspective, positivism is employed as the guiding research philosophy behind this study and it is based on the need to obtain factual, reliable and valid data on consumers' views on sustainability in luxury fashion in order to explain and predict sustainable consumer behaviour in luxury fashion (Weber, 2004; Creswell and Garrett, 2008; Park, Konge and Artino, 2020). Positivism accentuates the importance of rigour, replicability, reliability and generalisable conclusions (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The general belief among researchers is that the application of positivist philosophical assumptions is necessary for measuring the effectiveness of corporate social responsibility (Samy and Robertson, 2017) and identifying explanatory and causal relationships to predict consumer behaviour (Hunt, 1991).

3.5. Implications of Alternative Research Philosophies

Critical realism assumes that an objective truth exists independently from human constructions but social phenomena cannot always be objectively observable, which indicates that empirical research commonly generates deficient and imperfect findings (Gorski, 2013; Haigh *et al.*, 2019). Because of using triangulation to cross validate research findings, critical realism is a research philosophy that suits mixed-methods research (Bhaskar, 2008; Tekin and Kotaman, 2013).

As the strongest proponents of using triangulation in research, Campbell and Fiske (1959), Webb *et al.* (1966) and Denzin (1970) argue that the use of multiple research methods, data sources or researchers lessens bias in research and generates convergent data on the phenomenon under study. The cancellation of bias in research is reflected in enhancing the quality of findings based on a high level of validity and reliability (Campbell and Fiske, 1959; Jick, 1979; Mathison, 1988; Denzin, 2017). However, probably the most common accepted meaning of triangulation among researchers nowadays relates to the usage of triangulation as a means for providing complementary data rather than discovering an objective truth on the research problem (Erzberger and Prein, 1997; Olsen, 2004; Hammersley, 2008; Turner and Turner, 2009; Östlund *et al.*, 2010).

Interpretivism is used as a research philosophy when the researcher aims to understand, interpret and construct the meanings of social actors' motives, attitudes and behaviours within certain contexts (Crotty, 1998; Strauss and Corbin, 2008; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). As per the tenet of the relativistic nature of the social world, interpretivists would argue that corporate social responsibility is a social phenomenon cognised through the complex process of interactive shaping and sharing values between the business sector and society (Boubakary and Moskolai, 2016). However, this study is guided with the aim to examine consumers' views on sustainability in luxury fashion and their willingness to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands by the employment of a highly structured quantitative research methodology that enables and facilitates statistical hypothesis tests in order to make generalisations to the population of research. The positivist research paradigm is therefore more applicable for the research process underlying this thesis (Hunt, 1991).

The limitation of using qualitative research methods stems from the idiographic nature of qualitative findings. Qualitative findings can be extrapolated only to similar contexts and situations without a possibility for replication. Qualitative findings cannot be applied to ‘wider populations with the same degree of certainty’ as nomothetic quantitative findings. In other words, qualitative findings ‘are not tested to discover whether they are statistically significant or due to chance’ (Atieno, 2009, p. 17). The main metatheoretical assumptions on positivism and interpretivism as the research paradigms commonly compared by researchers are summarised in the Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Metatheoretical Assumptions of Positivism and Interpretivism

Metatheoretical assumptions	Positivism	Interpretivism
Research object	Having essential attributes existing independent from the researcher	Possessing covert and abstract meanings that are examined and interpreted by the researcher’s interactions with the social world
Methods	Quantitative	Qualitative
Validity	Internal and external validity	Credibility and transferability
Reliability	Replicability	Dependability

Based on: Guba (1981); Weber (2004); Bryman (2012)

3.6. Research Methodology Choice

Crotty (1998) defines research methodology as ‘the strategy, plan of action, process or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of methods to the desired outcomes’ (Crotty, 1998, p. 3). In line with the positivist research philosophy guiding this research, the research approach adopted for this study is quantitative, deductive and explanatory. The quantitative research approach is an apposite choice for answering the research questions of this study because of its explanatory nature. Explanatory research is justifiable to employ when the research problem is clearly identified in the academic literature and the researcher is familiar with the given variables but the causal and explanatory relationships between those variables have not been sufficiently studied (Creswell, 1994).

Qualitative exploratory research would be necessary for this study if the problem of corporate social responsibility has never been addressed with a sample of luxury and fashion consumers or if existing theories on corporate social responsibility do not apply to the population being studied (Creswell, 1994). As specified by Guba (1978), qualitative research is associated with discovering 'phenomena whose empirical elaboration and testing would be worthwhile' (Guba, 1978, p. 13). Inconsistent findings about the problem of the growth of sustainable luxury and fashion consumption suggest the need for more quantitative studies in the field (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013; Beckham and Voyer, 2014; Janssen *et al.*, 2014; Nash, Ginger and Cartier, 2016; Amatulli *et al.*, 2018; Sipilä *et al.*, 2021).

Deductive research is considered an appropriate research approach for this study because the hypotheses for statistical testing were developed on the basis of existing knowledge about the phenomenon under study. Deductive research has the aim to revise an existing theory through amelioration or refutation or create a new theory necessary for solving the research problem (Hyde, 2000; Bryman and Bell, 2011; Gray, 2018).

In order to emphasise that objectivity is an indispensable element of any research process, qualitative or quantitative, Guba (1978) highlighted that data in research 'should be reliable, factual, and confirmable' (Guba, 1978, p. 74). However, due to the lack of standardised procedures for analysing data in qualitative research, the level of subjective interpretation of data is sometimes cited as the main interfering factor for generating objective inferences (Patton, 1980; De Vos *et al.*, 2002; Daniel, 2016). As stressed by Denzin and Lincoln (2005), qualitative research implies 'an interpretive, naturalistic approach to the world' (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005, p. 4).

Qualitative and quantitative research methods aim to reveal variations, that is, to investigate how cases differ and some of the factors linked to those variations (Bryman, 2012). Qualitative analysis, however, does not allocate 'frequencies to the linguistic features', which suggests that in qualitative research 'rare phenomena receive (or should receive) the same amount of attention as more frequent phenomena' (Atieno, 2009, p. 17).

In quantitative research, the reliability and validity of findings are dependent on the measure rather than the researcher. Measurement in quantitative research allows identifying fine differences between cases regarding the attributes of interest by the usage

of consistent standards, which highlights the significance of assuring reliability in research. Quantitative research provides more accurate assessments of the levels of the relationships between variables (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Quantitative research has the advantage of reducing social desirability bias in comparison to qualitative research administered by face-to-face interviewing (McGoldrick and Freestone, 2008; McDonald, Oates and Alevizou, 2016). Quantitative research has the power to reveal the percentages of consumers with positive and negative attitudes and intentions towards products and services and their distribution by age, gender, education, income and regularity of purchase (Hammarberg, Kirkman and De Lacey, 2016). On the other hand, quantitative research is dependent on sample size and does not allow an in-depth investigation of the phenomenon under observation (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Following a qualitative research design allows researchers to redefine the research questions based on new insights into the problem of consideration (Armstrong, 2010).

Regardless of the differences between qualitative and quantitative research, both research methods allow the researcher to find answers to the 'questions of "how, where, when, who and why" with a perspective to build a theory or refute an existing theory' (Leung, 2015, p. 324). Quantitative research is concerned with 'people's behaviour' while qualitative research aims to reveal 'the meaning of action' (Bryman, 2012, p. 408). The main characteristics of quantitative and qualitative research are presented in the Table 3.2. The advantages and disadvantages of quantitative and qualitative research are summarised in the Table 3.3. The Table 3.4 outlines the research process of this study.

Table 3.2: Main Characteristics of Quantitative and Qualitative Social Research

Quantitative research	Qualitative research
Objectivist epistemological paradigm	Constructivist epistemological paradigm
Explanatory research	Exploratory research
A deductive approach is commonly used to confirm or refute an existing theory	An inductive approach is commonly used to generate a new theory
Examining research objects based on the distance between the researcher and participants	An in-depth understanding of phenomena in their contextual environments through close interaction with respondents
Often controlled settings	Natural settings
Focus is on facts and behaviour	Focus is on meanings
Statistical analysis of data	Conceptualisation
Based on meanings obtained from numbers	Based on meanings
Reliability	Dependability
Generalisability	Transferability
Validity	Credibility
Objectivity	Confirmability
Nomothetic findings	Idiographic findings
Resulting in numerical and standardised data	Findings are presented in words
A value-free position	The social world is constructed through interactions between the researcher and respondents
Probability or random sampling	Purposive sampling

Based on: Guba (1981); Guba and Lincoln (1994); Armstrong (2010); Merriam (2015); Robson and McCartan (2016); Sekaran and Bougie (2016); Gray (2018)

Table 3.3: Advantages and Disadvantages of Quantitative and Qualitative Research

Quantitative research	Qualitative research
<p>Advantages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical generalisability • Objectivity • Rigour • Replicability • Precision and confidence • Explanations • Persuasiveness of findings based on higher emphasis on frequencies within collected data • Large samples 	<p>Advantages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uniqueness • Contextual and in-depth understanding of phenomena • Richness of data • Theory emerging from data • Receptivity and reflexivity of the researcher
<p>Disadvantages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dependency on sample size • Difficulty in gaining an in-depth understanding of phenomena • Does not stimulate creative and imaginative thinking 	<p>Disadvantages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restricted to exploratory research • Lack of scientific rigour • Subjective or emotional interpretations of findings • Activation of bias • Difficult to replicate • Problems of generalisation • Small samples • Lack of transparency • Limited to textual-data gathering methods • Discrepancy between words and complex situations being investigated

Based on: Bryman and Bell (2011); Bryman (2012); Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson (2015); Daniel (2016); Robson and McCartan (2016); Sekaran and Bougie (2016); Pajo (2018)

Table 3.4: Research Process of the Study

Literature review
Development of the research questions
Development of the hypotheses
Survey questionnaire data collection
Data analysis
Interpretation of the findings
Discussion of the findings
Managerial and theoretical implications
Limitations of the study
Suggestions for future research

3.7. Questionnaire Survey

In social science research, five broad types of research design can be used for data collection and knowledge acquisition: 'laboratory studies, field studies, meta-analyses, survey studies and case studies' (Lunenburg, 2011, p. 1). Denzin (1970) defines research methods as 'lines of action taken toward the empirical world' and 'different means of acting on the environment of the scientist', emphasising that surveys 'dictate a stance toward the invariant and stable features of this reality' (Denzin, 2017, p. 298).

Explanatory survey in consumer behaviour research relates to a method of collecting data about the features, attitudes, motives, intentions, actions, etc. of a certain consumer population concerning the topic of interest based on a structured set of questions (Roopa and Rani, 2012). My inference is that the employment of a cross-sectional research design and the survey questionnaire research method is the most relevant research strategy for answering the research questions of this study. It is also a realisable strategy within the time and cost constraints for conducting this research. In marketing and social science studies, questionnaires are frequently employed in surveys with the aim to understand, explain and predict behaviour. A necessary prerequisite for the fruitfulness of using surveys in investigating phenomena is the utilisation of standardised, structured questions that have the same meaning for all respondents in a study, which is difficult to accomplish within exploratory research (De Vaus, 2014; Robson and McCartan, 2016).

3.7.1. Overview, Design and Scale of the Questionnaire

A questionnaire is a list of questions used for collecting data from participants on a given phenomenon in a reliable and valid way (Taherdoost, 2016). In accordance with the guideline from the academic literature, I started the questionnaire for this research with a short opening statement in which I introduced myself, I explained the nature of this study to participants and I invited participants to take part in the study. The statement that this research project was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland was given. The statements on ensuring confidentiality and anonymity in the study were provided. Participants' right to refuse to take part in the research and to withdraw at any time was agreed. I provided a general guideline for filling in the questionnaire and I specified the approximate time for completing the questionnaire. It was explained that the achievement of the purpose of the study requires obtaining consumers' true views and opinions about sustainability in luxury fashion and not socially acceptable or unacceptable answers. I indicated to participants to feel free to contact me if they had any questions regarding this research or if they needed any further information and I provided my university email address. I expressed my gratitude to participants for helping me to carry out this research in advance (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

This study adopts a quantitative research design to test the relationship between consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability, perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability, perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands and consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The questionnaire's scales for measuring the constructs in the proposed model were adapted from the prior academic literature. Churchill's (1979) work is considered the gold standard for developing the measures of constructs within the marketing literature. As the Table 3.5 shows, Churchill's (1979) procedure for developing the measures starts with the specification of the domain of a construct and the generations of items that adequately capture the domain. Firstly, the constructs were clearly defined and evidence that the constructs can be measured was obtained, that is, the scales with the evidence of reliability and validity were adapted from the prior academic studies (Churchill, 1979). The Table 3.6 shows how the questionnaire with the multi-item scales operationalises the constructs specified in the proposed model. The Table 3.6. provides the constructs, the

operational definitions of the constructs, the items for measuring the constructs and the references used for adapting the scales. The Table 3.7 shows the items measuring the constructs in the model along with the items from the established scales from the previous studies.

The dependent variable, that is, consumers' purchase intention of sustainable luxury fashion brands was measured by a three-item scale adapted from Hung *et al.* (2011). The scale items were revised by adding 'if my budget allows' to fit the context of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Consumers' attitude towards sustainable luxury fashion brands was measured by five items adapted from Lee, Zailani and Rahman's (2020) scale. Because Lee, Zailani and Rahman's (2020) scale was used to measure consumers' attitude towards social enterprise products, the scale items were revised to measure consumers' attitude towards sustainable luxury fashion brands by replacing social enterprise products with sustainable luxury fashion brands. Consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability was measured by a three-item scale adapted from Olšanová *et al.* (2022). Consumers' expectation for luxury fashion brands' sustainability was operationalised as a second-order construct. The sustainability expectations for luxury fashion brands are consumers' ethical and legal, social and environmental expectations. Each dimension of consumers' sustainability expectation for luxury fashion brands was measured by a multi-item scale adapted from Ng (2022). Consumers' ethical and legal sustainability expectation was measured by a four-item scale, social sustainability expectation was measured by a three-item scale and environmental sustainability expectation was measured by a two-item scale.

Consumers' attribution for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability was measured by a three-item scale adapted from Vlachos, Panagopoulos and Rapp (2013). Consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability was measured by a two-item scale adapted from Kapferer and Michaut (2014). Consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands was operationalised as a second-order construct. The perceived values of circular luxury fashion brands are consumers' emotional, social, epistemic and environmental values. Each dimension of consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands was measured by a multi-item scale adapted from Kim, Jung and Lee (2021). Consumers' emotional value was measured by a four-item scale, social value was measured by a three-item scale, epistemic value was measured by a three-item scale and environmental value was measured by a four-item scale. Because Kim, Jung

and Lee's (2021) scales were used to measure consumers' perceived values of circular clothing, the scales were revised to measure consumers' perceived values of circular luxury fashion brands by replacing circular clothing with circular luxury fashion brands. Therefore, the minor modifications of the scales were made to fit the specific context of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

Table 3.5: Scale Adaptation Procedure Modified from Churchill (1979)

Step	Recommended procedure	Technique implemented
1	Specify domain of construct	Literature review on consumer behaviour and sustainable consumption
2	Generate sample of items	Literature review; discussion with marketing quantitative researchers; expert-driven pretest (with an expert in marketing and quantitative research); participant-driven pretest
3	Collect data	Pilot test with participants (n = 140)
4	Purify measure	Cronbach's alpha reliability test and exploratory factor analysis
5	Collect data	Main research with participants (n = 453)
6	Assess reliability and validity	Cronbach's alpha reliability test and confirmatory factor analysis (composite reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity)
7	Develop norms	Future research

Table 3.6: Constructs and Items in the Questionnaire

Construct	Operational definition	Items and scaling	References
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention	The degree of consumers' willingness to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands	1. I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	Hung <i>et al.</i> (2011)
		2. I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	
		3. I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	

Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude	The degree to which consumers have a favourable or unfavourable evaluation of sustainable luxury fashion brands	1. Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	Lee, Zailani and Rahman (2020)
		2. Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	
		3. Sustainable luxury fashion brands are unique and special	
		4. Sustainable luxury fashion brands are of quality	
		5. I trust sustainable luxury fashion brands	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	The degree of consumers' knowledge of luxury fashion brands' sustainability	1. When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	Olšanová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
		2. When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	
		3. When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation	The degree to which consumers believe that luxury fashion brands will comply with policies within the legal and ethical, social and environmental domains of sustainability	Legal and ethical sustainability expectation	Podnar and Golob (2007); Ng (2022)
		1. Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	
		2. Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	
		3. Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	
		4. Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	
		Social sustainability expectation	
		5. Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	
		6. Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	

		7. Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	
		Environmental sustainability expectation	
		8. Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	
		9. Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	The degree to which consumers believe that luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability because they have genuine concern for sustainability	1. Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable 2. Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help 3. Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	Vlachos, Panagopoulos and Rapp (2013)
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	The degree to which consumers believe that luxury fashion and sustainability are contradictory	1. Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory 2. Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	Kapferer and Michaut (2014)
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value	The degree to which consumers have a favourable or unfavourable evaluation of the emotional, social, epistemic and environmental value of circular luxury fashion brands	Emotional perceived value 1. I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand 2. Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good 3. The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands 4. Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure Social perceived value 5. Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval 6. Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people 7. Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	Kim, Jung and Lee (2021)

		Epistemic perceived value	
		8. Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	
		9. Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	
		10. Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	
		Environmental perceived value	
		11. Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources	
		12. Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials	
		13. Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly	
		14. Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	

Table 3.7: Scales' Items from the Prior Academic Studies and Constructs' Items in the Questionnaire

Construct	Initial items	Modified items	References
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention	1. I have strong possibility to purchase Luxury Brand X's product	1. I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	Hung <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	2. I'm likely to purchase Luxury Brand X's product	2. I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	
	3. I have high intention to purchase Luxury Brand X's product	3. I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude	1. Buying social enterprise products fits my personal values	1. Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	Lee, Zailani and Rahman (2020)
	2. Buying social enterprise products makes me feel good	2. Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	

	3. Social enterprise products are unique and special	3. Sustainable luxury fashion brands are unique and special	
	4. Social enterprise products are of quality	4. Sustainable luxury fashion brands are of quality	
	5. I trust the brand of social enterprise products	5. I trust sustainable luxury fashion brands	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	1. When I buy luxury brand X, I was aware of its socially responsible activities	1. When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	Olšanová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	2. When I buy luxury brand X, I would have appreciated knowing about its socially responsible activities	2. When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	
	3. When I buy luxury brand X, it is important to me if X is trying to be highly committed to well-defined ethical principles	3. When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation		Legal and ethical sustainability expectation	Ng (2022); Podnar and Golob (2007)
	1. Companies should consider moral standards on account of profit	1. Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	
	2. Companies should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	2. Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	
	3. Companies should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	3. Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	
	4. Companies should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	4. Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	
		Social sustainability expectation	
	5. Companies should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	5. Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	

	6. Companies should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	6. Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	
	7. Companies should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	7. Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	
		Environmental sustainability expectation	
	8. Companies should play a key role in environmental protection	8. Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	
	9. Companies should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	9. Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	1. (Company name) is genuinely concerned about being socially responsible	1. Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable	Vlachos, Panagopouls and Rapp (2013)
	2. (Company name) engages in socially responsible initiatives because it feels morally obligated to help	2. Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help	
	3. (Company name) engages in socially responsible initiatives in order to give back something to the community	3. Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	1. Luxury and sustainable development are contradictory	1. Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	Kapferer and Michaut (2014)
	2. Luxury has no future in a sustainably driven world	2. Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	

Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value		Emotional perceived value	Kim, Jung and Lee (2021)
	1. I feel happy when I wear this clothing	1. I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand	
	2. Purchasing this clothing makes me feel good.	2. Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	
	3. The stress is relieved by purchasing this clothing	3. The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands	
	4. This clothing provides joy and pleasure	4. Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure	
		Social perceived value	
	5. Purchasing this clothing can give its owner social approval	5. Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval	
	6. This clothing would make a good impression on other people	6. Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people	
	7. This clothing would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	7. Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	
		Epistemic perceived value	
	8. This clothing offers uniqueness	8. Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	
	9. This clothing has points of difference from general clothing	9. Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	
	10. This clothing has many new features	10. Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	
	Environmental perceived value		
11. This clothing helps save resources	11. Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources		
12. This clothing has a positive impact on the environment in that it extends the life of discarded materials	12. Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials		
13. This clothing is environmentally friendly	13. Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly		

	14. This clothing has more environmental benefits than other clothing	14. Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	
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Bias in a survey questionnaire can be induced by the effects of the wording of questions or statements, question order and response categories on survey responses (Choi and Pak, 2005). The adapted scales in the questionnaire for this research did not involve reverse-coded items. A myriad of studies recommend against using reverse-coded items for measuring constructs because it decreases reliability and validity rather than control acquiescence response bias or any other allegedly unacceptable result (Johnson, Bristow and Schneider, 2004; Roszkowski and Soven, 2010; Salazar, 2015). Participants under high involvement in surveys are not likely to be influenced by the wording of questions because questions are answered with more attention, higher carefulness and deeper contemplation (Garg, 1996).

The items measuring the dependent variable were introduced before the items measuring the independent variables in the questionnaire. This is based on the aim to reduce the risk of skewing participants toward a particular answer, that is, the need to obtain more sincere and unbiased answers on consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Asking participants if they intend to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands at the beginning of the questionnaire is relevant considering that respondents are likely to have higher concentration upon starting to fill in the questionnaire. Many scholars recommend that questionnaires in survey research do not start with polemical and emotional items. In this regard, the indicators measuring consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability and expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability are placed before the indicators measuring consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability, perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability and perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands. The last questions in the questionnaire are about the demographics of participants (age, gender, level of income and level of education), followed by the questions on participants' consumption level of luxury fashion brands and first attribute in defining luxury fashion. These questions are placed in the end of the questionnaire based on the aim to increase participants' engagement and avoid boredom (Rattray and Jones, 2007).

The scales' items were measured using seven-point Likert scales with response anchors ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). When using seven-point Likert scales, respondents are less likely to choose responses that may be contradictory to their true evaluations. Seven-point Likert scale is especially more appropriate for electronically distributed questionnaire surveys. When a questionnaire is administered electronically, the researcher is not in person to clarify an item and participants are more likely to ignore it (Finstad, 2010).

The direction of rating scales in Likert-type questionnaires is not supposed to have an effect on the accuracy of findings if participants are highly involved with questions or statements in the questionnaire (Leon, Aizpurua and Van der Valk, 2021). However, it is recommended that the strongly disagree response category is placed on the left side of the scale because it reduces agreement bias, which was followed in designing the questionnaire for this study (Friedman and Amoo, 1999).

Data obtained using Likert-type scale questionnaires are liable to central tendency bias, which suggests that participants are inclined to choose most answers in the middle of the scale. Likert scales are susceptible to social desirability bias if participants answer questions in a way which is regarded as favourable by others. Non-differentiation bias occurs when participants are inclined to provide alike or almost the same answers to all questions on the scale. Furthermore, acquiescence or agreement bias in data happens when participants have a tendency to agree with statements regardless of their content while dissent bias means that participants provide mostly negative answers. Regardless of these possible drawbacks of using Likert scale in questionnaires, Likert scale is commonly employed as a variable measurement method in collecting attitudinal and behavioural data due to providing more variance based on using larger scales (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

Likert scale is considered an ordinal or interval level scale and treated as a variable that can take a countable or uncountable number of levels (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The categorical nature of variables can be disregarded when ordinal-scale responses are coded numerically in the ascending order of values and when the scale has at least 5 points (Rhemtulla, Brosseau-Liard and Savalei, 2012). In contrast to nominal scale that has only labelling and classification purposes, ordinal scale is used to rank categorised values in a meaningful order but the difference between the ranked values is not

quantifiable and relevant as in the case of interval and ratio scales. Likert scale is therefore treated as an ordinal scale if it is not assumed that 'all pairs of adjacent levels are equidistant' (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016, p. 216). Participants' residency, gender, regularity of purchasing luxury fashion brands and first attribute in defining luxury fashion are the categories of nominal scale. Participants' education status and level of monthly income are the examples of ordinal scales while participants' age is a ratio variable. In ratio scales, values are labelled, have a meaningful order with the equal distances between the adjacent values and can accept a true zero point (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

3.7.2. Sampling Method and Procedure of the Study

After this research project was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland, the survey research, that is, collecting data for the preliminary and main study was performed from the 10th May until the 21st June 2024. The convenience sampling and voluntary response sampling methods were used for recruiting participants in the preliminary and main research (Jager, Putnick and Bornstein, 2017). Data were collected using a web-based survey implemented on the survey administration software Google Forms.

3.7.2.1. Pre-testing of the Instrument and Pilot Study

The academic literature suggests that a pre-test of the research instrument is an indispensable preliminary test which allows the detection of any problem with the questionnaire, for example, if some of the questions are ambiguous or unintelligible and if there is any ambiguity in the instructions for filling in the questionnaire (Hunt, Sparkman and Wilcox, 1982; Robson and McCartan, 2016). The questionnaire for this survey research was scrutinised by an expert in marketing and quantitative research before the research project was submitted for the Ethics Committee's approval. It was necessary to ensure that the questionnaire's scales were created in accordance with a scale adaptation procedure and to follow consistency in the wording of the statements. The items measuring consumers' purchase intention were revised by adding 'if my budget allows' to fit the context of sustainable luxury fashion brands. After the research project was approved by the Ethics Committee, the pre-test of the questionnaire with participants was conducted to assess how adequately the questionnaire works (Churchill, 1979).

Participants were recruited using convenience sampling for pretesting the questionnaire. I invited my family members, fellow students and friends by WhatsApp messenger to fill in the questionnaire and provide any comments relevant for the improvement and clarification of the statements in the questionnaire. Among twenty one testers, who were the self-reported consumers of luxury fashion brands, nobody pointed out any problem with the questionnaire. The comments were that all statements in the questionnaire were 'straightforward' and 'easy to understand'. The questionnaire was proofread again for the purpose of providing linguistic clarity and detecting any mistake in the formulation of the statements in order to proceed with the pilot study (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

At this stage, the decision about the sample size for this research was made. Following Roscoe (1975), the appropriate sample size for most research studies is larger than 30 and lower than 500 observations (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). For studies performing multivariate analysis, following Hair *et al.* (2019), the sample size should be at least ten times greater than the number of items or the number of estimated model coefficients (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The sample size of a research study is also influenced by the cost and time constraints for its completion (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Following these rules of thumb and considering the cost and time constraints for conducting the whole study, I determined the sample size to be between 400 and 500 participants.

Following Churchill's (1979) procedure for creating better scales in research, conducting a pilot test is necessary to evaluate the quality of the questionnaire's scales generated from the academic literature through reliability analysis and factor analysis (Churchill, 1979). Different authors recommend that the adequate sample size for the pilot study is minimally 10-20% of the future sample, which should be adapted according to the specific objectives of the test (Whitehead *et al.*, 2016). Accordingly, the sample size for the pilot test should be large enough to ensure the assessment of the feasibility of conducting the main study (Ismail, Kinchin and Edwards, 2018). Hair *et al.* (2019) recommend that the sample size for pilot studies should be at least 100 observations such that the sample has sufficient statistical power to help evaluate the acceptability of using measure instruments in the main study (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Recruiting participants for the pilot survey was done using the convenience and voluntary response sampling methods. I invited my friends and colleagues by WhatsApp messenger and email to fill in the survey questionnaire. In survey advertising and exchange groups on

the social media platform Facebook, I invited 240 potential participants to fill in the questionnaire after I completed their questionnaires. 140 participants filled in the questionnaire successfully, that is, 140 responses were received without missing data. The response rate above 50% is regarded as adequate for pilot studies in marketing and social science studies (Nulty, 2008).

Cronbach's alpha coefficient is regarded as the most common measure of the reliability and internal consistency of survey responses. Churchill (1979) stressed that Cronbach's alpha coefficient 'absolutely should be the first measure one calculates to assess the quality of the instrument' (Churchill, 1979, p. 68). When the questionnaire scale is multidimensional, it is more apposite to calculate Cronbach's alpha score for each construct than for the questionnaire as a whole (Panayides, 2013; Li *et al.*, 2022). The internal consistency reliabilities for the questionnaire's scales were calculated using the pilot study's data with the software Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 29. The values of Cronbach's alpha are reported in the Table 3.8, which shows that the constructs had a high level of internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha for the constructs was higher than 0.70, ranging from 0.731 to 0.935. Following Nunnally (1967), the value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.60 indicates a minimum acceptable level of reliability in preliminary research (Peterson, 1994).

Table 3.8: Reliability of the Measure Instruments (Pilot Study)

Variable	Initial number of items	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention	3	0.931
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude	5	0.872
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	3	0.786
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation	9	0.901
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	3	0.836
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	2	0.731
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value	14	0.935

3.7.2.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis

Factor analysis is used in combination with Cronbach's alpha coefficient to assess the quality of scales (Churchill, 1979; Cortina, 1993). Factor analysis is a statistical technique which 'attempts to determine which sets of observed variables share common variance-covariance characteristics that define theoretical constructs or factors' (Schumacker and Lomax, 2010, p. 164). The rationale behind factor analysis is the reduction of multiple variables into a smaller number of factors that explain the relationships between variables (Fein *et al.*, 2022).

With regard to adapting the items from the prior scales and using them in the context of sustainable luxury fashion brands, the usage of exploratory factor analysis was considered appropriate to explore the underlying factor structure of the questionnaire's scale using the pilot study's data. The academic literature explains that exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis are used to evaluate the quality of scales in scale development and scale adaptation studies. Exploratory factor analysis is commonly used in an initial stage of research to find out how the questionnaire's items load on undetermined or non-hypothesised factors. Confirmatory factor analysis is used to test and validate the theoretical model in which the number of hypothesised factors is pre-specified (Hurley *et al.*, 1997; Orçan, 2018; Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Performing exploratory factor analysis is based on a number of assumptions. According to Kline (2011) and Hair *et al.* (2019), the sample size for factor analysis should be at least 100 participants (Kline, 2011; Hair *et al.*, 2019). In the pilot study for this research, the sample size of 140 was accomplished. The exploratory factor analysis was performed with the software SPSS 29. A visual examination of the correlation matrix showed that almost all correlations were significant at the significance level of .001 ($p < .001$) and almost all correlation coefficients were lower than 0.7, which indicates the solid foundation for factor analysis. The determinant of data is provided at the bottom of the correlation matrix and its value was 9.579E-16, which is 0.0009579, and it is greater than the necessary value of 0.00001. This suggests that multicollinearity was not a problem for these data, that is, all statements in the questionnaire correlated fairly well (Field, 2009).

The communality of a scale indicates 'the proportion of common variance in an item' (Fein *et al.*, 2022, p. 79). Communalities closer to 1 suggest that factors better explain data. The communality of the scale was assessed and the results showed that all initial communalities were over 0.5 and almost all communalities after extraction were over 0.5. Ideal communalities are considered to be 0.5 or above but communalities between 0.25 and 0.4 are regarded as the acceptable cut-off values, especially when an item is needed to ensure the content validity of the scale. Hence, there was no need to consider the elimination of any item at this stage (Field, 2009; Eaton *et al.*, 2019).

The result of the Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 (n = 140) = 4328.486, p < .001$), which means that the correlation matrix has the significant correlations among some of its variables. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value of sampling adequacy was .836, which suggests a great level of the correlations between the scale's items, that is, the sample size is adequate for factor analysis. Field (2009) explains that 'a value close to 1 indicates that patterns of correlations are relatively compact and so factor analysis should yield distinct and reliable factors' (Field, 2009, p. 647).

Using the pilot study's data, the principal factor axis analysis was conducted on thirty nine items with orthogonal rotation (Varimax) to explore the dimensional structure of the scale with the software SPSS 29. Principal axis factoring is an exploratory factor analysis method designed to identify latent factors that underlie a set of variables and explain the variance in data. This approach is commonly used when more emphasis is put on studying the relationships between variables than on data reduction (Mabel and Olayemi, 2020).

Rotation is a process in factor analysis which makes the interpretation of the underlying factor structure more simple and reliable by transforming factors in a way which increases already large factor loadings and decreases small factor loadings. The academic literature suggests that different oblique and orthogonal rotation methods basically produce similar factor loadings. For example, Fabrigar *et al.* (1999) stressed that 'a successful oblique rotation will provide estimates of the correlations among factors that are close to zero and produce a solution that is quite similar to that produced by a successful orthogonal rotation' (Fabrigar *et al.*, 1999, p. 281).

Oblique rotation allows factors to be correlated whereas in orthogonal rotation factors are held independent. Oblique rotation is the recommended method when there is the theoretical foundation to expect that factors are not completely separated and can have some shared variance. Orthogonal rotation is the preferred method when the goal of the analysis is replicability as the results are more parsimonious (Gabriel, 2019). Field (2009) advises the use of Varimax among orthogonal rotations because it aims to maximise the spread of loadings within each factor, which helps to achieve a simpler and more interpretable structure in which variables load high on one factor and low on other factors. As Field (2009) stated, Varimax is 'a good general approach that simplifies the interpretation of factors' (Field, 2009, p. 644).

A common guideline to determine the number of factors is to check eigenvalues for each component in data. Following the Kaiser's criterion of 1, the number of factors is determined by the number of eigenvalues greater than one. An initial analysis was performed to obtain eigenvalues for each component in data. Eight components had eigenvalues over the Kaiser's criterion of 1 and in combination explained 66% of the variance in data. This procedure is regarded as acceptable only when the number of variables in the analysis is less than thirty and all communalities after extraction exceed 0.7 or for the sample size greater than 250 with the average communality equal to or greater than 0.6 (Field, 2009). The scree plot technique is commonly used as a complementary procedure to select the number of factors. The number of factors can be seen where there is the flatness on a curve. The line fattened at about the point of seven, indicating that there were six main factors. The six main factors accounted for 61% of the variation in data (Fein *et al.*, 2022).

In factor analysis, the factor loading of an observable variable quantifies the level to which the variable is related to the underlying latent factor (Field, 2009). Following Hair *et al.* (2019), the accepted threshold value of standardised factor loadings should be 0.50. Hence, the minimum factor loading criterion was set to 0.50 (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

The Table 3.9 shows the constructs and items in the questionnaire and the items' codes. The results of the exploratory factor analysis are presented in the Table 3.10. Based on this initial exploratory factor analysis, thirty six items on the scale were retained because they had a factor loading greater than 0.5. Three items (i.e., ATTI3, ATTI4 and ATTI5) failed to load on any factor significantly. The exploratory factor analysis was run again

without including these items. The determinant of the correlation matrix for the remaining set of data was 2.22E-014, which is 0.000222, and it is greater than the necessary value of 0.00001. The result of the Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant (χ^2 (n = 140) = 3966.327, $p < .001$) and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value of sampling adequacy was .837, which suggests that there is substantial correlation in data for factor analysis (Field, 2009).

The Table 3.11 summarises the internal consistency reliabilities for the constructs in the questionnaire based on using the pilot study's data. As shown in the Table 3.11, the construct sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude retained a high level of internal consistency after deleting the three items, that is, the value of Cronbach alpha for the construct was 0.868. The validity of the scale was increased, that is, the six main factors accounted for 63% of the variation in data (Field, 2009).

Table 3.9: Constructs, Items and Codes in the Questionnaire

Construct	Items	Code	References
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention	I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	PURIN1	Hung <i>et al.</i> (2011)
	I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	PURIN2	
	I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	PURIN3	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude	Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	ATTI1	Lee, Zailani and Rahman (2020)
	Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	ATTI2	
	Sustainable luxury fashion brands are unique and special	ATTI3 *	
	Sustainable luxury fashion brands are of quality	ATTI4 *	
	I trust sustainable luxury fashion brands	ATTI5 *	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	AWAR1	Olšanová <i>et al.</i> (2022)
	When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	AWAR2	
	When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	AWAR3	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation	Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	LEEX1	Ng (2022); Podnar and Golob (2007)
	Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	LEEX2	
	Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	LEEX3	
	Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	LEEX4	

	Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	SOEX1	
	Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	SOEX2	
	Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	SOEX3	
	Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	ENEX1	
	Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	ENEX2	
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable	INATT1	Vlachos, Panagopou and Rapp (2013)
	Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help	INATT2	
	Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	INATT3	
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	PECON1	Kapferer and Michaut (2014)
	Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	PECON2	
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value	I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand	EMPV1	Kim, Jung and Lee (2021)
	Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	EMPV2	
	The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands	EMPV3	
	Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure	EMPV4	
	Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval	SOPV1	
	Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people	SOPV2	
	Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	SOPV3	
	Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	EPPV1	
	Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	EPPV2	
	Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	EPPV3	
	Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources	ENPV1	
	Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials	ENPV2	
	Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly	ENPV3	
	Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	ENPV4	

Note: * Deleted based on the exploratory factor analysis

Table 3.10: Results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis

Item/Code	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6
PURIN1	0.821					
PURIN2	0.806					
PURIN3	0.803					
ATTI1	0.770					
ATTI2	0.688					
AWAR1	0.560					
AWAR2	0.599					
AWAR3	0.616					
LEEX1			0.653			
LEEX2			0.631			
LEEX3			0.656			
LEEX4			0.531			
SOEX1			0.712			
SOEX2			0.739			
SOEX3			0.808			
ENEX1			0.737			
ENEX2			0.812			
INATT1					0.805	
INATT2					0.591	
INATT3					0.715	
PECON1						-0.789
PECON2						-0.660
EMPV1		0.595				
EMPV2		0.640				
EMPV3		0.553				
EMPV4		0.713				
SOPV1		0.748				
SOPV2		0.778				
SOPV3		0.581				
EPPV1		0.550				
EPPV2		0.578				
EPPV3		0.581				
ENPV1				0.661		
ENPV2				0.832		
ENPV3				0.841		
ENPV4				0.730		

Table 3.11: Reliability of the Measure Instruments (Pilot Study with the Second Calculation for the Construct Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brand Attitude)

Variable	Number of items	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention	3	0.931
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude *	2	0.868 **
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	3	0.786
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation	9	0.901
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	3	0.836
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	2	0.731
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value	14	0.935

Notes: * Construct for which the three items were deleted based on the exploratory factor analysis; ** Cronbach's alpha coefficient calculated after the deletion of the items

3.7.2.2.1. Common Method Variance

The reliability and validity of research findings can be threatened by the influence of common method variance and common method bias. Common method variance is the variance that is likely to be caused by the common method employed to measure constructs. Common method bias occurs when common method variance has an effect on the relationship between variables, which leads to alternative conclusions about the relationships manifested in systematic error. One way to control common method bias was to follow the procedure regarding the design of the questionnaire. As a strong body of the academic literature on questionnaire development suggests, common method bias is likely to be reduced through the careful construction of questions or statements in the questionnaire (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003). The statements for this research were created through adapting the established scales from the prior academic studies to fit the context of sustainable luxury fashion brands (Churchill, 1979). The statements are specific, simple and easily understandable. The pre-test of the questionnaire indicated no item ambiguity or complexity. In the information sheet of the questionnaire, I provided the definitions of

sustainable luxury fashion brands and circular luxury fashion brands straightforwardly, that is, using plain language (Choi and Pak, 2005; Rattray and Jones, 2007). Participants in this study were informed that their answers were anonymous and kept confidential and only their sincere answers could help the researcher to achieve the purpose of the study (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003; Robson and McCartan, 2016).

Another way to control for common method bias is statistical control. Harman's single factor test is one of the most widely used methods for controlling common method bias. The method is especially useful when the same measurement instrument is utilised for collecting data for both dependent and independent variables (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2003; Malhotra, Kim and Patil, 2006; Kock, Berbekova and Assaf, 2021).

Harman's single factor test is used to assess common method bias by loading all statements in the questionnaire into exploratory factor analysis and examining unrotated factor solution. If the total variance extracted by one factor exceeds 50%, common method bias is present in a study. However, there is no problem with common method bias in this study because the total variance extracted by a single factor was 30% and it is less than the recommended threshold of 50% (Field, 2009). The SPSS outputs for the preliminary analyses presented above are in Appendix 1.

3.7.3. Main Study Data Collection

Collecting data for the main study was performed from the 23rd May until the 21st June 2024. Recruiting participants for the main survey was done using the voluntary response sampling and convenience sampling methods. The social media platform Facebook was used for recruiting participants, that is, the survey questionnaire was advertised in survey advertising groups, groups related to fashion, sustainability and sustainable fashion as well as in general advertising and student groups based in the UK. The survey was also published on the platforms for paid surveys Amazon Mechanical Turk and Prolific by which 240 responses were collected from respondents in the UK. 453 responses without missing data were collected in total, which indicates that 213 responses were collected from Facebook users. The response rate of 40-60% is considered adequate for web-based surveys in marketing and social science studies (Ilieva, Baron and Healey, 2002).

3.7.3.1. Convenience and Voluntary Response Sampling

In comparison to probability sampling, non-probability sampling is a more cost- and time-effective technique that allows selecting easily accessible participants from the target population with small efforts. Convenience sampling is, however, a potential source of producing selection bias and weakening validity because it is not guaranteed that a sample truly represents the entire population. Selection bias in this study would exist if the sample was not representative of the target population, that is, if respondents in the sample differed systematically from the target population in their characteristics and views, attitudes and behaviours regarding sustainable luxury fashion brands (Jager, Putnick and Bornstein, 2017).

Participants who responded through voluntary response sampling probably had stronger opinions and beliefs about sustainability in luxury fashion than those who chose not to fill in the survey questionnaire. In other words, it is not certain that participants' views on sustainability in luxury fashion obtained through voluntary response sampling are representative of all potential luxury fashion consumers in Facebook groups in which the survey questionnaire was posted (Murairwa, 2015). Nevertheless, a study based on non-probability sampling can generate high internal validity. It happens when the study reflects methodological soundness, that is, the methods and procedures used to collect and analyse data allow the researcher to answer the research questions. The non-probability sampling method was an appropriate sampling method to choose because the purpose of this study is to test the hypotheses and find the relationships between the variables (Andrade, 2021).

3.7.3.2. Implications of an Alternative Sampling Method

In random sampling, each sampling unit has the same probability to be included in a sample and the chance to be selected as the representative group of the entire population is equal for each sample. The fact that some participants are not more likely to be selected into the sample than others allows the researcher to make the assumption of obtaining more generalisable and unbiased findings. However, the randomisation of sample selection is a time-consuming and expensive technique and its operationalisation requires a complex procedure to ensure that each sampling unit within the population has the same chance to be selected into the sample. The disadvantages of random sampling are

probably the reason why non-random sampling has become the most commonly used sampling method in academic and market research (Jager, Putnick and Bornstein, 2017). Because of the time constraints to carry out this research, my inference was that the use of the convenience and voluntary response sampling techniques was the appropriate choice for recruiting participants.

3.7.3.3. Online Survey

Using online surveys in research allows recruiting participants with common characteristics, even geographically dispersed, which would be difficult or not possible to perform using other survey tools. In the traditional face-to-face, telephone or postal research setting, the recruitment process takes more effort and time and it is a costly less effective way of obtaining data. Accordingly, the important advantages of online survey research are associated with increased response rates and the ease of data collection at a very small fraction of the usual cost of conducting the survey and in a short period of time (Wright, 2005).

However, online surveys have a few disadvantages. Although it may be difficult or impossible to find the groups of potential participants outside the online environment, the profiles of people in online communities are obscure. There is no much information on participants' characteristics apart from their essential demographic determinants, which can be questionable in respect of accuracy. When the researcher targets potential participants in virtual communities through advertising an invitation for taking part in the survey, it may take a long time before the admin approves it or the admin can even decline it (Wright, 2005).

Electronic surveys are likely to achieve comparable response rates as traditional surveys (Converse *et al.*, 2008; Shih and Fan, 2008). A lower response rate in online surveys may occur because, for example, potential participants are not willing to click on the survey link because of the suspicion that it could be a spam message. Potential participants may be unwilling to take part in the survey because of saturation caused by filling other surveys delivered in their inboxes or advertised in groups on social media platforms. This indicates that potential participants are likely to take part in online survey research only if they are really interested in or they have strong attitudes towards the phenomenon under study. A higher response rate in telephone surveys in comparison to online and mail surveys may

be due to the self-administered nature of web-based and postal surveys and difficulties concerning ignoring an offer for the survey in comparison to when an invitation for the survey is received electronically or by surface mailing. Nevertheless, online surveys have become the standard in gathering data in market and academic research. It is the most cost-effective tool for data collection in a time-saving manner which can accomplish great response rates in any instances when participants can use the Internet (Wright, 2005; Manfreda *et al.*, 2008; Robson and McCartan, 2016).

3.8. Quality of Quantitative Data

Reliability and validity are considered the key indicators of the quality of data obtained in quantitative research (Roe and Just, 2009; Andrade, 2018). Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007) stress that three basic types of reliability are 'stability, equivalence and internal consistency' (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007, p. 146). Kerlinger (1973) explained that the first approach to defining reliability is concerned with the consistency of findings based on employing the same or comparable measuring instrument, focusing on predictability, stability and repeatability. The second approach to defining reliability is associated with the matter of how accurately the instrument's measures reflect the property measured, emphasising stability and accuracy. The third approach to defining reliability relates to the accuracy of the instrument and concentrates on reducing measurement error (Kerlinger, 1973). Hair *et al.* (2019) elucidate that reliability is different from validity because 'it relates not to what should be measured, but instead to how it is measured' (Hair *et al.*, 2019, p. 3).

Reliability is not a separate aim yet it is a prerequisite for validity. As stressed by Lincoln and Guba (1985), 'an unreliable measure cannot be valid' (Lincoln and Guba, 1985, p. 292). Internal validity is associated with 'truth in the study' while external validity is concerned with 'truth in real life' (Patino and Ferreira, 2018, p. 183). Generalisability demonstrates the extent to which the findings of a study can be applied to other contexts (House, 1980; Kukull and Ganguli, 2012) while construct or measurement validity refers to 'the extent to which a set of measured items actually reflects the theoretical latent construct the items are designed to measure' (Hair *et al.*, 2019, p. 787).

The reliability of findings is subject to random error while the internal validity of findings may be threatened by different factors that fall under the influence of both systematic and random error (Andrade, 2018). Measurement error and sample design error form

systematic or non-sampling error which is associated with 'all sources of error except those introduced by the random sampling process' (McDaniel and Gates, 2012, p. 153). In order to ensure the reliability and validity of findings obtained in this quantitative research, a few steps were taken following the aim of minimising errors.

3.8.1. Sampling Error

Sample size refers to 'the actual number of subjects chosen as a sample to represent the population characteristics' (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016, p. 396). The reduction of sampling error in this research was assured by increasing the sample size. In the context of sustainable luxury, the sample size in quantitative studies commonly ranged between 100 and 250 participants (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012, n = 199; Janssen, Vanhamme and Leblanc, 2017, n = 124; Amatulli *et al.*, 2018, n1 = 119, n2 = 121, n3 = 221; Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019, n1 = 121, n2 = 106). In the the context of sustainable luxury fashion, the sample size in quantitative studies ranged between 100 and 200 participants (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013, n = 131; Janssen *et al.*, 2014, n = 120; Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021, n1 = 128, n2 = 88, n3 = 189).

In this study, the sample size of 453 respondents was accomplished, which suggests efforts in reducing the presence of sampling error. As already explained in this paper, Roscoe's (1975) guideline suggests that the adequate sample size for most research is larger than 30 and lower than 500 observations (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Following Hair *et al.* (2019), the minimum sample size should be ten times or more greater than the number of items or the number of estimated model coefficients (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

A sample size greater than 500 may lead to the occurrence of type II errors, which happens when the researcher fails to reject the null hypothesis that is actually false. In other words, the weak relationships between variables are likely to reach significance levels, which leads to the conclusion that the significant relationships or effects found in a sample truly exist in the entire population but they are actually false (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). A small sample would increase the margin of error and not be sufficient to demonstrate the desired and acceptable level of uncertainty. The presence of sampling error can be reduced through probability sampling but even randomised samples are likely to have a certain amount of sampling error. The postulate of reliability theory is that research findings are always susceptible to random error due to chance variation. Chance

variation refers to 'the difference between the sample value and the true value of the population mean' (McDaniel and Gates, 2012, p. 153).

Sampling error is measured by the standard error of the mean, which is an inferential statistic that estimates how accurately data from a sample represents the entire population, that is, how different the mean of the population is likely to be from the mean of the sample (Field, 2009). The Figure 3.1 represents the distribution of sample means and indicates the importance of precision and confidence in quantitative research. Precision and confidence in research can be accomplished by following the relevant sampling procedures and design so that the findings from the sample are close to the findings that could be obtained based on studying the whole population of interest. A p-value less than 0.05 is typically considered statistically significant, which indicates that researchers can confidently claim that there is less than 5% chance that the findings of research may not be true. The confidence level or the 95% confidence interval, as the Figure 3.1 shows, means the probability of 95% that the population mean value is between -1.96 and +1.96 standard deviations (Bryman, 2012; Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

Figure 3.1: Distribution of Sample Means

Source: Adapted from Bryman (2012, p. 196)

3.8.2. Coverage Error

Web-based surveys have the problem of developing the sampling frame from which a random sample would be chosen and the problem that some members of the population of interest may not be included in the sampling frame (Couper, 2000). For reaching participants not possible to access online, it is beneficial to use a postal, telephone or face-to-face survey as the complementary survey mode for data collection within the available time and costs for conducting research in order to reduce coverage error (Kaplowitz, Hadlock and Levine, 2004; Converse *et al.*, 2008). Research has shown that older adults are likely to use social media applications and websites less often than younger adults or they may choose not to use the Internet, which causes the low representation of older cohorts in the sample and generates biased data (Sharifian *et al.*, 2021). In this regard, Couper (2000) concluded that 'coverage error represents the biggest threat to the representativeness of sample surveys conducted via the Internet' (Couper, 2000, p. 467).

3.8.3. Non-response Error

Non-response bias is regarded as a more serious problem than coverage error when the target population are the actual users of the Internet. Non-response bias would exist in this research if participants and non-participants differed systematically in their views, attitudes and behaviours concerning sustainable luxury fashion brands, which was not possible to determine during administering the survey questionnaire (Couper, 2000).

Some scholars suggest that the risk of activating non-response bias in survey data can be reduced through achieving higher response rates. As Sedgwick (2014) stated, 'non-response bias can be minimised by ensuring that the response rate for a survey is as high as possible' (Sedgwick, 2014, p. 1). However, low response rates achieved in surveys do not definitely mean that there is a high level of non-response bias in data. Krosnick (1999) wrote that 'new findings challenge a long-standing prejudice against studies with low response rates' (Krosnick, 1999, p. 537).

Studies have shown that a lack of perceived anonymity and confidentiality in research is likely to decrease response rates in surveys (Hoonakker and Carayon, 2009). Participants in the survey for this study were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. An explicit pledge of confidentiality was given to participants through letting them know that their

answers were going to be kept strictly confidential in a password protected electronic file and used only for academic purposes. The information sheet of the questionnaire also indicated that the survey was not going to collect any identifying information on participants. The survey administration software's option for collecting participants' emails was cancelled. The disclosure of participants' emails is likely to be perceived as a breach of anonymity and reduce response rates in surveys (Wright, 2005; Van Selm and Jankowski, 2006).

Participants in this study were informed that the completion of the survey questionnaire takes approximately five to ten minutes. It has been suggested that survey response rates are likely to be increased if participants perceive the questionnaire as short and easy to complete (Dillman, 2007). Participants did not receive any monetary incentives for filling in the questionnaire, except participants who were recruited using the platforms Amazon Mechanical Turk and Prolific. They were paid £0.40-0.60 for filling in the questionnaire. Using monetary rewarding is not always effective in conducting online surveys because some participants may be stimulated to fill in the questionnaire multiple times in order to win the prize (Brennan, Rae and Parackal, 1999).

Building trust between the researcher and participants has been emphasised as a more effective strategy for increasing response rates, which is based on the perceived benefits of filling in the questionnaire that surpass the costs of participating in the survey. In this regard, the purpose of the study was explained to participants in the information sheet of the questionnaire. The importance of gaining their sincere answers for a better understanding of sustainable luxury fashion consumption was emphasised. I specified the origin of this project, that is, I informed participants that the project was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland. I provided my university email address to participants to contact me if they had any questions or if they needed any further information about this research. I expressed my gratitude to participants for taking part in the research in advance, which is a beneficial step and useful symbolic gesture in increasing response rates (Dillman, 2007).

3.8.4. Measurement Instrument Error

The occurrence of random sampling error is harmless regarding its influence on inferences drawn from data analysis while the accuracy of findings can be severely threatened by the presence of questionnaire or measurement error that refers to 'a variation between the information being sought (true value) and the information actually obtained by the measurement process' (McDaniel and Gates, 2012, p. 155). Following Choi and Pak (2005), measurement instrument bias may result from mistakes associated with 'the way individual questions are designed, the way the questionnaire as a whole is designed, and how the questionnaire is administered or completed' (Choi and Pak, 2005, p. 1).

I ensured that the design of the questionnaire reflects the defined research problem by measuring consumers' willingness to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands and the relevant factors that are likely to affect sustainable luxury fashion consumption. In other words, the right balance between the information necessary for solving the research problem and the information obtained by data collection was provided, which eliminated the presence of surrogate information error (McDaniel and Gates, 2012).

The necessary procedure regarding the order and wording of the statements in the questionnaire was followed. The dependent variable was placed before the independent variables because it helps to obtain more accurate and sincere responses on consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands (Rattray and Jones, 2007). A thorough review of theory was conducted to develop the constructs and statements, that is, the constructs adapted the items from the established scales to fit the context of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The constructs were created as the multi-item scales, which improves their content validity (Hardesty and Bearden, 2004; Kimberlin and Winterstein, 2008). The statements were created as easily understandable for participants, that is, the statements are not too short, ambiguous, comprised or two or more questions and with uncommon words, which contributes to the reduction of response bias (Choi and Pak, 2005). Seven-point Likert scale was used for measuring the scales' items. The usage of a higher number of response categories increases the validity and reliability of data (Lozano, García-Cueto and Muñiz, 2008).

Measurement error may arise as a result of providing insincere, inaccurate or false responses. The information sheet of the questionnaire informed participants that their answers formed anonymised data that did not allow any participant to be identified or identifiable and that there were no socially acceptable or unacceptable answers to the questions. That is to say, participants were informed that only their opinions were relevant for the realisation of the purpose of this research, which helped annulling the prevalence of social desirability and response bias. The interaction between the researcher and participants was just to invite participants to take part in the survey, suggesting the non-existence of interviewer or researcher error (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

These steps within the procedure for designing and administering the questionnaire ensured that the occurrence of measurement error was minimised. The questionnaire of this study was developed as a reliable research instrument. Cronbach's alpha coefficient for each of the questionnaire's scales was calculated using the main study's data with the software SPSS 29. As the Table 3.12 shows, the constructs in the questionnaire had a high level of internal consistency, that is, Cronbach's alpha for the constructs was higher than 0.70, ranging from 0.779 to 0.934. Cronbach's alpha value of 0.70 is regarded as the threshold of the desired reliability of a scale (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The SPSS outputs for measuring the reliability of the scales using the main study's data are in Appendix 2.

Table 3.12: Reliability of the Measure Instruments (Main Study)

Variable	Number of items	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention	3	0.914
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude	2	0.842
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	3	0.786
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation	9	0.894
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	3	0.861
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	2	0.779
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value	14	0.934

3.8.4.1. Processing Error

Upon completing the collection of data, data were systematically checked. Data were systematically coded in a spreadsheet in the software Excel and transferred into a data tabular matrix in the softwares SPSS 29 and SmartPLS 4 for the further analysis. Because online surveys do not require data entry by the researcher, the likelihood of processing error was eliminated (Bryman, 2012; McDaniel and Gates, 2012).

3.9. Research Ethics and Integrity in the Study

The ethical principle of responsibility towards all parties in the research process is integrated in this study. The recruitment of participants and data collection started after this research project was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland. The information sheet of the questionnaire provided this information to participants. Ethical concerns were followed when involving participants and gathering, analysing and reporting data. The purpose of this study was explained to participants and participants were informed that their participation in the survey is voluntary with their right to refuse to take part in the survey and withdraw at any time during completing the questionnaire. Informed consent is a key ethical principle in research that requires from the researcher to provide the adequate and accurate information about the purpose of a study so that participants can make an informed decision about accepting or refusing to take part in the study (Robson and McCartan, 2016). Informed consent was obtained from participants by asking them to indicate if they were at least 18 years old, if they read and understood the information sheet and consent form and if they agreed to participate in this study.

Data for this study were collected following the principle of anonymity, that is, without gaining any identifying information on participants. Participants were informed that data collection was completely anonymous and reporting data does not include any information related to their identity. Participants were informed that data were treated as strictly confidential and locked in a password protected file. The questionnaire was electronically distributed with an invitation for participating in the survey without causing inconvenience or putting pressure on participants. In persuading participants to take part in research, undue inducements are not considered appropriate because it could cause that participants feel obligated or pressured to take part in research. In other words, the ethical

principle of voluntary consent cannot be threatened by creating the perception that participation in research is mandatory through manipulating participants (Robson and McCartan, 2016).

As required by the University of the West of Scotland, the Harvard referencing guide was used for referencing. All sources used for writing this dissertation are cited within the text and in the reference list. The Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) of the electronic sources are provided in the reference list. Acknowledging the sources used by the researcher in writing academic papers ensures the quality of the paper, demonstrates the researcher's academic capability, moral correctness and fairness and eliminates the indication of plagiarism (Santini, 2018).

The ethical principle of transparency is followed in all aspects of the research process, starting with defining the research questions and objectives of the study and conducting an in-depth literature review to develop the understanding of the topic and research problem. The justification for using the selected research design, methodology and procedures for answering the research questions of the study has been elaborated. The project will be finalised with the valid interpretations of the results, drawing the conclusions and managerial recommendations from the findings and presenting the theoretical contributions and limitations of the study. Research integrity is commonly associated with 'honesty, transparency, and objectivity' and 'sticking to the research question and avoiding bias in data interpretation' (Shaw and Satakar, 2018, p. 79).

3.10. Summary

This chapter discussed the philosophical assumptions underlying this research, the justification for using the deductive and explanatory research strategy for answering the research questions and the implications of the alternative research philosophies, approaches and methods in order to demonstrate the relevancy of using the selected research strategy and method. Positivism is an indispensable research philosophy to underpin quantitative research aimed to explain and predict consumer behaviour (Hunt, 1991). Positivism is in accordance with deductive research, which seeks to explore prior existing theories regarding the phenomenon of interest in order to test if those theories are valid in certain settings (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Explanatory research is an apposite strategy for this study because the research problem and the variables are clearly

identified but the explanatory and causal relationships between the variables have not been explored to an adequate degree in previous research (Creswell, 1994).

The structure of the questionnaire has been presented. The rationale for employing the survey technique, convenience and voluntary response sampling methods and online survey mode for collecting data as well as the implications of the alternative sampling method and data collection sources have been discussed. The measures undertaken to minimise sampling, non-response and measurement instrument error have been elucidated. The concepts of reliability and validity have been described and the initial reliability and validity tests have been performed. The ethical concerns taken into account in conducting this research have been explained.

Chapter 4: Results of the Quantitative Study

4.1. Overview

In this chapter, the results of the survey research are reported and interpreted. The main study's data were analysed using the softwares SPSS 29 and SmartPLS 4. Using the software SPSS 29, the frequencies procedure was run to summarise the categorical data. The characteristics of the sample are presented and described. The descriptives procedure was performed to present and describe the continuous data. The mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis values are reported and interpreted. The partial least squares based structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) method was used to perform the confirmatory factor analysis and test the hypotheses H1-H6 with the software SmartPLS 4. Using the software SPSS 29, the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was performed to test the hypothesis H7.

4.2. Characteristics of the Sample

This study is focused on luxury consumers in a fashion context. Participants were recruited as self-reported luxury fashion consumers to avoid recruiting individuals who just had opinions and beliefs about sustainability in luxury fashion but who were not actual luxury fashion consumers. Recent research has shown that luxury consumers are defined in terms of having a desire to purchase luxury products. Earning higher incomes and owning

opulence do not necessarily define luxury consumers in the era of the democratisation of luxury and the deluge of accessible luxury (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

Among 453 self-declared luxury fashion consumers in this study, 60.5% were females, 38.2% were males and 1.3% were gender-neutral. The greater representation of women in the sample may reflect the findings of previous research that women tend to be more interested in luxury and fashion (Janssen *et al.*, 2014) as well as in socially responsible behaviours than men (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013). However, this representation may also implicate that females were just more active on the Internet during the period of data collection. The sample was chosen using the voluntary response and convenience sampling technique that is a method for recruiting participants conveniently available, in this case around the Internet service (Jager, Putnick and Bornstein, 2017).

The most represented age group in the sample was the group 25-34 (37.1%), followed by the group 18-24 (27.4%), the group 35-44 (20.8%) and the group 45-54 (10.6%). The groups 55-64 and 65 and above were not significantly represented in the sample (2.9% and 1.3% respectively). The greater representation of younger demographic cohorts in the sample may be because of the age-related differences in using social media and online platforms. Research has shown that younger adults are more likely to use social media and they use social media more often than older adults (Sharifian *et al.*, 2021). Luxury consumers are increasingly defined by youth culture (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). It has been predicted that consumers within Generation Z and Generation Y will be soon accountable for almost 50% of total luxury consumption, although these cohorts represent a minor part of the true luxury market (Monteros, 2022). On the other hand, some studies indicate that middle-aged and older adults are more interested in socially responsible purchases than younger adults (Roberts, 1996a; Roberts, 1996b; Morrison and Beer, 2017).

I chose the lower limit of £3000 for consumers' personal monthly income, considering that it should not be too low in respect of the targeted audience. The figures from the statistics portal Statista show that the average UK annual salary for full-time workers was £34,963 in 2023 (Clark, 2024). The personal monthly income is less than £3000 for 72.0% of respondents, between £3000 and £5000 for 22.3% of respondents and above £5000 for 5.7% of respondents. This is consistent with the suggestion that the modern luxury consumer is defined by a desire to purchase luxury brands rather than a very high income

and buying power, that is, luxury is not restricted to people with high social rank. Because the mean income is not set too high, the findings of this study have relevance for the majority of the population of interest and not only for a very small rich population (Dubois and Laurent, 1994; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

23.2% of respondents reported to be regular luxury fashion consumers (purchasing luxury fashion brands always or often) and 76.8% of respondents reported to be occasional luxury fashion consumers (purchasing luxury fashion brands sometimes or rarely). The case data grid revealed that consumers with a higher income do not have to purchase luxury fashion brands on a regular basis and vice versa. Individuals with a lower income may be regular luxury fashion consumers. Luxury is a subjective concept and the perception of luxury is very individual and personalised (Brun and Castelli, 2013; Kasztalska, 2017).

Most participants in the sample were highly educated individuals holding a bachelor's degree or postgraduate qualification, followed by participants with high school or below (49.2%, 27.6% and 12.1% respectively). The least represented education group were participants with a diploma or vocational certificate (11.0%). Taking into account that the convenience and voluntary response sampling techniques were used for recruiting participants online, this representation may indicate that the dominant education groups in the sample were more available online during conducting this research (Jager, Putnick and Bornstein, 2017). However, the higher representation of more educated participants in the sample may also indicate that they were more interested in the topic. Research has shown that highly educated consumers are more likely to be socially minded and interested in socially responsible behaviour than less educated consumers (Roberts, 1996a).

79.2% of participants in this research were UK residents while 20.8% of participants did not reside in the UK. The inclusion of the question about participants' residency is important in terms of the applicability of the research findings, that is, identifying the population to which the findings can mostly be applicable. The idea behind is that consumers in a particular country, area, etc. have similar needs and desires, cultural and subcultural norms and customs, beliefs, prejudices, awareness, etc. and they are different from consumers who reside in other localities, which is reflected in differences in consumer behaviour (Lynn, Zinkhan and Harris, 1993; Yang and Jolly, 2009; Peña-García *et al.*, 2020). Others are of the opinion that luxury research is becoming less dependent on

a single culture or nationality due to the industry's global growth and expansion (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). The characteristics of the sample are presented in the Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Demographic Profile for Respondents in the Survey Study (n = 453)

Variable	Group	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Age	25-34	168	37.1	37.1
	18-24	124	27.4	64.5
	35-44	94	20.8	85.2
	45-54	48	10.6	95.8
	55-64	13	2.9	98.7
	65 and above	6	1.3	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	
Gender	Female	274	60.5	60.5
	Male	173	38.2	98.7
	Prefer not to answer	6	1.3	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	
Income	Below £3000	326	72.0	72.0
	£3000 - £5000	101	22.3	94.3
	Above £5000	26	5.7	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	
Education	Bachelor's degree	223	49.5	49.5
	Postgraduate level	125	27.6	76.8
	High school or below	55	12.1	89.0
	Diploma or vocational certificate	50	11.0	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	
Consumption level	Occasional consumer	348	76.8	76.8
	Regular consumer	105	23.2	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	
Residency	UK resident	359	79.2	79.2
	Not UK resident	94	20.8	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	

The operationalisation of consumers' perceptions of luxury fashion was done on the basis of the first criterion in defining luxury fashion. Although luxury is a complex phenomenon defined by different features, I chose the approach that emphasises the most important attribute rather than a bunch of the attributes in examining consumers' perceptions of luxury fashion. This is based on the notion of prototype and its role in an individual's perceptions of phenomena and situations. According to Kleiber's (1990) semantic theory of prototypes, the first attribute plays a central role in consumers' perception of luxury fashion, that is, the first perceived attribute of luxury fashion is more original and typical than the second perceived attribute (Jaén, 2006).

The Table 4.2 shows that most respondents chose exceptional quality, high price and exclusivity as the first attribute in defining luxury fashion (45.9%, 16.3% and 15.7% respectively). 9.3% of respondents connected luxury fashion foremost with creativity, hedonism (beauty) was the first attribute in defining luxury fashion for 7.1% of respondents while rarity was the first attribute in defining luxury fashion for 5.7% of respondents. In Kapferer and Michaut's (2015) study, in comparison, consumers perceived exceptional quality, rarity and exclusivity as the most important attribute in defining luxury, followed by high price, hedonism and creativity (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

Table 4.2: Consumers' Most Important Luxury Fashion Attributes

First attribute	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Exceptional quality	208	45.9	45.9
High price	74	16.3	62.3
Exclusivity	71	15.7	77.9
Creativity	42	9.3	87.2
Hedonism (Beauty)	32	7.1	94.3
Rarity	26	5.7	100.0
Total	453	100.0	

Kapferer and Michaut (2015) propose that the perceived contradiction between luxury and sustainability depends on how consumers define luxury. Consumers who define luxury as exceptional quality are likely to perceive a lower contradiction between luxury and sustainability than consumers who define luxury as high price, rarity, exclusivity, hedonism and creativity (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

The cross-tabulation analysis was performed to examine if consumers' first attribute in defining luxury fashion was associated with consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability (Robson and McCartan, 2016). The results of the analysis are summarised in the Table 4.3. In the sample for this study, a lower contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability was perceived by participants who defined luxury fashion as exceptional quality than by participants who defined luxury fashion as exclusivity, creativity, high price, hedonism (beauty) and rarity.

The Chi-square test was used to check if the results of the cross tabulation analysis are statistically significant. As the Table 4.4 shows, the value of the Chi-square statistic is 30.737. The footnote for this statistic refers to the expected cell count assumption, that is, if expected cell counts are greater than 5. Because 12 cells (28.6%) have the expected value of less than 5, this assumption was not met. Because the test statistic is based on a 6x7 cross-tabulation table, the degrees of freedom (df) for the test statistic is 30 ($df = (R-1)*(C-1) = (6-1)*(7-1) = 5*6 = 30$). The corresponding p-value of the test statistic is $p = 0.428$, which is very much larger than the conventional 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). The null hypothesis is not rejected, that is, there is no enough evidence to suggest the association between consumers' first attribute in defining luxury fashion and consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability. In other words, the observed relationship is accidental, that is, it happened as a result of some chance factor (Robson and McCartan, 2016). The SPSS outcomes for the frequencies procedure for the categorical data, the cross-tabulation analysis and the Chi-square test are in Appendix 3.

Table 4.3: Relationship between Consumers' Perceived Contradiction between Luxury Fashion and Sustainability and First Attribute in Defining Luxury Fashion

Group	N Low	N High	N Neutral	N Total	% Low	% High
Exceptional quality	79	88	41	208	47.3	52.7
High price	21	37	16	74	36.2	63.8
Exclusivity	28	34	9	71	45.2	54.8
Creativity	14	20	8	42	41.2	58.8
Hedonism (Beauty)	8	14	10	32	36.4	63.6
Rarity	6	14	6	26	30.0	70.0
Total	156	207	90	453		

Table 4.4: Chi-square Test

	Value	Df	Asymptotic significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-square	33.737	30	0.428
Likelihood ratio	33.646	30	0.295
N of valid cases	453		

12 cells (28.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.95.

4.3. Mean and Standard Deviation for the Item Measures

The Table 4.5 shows the mean and standard deviation for each statement in the questionnaire. The mean is the measure of central tendency while the standard deviation measures the variability or spread of the values of individual responses around the mean (Lee, In and Lee, 2015). The standard deviation represents 'the square root of the variance' (Livingston, 2004, p. 121). A standard deviation higher than 1 indicates that the values of responses on average were less closer to the mean, that is, more spread around the mean (Lee, In and Lee, 2015).

As parametric tests in statistical data analysis, the mean and standard deviation assume that data in the larger population from which a sample was taken follows a normal distribution. Normal distribution, also referred to as the Gaussian distribution, relates to a probability theoretical distribution in which data are scattered symmetrically around the mean, indicating that data around the mean occur more frequently than data far from the mean (Siegel, 1957; Robson and McCartan, 2016).

Table 4.5: Mean and Standard Deviation Values for the Item Measures

Statement wording	Mean	Standard deviation
I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	4.91	1.680
I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	4.97	1.735
I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	4.80	1.831
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	4.74	1.694
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	4.98	1.631
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	4.25	1.712
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	5.37	1.530
When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	5.22	1.572
Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	5.65	1.274
Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	5.72	1.326
Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	5.85	1.305
Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	6.19	1.226
Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	5.40	1.404
Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	4.92	1.608
Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	5.21	1.437
Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	5.57	1.380

Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	5.97	1.264
Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable	3.90	1.753
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help	4.31	1.663
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	3.99	1.648
Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	4.17	1.689
Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	3.56	1.836
I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand	4.97	1.489
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	4.98	1.517
The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands	4.17	1.753
Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure	4.76	1.492
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval	4.87	1.494
Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people	5.03	1.355
Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	4.08	1.789
Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	4.72	1.471
Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	5.04	1.334
Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	4.51	1.415
Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources	5.12	1.472
Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials	5.20	1.425
Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly	5.06	1.492
Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	5.30	1.395

The Table 4.6 summarises the mean values for the variables measuring consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability. The means for the measures are high, that is, on average between 5 and 6 on the seven-point Likert-type scale. This indicates that consumers expect that luxury fashion brands have the responsibilities beyond the economic responsibility, which reflects Carroll's (1991) theory of corporate social responsibility (Carroll, 1991). The findings support the suggestion of Kapferer and Michaut (2015) that consumers have high expectations for luxury brands' dedication to sustainability (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

Table 4.6: Mean Values for the Items Measuring Consumers' Expectations for Luxury Fashion Brands' Sustainability

Dimension	Items	Mean
Legal and ethical sustainability	Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	6.19
	Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	5.85
	Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	5.72
	Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	5.65
Environmental sustainability	Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	5.97
	Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	5.57
Social sustainability	Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	5.40
	Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	5.21
	Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	4.92

4.4. Normality Test

The common statistics used to test if data follows a normal distribution are skewness and kurtosis. The absolute values of skewness and kurtosis are considered the reliable measures for assessing data normality for large samples ($n > 300$). Skewness measures the asymmetry of a data distribution relative to a normal distribution, that is, the extent to which the distribution of responses for a variable is symmetrical around its mean values. Kurtosis measures the flatness and peakedness of the distribution, that is, the extent to which the distribution of responses is peaked with most responses in the centre of the distribution (Mishra *et al.*, 2019).

The perfect normal distribution of data implies that the values of skewness and kurtosis are zero. Hair *et al.* (2019) explain that the values of skewness lower than -1 reflect a skewed distribution to the right while the values higher than +1 indicate that the distribution is skewed to the left. The values of kurtosis lower than -1 denote a flatter distribution while the values greater than +1 indicate that the distribution is too peaked (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

The skewness and kurtosis values for each survey statement and variable were calculated to evaluate the normality of data. For the majority of the statements, as seen in the Table 4.7, the skewness values are within the range of -1 and +1, except for the following variables: AWAR2 (skewness -1.080), LEEX2 (skewness -1.103), LEEX3 (skewness -1.346), LEEX4 (skewness -1.738), ENEX1 (skewness -1.131) and ENEX2 (skewness -1.410). Likewise, the kurtosis values are within the range of -1 and +1 for the majority of the cases, except for the following variables: LEEX3 (kurtosis 1.729), LEEX4 (kurtosis 2.940), ENEX1 (kurtosis 1.165), ENEX2 (kurtosis 1.903), INATT1 (kurtosis -1.085) and PECON2 (kurtosis -1.132). The Table 4.8 shows the skewness and kurtosis values for the latent variables in the model along with the standard errors of skewness and kurtosis. The skewness and kurtosis values of the independent variable sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation is not within the range of -1 and +1 (skewness -1.183 and kurtosis 2.411). The skewness and kurtosis values of the dependent variable and the remaining five independent variables fit within the range of -1 and +1 (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Kline (2011) explains that a more flexible approach to testing the normality assumption accepts that data are normally distributed when the skewness and kurtosis values are individually within ± 3 and ± 10 , that is, the values of skewness should not be greater than 3 and the values of kurtosis should be lower than 10 (Kline, 2011). However, following Hair *et al.* (2019), data are normally distributed when the skewness and kurtosis values are individually within the range of -1 and +1 (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The SPSS outcomes for the calculated values of the mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis are in Appendix 4.

Table 4.7: Skewness and Kurtosis Values of the Item Measures

Item/Statement wording	Code	Skewness	Kurtosis
I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	PURIN1	-0.696	-0.334
I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	PURIN2	-0.865	-0.154
I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	PURIN3	-0.712	-0.525
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	ATTI1	-0.573	-0.525
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	ATTI2	-0.820	0.041
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	AWAR1	-0.325	-0.800
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	AWAR2	-1.080	0.719
When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	AWAR3	-0.972	0.370
Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	LEEX1	-0.966	0.798
Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	LEEX2	-1.103	0.927
Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	LEEX3	-1.346	1.729
Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	LEEX4	-1.738	2.940
Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	SOEX1	-0.682	0.008
Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	SOEX2	-0.550	-0.387
Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	SOEX3	-0.866	0.513
Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	ENEX1	-1.131	1.165
Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	ENEX2	-1.410	1.903
Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable	INATT1	-0.031	-1.085
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help	INATT2	-0.332	-0.788

Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	INATT3	-0.045	-0.899
Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	PECON1	-0.180	-0.833
Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	PECON2	0.156	-1.132
I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand	EMPV1	-0.654	0.154
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	EMPV2	-0.757	0.210
The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands	EMPV3	-0.231	-0.846
Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure	EMPV4	-0.662	0.117
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval	SOPV1	-0.631	-0.122
Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people	SOPV2	-0.692	0.507
Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	SOPV3	-0.192	-0.888
Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	EPPV1	-0.374	-0.433
Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	EPPV2	-0.560	-0.005
Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	EPPV3	-0.232	-0.271
Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources	ENPV1	-0.722	0.031
Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials	ENPV2	-0.685	0.019
Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly	ENPV3	-0.736	0.149
Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	ENPV4	-0.787	0.256

Table 4.8: Skewness and Kurtosis Values of the Research Variables

Variable	Skewness	Std. error of skewness	Kurtosis	Std. error of kurtosis
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention	-0.751	0.115	-0.223	0.229
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude	-0.758	0.115	-0.029	0.229
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	-0.942	0.115	0.671	0.229
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation	-1.183	0.115	2.411	0.229
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	-0.143	0.115	-0.836	0.229
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	0.020	0.115	-0.903	0.229
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value	-0.645	0.115	0.639	0.229

4.5. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) Statistical Assumptions

Structural equation modeling incorporates factor analysis and path analysis to test and analyse the complex relationships between variables. The measurement model and structural model were assessed and the hypotheses H1-H6 were tested using the PLS-SEM method, which is an approach to structural equation modeling based on an analysis of total variance. It is an alternative method to covariance-based structural equation modeling (CB-SEM), which is a method for structural equation modeling based on covariance. The CB-SEM method assumes that data originates from a common factor model, which implies that the covariances between observed variables are caused by the factor. The PLS-SEM method is a composite-based approach that creates the factor as a linear combination of its observed variables (Hair and Alamer, 2022).

It has been argued that composite-based methods do not account for measurement error while in common factor models observed variable residuals are equal to measurement errors. The counterargument is that observed variable residuals can be equal to measurement errors only when common factors are identical with conceptual variables.

That is to say, factor indeterminacy induces 'a validity gap between a common factor and the conceptual variable that it represents' (Hair Jr and Sarstedt, 2019, p. 622).

Composites and common factors are used to represent conceptual variables that are formed as approximations to data sets. Accordingly, composites and common factors are proxies for conceptual variables and they both account for measurement error. Such argumentation upholds the use of a composite approach to structural equation modeling (Rigdon, 2016) and its usage has been intensified in social science, marketing and strategic management research (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2017).

The use of the PLS-SEM method is suitable when the research objective is theory development as well as explanation and prediction in terms of providing recommendations for managerial practice and supporting external validity. Although the PLS-SEM method is basically a prediction-oriented perspective, it is considered adequate for theory confirmation. The CB-SEM method is the preferred method when the research objective is the testing and confirmation of an existing model with focus on explanation (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2017; Hair Jr and Sarstedt, 2019; Dash and Paul, 2021).

This study is designed to provide managerial recommendations regarding the growth of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Although the aim of this study is to test if prior theories are valid in a sustainable luxury fashion context, the proposed conceptual model is a new model which examines how to stimulate consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Therefore, the PLS-SEM method is an appropriate approach for this study because its goal is to identify and predict the key drivers of sustainable luxury fashion consumption (Hair and Alamer, 2022).

Different rules-of-thumb have been proposed concerning the sample size requirements for structural equation modeling, for example, minimum 100 or 200 observations, minimum 5 to 10 observations per estimated parameter and minimum 10 observations per variable. However, such recommendations can be problematic because other factors that affect statistical power need to be considered, such as data normality, model complexity and effect size (Wolf *et al.*, 2013).

The PLS-SEM method is developed as a non-parametric procedure which does not require data to follow a normal distribution. When using the CB-SEM method for the evaluation of the path model, non-normal distributed data can underestimate standard errors and inflate goodness-of-fit measures. The PLS-SEM method transforms non-normal data in accordance with the central limit theorem, which suggests that the sampling distribution of the mean is always normally distributed if the number of observations in research is large enough. Nevertheless, researchers need to be aware that highly skewed data can inflate standard errors obtain through bootstrapping (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2014).

The necessary sample size for structural equation modeling increases with the model complexity. The advantage of the PLS-SEM method is that it can be used with a smaller sample in relation to the complexity of the model. The CB-SEM method requires larger sample sizes to avoid improper solutions, such as lower efficiency and accuracy in parameter estimation, Heywood cases and convergence problems (Kyriazos, 2018; Hair and Alamer, 2022). With a lower dependency on sample sizes, applying the PLS-SEM method is more suitable for models with many latent variables and indicators and models with higher-order constructs (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2014). Because the PLS-SEM method has stronger statistical power, it is more likely that effects identified as significant are indeed significant in the population (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021).

Structural equation modeling goes beyond multiple regression because it allows the evaluation of the measurement model in which observed variables are linked with latent variables. It enables the evaluation of the structural model that specifies the causal relationships between exogenous and endogenous variables (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2017).

In structural equation modeling and multiple regression analysis, the relationships between variables are assessed based on the size and significance of beta coefficients. In both research methods, the model prediction is commonly measured by the coefficient of determination. In comparison to regression analysis, structural equation modeling is a more powerful technique for assessing the relationships between variables in complex models due to its stronger reliability of measurement, which results in the higher observed power of predictive variables (Nusair and Hua, 2010).

4.6. Measurement Model Assessment

Following the guideline from the academic literature, the measurement model was evaluated for its reliability and validity (composite reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity). In the first step, the PLS-SEM method enabled the validation of the factor structure of the questionnaire's scale identified in the exploratory factor analysis (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Confirmatory factor analysis differs from exploratory factor analysis because it specifies the number of factors and variables based on theory-strong literature base, estimates if variables load on a specific factor or factors and verifies how well variables represent the number of factors (Fein *et al.*, 2022). Confirmatory factor analysis allows the researcher to test whether the theoretical model of factors and variables fits actual data (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The demonstration of construct validity requires evidence that both convergent and discriminant validity are established in research findings. Exploratory factor analysis addresses only convergent validity while confirmatory factor analysis provides convergent and discriminant validity information (Cole, 1987).

4.6.1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity refers to the extent to which a measure converges or highly correlates with other measures of the same construct. The assessment of the convergent validity of the scales was done following the guideline by Hair *et al.* (2019). The standardised factor loadings of observable variables or indicators should be above 0.5 or ideally greater than 0.7 at a statistical significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). The factor loading of an observable variable reflects the degree of the correlation between the variable and the underlying latent factor. As shown in the Table 4.9, the confirmatory factor analysis revealed that all standardised indicator loadings were greater than 0.70. It suggests that the indicators are strongly related to their related construct, that is, each factor sufficiently captures the variance of its related indicators (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

It is common in social science research that items display weaker factor loadings (< 0.708), especially when scales are newly developed. However, researchers need to carefully consider the elimination of items with a factor loading less than 0.7. Hair Jr *et al.* (2021) explain that the elimination of indicators with the loading within the range of 0.40

and 0.708 should be done only if it is necessary to increase the validity and reliability of the construct. As seen in the Table 4.9, the factor loading of the indicator LEEX4 is approaching 0.708 (0.706). However, the values of average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (CR) for the related construct are above the recommended threshold (AVE = 0.712; CR = 0.907). Equally important, this indicator is essential for assuring the content validity of the construct such that the indicators represent all aspects of the construct. On the other hand, indicators with factor loadings below 0.40 should be always eliminated from the model (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021).

Average variance extracted values for constructs should be at least or greater than 0.5 while composite reliability values should be at least or greater than 0.7 at a statistical significance level of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). As seen in the Table 4.9, the average variance extracted values for the constructs are higher than 0.5, ranging from 0.538 to 0.864. Average variance extracted is a measure of the average amount of the variance for a given construct. Average variance extracted values greater than 0.5 suggest that items explain more variance than error in the construct. For example, consumers' purchase intention of sustainable luxury fashion brands was measured by three items and the average variance extracted value for these items is 0.854, which means that 85.4% of the variation in the variable was explained by these three items (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

The Table 4.9 shows that the composite reliability values for the constructs are higher than 0.70 and lower than 0.95, ranging from 0.875 to 0.948. The high composite reliability values of the constructs indicate that the indicators consistently measured their associated constructs. Reliability values above 0.95 are not recommended because they may indicate a high level of item redundancy and the possibility that response patterns are undesirable, such as straight-lining, which is a threat to data quality. Because Cronbach's alpha tends to underestimate true reliability when the assumption of tau-equivalence is not satisfied, it is advised to measure composite reliability to more accurately assess the internal consistency of a set of scale items (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The assumption of tau-equivalence indicates that latent factors have equal loadings in all items on the scale, that is, each item on the scale measures the same factor (Cronbach, 1951).

In research practice, the assumption of tau-equivalence is commonly violated because multiple factors underlie items on the scale. The congeneric model is more realistic because it accepts the existence of different factor loadings for items on the scale (Hair *et*

al., 2019). Likewise, Cronbach's alpha is affected by the number of items, that is, a small number of items can violate the assumption of tau-equivalence (Tavakol and Dennick, 2011).

The Table 4.10 provides the values of Cronbach's alpha, consistent reliability and composite reliability coefficients for the constructs. The values of composite reliability for the constructs refer to the rho_c values. It has been argued that the values of composite reliability may be too liberal. Based on Dijkstra (2010), the exact or consistent reliability coefficient rho_a has been proposed as an alternative to Cronbach's alpha as a conservative measure and composite reliability as a liberal measure (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021).

Table 4.9: Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Constructs and items	Standardised loadings
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention (CA = 0.914, CR = 0.946, AVE = 0.854)	
1. I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows (PURIN1)	0.894
2. I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows (PURIN2)	0.939
3. I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows (PURIN3)	0.938
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude (CA = 0.843, CR = 0.927, AVE = 0.864)	
1. Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values (ATTI1)	0.929
2. Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good (ATTI2)	0.930
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness (CA = 0.790, CR = 0.877, AVE = 0.704)	
1. When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities (AWAR1)	0.807
2. When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities (AWAR2)	0.846
3. When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles (AWAR 3)	0.862
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation (CA = 0.897, CR = 0.912, AVE = 0.538)	
Legal and ethical expectation (CR = 0.907, AVE = 0.712)	
1. Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit (LEEX1)	0.887
2. Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient (LEEX2)	0.854

3. Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times (LEEX3)	0.912
4. Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances (LEEX4)	0.706
Social expectation (CR = 0.898, AVE = 0.745)	
5. Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups (SOEX1)	0.826
6. Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems (SOEX2)	0.871
7. Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare (SOEX3)	0.891
Environmental expectation (CR = 0.881, AVE = 0.788)	
8. Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection (ENEX1)	0.939
9. Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions (ENEX2)	0.833
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution (CA = 0.861, CR = 0.915, AVE = 0.783)	
1. Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable (INATT1)	0.892
2. Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help (INATT2)	0.854
3. Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community (INATT3)	0.908
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability (CA = 0.781, CR = 0.897, AVE = 0.814)	
1. Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory (PECON1)	0.860
2. Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world (PECON 2)	0.943
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value (CA = 0.936, CR = 0.943, AVE = 0.545)	
Emotional perceived value (CR = 0.930, AVE = 0.770)	
1. I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand (EMPV1)	0.901
2. Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good (EMPV2)	0.923
3. The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands (EMPV3)	0.790
4. Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure (EMPV4)	0.890
Social perceived value (CR = 0.887, AVE = 0.724)	
5. Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval (SOPV1)	0.882
6. Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people (SOPV2)	0.869
7. Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends (SOPV3)	0.799
Epistemic perceived value (CR = 0.875, AVE = 0.701)	
8. Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness (EPPV1)	0.854

9. Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands (EPPV2)	0.817
10. Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features (EPPV3)	0.840
Environmental perceived value (CR = 0.933, AVE = 0.778)	
11. Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources (ENPV1)	0.886
12. Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials (ENPV2)	0.907
13. Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly (ENPV3)	0.898
14. Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands (ENPV4)	0.837

Notes: CA = Cronbach's alpha; CR = Composite reliability; AVE = Average variance extracted; The p-values are two-tailed: significant at $p < 0.001$

Table 4.10: Reliability of the Constructs (Cronbach alpha, rho_a and rho_c)

Construct	Cronbach alpha	rho_a	rho_c
Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention	0.914	0.919	0.946
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude	0.843	0.843	0.927
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	0.790	0.793	0.877
Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation	0.897	0.912	0.912
Sustainable luxury fashion brand legal and ethical expectation	0.870	0.948	0.907
Sustainable luxury fashion brand social expectation	0.829	0.834	0.898
Sustainable luxury fashion brand environmental expectation	0.744	0.862*	0.881
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	0.861	0.864	0.915
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	0.781	0.881*	0.897
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value	0.936	0.946	0.943
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived emotional value	0.900	0.913	0.930
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value	0.808	0.813	0.887
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value	0.788	0.794	0.875
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived environmental value	0.905	0.919	0.933

Notes: rho_a = Consistent reliability; rho_c = Composite reliability; The p-values are two-tailed: significant at $p < 0.001$; *non-significant ($p > 0.05$)

4.6.2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity refers to the extent to which the measures of different constructs are distinct or minimally correlated with each other (Carmines and Zeller, 1979; Heale and Twycross, 2015; Hair *et al.*, 2019). The cross-loading, Fornell-Larcker and Heterotrait-monotrait criterion values were examined to assess the discriminant validity of the scales. The visual assessment of the cross-loading values indicated that each indicator correlated strongly on its related construct than on other constructs. Following Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt (2015), assessing discriminant validity based on cross-loadings is a statistically weak test which does not have strong theoretical and empirical justifications (Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2015).

Based on the assessment of the Fornell-Larcker criterion values, as seen in the Table 4.11, discriminant validity is established because each construct shares more variance with its indicators than with any other construct's indicators. The square roots of the AVE values are shown on the diagonals while the non-diagonals refer to the latent variables correlations. The square root of the AVE for each construct is greater than the correlation between the construct and other constructs in the model. The Fornell-Larcker criterion compares 'the AVE (shared variance within) of the constructs to the squared correlation between the constructs (shared variance between)' (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2017, p. 111).

Table 4.11: Fornell-Larcker Criterion for the Constructs

Construct	ATTI	AWAR	EMPV	ENEX	ENPV	EPPV	INATT	LEEX	PECO	PUIN	SOEX	SOPV
ATTI	0.930											
AWAR	0.584	0.839										
EMPV	0.671	0.557	0.878									
ENEX	0.367	0.500	0.382	0.888								
ENPV	0.500	0.452	0.600	0.366	0.882							
EPPV	0.506	0.497	0.670	0.294	0.619	0.837						
INATT	0.443	0.427	0.434	0.131	0.308	0.492	0.885					
LEEX	0.302	0.455	0.305	0.659	0.394	0.270	0.000	0.844				
PECO	-0.117	0.013	-0.046	-0.068	-0.066	0.068	0.113	-0.062	0.902			
PUIN	0.769	0.512	0.556	0.252	0.376	0.419	0.413	0.180	-0.089	0.924		

SOEX	0.334	0.525	0.333	0.633	0.307	0.353	0.275	0.517	0.141	0.289	0.863	
SOPV	0.467	0.475	0.671	0.273	0.561	0.727	0.418	0.227	0.096	0.381	0.321	0.851

Notes: ATTI = Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude; AWAR = Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness; EMPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived emotional value; ENEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand environmental expectation; ENPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived environmental value; EPPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value; INATT = Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution; LEEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand legal and ethical expectation; PECO = Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability; PUIN = Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention; SOEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand social expectation; SOPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value; The square roots of the AVE are shown on the diagonals; The correlations of the constructs are shown off the diagonals

Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt (2015) argue that the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) of correlations is a more robust procedure to evaluate discriminant validity than the assessment of the cross loading and Fornell-Larcker criterion values. Because variance-based structural equation modeling is dependent on composites as substitutes for latent variables, factor loadings tend to be overestimated while cross-loadings are largely unchanged. Additionally, the Fornell-Larcker criterion does not rely on statistical inference procedure. The Heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations compares ‘the average of the heterotrait-heteromethod correlations (i.e., the correlations of indicators across constructs measuring different phenomena)’ with ‘the average of the monotrait-heteromethod correlations (i.e., the correlations of indicators within the same construct)’ (Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2015, p. 121).

As the Table 4.12 shows, the constructs have the acceptable values of the Heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations as they are below 0.9, which is the threshold value for constructs that are conceptually similar. For constructs that are conceptually more distinguishable, the threshold value of 0.85 can be applied as a more rigorous approach. The evaluation of the Heterotrait-monotrait criterion values showed that two constructs (SOPV <-> EPPV) shared the value within the required threshold of 0.9 (0.908). These are the first-order constructs that are constructed as the second-order construct (PEVAL) along with the first-order constructs (EMPV and ENPV). The Heterotrait-monotrait criterion values for these contracts are summarised in the Table 4.13. A complementary evaluation of discriminant validity was conducted to find out if the 95% bootstrapped confidence

intervals around the correlation coefficients include the value of 1. The bootstrapping procedure showed that none of the confidence intervals across all pairs of the correlations did not contain the value of 1. The Table 4.14 shows that the 95% bootstrapped confidence interval value for the estimated correlation between the constructs (SOPV <-> EPPV) did not reach 1. Although the relationship seemed invalid, the acceptable confidence interval was produced, which indicates that the constructs are distinct, that is, discriminant validity is supported between them (Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2015; Cheung *et al.*, 2024).

Table 4.12: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations for the First-order Constructs

Construct	ATTI	AWAR	EMPV	ENEX	ENPV	EPPV	INATT	LEEX	PECO	PUIN	SOEX	SOPV
ATTI												
AWAR	0.713											
EMPV	0.767	0.658										
ENEX	0.453	0.659	0.452									
ENPV	0.572	0.540	0.662	0.461								
EPPV	0.622	0.627	0.800	0.380	0.743							
INATT	0.520	0.502	0.500	0.169	0.343	0.589						
LEEX	0.340	0.544	0.314	0.859	0.444	0.310	0.088					
PECO	0.129	0.106	0.119	0.096	0.093	0.111	0.146	0.128				
PUIN	0.875	0.595	0.607	0.291	0.409	0.489	0.464	0.183	0.101			
SOEX	0.400	0.655	0.387	0.789	0.356	0.435	0.323	0.592	0.185	0.331		
SOPV	0.565	0.590	0.792	0.338	0.652	0.908	0.505	0.260	0.133	0.442	0.390	

Notes: ATTI = Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude; AWAR = Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness; EMPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived emotional value; ENEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand environmental expectation; ENPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived environmental value; EPPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value; INATT = Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution; LEEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand legal and ethical expectation; PECO = Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability; PUIN = Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention; SOEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand social expectation; SOPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value

Table 4.13: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (Second-order Construct PEVAL)

Construct	EMPV	SOPV	EPPV	ENPV
EMPV				
SOPV	0.792			
EPPV	0.800	0.908		
ENPV	0.662	0.652	0.743	

Notes: EMPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived emotional value; SOPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value; EPPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value; ENPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived environmental value

Table 4.14: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations Confidence Intervals for the Structural Relationship SOPV <-> EPPV

Structural relationship	Original sample	Sample mean	2.5%	97.5%
SOPV - EPPV	0.908	0.908	0.844	0.962

Notes: SOPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value; EPPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value

The Table 4.15 summarises the Heterotrait-monotrait criterion values for the first-order constructs (ENEX, LEEX and SOEX) that are constructed as the second-order construct (EXP). The Table 4.16 shows the Heterotrait-monotrait criterion values for the first-order constructs (PURIN, ATTI, AWAR, INATT and PECON) and the second-order constructs (EXP and PEVAL), that is, for the main variables in the model. The constructs have the acceptable values of the Heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations below 0.9, which demonstrates that there is no lack of discriminant validity between the constructs (Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2015).

The evaluation of the Heterotrait-monotrait criterion values identified that two constructs (PURIN <-> ATTI) shared the value which is close to 0.9 (0.875). The Table 4.17 shows that the 95% bootstrapped confidence interval value for the estimated correlation between the constructs (PURIN <-> ATTI) did not reach 1. It indicates that the constructs are distinct, that is, discriminant validity is demonstrated between them (Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt, 2015; Cheung *et al.*, 2024).

The bias-corrected bootstrap confidence interval method was used because research has suggested that for complex structural models standard bootstrap confidence intervals are inferior to bias-corrected bootstrap confidence intervals regarding accuracy, statistical power and type I errors. The bias-corrected bootstrap confidence interval method adjusts for bias because of skewed distribution (Streukens and Leroi-Werelds, 2016).

Table 4.15: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (Second-order Construct EXP)

Construct	LEEX	SOEX	ENEX
LEEX			
SOEX	0.592		
ENEX	0.859	0.789	

Notes: LEEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand legal and ethical expectation; SOEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand social expectation; ENEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand environmental expectation

Table 4.16: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations for the First-order and Second-order Constructs

Construct	ATTI	AWAR	EXP	INATT	PECON	PEVAL	PURIN
ATTI							
AWAR	0.713						
EXP	0.431	0.679					
INATT	0.520	0.502	0.206				
PECON	0.129	0.106	0.157	0.146			
PEVAL	0.716	0.676	0.469	0.528	0.126		
PURIN	0.875	0.595	0.287	0.464	0.101	0.550	

Notes: ATTI = Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude; AWAR = Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness; EXP = Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation; INATT = Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution; PECON = Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability; PEVAL = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value; PURIN = Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention

Table 4.17: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations Confidence Intervals for the Structural Relationship PURIN <-> ATTI

Structural relationship	Original sample	Sample mean	2.5%	97.5%
PURIN <-> ATTI	0.875	0.874	0.825	0.916

Notes: PURIN = Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention; ATTI = Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude

The assessment of the Fornell-Larcker criterion values has been commonly used to evaluate discriminant validity in studies using covariance-based structural equation modeling. The Heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) is the recommended measure of discriminant validity for data analysed using variance-based structural equation modeling. Researchers commonly report the values of both measures (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2017). The Heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations provides a more statistically powerful evaluation of discriminant validity but it assumes tau-equivalence measurement models. The assumption that each item measures the same latent construct is not realistic in common empirical research (Roemer, Schuberth and Henseler, 2021).

4.7. Model Fit Analysis

The PLS-SEM method offers the approximate measures for model fit indices: SRMR (i.e., the standardised root mean squared residual), NFI (i.e., the normed fit index) and Chi-square. The exact measures provided are: d_ULS (i.e., the squared Euclidean distance) and d_G (i.e., the geodesic distance). In comparison to the CB-SEM method, the PLS-SEM method provides less options for assessing model fit (Dash and Paul, 2021).

The overall model fit was evaluated to examine how the proposed theoretical model is supported with data from the sample. As the Table 4.18 shows, the value of the standardised root mean squared residual (SRMR) was used to evaluate the goodness of fit of the model. The value of the standardised root mean squared residual can be evaluated on the basis of the cut-off value instead of statistical inference. The value of the measure up to 0.08 is generally regarded as the acceptable and fair value for a good model fit. The value of the standardised root mean squared residual measure was 0.063, which indicates the good model fit (Hu and Bentler, 1999). The PLS-SEM method provides the exact measures: d_ULS (i.e., the squared Euclidean distance) and d_G (i.e., the geodesic distance). As the Table 4.18 shows, the values of both measures are non-

significant, which indicates the good model fit. These measures collectively support the validity of the model, suggesting strong support for the further analysis (Dash and Paul, 2021).

Table 4.18: The Goodness of Model Fit (Estimated Model)

Measure	Value	95%	99%
SRMR	0.063	0.035	0.046
d_ULS	2.654	0.814	1.408
d_G	0.913	0.684	0.844

The PLS-SEM method provides the values of the Chi-square and the normed fit index (NFI). Using these statistics may not be a reliable procedure for assessing model fit. Because they are statistical significance tests, using their values for model fit indices can reject the model even when the model is correct, that is, when other measures point towards an acceptable model fit. The tests lack statistical power when small samples are used in relation to the complexity of the model (Hu and Bentler, 1999).

The Chi-Square evaluates ‘the magnitude of discrepancy between the sample and fitted covariances matrices’ (Hu and Bentler, 1999, p. 2). The normed fit index (NFI) is an incremental fit measure that evaluates the model based on comparing the Chi-square value of the model and the null model in which all measured variables are specified as uncorrelated (Bentler and Bonett, 1980). The index cannot be considered alone in assessing model fit yet it needs to be complemented with alternative measures such as the non-normed fit index (NNFI). However, the non-normed fit index has not been implemented in the software SmartPLS 4 (Dash and Paul, 2021).

4.8. Structural Model Assessment

After the measurement model has been validated, the next stage in evaluating the results of PLS-SEM is the assessment of the structural model. Following the guideline by Hair *et al.* (2019) and Hair Jr *et al.* (2021), the model was examined for collinearity issues, followed by the assessment of the significance and size of the coefficients of determination and path coefficients (Hair *et al.*, 2019; Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021).

4.8.1. Collinearity Issues of the Structural Model

Multicollinearity problem occurs when two or more independent variables are highly correlated in the model. The collinearity issues of the constructs were assessed based on validating the variance inflation factor (VIF). The results of the variance inflation factor test indicate that the amount of collinearity in the model is low. The Table 4.19 shows that the variance inflation factor values range between 1.134 and 2.944, which is less than 5 (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Table 4.19: Collinearity Statistics of Structural Model (Inner VIF)

Construct	VIF
Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude	2.205
Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness	2.179
Sustainable luxury fashion brand legal and ethical expectation	2.089
Sustainable luxury fashion brand social expectation	2.056
Sustainable luxury fashion brand environmental expectation	2.380
Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution	1.632
Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability	1.134
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived emotional value	2.944
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value	2.541
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value	2.842
Circular luxury fashion brand perceived environmental value	2.010

4.8.2. Assessment of the Structural Model Relationships

Bootstrapping allows the validation of the structural model based on producing a large number of randomly drawn subsamples from the sample's data. The p-values and confidence intervals are calculated based on combining the model estimates from the subsamples, which provides the means of estimated coefficients across these subsamples and their probability of differing from zero. The evaluation of statistical significance does not rely on statistical assumptions about the population. The percentile bootstrapping procedure was conducted with the recommended 5000 bootstrap subsamples and a two tailed test was used (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

4.8.2.1. R-squared of the Model

The coefficient of determination or the parameter R-squared indicates the explanatory or in-sample predictive power of the model based on determining the proportion of the variance in the endogenous (dependent) variable that can be explained by the exogenous (independent) variable. The parameter R-squared is commonly used to predict the accuracy of the model. The R-squared for the structural model of this study is 0.613 ($p < 0.001$; $t = 17.918$). The p-value and t-value indicate if the parameter is significant or not. Using a two-tailed t-test with a significance level of 5%, the coefficient is significant if the t-value is greater than 1.96 (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

The R-squared value for the model indicates that the combined effect of the exogenous variables explains 61.3% of the variance of the endogenous variable while the rest is influenced by other variables not included in this study. The model has a moderate explanatory power. The general guideline in social science research is that the model is weak, moderate and strong with the values of the coefficient of 0.25, 0.50 and 0.75 respectively (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021).

The acceptability of the value of the coefficient can be interpreted in relation to the research context, R-squared values from related studies and similarly complex models (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021). In the context of sustainable consumption, for example, a study by Minh and Quynh (2024) suggests that consumer environmental concerns, attitudes, subjective norms, personal norms and perceived behavioural control are positively influenced by pandemics. Except for subjective norms, the variables had positive effects on consumer sustainable consumption intention and sustainable consumption behaviour. The model of the study proposed the moderating effect of perceived consumer effectiveness on the relationship between consumer sustainable consumption intention and sustainable consumption behaviour. The study generated the R-squared value of 0.65 (Minh and Quynh, 2024). In the context of sustainable fashion consumption, for example, a study by Hasbullah *et al.* (2022) examined how consumer motivation measured as the higher-order construct and consumer ability and opportunity measured as the first-order constructs affect consumer sustainable apparel purchase intention. The study identified the positive relationship between the variables and proposed the moderating effect of consumer fashion consciousness on consumer purchase intention of sustainable apparel. The study generated the R-squared value of 0.536 (Hasbullah *et al.*, 2022).

The value of the R-squared is likely to be increased with adding more explanatory variables into the model. In marketing and consumer behaviour research, a too high value of the R-squared may indicate that the model overfits data because concepts related to human perceptions, attitudes and intentions are not inherently predictable. In other words, it is not realistic to assume that a single model can explain all factors that have influence on consumer behaviour at a given point of time (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021).

Sustainable luxury and fashion consumption choices are specific and affected by different factors, such as quality, price, status motives, cultural influences, individual preferences, subjective norms and so forth (Griskevicius, Tybur and Van den Bergh, 2010; Joy *et al.*, 2012; Cervellon and Shamma, 2013; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Accordingly, the value of the R-squared coefficient for the model of this study indicates that the input variables of the model are appropriate and have a good explanatory or in-sample predictive power (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021).

The R-squared adjusted adjusts the value of the R-squared on the basis of the number of independent variables relative to the size of data. However, the adjusted R-squared does not precisely indicate the dependent variable's explained variance due to 'the correction factor introduced to account for data and model size' (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021, p. 119).

The Table 4.20 shows the values of the parameters R-squared and R-squared adjusted for the hypothesised effects along with the p-values and t-values. The p-values for the relationships are significant at 0.001 and 0.05. For the relationship PECON - PURIN, the p-value is non-significant. For the relationship LEEEX - PURIN, the p-value is only significant at $p < 0.10$. However, the 95% bootstrapped confidence interval for the R-squared value did not show the value of 'no effect', indicating support for the significance of this result (Hair and Alamer, 2022). The p-value does not provide information about the precision of results. When an observed result is significant at 0.05, the null hypothesis should not fall within the 95% confidence interval, indicating that the effect exists in the population (Flechner and Tseng, 2011). The Table 4.21 summarises the confidence intervals for the R-squared values of the relationships in the model.

The results indicate that consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands are the strongest predictor of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands (R-squared = 0.593, $p < 0.001$, $t = 16.895$), followed by consumers' perceived

value of circular luxury fashion brands (R-squared = 0.278, $p < 0.001$, $t = 7.062$), consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability (R-squared = 0.262, $p < 0.001$, $t = 6.280$), consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability (R-squared = 0.171, $p < 0.05$, $t = 4.962$) and consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability (R-squared = 0.082, $p < 0.05$, $t = 3.027$).

Consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' social sustainability (R-squared = 0.083, $p < 0.05$, $t = 2.822$) were a stronger determinant of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' environmental sustainability (R-squared = 0.064, $p < 0.05$, $t = 2.432$) and legal and ethical sustainability (R-squared = 0.033, $p < 0.10$, $t = 1.846$). The emotional dimension of consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands was a stronger determinant of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands (R-squared = 0.309, $p < 0.001$, $t = 7.159$) than the epistemic dimension (R-squared = 0.175, $p < 0.001$; $t = 4.668$), the social dimension (R-squared = 0.145, $p < 0.001$; $t = 4.224$) and the environmental dimension (R-squared = 0.140, $p < 0.001$; $t = 4.023$).

Table 4.20: R-squared Values for the Hypothesised Effects

Structural relationship	R-squared value	R-squared adjusted value	P-value	T-value
PECON - PURIN	0.008	0.006	0.389	0.862
AWAR - PURIN	0.262	0.261	0.000***	6.280
EXP - PURIN	0.082	0.080	0.002**	3.027
SOEX-PURIN	0.083	0.081	0.005**	2.822
ENEX-PURIN	0.064	0.061	0.015**	2.432
LEEX-PURIN	0.033	0.031	0.065*	1.846
ATTI - PURIN	0.593	0.592	0.000***	16.895
INATT - PURIN	0.171	0.169	0.000***	4.962
PEVAL - PURIN	0.278	0.276	0.000***	7.069
EMPV-PURIN	0.309	0.307	0.000***	7.159
EPPV-PURIN	0.175	0.174	0.000***	4.668
SOPV-PURIN	0.145	0.143	0.000***	4.224
ENPV-PURIN	0.142	0.140	0.000***	4.023

Notes: PECON = Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability; ATTI = Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude; AWAR = Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness; EXP = Sustainable luxury fashion brand expectation; SOEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand social expectation; ENEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand environmental expectation; LEEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand legal and ethical expectation; INATT = Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution; PEVAL = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived value; EMPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived emotional value; EPPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value; SOPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value; ENPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived environmental value; PURIN = Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention; The p-values are two-tailed: *significant at $p < 0.10$; ** significant at $p < 0.05$; *** significant at $p < 0.001$

Table 4.21: Confidence Intervals of the R-squared Values

Structural relationship	R-squared value	2.5%	97.5%
PECON - PURIN	0.008	0.001	0.024
AWAR - PURIN	0.262	0.182	0.345
EXP - PURIN	0.082	0.034	0.134
SOEX - PURIN	0.083	0.033	0.144
ENEX - PURIN	0.064	0.022	0.119
LEEX - PURIN	0.033	0.008	0.072
ATTI - PURIN	0.593	0.517	0.656
INATT - PURIN	0.171	0.103	0.239
PEVAL - PURIN	0.278	0.199	0.351
EMPV - PURIN	0.309	0.219	0.390
EPPV - PURIN	0.175	0.107	0.251
SOPV - PURIN	0.145	0.082	0.216
ENPV - PURIN	0.142	0.079	0.217

4.8.2.2. Hypothesis Testing (H1-H6)

The path coefficient or the parameter beta (β) indicates the strength and direction of the relationship between variables. The p-value and t-value indicate if the parameter is significant or not. Using a two-tailed t-test with a significance level of 5%, the path coefficient is significant if the t-value is greater than 1.96 (Hair *et al.*, 2019). The path coefficients along with the p-values and t-values are shown in the Table 4.22. The 95% bootstrapped confidence intervals for the path coefficients are shown in the Table 4.23. The results show that all relationships in the model are supported. The results are illustrated in the Figure 4.1 and discussed as follows.

Consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability negatively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands ($\beta = -0.089$; $p < 0.10$; $t = 1.674$). The higher consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability, the lower probability that consumers intend to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. Although the coefficient for the path between these variables is only significant at $p < 0.10$, the fact that the 95% bootstrapped confidence interval for the path coefficient did not include the value of 'no effect' provides support for the significance of this path (Hair and Alamer, 2022). The confidence interval is a measure of the precision of results. The null hypothesis does not fall within the 95% confidence interval when an observed result is significant at 0.05, indicating that the effect exists in the population (Flechner and Tseng, 2011). Therefore, the hypothesis H1 is supported.

Consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability positively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands ($\beta = 0.512$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 12.573$). The higher consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, the higher probability that consumers intend to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. Therefore, the hypothesis H2 is supported.

Consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The higher consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, the higher probability that consumers intend to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. Consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands are positively affected by consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' legal and ethical sustainability ($\beta = 0.181$; $p <$

0.001; $t = 3.880$), social sustainability ($\beta = 0.289$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 5.727$) and environmental sustainability ($\beta = 0.252$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 5.003$). Therefore, the hypothesis H3 is fully supported.

It appears that consumers have the greatest expectations for luxury fashion brands' social and environmental sustainability. The social dimension ($t = 5.727$; $p < 0.001$) and the environmental dimension ($t = 5.003$; $p < 0.001$) were more important for consumers than the legal and ethical dimension of sustainability ($t = 3.880$; $p < 0.001$).

Consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands ($\beta = 0.770$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 33.669$). The higher consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, the higher probability that consumers intend to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. Therefore, the hypothesis H4 is supported.

Consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands ($\beta = 0.413$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 9.898$). The higher consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability, the higher probability that consumers intend to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. Therefore, the hypothesis H5 is supported.

Consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands positively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The higher consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands, the higher probability that consumers intend to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. Consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands are positively affected by consumers' perceived emotional value of circular luxury fashion brands ($\beta = 0.556$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 14.276$), perceived social value ($\beta = 0.381$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 8.473$), perceived epistemic value ($\beta = 0.419$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 9.371$) and perceived environmental value ($\beta = 0.377$; $p < 0.001$; $t = 8.077$). Therefore, the hypothesis H6 is fully supported.

It appears that the perceived emotional value of circular luxury fashion brands is of the greatest importance for consumers. The perceived emotional value of circular luxury fashion brands ($t = 14.276$; $p < 0.001$) was more important for consumers than the

perceived epistemic value ($t = 9.371$; $p < 0.001$), the perceived social value ($t = 8.473$; $p < 0.001$) and the perceived environmental value dimension ($t = 8.077$; $p < 0.001$).

Table 4.22: Path Coefficient Values for the Hypothesised Effects

Hypothesis	Structural relationship	Path coefficient (β) value	P-value	T-value
H1	PECON - PURIN	-0.089	0.094*	1.674
H2	AWAR - PURIN	0.512	0.000**	12.573
H3a	LEEX - PURIN	0.181	0.000**	3.880
H3b	SOEX - PURIN	0.289	0.000**	5.727
H3c	ENEX - PURIN	0.252	0.000**	5.003
H4	ATTI - PURIN	0.770	0.000**	33.669
H5	INATT - PURIN	0.413	0.000**	9.898
H6a	EMPV - PURIN	0.556	0.000**	14.276
H6b	SOPV - PURIN	0.381	0.000**	8.473
H6c	EPPV - PURIN	0.419	0.000**	9.371
H6d	ENPV - PURIN	0.377	0.000**	8.077

Notes: PECON = Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability; AWAR = Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness; LEEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand legal and ethical expectation; SOEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand social expectation; ENEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand environmental expectation; ATTI = Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude; INATT = Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution; EMPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived emotional value; SOPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value; EPPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value; ENPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived environmental value; PURIN = Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention; The p-values are two-tailed: *significant at $p < 0.10$; **significant at $p < 0.001$

Figure 4.1: Hypotheses (H1-H6)

Table 4.23: Confidence Intervals of the Path Coefficient Values

Structural relationship	Path coefficient (β) value	2.5%	97.5%
PECON - PURIN	-0.089	-0.159	0.133
AWAR - PURIN	0.512	0.427	0.588
LEEX - PURIN	0.181	0.092	0.268
SOEX - PURIN	0.289	0.181	0.380
ENEX - PURIN	0.252	0.148	0.344
ATTI - PURIN	0.770	0.719	0.810
INATT - PURIN	0.413	0.321	0.489
EMPV - PURIN	0.556	0.468	0.625
SOPV - PURIN	0.381	0.286	0.465
EPPV - PURIN	0.419	0.328	0.501
ENPV - PURIN	0.377	0.281	0.465

4.8.2.3. Out-of-sample Predictive Power of the Structural Model

The PLSpredict test was conducted to assess the predictive performance of the research model. In the bootstrap procedure in PLS-SEM, each sample is used for the estimation of the model and the prediction of in-sample cases. The PLSpredict algorithm uses separated training and holdout samples to evaluate the model's predictive relevance from the estimation of parameters in PLS path models. Training data are in-sample data used in the trained model for estimating parameters, which can be used for prediction. Holding data are out-of-sample unseen data that are not used in the trained model yet intended for use in making predictions about the outcome variable (Shmueli *et al.*, 2016).

The PLSpredict test provides the value of the Q-squared for the indicators of the endogenous construct. The Table 4.24 shows that the value of the Q-squared for each indicator of the endogenous construct is higher than zero (0.401, 0.538 and 0.564). It offers evidence for the predictive accuracy of the structural model for the construct (Shmueli *et al.*, 2019).

For the evaluation of the predictive relevance of the model, the root mean square error (RMSE) value and the mean absolute error (MAE) value were compared with the naive linear model (LM) benchmark value for each indicator of the endogenous construct. For all three indicators, as seen in the Table 4.24, the RMSE value and the MAE value are lower than the LM benchmark value, which indicates that the model has a high out-of-sample predictive power (Shmueli *et al.*, 2019).

Table 4.24: Out-of-sample Predictive Power of the Model Based on PLSpredict

	Q-squared	PLS-SEM_RMSE	PLS-SEM_MAE	LM_RMSE	LM_MAE
PURIN1	0.401	1.302	0.982	1.348	1.010
PURIN2	0.538	1.182	0.897	1.220	0.921
PURIN3	0.564	1.211	0.903	1.234	0.939

The cross-validated predictive ability test (CVPAT) is an alternative to the PLSpredict test for assessing the predictive relevance of the structural model. The cross-validated predictive ability test was conducted with PLS-SEM to evaluate and substantiate the predictive relevance of the model. As seen in the Table 4.25, the difference of the average

loss is significantly below zero, which means that the average loss of PLS-SEM is significantly lower than the average loss of the benchmarks. This indicates that the model has a high out-of-sample predictive power (Lienggaard *et al.*, 2021).

Table 4.25: Out-of-sample Predictive Power of the Model Based on CVPAT

	Average loss difference	T-value	P-value
PURIN	-1.552	9.352	0.000
Overall	-1.552	9.352	0.000

Note: The p-values are two-tailed: significant at $p < 0.001$

4.8.2.4. Effect Size of the Structural Model

The F-squared effect size test is used to assess how the R-squared value of the endogenous construct is affected by the removal of the selected exogenous construct from the model. The F-squared coefficient indicates the effect size of the structural model. The effect sizes of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 are regarded as small, medium and large. The results in the Table 4.26 show that the effect size of the model is at a moderate to high level (Hair Jr *et al.*, 2021). The PLS-SEM outputs for the performed analyses are in Appendix 5.

Table 4.26: F-squared Effect Size Test

Structural relationship	F-squared value	P-value	T-value
PECON - PURIN	0.008	0.403	0.836
AWAR - PURIN	0.356	0.000**	4.493
LEEX - PURIN	0.034	0.082	1.737
SOEX - PURIN	0.091	0.012*	2.512
ENEX - PURIN	0.068	0.027*	2.210
ATTI - PURIN	1.457	0.000**	6.753
INATT - PURIN	0.206	0.000**	4.031
EMPV - PURIN	0.446	0.000**	4.821
SOPV - PURIN	0.170	0.000**	3.518
EPPV - PURIN	0.213	0.000**	3.741
ENPV - PURIN	0.165	0.001*	3.358

Notes: PECON = Perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability; AWAR = Sustainable luxury fashion brand awareness; LEEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand legal and ethical expectation; SOEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand social expectation; ENEX = Sustainable luxury fashion brand environmental expectation; ATTI = Sustainable luxury fashion brand attitude; INATT = Sustainable luxury fashion brand intrinsic attribution; EMPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived emotional value; SOPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived social value; EPPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived epistemic value; ENPV = Circular luxury fashion brand perceived environmental value; PURIN = Sustainable luxury fashion brand purchase intention; The p-values are two-tailed: *significant at $p < 0.05$; ** significant at $p < 0.001$

4.8.2.5. One-way Analysis of Variance Test (H7)

Using the software SPSS 29, the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was performed to test if three gender consumer groups (males, females and gender-neutral) differ from one another on the dependent variable. The Table 4.27 shows that the means of the dependent variable are higher for females and males in comparison to the gender-neutral group, which indicates that female and male consumers tend to have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than gender-neutral consumers. Because the difference between the means for males and females is very small, it does not appear that females tend to have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than males (Field, 2009).

The Table 4.28 shows that the difference between the gender groups is significant, that is, the variation between the means is not due to chance ($F = 3.157$; $p < 0.05$; with 2 and 450 df). It indicates that data are not consistent with the null hypothesis that the population means for the groups are identical. However, the F-test for the analysis of variance does not show between which gender groups there is a significant difference, that is, which of the differences between the pairs of the means are attributed to the overall difference. The post hoc analysis needs to be performed to examine it (Field, 2009).

Table 4.27: Descriptives for the Means of the Gender Groups

95% Confidence Interval for Mean								
Group	N	Mean	Std. deviation	Std. error	Lower bound	Upper bound	Min	Max
Female	274	14.9234	4.75225	0.28709	14.3582	15.4886	3.00	21.000
Male	173	14.4566	4.93618	0.37529	13.7159	15.1974	3.00	21.000
Neutral	6	10.1667	4.99667	2.03988	4.9230	15.4103	5.00	18.000
Total	453	14.6821	4.84910	0.22783	14.2344	15.1299	3.00	21.000

Table 4.28: One-way Analysis of Variance

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Between groups	147.076	2	73.538	3.157	0.043
Within groups	10481.149	450	23.291		
Total	10628.225	452			

The Table 4.29 reports the Levene's test for the equality of variances. Because the probability level for the Levene's test is non-significant ($p > 0.05$), the homogeneity assumption of the variance is not violated. It indicates that the variances in the dependent variable are not significantly different across gender, that is, the gender groups come from populations with the same variance. When the homogeneity assumption of the variance is met, the post hoc analysis needs to be done using a post hoc test that assumes equal variances (Field, 2009).

Table 4.29: Test of the Homogeneity of Variances

	Levene statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Based on mean	0.226	2	450	0.798
Based on median	0.011	2	450	0.989
Based on median and with adjusted df	0.011	2	434.368	0.989
Based on trimmed mean	0.153	2	450	0.858

A conservative test is strict in declaring statistical significance, which implies that the probability of a type I error is smaller but it may not have sufficient statistical power, that is, the probability of a type II error is higher. A liberal test is less strict in declaring statistical significance, which implies that the probability of a type I error is higher. However, it has stronger statistical power, that is, the probability of a type II error is lower. The type I error means that the null hypothesis is rejected when it is true while the type II error means that the null hypothesis is not rejected when it is actually false (Field, 2009).

In a multiple comparison procedure, it is necessary that the type I error is controlled and statistical power is high. Less conservative tests are designed to control the type I error and maintain statistical power, which makes them more adequate for situations when it is more important to detect the true differences between groups than to control over the type I error. A very common and popular less conservative post hoc test is the Tukey test which assumes that all sample sizes are the same in the null hypothesis. Accordingly, the test becomes quite conservative when there are large differences in sample sizes, controlling over the type I error but lacking statistical power in identifying a true effect when it actually exists. The Tukey-Kramer pairwise test, which is also known as the Tukey honestly significant difference (HSD) test, uses the harmonic mean of sample numbers but it is appropriate to use when there is a large number of groups that have equal sizes (Field, 2009).

The Gabriel's pairwise test is more powerful than the Hochberg's GT2 test with different sample sizes but it may be too liberal when sample sizes are very different, which makes it more adequate when sample sizes are slightly different. The Hochberg's GT2 test can be used when sample sizes are very different but it is less powerful to detect a difference when it truly exists. The least significant difference (LSD) test is the preferred multiple comparison procedure when there is a smaller number of groups and it can be used when sample sizes are unequal. The test is the most liberal test, that is, it is mostly likely to show statistical differences in multiple comparison procedures (Field, 2009).

Post hoc tests with greater statistical power need to be used to detect a statistical difference when it exists. The F-test for the analysis of variance found that at least one gender group significantly differs from other gender groups. The Table 4.30 shows the results of the least significant difference (LSD) test and the Hochberg's test. Focusing on the results of the least significant difference test, the variances of consumers' purchase

intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands based on gender significantly vary. As the Sig. column shows, female consumers were found to have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than gender-neutral consumers ($p = .017$). Male consumers were found to have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than gender-neutral consumers ($p = .033$). It was found that there is no significant difference between males and females in purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands ($p = .320$). Therefore, the hypothesis H7 is not supported. The mean level of purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands for female and male consumers is greater than the mean level of purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands for gender-neutral consumers ($p < 0.05$) (Field, 2009). The SPSS outputs for the analysis are in Appendix 6.

Table 4.30: Multiple Comparison Procedures

Test	Gender	Gender	Mean difference	Std. error	Sig.	Lower bound	Upper bound
LSD	Female	Male	0.46671	0.46866	0.320	-0.4543	1.3877
		Neutral	4.75669*	1.99171	0.017	0.8425	8.6709
	Male	Female	-0.46671	0.46866	0.320	-1.3877	0.4543
		Neutral	4.28998*	2.00413	0.033	0.3514	8.2286
	Neutral	Female	-4.75669*	1.99171	0.017	-8.6709	-0.8425
		Male	-4.28998*	2.00413	0.033	-8.2286	-0.3514
Test	Gender	Gender	Mean difference	Std. error	Sig.	Lower bound	Upper bound
Hochberg	Female	Male	0.46671	0.46866	0.685	-0.6564	1.5898
		Neutral	4.75669	1.99171	0.051	-0.0162	9.5295
	Male	Female	-0.46671	0.46866	0.685	-1.5898	0.6564
		Neutral	4.28998	2.00413	0.095	-0.5126	9.0926
	Neutral	Female	-4.75669	1.99171	0.051	-9.5295	0.0162
		Male	-4.28998	2.00413	0.095	-9.0926	0.5126

Note: *The mean difference is significant at $p < 0.05$

4.9. Summary

In this chapter, the results of the analysis of data were presented and interpreted. By the usage of the PLS-SEM method, the measurement model was assessed, that is, the confirmatory factor analysis was performed and the constructs' validity and reliability were examined. In the context of construct validity, the values of convergence and discriminant validity were assessed. In the context of construct reliability, the values of Cronbach's alpha, consistent and composite reliability were assessed. The overall model fit and the collinearity issues of the structural model were assessed. The in-sample predictive relevance of the structural model was assessed and the hypotheses H1-H6 were tested, followed by the assessment of the out-of-sample predictive power and the effect size of the structural model. The Hypothesis H7 was tested based on the one-way analysis of variance procedure.

Chapter 5: Discussion

5.1. Overview

This chapter discusses the findings of the research in conjunction with answering the research questions of the study and the findings of prior studies on consumer behaviour in the field of corporate social responsibility and sustainable luxury and fashion. The chapter presents the managerial implications, theoretical contributions and limitations of the study and the suggestions for future research.

5.2. General Discussion

This study demonstrated that consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability negatively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability and perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. It was found that males and females have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than gender-neutral consumers.

In the following sections, each factor is discussed in relation to encouraging sustainable luxury fashion consumption.

5.2.1. Perceived Contradiction between Luxury Fashion and Sustainability

This study indicates that consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability negatively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. When consumers perceive a high contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability, they are less likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. This is in line with the view of Beckham and Voyer (2014) that consumers are not willing to purchase sustainable luxury brands because they perceive luxury and sustainability as contradictory. Consumers are likely to choose a non-sustainable luxury brand over a sustainable one because it brings the owner higher social status and prestige (Beckham and Voyer, 2014). A similar stance is taken by Kapferer and Michaut (2014) who argue that consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury and sustainability is founded on the basic meaning of luxury in terms of symbolising social stratification and shallow values. The luxury industry's marketing is instrumentally effective in expanding its social pressure beyond high-income consumers, which suggests that luxury can be judged on the ground of creating social unrest and promoting superficiality (Kapferer and Michaut, 2014). Kapferer and Valette-Florence (2022) write that 'luxury does not create social inequality, but it makes it visible' (Kapferer and Valette-Florence, 2022, p. 362).

When consumers do not perceive a high compatibility between the true attributes of luxury and sustainability, luxury as something that symbolises classes, social inequality and extravagance is likely to be at the forefront of consumers' thoughts about sustainable luxury. This indicates that luxury fashion brands need to position themselves in a way which puts emphasis on their true qualities that may coexist with sustainability. Priming social ads and messages with information on the positive influence of sustainability on the quality, longevity and durability of luxury fashion products can contribute to the strengthening of consumers' perceived compatibility between luxury fashion and sustainability (Bendell and Kleanthous, 2007; Beckham and Voyer, 2014; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

In this study, consumers mostly perceived luxury fashion to be related to exceptional quality, high price and exclusivity, followed by creativity, hedonism (beauty) and rarity. In Kapferer and Michaut's (2015) study, consumers perceived exceptional quality, rarity and exclusivity as the most important attribute of luxury, followed by high price, hedonism and creativity (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

Kapferer and Michaut (2015) propose that consumers who define luxury as exceptional quality are likely to perceive a lower contradiction between luxury and sustainability than consumers who define luxury as high price, rarity and exclusivity (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Consumers who associate luxury fashion mainly with high price and rarity are interested in luxury fashion goods made from the most expensive and first-class rare fabrics, such as silk, cashmere, vicuna wool and exotic leather, rather than in luxury fashion goods made from sustainably sourced materials. Consumers who perceive luxury fashion based on exclusivity are interested in limited edition luxury fashion goods that are produced in small quantities and with a slightly different style (Kapferer, 2012).

In the marketing literature, the concepts of exclusivity, scarcity and rarity have been used to point at restrictions in the distribution of products (Kapferer, 2012; Upshaw, Amyx and Hardy, 2017) or to describe the effects of limited supply, that is, the availability of products in small quantities (Dörnyei, 2020). For example, Balachander and Stock (2009) indicate that luxury brands can utilise a limited edition strategy to signal value based on high quality (Balachander and Stock, 2009). Chan, To and Chu (2015) emphasise that limited edition and scarce luxury products allow consumers with a higher self-presentation motive to signal status and define and enhance their sense of self to differentiate from others (Chan, To and Chu, 2015).

Wang, Sung and Phau (2022) address exclusivity and rarity as two independent marketing concepts in luxury, stressing the difference between 'limited availability of products versus limited accessible of consumers' (Wang, Sung and Phau, 2022, p. 366). In this regard, it is important to make the difference between natural and virtual rarity in luxury. Natural rarity in luxury relates to the use of valuable materials that are naturally scarce in a sense that supply never surpasses demand. On the other hand, virtual rarity is artificially created when product availability is controlled by the launch of limited edition products to enhance brand luxuriousness and brand desirability (Kapferer, 2012). Although it may appear that rarity is contradictory to sustainability, it should be acknowledged that rare and precious

luxury fashion materials and fabrics should be sourced sustainably in order to preserve natural resources necessary for the continuity of luxury fashion business. Additionally, rare luxury fashion materials and fabrics are very durable and have superior quality, which are the qualities that match sustainability (Ranfagni and Ozuem, 2022). Vehmas *et al.* (2018) found that consumers welcome limited edition sustainable fashion goods of high quality. Some consumers even suggested promoting them as the luxury fashion goods of the future (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

5.2.2. Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brand Awareness

This study indicates that consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability positively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. If consumers have high awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, they are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. This is in accordance with the findings of Olšanová *et al.* (2022) that consumers' purchase intentions of luxury brands are positively affected by consumers' awareness of luxury brands' corporate social responsibility (Olšanová *et al.*, 2022). The findings reflect the view of Pomeroy and Dolnicar (2009) that undertaking socially responsible activities can have practical relevance only if consumers' awareness of those efforts is high (Pomeroy and Dolnicar, 2009).

Many luxury brands have boosted their philanthropic responsibilities in order to combat climate change (Kapferer and Bastien, 2009a). For example, the luxury fashion brand Burberry allocated '£22.3 million to charitable activities between 2012 and 2017' (Sipilä *et al.*, 2021, p. 280). However, following the Business of Fashion, which is an online media company focused on the global fashion industry, luxury fashion brands on average perform less well than expected regarding labour rights, environmental protection and supply chain transparency. The luxury fashion brands Moët Hennessy Louis Vuitton, Hermès and Richemont have been evaluated to lag behind high street fashion companies in pursuing sustainability (Waldersee and Aloisi, 2021). The need for a strategic approach to managing sustainability in luxury fashion is evident, which implies that following sustainability by luxury fashion brands should go beyond philanthropic donations (Carroll, 2016).

Prior research identified consumers' low awareness of the sustainability aspects of the fashion industry (Joergens, 2006; Morgan and Birtwistle, 2009; Goworek *et al.*, 2012; Han *et al.*, 2017) and the luxury industry (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai (2012) explain that consumers' low awareness of ethics in luxury stems from the lack of information on environmental and social problems in the global luxury supply chain and luxury brands' ethical initiatives, that is, the insufficient presence of ethical luxury products in the market. Consumers do not perceive luxury as a sector that creates huge adverse changes to the natural environment and allows unfair relationships in manufacturing operations, which demonstrates the fallacy of clean luxury. Accordingly, consumers believe that the luxury sector cannot significantly contribute to solving social responsibility problems in the global supply chain (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012).

The separation fallacy between business and ethics relates to the widespread perceptions of business decisions as independent of ethical considerations, which misleads consumers to believe that ethical products always or commonly cost more than their non-ethical counterparts (Freeman, 1994; Harris and Freeman, 2008). Because of the fallacy of clean luxury, consumers believe that any extra charge for social responsibility by luxury brands does not go to producers and suppliers in developing countries and it does not help combat climate change, pollution and social injustice. Moreover, the irregularity of luxury purchases prevents consumers to search for more information about the ethical aspects of luxury brands (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012).

Henninger *et al.* (2017) suggest that consumers are likely to ignore sustainability information in their luxury fashion purchases because of being attracted by luxury fashion brands' qualities, such as unique design, rarity and exclusivity, in spite of the fact that they can be highly aware of sustainability issues in the industry (Henninger *et al.*, 2017). This is similar to the view of Ehrich and Irwin (2005) that consumers deliberately ignore social information in their purchase decisions to avoid negative emotions, regardless of if they have moral values and concerns for the environment and social progress (Ehrich and Irwin, 2005). Luxury and fashion purchases are operationalised as emotional spending in the moments of intensified emotions, such as happiness, stress, sadness or boredom. Purchasing luxury and fashion brands improves consumers' self-image and self-esteem or it satisfies their wish for indulgence, pleasure and self-rewarding. These situations contrast thinking about harsh working conditions and trampled human, labour and animal rights in the luxury and fashion supply chain (Henninger *et al.*, 2017).

Costa Pinto *et al.* (2019) recommend that luxury brands activate consumers' personal identity goals in social responsibility communication because accentuating consumers' social identity goals is likely to strengthen consumers' evaluations of the ethical unfairness of sophisticated luxury brands that satisfy consumers' self-enhancement needs. Namely, the perceived ethicality of luxury brands is influenced by brand personality (Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019), which refers to 'the set of human characteristics associated with a brand' (Aaker, 1997, p. 347). Social responsibility is perceived as more compatible with a sincere brand personality, which is characterised as honest and trustworthy, than with a sophisticated brand personality, which is characterised as less ethical and highly luxurious. Consumers are likely to perceive social information more favourably when marketing communication puts accent on consumer-focused activities that benefit consumers rather than on society-focused activities that benefit a wider population. Society-focused activities involve, for example, pollution reduction activities that have global environmental benefits. Consumer-focused activities involve, for example, delivering sustainable products that enable consumers' health benefits (Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019).

Following Joergens (2006), the use of chemicals in the manufacturing of fashion products is of consumers' concern when it affects their skin and health (Joergens, 2006). Similarly, Vehmas *et al.* (2018) discovered that consumers are concerned with how sustainable textiles feel on their skin and if they are breathable and different from synthetic fibres, which indicates that consumers are likely to evaluate sustainable fashion products more favourably if they can receive personal benefits from such products (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018). This concurs with the suggestion of Costa Pinto *et al.* (2019) that communicating socially responsible actions with accent on benefits for consumers has a stronger effect on activating consumers' positive evaluations of the ethicality of luxury brands and forming consumers' positive attitudes towards luxury brands promoting social responsibility. Accordingly, consumers should obtain personal benefits by purchasing sustainable luxury fashion brands rather than just perceive luxury fashion brands' sustainability efforts as beneficial for the environment and society. Communicating consumer-focused sustainability activities allows luxury fashion brands to effectively pursue sustainability, maintain their sophisticated image and be perceived as credible as sincere brands, which positively affects consumers' brand attitude formation (Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019).

Similarly, Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman (2013) propose that the environmental claim can improve consumers' evaluation of luxury brands when personal-social benefits are highlighted more than global environmental benefits in marketing communication because luxury purchases need to provide justification for self-indulgence. Therefore, when communicating activities within the environmental dimension of sustainability, luxury fashion brands should emphasise consumers' higher social status and improved image because of behaving sustainably (Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman, 2013).

5.2.3. Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brand Expectations

This study indicates that consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. If consumers have high expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, they are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. This is similar to the findings of Ng (2022) that consumers' expectations for social enterprises' social responsibility positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of social enterprise products (Ng, 2022). In the context of fashion brands, Lin, Wang and Yang (2023) found that consumers' sustainable purchase intentions are strongly affected by consumers' environmental expectations (Lin, Wang and Yang, 2023).

Following Kapferer and Michaut (2015), consumers have high expectations for luxury brands' sustainability engagement, although consumers mostly ignore sustainability in their luxury purchases (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Podnar and Golob (2007) propose that consumers have the highest expectations for the legal corporate social responsibilities, followed by the ethical and philanthropic corporate social responsibilities. Consumers' expectations for the ethical and philanthropic corporate social responsibilities were positively related to consumers' support for companies' socially responsible behaviour (Podnar and Golob, 2007). In the context of social enterprise products, Ng's (2022) study indicates that the legal and ethical dimension is a stronger indicator of consumers' corporate social responsibility expectations than the environmental and social dimensions (Ng, 2022).

This study suggests that consumers have high expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability. The legal sustainability responsibilities are closely linked with the ethical sustainability responsibilities of luxury fashion brands. The legal and ethical sustainability dimension operates in tandem with the social and environmental sustainability dimensions in the explanation of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. However, the social and environmental sustainability dimensions are a stronger predictor of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than the legal and ethical sustainability dimension.

The findings of this study challenge the ordering of the sustainability dimensions in a luxury fashion context based on Carroll's (1991) pyramid model of corporate social responsibility, that is, the appropriateness of the model to describe consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability (Carroll, 1991). It was found that luxury fashion consumers have the greatest expectations for the social and environmental dimensions of sustainability, followed by the legal and ethical dimension. A possible reason for these findings may be in line with the suggestion of Carrigan and Attalla (2001) that consumers are less concerned with labour standards because they are aware that different cultural norms and low legal and economic support in the developed world prevent noticeable improvements in the global supply chain (Carrigan and Attalla, 2001). Following Joergens (2006), it appears that the same reason prompts consumers to be indifferent about labour exploitation in the apparel supply chain (Joergens, 2006). Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai (2012) emphasise that consumers have false and unfounded beliefs about clean luxury and believe that luxury brands cannot create huge changes in supply chains, that is, luxury brands are perceived to have small negative and positive impacts (Davies, Lee and Ahonkhai, 2012).

The findings of this study support the view of Amatulli *et al.* (2018) that luxury consumers may be more responsive to more visible and noticeable social responsibility initiatives because they are in alignment with status and conspicuous luxury consumption (Amatulli *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, the planetary environmental crisis harming life on Earth has been vigorously addressed by governmental and non-governmental organisations and consumers are becoming increasingly aware that business operations have damaging effects on the environment, which increases their environmental concerns and expectations (Falk *et al.*, 2022).

Based on Carroll's model of corporate social responsibility, Amatulli *et al.* (2018) proposed a model of social responsibility in luxury by connecting the visibility and noticeability of the social responsibility dimensions with status and conspicuous consumption (Amatulli *et al.*, 2018). Pino *et al.* (2016) classified social responsibility initiatives into two groups based on how visible and noticeable they are for consumers. Improving working conditions and ethical supply chain management are the examples of internal social responsibility initiatives. Including necessary information on product packaging, supporting environmental clean-ups, health initiatives and donating to causes, for example, are within the external domain of social responsibility (Pino *et al.*, 2016). The difference between the ethical and philanthropic domains of social responsibility is made on the basis of the voluntary nature of philanthropy. Although philanthropy is often driven by ethical considerations, businesses' philanthropic responsibilities are desired by society but not expected as the ethical responsibilities and required as the legal responsibilities (Carroll, 2016).

Amatulli *et al.* (2018) demonstrated that luxury brands involved in external social responsibility initiatives are perceived as more luxurious, which is harmonised with the status-seeking and conspicuous dimensions of luxury. Consequently, promoting more observable social responsibility initiatives may be a more effective marketing strategy for increasing sustainable luxury purchases and more contributory to environmental protection and social welfare (Amatulli *et al.*, 2018). However, Sipilä *et al.* (2021) argue that the nature of luxury business may be perceived as more congruent with company-internal social responsibility initiatives such as employee satisfaction. Delivering superior luxury value is very dependent on employees' craftsmanship and satisfaction while philanthropy can be perceived as conflicting with luxury (Sipilä *et al.*, 2021).

Research suggests that highly educated and older consumers are likely to be more susceptible to the environmental aspects of business operations and behave as ecologically responsible consumers (Roberts, 1996a). Other studies indicate that younger individuals are more socially conscious and possibly more likely to engage in responsible consumption behaviour (Anderson and Cunningham, 1972; De Pelsmacker, Driesen and Rayp, 2005). However, the usage of demographics alone is not sufficient to identify the socially responsible luxury consumer yet marketing communication needs to consider the manifestation of luxury value dimensions for particular consumer cohorts and connect it with promoting initiatives within the external and internal domains of sustainability. Jiang

and Shan (2018) propose that older consumers have a higher rating of functional and social value in their luxury purchases while younger consumers are more liable to the influence of self-identity and hedonic value when purchasing luxury brands (Jiang and Shan, 2018). Srinivasan (2015) found that self-identity value in luxury is more important for consumers holding high qualifications, which indicates their lower inclination towards social prestige value (Srinivasan, 2015). Hence, luxury brands need to adjust promoting the sustainability dimensions in a way which is more likely to motivate different consumer segments to purchase sustainable fashion taking into account how the dimensions of luxury affect their behaviour (Amatulli *et al.*, 2018; Sipilä *et al.*, 2021).

Green and Peloza (2011) indicate that promoting the philanthropic domain of social responsibility creates consumers' emotional and social value. Emotional value is received when consumers benefit emotionally from purchasing brands with a social or environmental attribute. Social value is received when purchasing sustainable brands is in accordance with relevant social norms. Accordingly, marketers should use emotional marketing to connect consumers with sustainable luxury fashion brands and highlight the aspects of social status in marketing communication, such as consumers' increased social image and prestige because of purchasing sustainable luxury fashion brands (Green and Peloza, 2011).

5.2.4. Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brand Attitudes

This study indicates that consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. If consumers have high attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, they are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. This is similar to the findings of Lee, Zailani and Rahman (2020) that consumers' purchase intentions of social enterprise products are positively influenced by consumers' attitudes towards such products (Lee, Zailani and Rahman, 2020). Similarly, Rausch and Kopplin (2021) report that consumers' attitudes towards sustainable fashion products positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable fashion products (Rausch and Kopplin, 2021).

Managers should have an active role in forming consumers' positive attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands because it might motivate consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Han *et al.* (2017) recommend that consumers' positive attitudes towards sustainable fashion brands may be stimulated by creating emotional marketing experiences. Consumers prefer concrete narratives about the origin and manufacturing of sustainable fashion brands rather than abstract and vague information about the destruction of the natural environment and global warming caused by the fashion industry. Communicating sustainability by activating consumers' guilt for prior consumption does not make a real change in their attitudes towards sustainable fashion brands (Han *et al.*, 2017). In the democratised luxury world, as Cervellon and Shamma's study (2013) suggests, consumers perceive conspicuous luxury consumption as guilt-free pleasure and rewards for hard work (Cervellon and Shamma, 2013).

Others argue that following sustainability requires consumer attitude and behaviour change in terms of opposing overconsumption and investing in fashion items made of more durable materials that will last for a long time (Harris, Roby and Dibb, 2016). Peter and Honea (2012) explain that the transformation of consumer behaviour is a gradual process in which marketers should release consumers from guilt and encourage them to feel proud and hopeful about sustainability. It would pave the way for the second phase in which consumers will think optimistically about a sustainable future and adopt behaviours that do not harm the environment (Peter and Honea, 2012).

Folkes and Kamins' (1999) study predicted that corporate social responsibility may be a dimension of the brand's superior attributes. Folkes and Kamins (1999) argue that companies' ethical behaviour has little influence on consumers' attitudes if the product has inferior attributes. The product's superior attributes stimulate consumers' positive attitudes towards ethical companies more than towards unethical companies. Companies that refrain from using child labour were evaluated less positively than companies that implement prosocial hiring policies by employing the victims of disasters, although consumers were critical regarding the use of child labour. The authors suggest that consumers' positive attitudes towards ethical brands can be stimulated by taking a more proactive stance to corporate social responsibility and demonstrating intrinsic social responsibility (Folkes and Kamins, 1999).

According to SOMO, the Centre for Research on Multinational Corporations, child labour is used as forced labour at all stages of the textile supply chain but many fashion brands and retailers continue to underperform when it comes to supply chain transparency (Montessori, 2021). Companies are pressured to operate responsibly but consumers may be unresponsive to companies' marketing efforts that communicate improving unfair labour practices in the global supply chain. As Carrigan and Attalla's (2001) study indicated, consumers are aware that different legislation, cultural and moral norms and insufficiently developed economic infrastructure in developing countries prevent radical social and environmental reforms in the entire process of manufacturing and selling commercial products. It prompts consumers to express more sensitivity for animal welfare than for labour and human rights for workers in supply chains (Carrigan and Attalla, 2001).

Following Joergens (2006), consumers have positive attitudes towards ethical fashion only if chemicals used in the manufacturing of fashion products affect them directly (Joergens, 2006). Folkes and Kamins' (1999) study demonstrated that the company's ethical action affects consumers' attitudes even when consumers are not directly impacted by the action, such as hiring practices, when the unethical action is legal in the host country and there is no overt social pressure and when the company's ethical or unethical deeds do not impact product quality evaluations, that is, product quality inferences are not impacted by the type of workforce used in manufacturing, such as child labour and adult labour (Folkes and Kamins, 1999).

Basil and Weber (2006) recommend that marketers should consider if consumers have highly egoistic interest in their appearance or altruistic values, which helps to predict consumers' attitudes towards social responsibility. When targeting consumers with a value motivation, marketing communication should highlight the normative importance of social responsibility. In contrast, consumers concerned with their appearance are likely to act responsibly only if it is regarded as a socially desirable behaviour. Although consumers' motives for socially responsible behaviour greatly transcend the juxtaposition of altruism and egoism, this dichotomy is important because it demonstrates that different reasons can influence and shape consumers' attitudes towards responsible brands. These findings are relevant for fashion brands because appearance is of great importance for fashion consumers, which is emphasised in fashion advertising (Basil and Weber, 2006).

5.2.5. Sustainable Luxury Fashion Brand Intrinsic Attributions

This study indicates that consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. If consumers have high attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability, they are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. This matches Ellen, Webb and Mohr's (2006) and Ginder, Kwon and Byun's (2021) results which propose a positive relationship between consumers' attributions for intrinsic corporate social responsibility and purchase intentions. These studies offered a zero-sum and bipolar approach to companies' motives for corporate social responsibility, suggesting that consumers' attributions for extrinsic social responsibility motivations are likely to worsen consumers' responses to social responsibility (Ellen, Webb and Mohr, 2006; Ginder, Kwon and Byun, 2021).

Although corporate social responsibility motives are guided by both economic and social objectives, following Drumwright (1996), consumers perceive complex social responsibility motives to be driven either by profit maximisation or sincere social concerns (Drumwright, 1996). Ellen, Webb and Mohr (2006) found that consumers accept the duality of social responsibility motivations but they have negative evaluations of social responsibility initiatives undertaken as responding to the pressures of stakeholders (Ellen, Webb and Mohr, 2006). This is in agreement with the negative-duty perspective in valuing results which de-emphasises the importance of duty to others. In contrast, positive duty theory indicates that engaging in social responsibility is embodied in assisting others sincerely (Swanson, 1995).

Kim and Lee (2012) argue that consumers do not simply evaluate companies' corporate social responsibility based on the distinction between public-serving and firm-serving motivations. Their study demonstrated that in socially stigmatised industries the high correlation between the company's core business and the supported social cause is not the reason for consumers to attribute more firm-serving motivations to companies' social responsibility. Kim and Lee (2012) stress the importance of managerial caution when considering that consumers' purchase intentions can be encouraged based on hiding businesses' self-interested motivations (Kim and Lee, 2012). Therefore, demonstrating intrinsic sustainability is likely to be a more purposeful strategy in forming consumers'

positive attitudes towards sustainable brands and motivating their sustainable purchases (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004; Parguel, Benoît-Moreau and Larceneux, 2011).

However, creating consumers' favourable perceptions of the reasons why luxury brands choose to engage in corporate social responsibility is complex due to the intrinsic conceptual differences between luxury and corporate social responsibility. Torelli, Monga and Kaikati (2012) argue that the idea of brand concepts is important for a better understanding of the link between luxury and social responsibility (Torelli, Monga and Kaikati, 2012). Brand concepts are associated with the abstract meanings and essential ideas behind the brand's identity (Park, Milberg and Lawson, 1991). A self-enhancement concept of luxury brands contrasts a self-transcendence concept of social responsibility. A lack of control in spending money and resources, conspicuousness, snobbery and indulgence as the characteristics of luxury do not easily match resource conservation, income redistribution and reducing social inequalities as the qualities of social responsibility (Torelli, Monga and Kaikati, 2012).

The perceived conflict between corporate social responsibility and a self-enhancement concept of luxury brands embodied in self-centred values is likely to induce disfluency in processing social information. Discounting the effects of disfluency in interpreting social information may be achieved based on providing more concrete information about the luxury brand's social responsibility progress, creating the perceptions of a good congruence between the brand and its social responsibility activities, using influential philanthropists in social advertising, communicating social information more often to encourage consumers to think about social responsibility and using a sub-branding strategy when an introduction of a new secondary sustainable brand creates new information about the primary brand (Torelli, Monga and Kaikati, 2012).

Therefore, luxury fashion brands' communication needs to reflect the sincere motivations for sustainability engagement and to demonstrate the credibility of sustainability disclosures, which in return allows creating and maintaining long-term consumer relationships built on trust. It necessitates the improvement of supply chain transparency by monitoring business performance at every stage and addressing the breach of sustainability policies (Delmas and Burbano, 2011; Graafland, 2013; Lock and Schulz-Knappe, 2019).

In the luxury and fashion industry, Stella McCartney is an inspiring example of a profitable enterprise that has incorporated sustainability into its business model, mission and vision, demonstrating that luxury fashion and sustainability can coexist. This company differs from quasi-responsible luxury and fashion companies that have not justified their sincere motives for sustainability (Yang, Han and Lee, 2017).

5.2.6. Circular Luxury Fashion Brand Perceived Value

This study indicates that consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands positively affects consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. If consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands is high, they are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. This is similar to the findings of Kim, Jung and Lee (2021) that consumers' purchase intentions of circular clothing are positively affected by consumers' perceived emotional, social, environmental and epistemic values of circular clothing (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Similarly, Hussain, Saleem and Soomro (2023) found that consumers' emotional, environmental and social values of circular fashion products have a positive impact on consumers' sustainable purchase intentions (Hussain, Saleem and Soomro, 2023).

Kim, Jung and Lee's (2021) study suggests that the perceived emotional value of circular clothing is of the greatest importance for consumers, followed by the social, environmental and epistemic value dimensions (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Following Hussain, Saleem and Soomro's (2023) study, the perceived emotional value of circular fashion products is the most important for consumers, followed by the environmental and social values (Hussain, Saleem and Soomro, 2023). In this study, consumers' perceived emotional value of circular luxury fashion brands was a stronger predictor of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than the epistemic, social and environmental value. The emotional dimension was the strongest indicator of consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands, followed by the epistemic, social and environmental value dimension.

Product and marketing management should increase consumers' perceived emotional value by improving and communicating circular luxury fashion brands' true qualities, such as high quality, authenticity and aesthetic design. It is necessary for creating consumers' unique and intense positive emotions about purchasing circular luxury fashion brands,

such as joy, excitement and trust (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Vehmas *et al.* (2018) recommend that fashion brands use storytelling to engage consumers emotionally into the dream of sustainable circular fashion. Consumers welcome factually backed information about transforming textile waste into new fashion products, which suggests the importance of transparency in supply chain management (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

Adıgüzel and Donato (2021) argue that marketers should induce consumers' feelings of pride in influencing consumers to purchase circular luxury brands. Consumers attribute higher pride to upcycled than recycled luxury, which increases consumers' purchase intentions of upcycled luxury brands. Likewise, consumers are likely to evaluate upcycled luxury more favourably than non-sustainable luxury due to increased pride (Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021).

Managers should increase consumers' perceived epistemic value by emphasising circular luxury fashion brands' novelty, rarity and uniqueness (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Adıgüzel and Donato (2021) indicate that consumers attribute greater novelty to upcycled than recycled luxury, which prompts consumers' willingness to purchase upcycled luxury brands (Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021). Luxury brands should use and improve an aesthetic product design strategy for circular fashion as it is one of the most effective strategies in creating the uniqueness of products (Heine, 2012). Research indicates that consumers expressed disappointment in sustainable fashion because of limited and poor designs and styles. Being authentic is essential for sustainable fashion brands to successfully compete in the market (Shaw and Tomolillo, 2004).

Circular luxury fashion brands should be perceived as helpful and influential in resource conservation and reducing pollution. Managers need to increase consumers' perceived environmental value by communicating how circular luxury fashion brands contribute to protecting and saving the natural environment (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Vehmas *et al.* (2018) found that consumers ask for concrete information on circular fashion and how their sustainable behaviour can influence the environmental aspects of the textile manufacturing (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

Achabou and Dekhili (2013) reported that consumers perceive recycling negatively in terms of including recycled textile into new luxury fashion products and positively in terms of environmental protection (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013). Upcycling is considered a more prosperous sustainability strategy than recycling because upcycling adds high creative and environmental value to fashion goods. In contrast to upcycling, the degradation of fabrics in recycling is not highly sustainable due to using lots of energy and water and fabrics cannot be restored in full. Upcycling allows the extension of the lifespan of fabrics based on the inventiveness and imaginativeness of designers to discover a new life for textile waste (Bridgens *et al.*, 2018).

Managers should exploit the potential of the growing second-hand luxury fashion market to increase consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands. Kessous and Valette-Florence (2019) discovered that second-hand luxury fashion products can be perceived as more authentic, unique and rare than first-hand products available on the mass luxury market. Purchasing genuine, unique and rare second-hand luxury fashion products allows their owners to differentiate from the masses (Kessous and Valette-Florence, 2019). According to Turunen and Leipämaa-Leskinen (2015), searching for the originality and uniqueness of true luxury and timeless designs prompts consumers to purchase second-hand luxury fashion goods. Consumers' search for second-hand luxury fashion goods made of more durable materials and with a longer life cycle reflects their endeavours to oppose overconsumption and reduce animal suffering (Turunen and Leipämaa-Leskinen, 2015). Turunen and Pöyry (2019) argue that the trading of second-hand luxury fashion goods allows consumers to prolong luxury fashion goods' life cycle and contribute to sustainable consumption, although resale value consciousness and social status elevation may be the primary drivers of such investments (Turunen and Pöyry, 2019).

The consumption of luxury brands shows how consumers neglect a rational approach in making purchase decisions. Turunen and Pöyry (2019) explain that opposite consumer behaviour is likely to occur in second-hand luxury consumption because consumers put emphasis on the price-quality relationship by paying a high price for the quality, functionality and utility of a luxury product and not for the brand. Nevertheless, these consumers have high brand consciousness but they believe that the second-hand market unveils the real value of luxury brands. Therefore, managers need to have the understanding of the changing nature of the meanings attached to luxury brands.

Consumers trading on the second-hand luxury market do not need to necessarily perceive themselves as the end-users or owners of luxury products (Turunen and Pöyry, 2019). The impossibility to be the owner of luxury and fashion products is regarded as a hampering factor for sustainable consumption based on the fact that luxury and fashion purchases are often realised as irrational and emotional spending (Karpova *et al.*, 2022).

Luxury fashion brands can launch their own in-house resale programmes or work in collaboration with online resale platforms in order to stimulate sustainable consumption. For example, the luxury fashion brand Burberry collaborates with the platform TheRealReal, which is a second-hand channel for authenticated luxury consignment (Turunen, Cervellon and Carey, 2020).

The perceived social value of circular luxury fashion brands is high when consumers evaluate that circular luxury fashion brands have qualities that can impress relevant others within their social circle. Possessing luxurious fashion products made from discarded textiles or second-hand luxury fashion products can make a good impression on others if they are of high quality, unique, limited edition and better for the environment (Hussain, Saleem and Soomro, 2023).

Han *et al.* (2017) propose that the sustainable fashion market could be enlarged by appealing to consumers through price, quality, design and style. As an example, upcycled fashion products are likely to be perceived as more attractive if traditional product attributes are emphasised in the initial phase of launching those products. After the desired perception of the aesthetics, quality and uniqueness of upcycled fashion products has been accomplished, a marketing strategy can communicate the sustainability aspects of upcycled fashion products (Han *et al.*, 2017).

5.2.7. Gender

This study proposes that males and females have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than gender-neutral consumers. Gender-neutral fashion is a new movement within the fashion industry and luxury brands have been exploring gender-neutral fashion marketing in order to effectively connect with the target audience (Kim, Cho and Park, 2022). The findings indicate that male and female consumers do not significantly differ in their purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. This is

different from the findings of Dangelico, Alvino and Fraccascia (2022) that females are more likely to purchase garments made of organic materials than males (Dangelico, Alvino and Fraccascia, 2022). The current findings support the argument that the sustainable luxury fashion consumer cannot be narrowly defined and the market for sustainable luxury fashion brands is broadening (Roberts, 1996a; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015; Olšanová *et al.*, 2022).

5.3. Managerial Implications

The findings of this study have significant implications for businesses interested to promote and sell sustainable luxury fashion products and executives navigating product and communication management in sustainable luxury fashion. This study is the commencement in the understanding of how consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability impact consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Consumers with high expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. The findings indicate that greater emphasis on the social and environmental sustainability dimensions in marketing communication might motivate consumers to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands.

Green and Peloza (2011) argue that consumers can benefit emotionally and gain social approval based on purchasing brands with social and environmental claims. However, product quality should be stressed in production and marketing efforts because the actual benefit that the brand provides is more important for consumers than emotional and social values obtained from social responsibility. This indicates that value created by social and environmental sustainability should enhance luxury fashion brands' core attributes, such as high quality, longevity and durability. As Green and Peloza (2011) stressed, consumers perceive the quality of fashion products as higher if sweatshop labour is not used in their manufacturing. Hence, managers should use legal and ethical sustainability initiatives to enhance the perceived quality of luxury fashion brands and overall value that consumers can receive from sustainable luxury fashion brands (Green and Peloza, 2011). Shaping consumers' sustainability expectations for luxury fashion brands should follow transparency in business operations (Podnar and Golob, 2007).

This study serves as the starting point in the understanding of the relationship between consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands and consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Consumers are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if their perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands is high. Marketing efforts should establish an emotional link between consumers and circular luxury fashion brands, which indicates the importance of creating emotionally impactful and memorable messages about the quality, design and authenticity of circular luxury fashion brands (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Vehmas *et al.* (2018) recommend that marketing storytelling informs consumers how discarded textiles have been donated, collected and remanufactured into new luxurious fashion goods of high quality. The story should engage consumers and encourage them to purchase circular luxury fashion brands based on using emotional and even humorous appeals (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

In order to enhance consumers' epistemic value, circular luxury fashion brands should be rare, original and unique (Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021). Purchasing and wearing circular luxury fashion brands need to give their owners social approval, which can be achieved if circular luxury fashion brands are of exceptional quality, limited edition and harmless to the environment. Consumers will receive high environmental value when circular luxury fashion brands are perceived as truly contributory to environmental sustainability (Hussain, Saleem and Soomro, 2023). The perceived emotional, epistemic, social and environmental values should be complementary to the quality and price values of circular luxury fashion brands (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

Research indicates that consumers are likely to support sustainable brands if sustainability does not negatively affect product quality (Boulstridge and Carrigan, 2000; Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004; Page and Fearn, 2005). Indeed, sustainability has become a new element of the quality of luxury brands expected by consumers (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). Moreover, status motives could influence consumers to evaluate more expensive sustainable brands as more desirable than more affordable non-sustainable brands (Griskevicius, Tybur and Van den Bergh, 2010). Expensive sustainable luxury fashion brands should demonstrate high functional value, justify self-indulgence and enhance social status (Green and Peloza, 2011; Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman, 2013).

This study found that consumers are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if their awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability is high. Luxury fashion brands should inform consumers about their sustainability efforts because it is likely to stimulate consumers to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. Managers could use market segmentation based on consumers' sustainability awareness levels and willingness to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands (Carrigan and Attalla, 2001) as well as consumers' interest in the circular practices of luxury fashion brands, that is, upcycling and recycling in luxury fashion and second-hand luxury fashion (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

Vehmas *et al.* (2018) highlight that the utilisation of multiple communication channels in promoting sustainability is likely to have a more powerful effect on increasing sustainability awareness among fashion consumers, such as web page, sustainability report, social media and advertising in public spaces and on tv. Marketing efforts that communicate concrete and attractive information on luxury fashion brands' sustainability achievements are likely to be more effective in increasing consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

This study indicates that consumers are more likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if their attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability are high. In order to encourage consumers' sustainable purchases, luxury fashion brands should demonstrate their trustworthiness and transparency in implementing and communicating sustainability policies. Consumers need to be assured that sustainability is not followed and communicated because of the pressures of stakeholders and avoiding consumer boycotts (Graafland, 2013). Corporate hypocrisy expressed in the gap between communicating sustainability and actual sustainability performance can have more ruinous effects on the brand's reputation and profitability than avoiding to engage in sustainability (Yoon, Giirhan-Canli and Schwarz, 2006; Danciu, 2014; Sipilä *et al.*, 2021).

This study identified consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands as the strongest determinant of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Luxury fashion brands should proactively engage in sustainability to stimulate consumers' positive attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion. For example, it has been argued that increasing employment rates based on hiring vulnerable groups in deprived areas is likely to have a stronger effect on consumers' attitudes towards sustainable brands with superior attributes than just refraining from using unethical practices such as

hiring child labour (Folkes and Kamins, 1999). Likewise, performing more specific pollution prevention and global warming reduction practices based on using more sustainable manufacturing processes and technologies should be more effective in forming consumers' positive attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands than just using recycled materials in the manufacturing of new products (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013).

Beckham and Voyer (2014) reported that luxury fashion brands can be evaluated as less luxurious when labelled sustainable (Beckham and Voyer, 2014). Based on Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman's (2013) theory, however, luxury fashion brands can effectively promote sustainability if consumers' benefits are highlighted in marketing efforts rather than global environmental benefits, such as consumers' enhanced social status on the basis of sustainable purchasing (Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman, 2013). Similarly, following Costa Pinto *et al.* (2019), luxury brands should emphasise consumer-focused benefits rather than society-focused benefits in marketing communication, for example, the responsible manufacturing of healthier products (Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019). In a luxury fashion context, it can be the use of eco-friendly and naturally grown materials that have positive effects on consumers' skin and health (Joergens 2006; Vehmas *et al.*, 2018). Hence, communicating consumer-focused sustainability benefits allows sophisticated luxury fashion brands to signal fairness and be perceived as sincere brands, which can have a positive impact on consumers' attitudes towards purchasing sustainable luxury fashion brands. Managers should stress luxury fashion consumers' uniqueness because of making sustainable choices (Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019).

Consumers inclined to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands will probably be males and females. As per the findings of this research, there is no significant difference in purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands between male and female consumers. The findings indicate that male and female consumers have higher purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands than gender-neutral consumers. The genderless fashion trend has been already embraced by luxury brands. More efforts are needed to attract gender-neutral consumers with sustainable collections to effectively compete in the market (Kim, Cho and Park, 2022).

Product management and marketing communication should put more emphasis on true luxury values in fashion, such as high quality, durability and longevity. If consumers cannot perceive these basic characteristics of luxury fashion as intrinsically compatible with sustainability, it is likely that consumers' perceptions of sustainable luxury fashion will be formed on the basis of thinking of luxury as a symbol of irresponsible extravagance and social inequalities (Bendell and Kleanthous, 2007).

When using a rarity marketing strategy in promoting sustainable luxury fashion brands, the high quality, durability and sustainable sourcing of rare and precious luxury fashion materials and fabrics should be stressed in marketing messages. Sustainability efforts in preserving natural resources necessary for generating scarce luxurious materials from the natural environment should be perceived as beneficial for consumers and the environment (Karaosman, Brun and Morales-Alonso, 2015; Ranfagni and Ozuem, 2022). Luxury brands exploiting an exclusivity marketing strategy could launch limited edition sustainable fashion products of high quality. Following egalitarianism, luxury fashion brands could collaborate with high-street brands in selling limited edition sustainable products by the luxury name and create their limited availability only in selected stores (Kapferer, 2012; Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

5.4. Theoretical Contributions

Academic studies generated conflicting and inconclusive findings regarding the problem of effective corporate social responsibility implementation and communication in the business sector and in the luxury and fashion industry (Busch and Friede, 2018; Sipilä *et al.*, 2021). Little research on luxury and fashion consumers' motivations to engage in sustainable behaviour resulted in opposite findings (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013; Beckham and Voyer, 2014; Amatulli *et al.*, 2018; Athwal *et al.*, 2019; Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021). By filling in these gaps, the findings of this study can improve academic knowledge in several domains.

Most studies in the field of corporate social responsibility have been conducted in non-luxury settings (Janssen *et al.*, 2014) and focussed on either the environmental domain of social responsibility or the effects of social advertising concerning funding charitable causes (Maignan and Ferrell, 2004; Boenigk and Schuchardt, 2013; Hagtvedt and Patrick, 2016; Sung *et al.*, 2020; Adıgüzel and Donato, 2021), with some exceptions (in a luxury

context, Beckham and Voyer, 2014; Kapferer and Michaut 2014; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015; Amatulli *et al.*, 2018; Sipilä *et al.*, 2021). The findings of this study advance the overall academic literature on corporate social responsibility and academic knowledge on sustainable consumer behaviour in a luxury and fashion context.

Previous research mostly has not followed a multidimensional approach to study sustainable consumer behaviour in a luxury context (Janssen *et al.*, 2014; Nash, Ginger and Cartier, 2016). The main drawback of studies that put emphasis on the single matters of interest is omitting to understand the significance of different factors for the probability of sustainable consumption (Shaw and Clarke, 1999).

This research contributes to the literature on corporate social responsibility and sustainable luxury and fashion by developing a theoretical model which reveals how consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability, awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability, expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability, attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands, attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability, perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands and gender affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Hence, this study contributes to the comprehension of how the key psychological factors affect sustainable consumer behaviour in luxury and fashion based on measuring consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands and consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability (Salem and Chaichi, 2018; Rausch and Kopplin, 2021; Olšanová *et al.*, 2022). The study complements scarce research on consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury and sustainability and how it affects consumers' willingness to purchase sustainable luxury brands (Beckham and Voyer, 2014; Kapferer and Michaut, 2014; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

This study adds to the existing academic literature on testing Carroll's (1991) model of corporate social responsibility based on measuring consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability and linking them with consumers' sustainable purchase intentions (Podnar and Golob, 2007; Ng, 2022). The study enhances knowledge on the link between consumers' attributions for companies' motives for corporate social responsibility and consumers' responsible purchase intentions based on measuring consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability (Ellen, Webb and Mohr, 2006; Yoon, Giirhan-Canli and Schwarz, 2006; Kim and Lee, 2012). The study

contributes to the emerging literature on the link between consumers' perceived value of circular luxury and fashion brands and consumers' sustainable behaviour (Yu and Lee, 2018; Kim, Jung and Lee, 2021; Lou *et al.*, 2022; Hussain, Saleem and Soomro, 2023). The study helps to understand the usage of demographics in identifying consumers more likely to engage in sustainable behaviour in luxury and fashion (Achabou and Dekhili, 2013; Gazzola *et al.*, 2020; Dangelico, Alvino and Fraccascia, 2022).

5.5. Limitations of the Study and Suggestions for Future Research

Respondents in this study were assured of anonymity. Anonymity in social science and consumer behaviour research is a beneficial precondition for reducing bias. When this prerequisite is not satisfied, participants are more likely to provide socially desirable answers which can conflict their true attitudes and behaviours (Richman *et al.*, 1999; McGoldrick and Freestone, 2008). Nevertheless, surveys and Likert scales are liable to social desirability bias (Perera and Chaminda, 2013; Robson and McCartan, 2016). The phenomenon of a demand effect indicates that respondents may alter responses to fit the interpretation of the purpose of a study (Orne, 1962). Because people's concern for the natural environment and social betterment has mushroomed over years and consumers have been developing more socially conscious mindsets (Schlegelmilch, Bohlen and Diamantopoulos, 1996; Lantos, 2001; Morrison and Bridwell, 2011; Servera-Francés and Piqueras-Tomás, 2019), participants in this study might have extrapolated their general views on the existing sustainability trends into a luxury fashion context (Latkin *et al.*, 2017).

Likert-type scales in questionnaires are liable to central tendency, agreement and dissent bias (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Kreitchmann *et al.*, 2019). The unintentional distortion of research findings may happen as a consequence of, for example, mood swings, negligence and unconcern (Richman *et al.*, 1999). The activation of non-response bias in research findings happens when non-respondents differ systematically from those who participated in the survey (Baruch and Holtom, 2008).

The study has other potential limitations. Because the relationships between variables are more likely to be causal if they can be verified experimentally, more experimental studies are needed to understand the effects of sustainability on consumer behaviour in luxury fashion (Robson and McCartan, 2016). In order to test the external validity of the findings, future researchers could use probability sampling as a more representative method for

recruiting participants (Jager, Putnick and Bornstein, 2017). The findings of this study are cross-sectional, that is, restricted to a particular point in time without providing the possibility to evaluate how sustainable consumer behaviour in luxury fashion is evolving, which suggests that it would be beneficial to gather new data from a longitudinal survey (Bryman, 2012).

The inferences drawn from the findings of this study are based on a heterogeneous sample of luxury fashion consumers. The maximum heterogeneity sampling method provides more generalisable data on phenomena, which may diminish internal validity in comparison to when more homogeneous samples are used. Homogenous sampling in consumer behaviour research aims to develop the understanding of the attitudes and behaviours of a narrowly defined sample of consumers through the selection of similar cases (Suri, 2011; Palinkas *et al.*, 2015). Future researchers may be interested to research how different categories of luxury consumers, such as patricians, parvenus, poseurs and proletarians, perceive sustainable fashion (Han, Nunes and Drèze, 2010).

The educational level of participants in the sample is higher than the average educational level of the population and females are more represented than males and gender-neutral individuals. Younger generations and occasional treaters dominate over older and regular consumers in the sample. Most participants in the study were residents in the UK and the application of the findings may be limited to this country. Although it appears that overall consumer behaviour in luxury has becoming more similar across different countries, as cultural psychologists explain, luxury consumers' motives, decisions, attitudes and behaviours are influenced by the cultural settings in which they happen (Solomon *et al.*, 2006; Cervellon and Shammas, 2013; Carey and Cervellon, 2014). Cross-cultural psychology has an important role in consumer behaviour research and future researchers could carry out cross-cultural studies on the influence of sustainability on consumption choices in luxury fashion, which may reveal the differences between individualist and collectivist cultures (Bian and Forsythe, 2012; Chu and Lin, 2013; Peña-García *et al.*, 2020).

This study examined the key determinants of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Future studies could build up on this work by including other relevant independent variables into the model, such as consumers' subjective norms, personal norms and perceived behavioural control (Lee, Zailani and Rahman 2020; Minh

and Quynh, 2024) or consumers' ecological concerns, sustainability trust and sustainable advertising scepticism (Wei *et al.*, 2017; De Canio, Martinelli and Endrighi, 2021).

This research was an attempt to develop a wider coverage of the factors that affect sustainable luxury fashion consumption. This approach has a drawback in limiting the understanding of the very complex matters. Qualitative researchers should explore the luxury fashion consumer in depth to identify and scrutinise the meanings that consumers attach to sustainable luxury fashion brands (Zaltman, 2003; Hammarberg, Kirkman and De Lacey, 2016).

Existing qualitative research has predominantly used the focus group research strategy and semi-structured interviews to explore sustainable consumer behaviour (Boulstridge and Carrigan, 2000; Carrigan and Attalla, 2001; Cervellon, 2013; Öberseder, Schlegelmilch and Murphy, 2013). Qualitative researchers could use ethnography to examine luxury fashion consumers' attitudes and behaviours in-depth, which can reveal consumers' covert and surprising experiences regarding sustainable luxury fashion consumption over an extended period of time (Elliott and Janke-Elliott, 2003; Bass and Milosevic, 2018). For example, qualitative researchers may wish to use ethnographic methods to observe the potential of swapping luxury fashion products between consumers in their real-life settings (Karpova *et al.*, 2022).

Considering the detrimental effects of the textile dyeing process on the quality of soil, drinking water and other forms of life and human health, future researchers could conduct studies on how consumers perceive the textile dyeing process performed in a more environmentally friendly way and if this sustainability aspect could affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands (Joergens, 2006; Kant, 2012). In the context of cruelty-free luxury fashion, it would be beneficial to investigate how consumers perceive the usage of plant-based leather in the manufacturing of luxury fashion products. Studying the potential for adopting plant-based leather into the luxury fashion market is important in light of consumers' interest in animal rights and the environmental benefits of vegan leather (Choi and Lee, 2021; Gupta and Dave, 2021; Joe, 2021; Kinge, Landage and Wasif, 2013; Saha *et al.*, 2020).

Luxury fashion designers draw inspiration from art and luxury fashion is perceived as an economic activity that connects art and marketing (Godart and Seong, 2014). The luxury fashion brand Vivienne Westwood, for example, has successfully merged artistic patterns with sustainable materials in the designing and manufacturing of its creations (Meda, 2021). Future researchers could explore how consumers perceive sustainable luxury fashion brands that combine patterns inspired by art with recycling and upcycling in their design and manufacturing (Chailan, 2018).

Because the predictive accuracy of purchase intentions is likely to be higher when consumers anticipate their intentions regarding purchasing specific brands (Morwitz, 1997; Morwitz, Steckel and Gupta, 2007), it would be beneficial to conduct more case studies to explore and understand sustainable luxury fashion consumption within real-life situations (Tekin, Yiltay and Ayaz, 2016; Yang, Han and Lee, 2017). More studies are needed to explore sustainable luxury fashion in the context of luxury fashion manufacturers and retailers because they have a momentous role in stimulating sustainable luxury fashion consumption (Goworek *et al.*, 2012; Towers, Perry and Chen, 2013).

5.6. Summary

This chapter discussed the findings of this study in relation to answering the research questions of the study and the findings of prior research on consumer behaviour in the field of corporate social responsibility and sustainable luxury and fashion. The managerial implications, theoretical contributions and limitations of the study as well as the avenues for future research have been elaborated. The following chapter provides the summary of the main findings and inferences following the research questions and objectives of the study.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

The basic idea underlying this study is that sustainable luxury fashion consumption significantly influences the sustainable economy potential within the luxury and fashion industry because taking an active role in making production more sustainable can be justified only if sustainability values are embraced by consumer purchase behaviour (Carroll and Shabana, 2010; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). In this investigation, the aim was to provide recommendations for the business case for corporate social responsibility

in luxury fashion, that is, to identify and scrutinise the key drivers of the growth of sustainable luxury fashion brands from the consumer's point of view.

Sustainability can be a relevant tool for differentiating a brand in the market when sustainability implementation and communication are approached strategically (Porter and Kramer, 2006). This study indicates that consumers' perceived contradiction between luxury fashion and sustainability is in a negative relation with consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. Accordingly, luxury fashion brands need to promote the true attributes of luxury fashion as the values that can be compatible with sustainability, such as high quality, durability, longevity, timelessness, rarity, respect for materials and exclusivity. It will help to decrease or annul consumers' perceptions of shallow, wasteful and superficial luxury fashion and stimulate consumers' perceptions of deep luxury fashion that can support sustainable development (Bendell and Kleanthous, 2007; Kapferer and Michaut, 2015).

The evident and outstanding result of this study is the indication of the compatibility between luxury fashion and sustainability as well as the multidimensional nature of sustainable luxury fashion. This study indicates that consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands are the cornerstone of sustainable luxury fashion consumption. Consumers' attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands were found to be the strongest predictor of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

Fostering consumers' positive attitudes towards sustainable luxury fashion brands should be one of the most important measures in managerial efforts to motivate consumers to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands. Likewise, luxury fashion brands need to increase consumers' awareness of their sustainability efforts and form consumers' attributions for their intrinsic sustainability motivations. It was found that consumers' awareness of luxury fashion brands' sustainability and consumers' attributions for luxury fashion brands' intrinsic sustainability positively affect consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The academic literature suggests that consumers' low corporate social responsibility awareness and consumers' attributions for extrinsic corporate social responsibility are the main barriers to stimulate consumers' positive attitudes and purchase intentions towards brands promoting social responsibility (Bhattacharya and Sen, 2004; Du, Bhattacharya and Sen, 2010).

Consumers need to receive value from sustainable luxury fashion brands in order to support sustainability implementation within the luxury and fashion industry (Green and Peloza, 2011). This study found that consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands is the second most important predictor of consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands. The emotional dimension appears to be the strongest indicator of consumers' perceived value of circular luxury fashion brands, followed by the epistemic, social and environmental dimensions.

Consumers need to receive high emotional, epistemic, social and environmental value from circular luxury fashion brands and these values operate in tandem with the quality and price values of circular luxury fashion brands. Circular luxury fashion brands need to be of high-quality, novel, authentic, unique, limited edition and harmless to the environment. Emotional marketing is crucial for stimulating luxury fashion consumers' sustainable purchase intentions because it induces and mobilises their emotions to remember the stories behind circular luxury fashion brands (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018).

It has become common that customers express disappointment and anger if expensive luxury brands do not respect the environment and society (Kapferer and Michaut, 2015). This study demonstrated that consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability are in a positive relationship with consumers' purchase intentions of sustainable luxury fashion brands.

The findings of this study indicate that luxury fashion brands should have a higher dependence on the social and environmental sustainability responsibilities to gain consumers' support. The findings challenge the relevance of Carroll's (1991) pyramid model of corporate social responsibility to describe consumers' expectations for luxury fashion brands' sustainability. However, the model highlights that companies need to balance their social responsibilities above the economic responsibilities (Carroll, 1991). Moreover, the high quality of fashion brands is associated with sweatshop-free manufacturing, which indicates the importance of using legal and ethical sustainability initiatives to enhance consumers' perceptions of sustainable luxury fashion brands' superior quality (Green and Peloza, 2011). As per the findings of this research, consumers expect that luxury fashion brands fulfil the legal and ethical sustainability responsibilities parallel with the social and environmental sustainability responsibilities.

Luxury fashion brands should promote sustainability initiatives with the strongest strategic and shared value in terms of strengthening their competitiveness and creating benefits for society (Porter and Kramer, 2006). Because the observability of the sustainability dimensions is linked with status and conspicuous luxury consumption, emphasising initiatives within the more visible and noticeable dimensions of sustainability can be more effective in stimulating sustainable luxury fashion purchases and more beneficial for the environment and society. However, highlighting initiatives within the company-internal dimensions of sustainability might strongly affect and attract consumers who prioritise functional, self-identity and hedonic value in luxury fashion (Amatulli *et al.*, 2018).

It would be beneficial that consumers accept their personal responsibility towards the environment and social welfare. In this regard, marketing communication should promote personal benefits that consumers can gain from purchasing sustainable luxury fashion brands, that is, higher social status because of behaving sustainably and health benefits on the basis of using eco-friendly products without toxic chemicals and controlled environmental pollution (Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman, 2013; Costa Pinto *et al.*, 2019). The best combination of values is necessary to maintain and increase the luxuriousness of sustainable luxury fashion brands (Wiedmann, Hennigs and Siebels, 2009). The sustainable luxury fashion brand should provide functional value, that is, superior quality, durability and longevity. It should enable self-indulgence based on unique design and signal high social status based on high price and sustainability claims (Griskevicius, Tybur and Van den Bergh, 2010; Steinhart, Ayalon and Puterman, 2013).

High-quality products made of durable materials will be at the core of value created by sustainability in the luxury and fashion industry (Godart and Seong, 2014). Consumers expect sustainable fashion brands to be of exceptional quality, stylish and luxurious (Vehmas *et al.*, 2018). Luxury brands could be the powerful leaders in making fashion more sustainable because of focusing on high artisanal quality, superb craftsmanship and timeless designs parallel with the uniqueness of each creation (Joy *et al.*, 2012). Luxury fashion brands may not be perceived as naturally compatible with sustainability based on their high quality and durability, indicating the need to work on creating consumers' perceptions of the compatibility between these qualities of luxury fashion brands and sustainability (Beckham and Voyer, 2014).

Luxury brands' capability to trigger consumers' imagination in attaching the symbolic meanings to sustainable fashion is of crucial importance for success in crafting strategies on how to deliver the highest brand value based on selling and fulfilling dreams (Kapferer, 2012). Given that savvy consumers distinguish manipulation in marketing from providing true value, being sincere, credible and transparent in forming the sustainability message is indispensable to capitalise on the emerging sustainable luxury fashion market (Delmas and Burbano, 2011; Danciu, 2014; Lock and Schulz-Knappe, 2019).

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Appendix 1

Reliability Analysis (Pilot Study)

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	99.3
	Excluded ^a	1	.7
	Total	141	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.931	.933	3

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	4.87	1.846	140
I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	5.11	1.734	140
I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	4.65	1.930	140

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	99.3
	Excluded ^a	1	.7
	Total	141	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.872	.872	5

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	4.54	1.736	140
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	4.78	1.730	140
Sustainable luxury fashion brands are unique and special	4.80	1.494	140
Sustainable luxury fashion brands are of quality	4.99	1.407	140
I trust sustainable luxury fashion brands	4.57	1.610	140

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	99.3
	Excluded ^a	1	.7
	Total	141	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.868	.868	2

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	4.54	1.736	140
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	4.78	1.730	140

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	99.3
	Excluded ^a	1	.7
	Total	141	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.786	.785	3

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	3.89	1.619	140
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	4.99	1.694	140
When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	4.99	1.634	140

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	99.3
	Excluded ^a	1	.7
	Total	141	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.901	.904	9

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	5.79	1.333	140
Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	5.98	1.178	140
Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	5.99	1.292	140
Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	6.32	1.183	140
Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	5.74	1.339	140
Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	5.16	1.652	140
Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	5.44	1.343	140
Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	5.77	1.266	140
Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	6.23	1.068	140

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	99.3
	Excluded ^a	1	.7
	Total	141	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.836	.837	3

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable	3.73	1.666	140
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help	4.06	1.650	140
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	3.86	1.589	140

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	99.3
	Excluded ^a	1	.7
	Total	141	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.731	.731	2

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	4.29	1.676	140
Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	3.44	1.714	140

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	140	99.3
	Excluded ^a	1	.7
	Total	141	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.935	.936	14

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand	4.69	1.512	140
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	4.64	1.550	140
The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands	3.91	1.666	140
Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure	4.42	1.675	140
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval	4.77	1.481	140
Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people	4.81	1.464	140
Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	3.91	1.664	140
Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	4.37	1.519	140
Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	4.68	1.380	140
Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	4.21	1.351	140
Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources	4.79	1.534	140
Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials	5.13	1.507	140
Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly	4.90	1.475	140
Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	4.91	1.469	140

Exploratory Factor Analysis (Pilot Study)

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.855	.815
I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.861	.803
I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.827	.831
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	.780	.735
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	.806	.746
Sustainable luxury fashion brands are unique and special	.660	.451
Sustainable luxury fashion brands are of quality	.664	.621
I trust sustainable luxury fashion brands	.707	.580
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	.593	.472
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	.781	.663
When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	.786	.664

Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	.616	.587
Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	.738	.610
Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	.738	.640
Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	.646	.460
Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	.721	.580
Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	.737	.714
Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	.785	.837
Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	.699	.592
Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	.774	.721
Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable	.745	.722
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help	.552	.427
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	.748	.768

Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	.631	.670
Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	.598	.507
I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand	.811	.650
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	.874	.741
The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands	.783	.589
Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure	.811	.749

Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval	.780	.688
Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people	.784	.697
Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	.647	.521
Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	.715	.590
Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	.732	.566
Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	.733	.644
Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources	.783	.725
Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials	.799	.814
Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly	.836	.829
Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	.822	.742

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

a. Determinant = 9.579E-16

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.836
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4328.486
	df	741
	Sig.	<.001

Total Variance Explained

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.594	32.293	32.293	12.277	31.480	31.480
2	5.402	13.850	46.144	5.043	12.930	44.410
3	2.806	7.194	53.338	2.532	6.492	50.902
4	2.244	5.754	59.092	1.913	4.904	55.807
5	1.722	4.415	63.507	1.367	3.505	59.311
6	1.396	3.579	67.086	1.089	2.792	62.104
7	1.104	2.831	69.917	.796	2.040	64.144
8	1.080	2.768	72.685	.746	1.912	66.056
9	.994	2.549	75.234			
10	.886	2.271	77.505			
11	.814	2.088	79.593			
12	.659	1.691	81.284			
13	.592	1.519	82.803			
14	.572	1.466	84.269			
15	.531	1.361	85.631			
16	.487	1.250	86.881			
17	.455	1.167	88.047			
18	.441	1.131	89.178			
19	.408	1.046	90.224			
20	.375	.961	91.185			
21	.351	.901	92.086			
22	.326	.836	92.922			
23	.303	.776	93.699			
24	.275	.706	94.405			
25	.250	.641	95.046			
26	.237	.607	95.653			
27	.211	.541	96.194			
28	.192	.491	96.685			
29	.183	.469	97.155			
30	.173	.443	97.598			
31	.153	.392	97.990			
32	.137	.352	98.341			
33	.127	.325	98.667			
34	.124	.318	98.985			
35	.112	.286	99.271			
36	.099	.253	99.523			
37	.069	.176	99.699			
38	.064	.165	99.864			
39	.053	.136	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Factor	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.594	32.293	32.293	12.234	31.369	31.369	6.113	15.674	15.674
2	5.402	13.850	46.144	4.996	12.811	44.180	5.018	12.867	28.541
3	2.806	7.194	53.338	2.487	6.376	50.556	4.924	12.626	41.167
4	2.244	5.754	59.092	1.854	4.754	55.310	3.729	9.561	50.728
5	1.722	4.415	63.507	1.308	3.354	58.665	2.633	6.750	57.478
6	1.396	3.579	67.086	1.041	2.668	61.333	1.503	3.855	61.333
7	1.104	2.831	69.917						
8	1.080	2.768	72.685						
9	.994	2.549	75.234						
10	.886	2.271	77.505						
11	.814	2.088	79.593						
12	.659	1.691	81.284						
13	.592	1.519	82.803						
14	.572	1.466	84.269						
15	.531	1.361	85.631						
16	.487	1.250	86.881						
17	.455	1.167	88.047						
18	.441	1.131	89.178						
19	.408	1.046	90.224						
20	.375	.961	91.185						
21	.351	.901	92.086						
22	.326	.836	92.922						
23	.303	.776	93.699						
24	.275	.706	94.405						
25	.250	.641	95.046						
26	.237	.607	95.653						
27	.211	.541	96.194						
28	.192	.491	96.685						
29	.183	.469	97.155						
30	.173	.443	97.598						
31	.153	.392	97.990						
32	.137	.352	98.341						
33	.127	.325	98.667						
34	.124	.318	98.985						
35	.112	.286	99.271						
36	.099	.253	99.523						
37	.069	.176	99.699						
38	.064	.165	99.864						
39	.053	.136	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Rotated Factor Matrix^a

	Factor					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.821					
I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.806					
I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.800					
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	.780					
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	.701					
Sustainable luxury fashion brands are unique and special						
Sustainable luxury fashion brands are of quality						
I trust sustainable luxury fashion brands						
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	.568					
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	.603					
When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	.617					

Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit		.651				
Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient		.630				
Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times		.658				
Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances		.528				
Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups		.704				
Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems		.746				
Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare		.815				
Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection		.732				
Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions		.806				
Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable					.793	
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help					.589	
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community					.692	

a. Determinant = 2.22E-014

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.837
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3966.327
	df	630
	Sig.	<.001

Rotated Factor Matrix^a

	Factor					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.821					
I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.806					
I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	.803					
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	.770					
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	.688					
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	.560					
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	.599					
When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	.616					

Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit			.653			
Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient			.631			
Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times			.656			
Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances			.531			
Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups			.712			
Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems			.739			
Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare			.808			
Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection			.737			
Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions			.812			
Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable					.805	
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help					.591	
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community					.715	
Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory						-.789
Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world						-.660

I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand		.595				
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good		.640				
The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands		.553				
Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure		.713				
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval		.748				
Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people		.778				
Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends		.581				
Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness		.550				
Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands		.578				
Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features		.581				
Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources				.661		
Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials				.832		
Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly				.841		
Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands				.730		
Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.						

Factor	Total Variance Explained								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.363	31.565	31.565	11.021	30.614	30.614	5.513	15.313	15.313
2	5.377	14.935	46.500	4.971	13.808	44.422	4.941	13.725	29.039
3	2.786	7.739	54.239	2.469	6.859	51.281	4.890	13.583	42.622
4	2.231	6.197	60.436	1.851	5.142	56.423	3.423	9.509	52.131
5	1.640	4.555	64.990	1.253	3.480	59.903	2.475	6.875	59.006
6	1.386	3.850	68.840	1.057	2.936	62.839	1.380	3.833	62.839
7	1.092	3.034	71.874						
8	.939	2.609	74.483						
9	.889	2.470	76.953						
10	.818	2.273	79.227						
11	.700	1.944	81.171						
12	.612	1.699	82.870						
13	.544	1.511	84.381						
14	.529	1.470	85.851						
15	.493	1.370	87.222						
16	.454	1.261	88.482						
17	.413	1.146	89.629						
18	.395	1.096	90.725						
19	.358	.993	91.718						
20	.310	.860	92.578						
21	.301	.837	93.415						
22	.283	.787	94.202						
23	.251	.697	94.898						
24	.229	.636	95.534						
25	.211	.587	96.121						
26	.195	.542	96.663						
27	.177	.492	97.155						
28	.176	.490	97.645						
29	.142	.396	98.041						
30	.139	.386	98.427						
31	.127	.351	98.778						
32	.123	.340	99.119						
33	.105	.291	99.410						
34	.087	.241	99.650						
35	.067	.185	99.836						
36	.059	.164	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Harman Single Factor Test (Pilot Study)

Total Variance Explained						
Factor	Total	Initial Eigenvalues		Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
		% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.594	32.293	32.293	12.004	30.780	30.780
2	5.402	13.850	46.144			
3	2.806	7.194	53.338			
4	2.244	5.754	59.092			
5	1.722	4.415	63.507			
6	1.396	3.579	67.086			
7	1.104	2.831	69.917			
8	1.080	2.768	72.685			
9	.994	2.549	75.234			
10	.886	2.271	77.505			
11	.814	2.088	79.593			
12	.659	1.691	81.284			
13	.592	1.519	82.803			
14	.572	1.466	84.269			
15	.531	1.361	85.631			
16	.487	1.250	86.881			
17	.455	1.167	88.047			
18	.441	1.131	89.178			
19	.408	1.046	90.224			
20	.375	.961	91.185			
21	.351	.901	92.086			
22	.326	.836	92.922			
23	.303	.776	93.699			
24	.275	.706	94.405			
25	.250	.641	95.046			
26	.237	.607	95.653			
27	.211	.541	96.194			
28	.192	.491	96.685			
29	.183	.469	97.155			
30	.173	.443	97.598			
31	.153	.392	97.990			
32	.137	.352	98.341			
33	.127	.325	98.667			
34	.124	.318	98.985			
35	.112	.286	99.271			
36	.099	.253	99.523			
37	.069	.176	99.699			
38	.064	.165	99.864			
39	.053	.136	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Total Variance Explained

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.363	31.565	31.565	10.775	29.929	29.929
2	5.377	14.935	46.500			
3	2.786	7.739	54.239			
4	2.231	6.197	60.436			
5	1.640	4.555	64.990			
6	1.386	3.850	68.840			
7	1.092	3.034	71.874			
8	.939	2.609	74.483			
9	.889	2.470	76.953			
10	.818	2.273	79.227			
11	.700	1.944	81.171			
12	.612	1.699	82.870			
13	.544	1.511	84.381			
14	.529	1.470	85.851			
15	.493	1.370	87.222			
16	.454	1.261	88.482			
17	.413	1.146	89.629			
18	.395	1.096	90.725			
19	.358	.993	91.718			
20	.310	.860	92.578			
21	.301	.837	93.415			
22	.283	.787	94.202			
23	.251	.697	94.898			
24	.229	.636	95.534			
25	.211	.587	96.121			
26	.195	.542	96.663			
27	.177	.492	97.155			
28	.176	.490	97.645			
29	.142	.396	98.041			
30	.139	.386	98.427			
31	.127	.351	98.778			
32	.123	.340	99.119			
33	.105	.291	99.410			
34	.087	.241	99.650			
35	.067	.185	99.836			
36	.059	.164	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Appendix 2

Reliability Analysis (Main Study)

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	453	99.8
	Excluded ^a	1	.2
	Total	454	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.914	.914	3

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	4.91	1.680	453
I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	4.97	1.735	453
I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	4.80	1.831	453

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	453	99.8
	Excluded ^a	1	.2
	Total	454	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.842	.843	2

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	4.74	1.694	453
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	4.98	1.631	453

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	453	99.8
	Excluded ^a	1	.2
	Total	454	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.786	.790	3

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	4.25	1.712	453
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	5.37	1.530	453
When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	5.22	1.572	453

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	453	99.8
	Excluded ^a	1	.2
	Total	454	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.894	.897	9

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	5.65	1.274	453
Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	5.72	1.326	453
Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	5.85	1.305	453
Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	6.19	1.226	453
Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	5.40	1.404	453
Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	4.92	1.608	453
Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	5.21	1.437	453
Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	5.57	1.380	453
Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts	5.97	1.264	453

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	453	99.8
	Excluded ^a	1	.2
	Total	454	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.861	.861	3

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable	3.90	1.753	453
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help	4.31	1.663	453
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	3.99	1.648	453

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	453	99.8
	Excluded ^a	1	.2
	Total	454	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.779	.781	2

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	4.17	1.689	453
Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	3.56	1.836	453

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	453	99.8
	Excluded ^a	1	.2
	Total	454	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.934	.936	14

Item Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand	4.97	1.489	453
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	4.98	1.517	453
The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands	4.17	1.753	453
Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure	4.76	1.492	453
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval	4.87	1.494	453
Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people	5.03	1.355	453
Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	4.08	1.789	453
Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	4.72	1.471	453
Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	5.04	1.334	453
Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	4.51	1.415	453
Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources	5.12	1.472	453
Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials	5.20	1.425	453
Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly	5.06	1.492	453
Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	5.30	1.395	453

Appendix 3

Descriptive Statistics (Characteristics of the Sample)

Are you a UK resident?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	359	79.2	79.2	79.2
	No	94	20.8	20.8	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	100.0	

What is your age?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	25-34	168	37.1	37.1	37.1
	18-24	124	27.4	27.4	64.5
	35-44	94	20.8	20.8	85.2
	45-54	48	10.6	10.6	95.8
	55-64	13	2.9	2.9	98.7
	65 and above	6	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	100.0	

What is your gender?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	274	60.5	60.5	60.5
	Male	173	38.2	38.2	98.7
	Prefer not to answer	6	1.3	1.3	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	100.0	

Which of the following best describes your personal monthly income?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below £3000	326	72.0	72.0	72.0
	£3000-£5000	101	22.3	22.3	94.3
	Above £5000	26	5.7	5.7	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	100.0	

What is your level of education?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor's degree	223	49.2	49.2	49.2
	Postgraduate level	125	27.6	27.6	76.8
	High school or below	55	12.1	12.1	89.0
	Diploma or vocational certificate	50	11.0	11.0	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	100.0	

Please specify your consumption level of luxury fashion brands.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Occasional consumer (purchasing luxury fashion brands sometimes or rarely)	348	76.8	76.8	76.8
	Regular consumer (purchasing luxury fashion brands always or often)	105	23.2	23.2	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	100.0	

Please specify the first attribute in defining luxury fashion.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Exceptional quality	208	45.9	45.9	45.9
	High price	74	16.3	16.3	62.3
	Exclusivity	71	15.7	15.7	77.9
	Creativity	42	9.3	9.3	87.2
	Hedonism (Beauty)	32	7.1	7.1	94.3
	Rarity	26	5.7	5.7	100.0
	Total	453	100.0	100.0	

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Please specify the first attribute in defining luxury fashion. * Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	453	100.0%	0	0.0%	453	100.0%

Please specify the first attribute in defining luxury fashion. * Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory Crosstabulation

Count

		Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory							Total
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree	
Please specify the first attribute in defining luxury fashion.	Creativity	5	2	7	8	9	6	5	42
	Exceptional quality	21	20	38	41	40	33	15	208
	Exclusivity	5	13	10	9	14	14	6	71
	Hedonism (Beauty)	1	4	3	10	10	2	2	32
	High price	2	9	10	16	19	10	8	74
	Rarity	0	4	2	6	6	7	1	26
Total		34	52	70	90	98	72	37	453

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	30.737 ^a	30	.428
Likelihood Ratio	33.646	30	.295
N of Valid Cases	453		

a. 12 cells (28.6%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.95.

Appendix 4

Mean, Standard Deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis Values							
Descriptive Statistics							
	N Statistic	Mean Statistic	Std. Deviation Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis	
				Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
I have strong possibility to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	453	4.91	1.680	-.696	.115	-.334	.229
I am likely to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	453	4.97	1.735	-.865	.115	-.154	.229
I have high intention to purchase sustainable luxury fashion brands if my budget allows	453	4.80	1.831	-.712	.115	-.525	.229
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands fits my personal values	453	4.74	1.694	-.573	.115	-.525	.229
Buying sustainable luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	453	4.98	1.631	-.820	.115	.041	.229
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I was aware of its sustainability activities	453	4.25	1.712	-.325	.115	-.800	.229
When I buy luxury fashion brand, I would have appreciated knowing about its sustainability activities	453	5.37	1.530	-1.080	.115	.719	.229
When I buy luxury fashion brand, it is important to me if luxury fashion brand is trying to be highly committed to well-defined sustainability principles	453	5.22	1.572	-.972	.115	.370	.229

Luxury fashion brands should consider moral standards on account of profit	453	5.65	1.274	-.966	.115	.798	.229
Luxury fashion brands should conduct ethical business despite being less economically efficient	453	5.72	1.326	-1.103	.115	.927	.229
Luxury fashion brands should define ethical standards and be faithful to them at all times	453	5.85	1.305	-1.346	.115	1.729	.229
Luxury fashion brands should obey the law and regulations in all circumstances	453	6.19	1.226	-1.738	.115	2.940	.229
Luxury fashion brands should offer job opportunities for vulnerable groups	453	5.40	1.404	-.682	.115	.008	.229
Luxury fashion brands should have a clear politics for solving urgent social and societal problems	453	4.92	1.608	-.550	.115	-.387	.229
Luxury fashion brands should reinforce their voluntary activities for society welfare	453	5.21	1.437	-.866	.115	.513	.229
Luxury fashion brands should play a key role in environmental protection	453	5.57	1.380	-1.131	.115	1.165	.229
Luxury fashion brands should consider environmental impacts when making decisions	453	5.97	1.264	-1.410	.115	1.903	.229
Luxury fashion brands are genuinely concerned about being sustainable	453	3.90	1.753	-.031	.115	-1.085	.229
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives because they feel morally obligated to help	453	4.31	1.663	-.332	.115	-.788	.229
Luxury fashion brands engage in sustainability initiatives in order to give back something to the community	453	3.99	1.648	-.045	.115	-.899	.229

Luxury fashion and sustainable development are contradictory	453	4.17	1.689	-.180	.115	-.833	.229
Luxury fashion has no future in a sustainably driven world	453	3.56	1.836	.156	.115	-1.132	.229
I feel happy when I wear a circular luxury fashion brand	453	4.97	1.489	-.654	.115	.154	.229
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands makes me feel good	453	4.98	1.517	-.757	.115	.210	.229
The stress is relieved by purchasing circular luxury fashion brands	453	4.17	1.753	-.231	.115	-.846	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands provide joy and pleasure	453	4.76	1.492	-.662	.115	.117	.229
Purchasing circular luxury fashion brands can give their owners social approval	453	4.87	1.494	-.631	.115	-.122	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands would make a good impression on other people	453	5.03	1.355	-.692	.115	.507	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands would improve the way I am perceived by my friends	453	4.08	1.789	-.192	.115	-.888	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands offer uniqueness	453	4.72	1.471	-.374	.115	-.433	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands have points of difference from general luxury fashion brands	453	5.04	1.334	-.560	.115	-.005	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands have many new features	453	4.51	1.415	-.232	.115	-.271	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands help save resources	453	5.12	1.472	-.722	.115	.031	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands have a positive impact on the environment in that they extend the life of discarded materials	453	5.20	1.425	-.685	.115	.019	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands are environmentally friendly	453	5.06	1.492	-.736	.115	.149	.229
Circular luxury fashion brands have more environmental benefits than other luxury fashion brands	453	5.30	1.395	-.787	.115	.256	.229
Valid N (listwise)	453						

Appendix 5

Measurement Model (Confirmatory Factor Analysis)

Outer loadings - Matrix

Zoom (60%)

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	ATTI	AWAR	EMOPEVAL	ENVEX	ENVIPEVAL	EPISPEVAL	INTATTR	LEGETEX	PERCON	PURIN	SOCEX	SOCPEVAL
ATTI1	0.929											
ATTI2	0.930											
AWAR1		0.807										
AWAR2		0.846										
AWAR3		0.862										
EMOPEVAL1			0.901									
EMOPEVAL2			0.923									
EMOPEVAL3			0.790									
EMOPEVAL4			0.890									
ENVEX1				0.939								
ENVEX2				0.833								
ENVIPEVAL1					0.886							
ENVIPEVAL2					0.907							
ENVIPEVAL3					0.898							
ENVIPEVAL4					0.837							
EPISPEVAL1						0.854						
EPISPEVAL2						0.817						
EPISPEVAL3						0.840						
INTATTR1							0.892					
INTATTR2							0.854					
INTATTR3							0.908					
LEGETEX1								0.887				
LEGETEX2								0.854				
LEGETEX3								0.912				
LEGETEX4								0.706				
PERCON1									0.860			
PERCON2									0.943			
PURIN2										0.939		
PURIN3										0.938		
SOCEX1											0.826	
SOCEX2											0.871	
SOCEX3											0.891	
SOCPEVAL1												0.882
SOCPEVAL2												0.869
SOCPEVAL3												0.799
PURIN1										0.894		

Outer loadings - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (67%)

Copy to Excel

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATT1 <- ATTI	0.929	0.929	0.008	119.144	0.000
ATT2 <- ATTI	0.930	0.929	0.008	115.186	0.000
AWAR1 <- AWAR	0.807	0.808	0.021	37.877	0.000
AWAR2 <- AWAR	0.846	0.845	0.021	39.628	0.000
AWAR3 <- AWAR	0.862	0.860	0.021	40.223	0.000
EMOPEVAL1 <- EMOPEVAL	0.901	0.901	0.012	78.254	0.000
EMOPEVAL2 <- EMOPEVAL	0.923	0.923	0.009	107.270	0.000
EMOPEVAL3 <- EMOPEVAL	0.790	0.789	0.024	33.270	0.000
EMOPEVAL4 <- EMOPEVAL	0.890	0.889	0.013	70.614	0.000
ENVEX1 <- ENVEX	0.939	0.939	0.023	40.994	0.000
ENVEX2 <- ENVEX	0.833	0.827	0.055	15.210	0.000
ENVIPEVAL1 <- ENVIPEVAL	0.886	0.885	0.017	53.564	0.000
ENVIPEVAL2 <- ENVIPEVAL	0.907	0.907	0.009	96.306	0.000
ENVIPEVAL3 <- ENVIPEVAL	0.898	0.898	0.011	78.979	0.000
ENVIPEVAL4 <- ENVIPEVAL	0.837	0.836	0.026	31.709	0.000
EPISPEVAL1 <- EPISPEVAL	0.854	0.853	0.020	43.087	0.000
EPISPEVAL2 <- EPISPEVAL	0.817	0.815	0.027	29.933	0.000
EPISPEVAL3 <- EPISPEVAL	0.840	0.840	0.020	41.170	0.000
INTATTR1 <- INTATTR	0.892	0.892	0.012	77.154	0.000
INTATTR2 <- INTATTR	0.854	0.853	0.021	41.042	0.000
INTATTR3 <- INTATTR	0.908	0.908	0.010	90.020	0.000
LEGETEX1 <- LEGETEX	0.887	0.887	0.037	23.860	0.000
LEGETEX2 <- LEGETEX	0.854	0.843	0.052	16.431	0.000
LEGETEX3 <- LEGETEX	0.912	0.907	0.034	27.198	0.000
LEGETEX4 <- LEGETEX	0.706	0.688	0.096	7.351	0.000
PERCON1 <- PERCON	0.860	0.821	0.176	4.898	0.000
PERCON2 <- PERCON	0.943	0.906	0.146	6.443	0.000
PURIN2 <- PURIN	0.939	0.939	0.007	140.541	0.000
PURIN3 <- PURIN	0.938	0.937	0.008	117.690	0.000
SOCEX1 <- SOCEX	0.826	0.826	0.026	31.311	0.000
SOCEX2 <- SOCEX	0.871	0.869	0.021	42.355	0.000
SOCEX3 <- SOCEX	0.891	0.890	0.018	50.460	0.000
SOCPEVAL1 <- SOCPEVAL	0.882	0.881	0.018	49.345	0.000
SOCPEVAL2 <- SOCPEVAL	0.869	0.869	0.018	47.945	0.000
SOCPEVAL3 <- SOCPEVAL	0.799	0.798	0.027	30.094	0.000
PURIN1 <- PURIN	0.894	0.894	0.017	52.397	0.000

Construct reliability and validity - Overview

Zoom (65%)

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	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
ATTI	0.843	0.843	0.927	0.864
AWAR	0.790	0.793	0.877	0.704
EMOPEVAL	0.900	0.913	0.930	0.770
ENVEX	0.744	0.862	0.881	0.788
ENVIPEVAL	0.905	0.919	0.933	0.778
EPISPEVAL	0.788	0.794	0.875	0.701
INTATTR	0.861	0.864	0.915	0.783
LEGETEX	0.870	0.948	0.907	0.712
PERCON	0.781	0.881	0.897	0.814
PURIN	0.914	0.919	0.946	0.854
SOCEX	0.829	0.834	0.898	0.745
SOCPEVAL	0.808	0.813	0.887	0.724

Average variance extracted (AVE) - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (115%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI	0.864	0.864	0.014	61.849	0.000
AWAR	0.704	0.703	0.022	32.293	0.000
EMOPEVAL	0.770	0.770	0.017	46.429	0.000
ENVEX	0.788	0.784	0.031	25.735	0.000
ENVIPEVAL	0.778	0.778	0.017	44.589	0.000
EPISPEVAL	0.701	0.700	0.022	31.454	0.000
INTATTR	0.783	0.782	0.016	47.617	0.000
LEGETEX	0.712	0.702	0.047	15.182	0.000
PERCON	0.814	0.774	0.111	7.321	0.000
PURIN	0.854	0.854	0.016	54.768	0.000
SOCEX	0.745	0.744	0.019	39.728	0.000
SOCPEVAL	0.724	0.723	0.019	38.687	0.000

Average variance extracted (AVE) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.864	0.864	-0.000	0.835	0.889
AWAR	0.704	0.703	-0.001	0.659	0.744
EMOPEVAL	0.770	0.770	-0.000	0.735	0.800
ENVEX	0.788	0.784	-0.004	0.716	0.837
ENVIPEVAL	0.778	0.778	-0.000	0.743	0.811
EPISPEVAL	0.701	0.700	-0.001	0.655	0.742
INTATTR	0.783	0.782	-0.001	0.749	0.813
LEGETEX	0.712	0.702	-0.010	0.626	0.764
PERCON	0.814	0.774	-0.041	0.692	0.859
PURIN	0.854	0.854	-0.000	0.819	0.882
SOCEX	0.745	0.744	-0.001	0.708	0.781
SOCPEVAL	0.724	0.723	-0.001	0.686	0.758

Average variance extracted (AVE) - Confidence intervals

Zoom (

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.864	0.864	0.835	0.890
AWAR	0.704	0.703	0.659	0.744
EMOPEVAL	0.770	0.770	0.736	0.800
ENVEX	0.788	0.784	0.713	0.835
ENVIPEVAL	0.778	0.778	0.743	0.811
EPISPEVAL	0.701	0.700	0.654	0.742
INTATTR	0.783	0.782	0.748	0.813
LEGETEX	0.712	0.702	0.602	0.760
PERCON	0.814	0.774	0.352	0.848
PURIN	0.854	0.854	0.821	0.883
SOCEX	0.745	0.744	0.706	0.779
SOCPEVAL	0.724	0.723	0.685	0.758

Cronbach's alpha - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (67%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI	0.843	0.842	0.019	44.863	0.000
AWAR	0.790	0.790	0.021	37.541	0.000
EMOPEVAL	0.900	0.899	0.009	95.071	0.000
ENVEX	0.744	0.743	0.036	20.418	0.000
ENVIPEVAL	0.905	0.905	0.010	95.166	0.000
EPISPEVAL	0.788	0.786	0.022	35.681	0.000
INTATTR	0.861	0.861	0.014	63.736	0.000
LEGETEX	0.870	0.869	0.015	57.652	0.000
PERCON	0.781	0.780	0.026	29.842	0.000
PURIN	0.914	0.914	0.011	84.284	0.000
SOCEX	0.829	0.828	0.017	49.263	0.000
SOCPEVAL	0.808	0.808	0.018	44.764	0.000

Cronbach's alpha - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.843	0.842	-0.000	0.802	0.876
AWAR	0.790	0.790	-0.001	0.745	0.827
EMOPEVAL	0.900	0.899	-0.000	0.879	0.916
ENVEX	0.744	0.743	-0.002	0.664	0.807
ENVIPEVAL	0.905	0.905	-0.000	0.885	0.922
EPISPEVAL	0.788	0.786	-0.001	0.740	0.827
INTATTR	0.861	0.861	-0.000	0.832	0.885
LEGETEX	0.870	0.869	-0.001	0.838	0.896
PERCON	0.781	0.780	-0.001	0.726	0.827
PURIN	0.914	0.914	-0.000	0.889	0.933
SOCEX	0.829	0.828	-0.001	0.792	0.858
SOCPEVAL	0.808	0.808	-0.000	0.769	0.840

Cronbach's alpha - Confidence intervals

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.843	0.842	0.802	0.876
AWAR	0.790	0.790	0.746	0.828
EMOPEVAL	0.900	0.899	0.880	0.916
ENVEX	0.744	0.743	0.664	0.807
ENVIPEVAL	0.905	0.905	0.886	0.923
EPISPEVAL	0.788	0.786	0.739	0.827
INTATTR	0.861	0.861	0.832	0.885
LEGETEX	0.870	0.869	0.837	0.896
PERCON	0.781	0.780	0.726	0.828
PURIN	0.914	0.914	0.891	0.934
SOCEX	0.829	0.828	0.793	0.859
SOCPEVAL	0.808	0.808	0.770	0.840

Composite reliability (rho_c) - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (115%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI	0.927	0.927	0.008	115.083	0.000
AWAR	0.877	0.876	0.011	77.311	0.000
EMOPEVAL	0.930	0.930	0.006	151.182	0.000
ENVEX	0.881	0.878	0.021	42.887	0.000
ENVIPEVAL	0.933	0.933	0.006	147.305	0.000
EPISPEVAL	0.875	0.875	0.012	74.784	0.000
INTATTR	0.915	0.915	0.008	121.242	0.000
LEGETEX	0.907	0.901	0.035	25.597	0.000
PERCON	0.897	0.857	0.131	6.834	0.000
PURIN	0.946	0.946	0.006	147.283	0.000
SOCEX	0.898	0.897	0.009	98.054	0.000
SOCPEVAL	0.887	0.886	0.009	93.684	0.000

Composite reliability (rho_c) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.927	0.927	-0.000	0.910	0.941
AWAR	0.877	0.876	-0.001	0.853	0.897
EMOPEVAL	0.930	0.930	-0.000	0.917	0.941
ENVEX	0.881	0.878	-0.003	0.831	0.911
ENVIPEVAL	0.933	0.933	-0.000	0.920	0.945
EPISPEVAL	0.875	0.874	-0.001	0.851	0.896
INTATTR	0.915	0.915	-0.000	0.899	0.929
LEGETEX	0.907	0.901	-0.007	0.865	0.928
PERCON	0.897	0.858	-0.040	0.808	0.924
PURIN	0.946	0.946	-0.000	0.931	0.957
SOCEX	0.898	0.897	-0.001	0.879	0.914
SOCPEVAL	0.887	0.887	-0.000	0.867	0.904

Composite reliability (rho_c) - Confidence intervals

Zoom (107%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.927	0.927	0.910	0.942
AWAR	0.877	0.876	0.853	0.897
EMOPEVAL	0.930	0.930	0.917	0.941
ENVEX	0.881	0.878	0.828	0.910
ENVIPEVAL	0.933	0.933	0.920	0.945
EPISPEVAL	0.875	0.874	0.850	0.896
INTATTR	0.915	0.915	0.899	0.929
LEGETEX	0.907	0.901	0.851	0.926
PERCON	0.897	0.858	0.399	0.918
PURIN	0.946	0.946	0.932	0.958
SOCEX	0.898	0.897	0.878	0.914
SOCPEVAL	0.887	0.887	0.867	0.904

Composite reliability (rho_a) - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (117%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI	0.843	0.843	0.019	44.993	0.000
AWAR	0.793	0.796	0.022	36.234	0.000
EMOPEVAL	0.913	0.915	0.010	95.445	0.000
ENVEX	0.863	0.975	1.191	0.725	0.469
ENVIPEVAL	0.919	0.923	0.011	83.888	0.000
EPISPEVAL	0.794	0.799	0.024	33.329	0.000
INTATTR	0.864	0.868	0.014	62.867	0.000
LEGETEX	0.948	0.926	0.177	5.344	0.000
PERCON	0.880	1.528	46.088	0.019	0.985
PURIN	0.921	0.921	0.009	102.571	0.000
SOCEX	0.834	0.844	0.023	35.493	0.000
SOCPEVAL	0.813	0.819	0.021	38.923	0.000

Composite reliability (rho_a) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.843	0.843	0.000	0.801	0.876
AWAR	0.793	0.796	0.004	0.740	0.829
EMOPEVAL	0.913	0.915	0.001	0.891	0.929
ENVEX	0.863	0.975	0.112	0.718	1.651
ENVIPEVAL	0.919	0.923	0.004	0.893	0.936
EPISPEVAL	0.794	0.799	0.005	0.739	0.833
INTATTR	0.864	0.868	0.004	0.829	0.885
LEGETEX	0.948	0.926	-0.022	0.880	1.096
PERCON	0.880	1.528	0.648	-4.903	7.721
PURIN	0.921	0.921	0.000	0.902	0.937
SOCEX	0.834	0.844	0.010	0.786	0.867
SOCPEVAL	0.813	0.819	0.006	0.764	0.847

Composite reliability (rho_a) - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (117%)[Copy to](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.843	0.843	0.803	0.877
AWAR	0.793	0.796	0.751	0.838
EMOPEVAL	0.913	0.915	0.895	0.933
ENVEX	0.863	0.975	0.722	1.707
ENVIPEVAL	0.919	0.923	0.901	0.945
EPISPEVAL	0.794	0.799	0.751	0.846
INTATTR	0.864	0.868	0.838	0.893
LEGETEX	0.948	0.926	0.716	1.043
PERCON	0.880	1.528	-5.988	6.028
PURIN	0.921	0.921	0.903	0.938
SOCEX	0.834	0.844	0.802	0.895
SOCPEVAL	0.813	0.819	0.779	0.861

Construct reliability and validity - Overview

Zoom (67%)

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	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
ATTI	0.843	0.843	0.927	0.864
AWAR	0.790	0.793	0.877	0.704
EXPEC	0.897	0.912	0.912	0.538
INTATTR	0.861	0.864	0.915	0.783
PERCON	0.781	0.880	0.897	0.814
PERVAL	0.936	0.946	0.943	0.545
PURINT	0.914	0.919	0.946	0.854

Average variance extracted (AVE) - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (102%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI	0.864	0.864	0.014	61.849	0.000
AWAR	0.704	0.703	0.022	32.293	0.000
EXP	0.538	0.533	0.034	15.921	0.000
INTATTR	0.783	0.782	0.016	47.618	0.000
PERCON	0.814	0.774	0.111	7.328	0.000
PERVAL	0.545	0.544	0.023	24.101	0.000
PURIN	0.854	0.854	0.016	54.713	0.000

Average variance extracted (AVE) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.864	0.864	-0.000	0.835	0.889
AWAR	0.704	0.703	-0.001	0.659	0.744
EXP	0.538	0.533	-0.005	0.467	0.597
INTATTR	0.783	0.782	-0.001	0.749	0.813
PERCON	0.814	0.774	-0.040	0.691	0.859
PERVAL	0.545	0.544	-0.000	0.500	0.588
PURIN	0.854	0.854	-0.000	0.819	0.882

Average variance extracted (AVE) - Confidence intervals [Zoom](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.864	0.864	0.835	0.890
AWAR	0.704	0.703	0.659	0.744
EXP	0.538	0.533	0.460	0.593
INTATTR	0.783	0.782	0.748	0.813
PERCON	0.814	0.774	0.356	0.848
PERVAL	0.545	0.544	0.500	0.588
PURIN	0.854	0.854	0.821	0.883

Cronbach's alpha - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values [Zoom \(102%\)](#)[Copy to Excel](#)[Copy to R](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI	0.843	0.842	0.019	44.863	0.000
AWAR	0.790	0.790	0.021	37.541	0.000
EXP	0.897	0.896	0.011	81.927	0.000
INTATTR	0.861	0.861	0.014	63.736	0.000
PERCON	0.781	0.780	0.026	29.842	0.000
PERVAL	0.936	0.936	0.006	162.348	0.000
PURIN	0.914	0.914	0.011	84.284	0.000

Cronbach's alpha - Confidence intervals bias corrected [Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.843	0.842	-0.000	0.802	0.876
AWAR	0.790	0.790	-0.001	0.745	0.827
EXP	0.897	0.896	-0.001	0.874	0.916
INTATTR	0.861	0.861	-0.000	0.832	0.885
PERCON	0.781	0.780	-0.001	0.726	0.827
PERVAL	0.936	0.936	-0.000	0.924	0.946
PURIN	0.914	0.914	-0.000	0.889	0.933

Cronbach's alpha - Confidence intervals

Zoom (107%)

Co

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.843	0.842	0.802	0.876
AWAR	0.790	0.790	0.746	0.828
EXP	0.897	0.896	0.873	0.916
INTATTR	0.861	0.861	0.832	0.885
PERCON	0.781	0.780	0.726	0.828
PERVAL	0.936	0.936	0.923	0.946
PURIN	0.914	0.914	0.891	0.934

Composite reliability (rho_c) - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (102%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI	0.927	0.927	0.008	115.083	0.000
AWAR	0.877	0.876	0.011	77.310	0.000
EXP	0.912	0.910	0.013	68.235	0.000
INTATTR	0.915	0.915	0.008	121.243	0.000
PERCON	0.897	0.858	0.131	6.848	0.000
PERVAL	0.943	0.943	0.005	190.242	0.000
PURIN	0.946	0.946	0.006	147.096	0.000

Composite reliability (rho_c) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoc

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.927	0.927	-0.000	0.910	0.941
AWAR	0.877	0.876	-0.001	0.853	0.897
EXP	0.912	0.910	-0.003	0.885	0.930
INTATTR	0.915	0.915	-0.000	0.899	0.929
PERCON	0.897	0.858	-0.040	0.808	0.924
PERVAL	0.943	0.943	-0.000	0.933	0.952
PURIN	0.946	0.946	-0.000	0.931	0.957

Composite reliability (rho_c) - Confidence intervals

Zoom (107%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.927	0.927	0.910	0.942
AWAR	0.877	0.876	0.853	0.897
EXP	0.912	0.910	0.881	0.929
INTATTR	0.915	0.915	0.899	0.929
PERCON	0.897	0.858	0.398	0.918
PERVAL	0.943	0.943	0.933	0.952
PURIN	0.946	0.946	0.932	0.958

Composite reliability (rho_a) - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI	0.843	0.843	0.019	44.993	0.000
AWAR	0.793	0.796	0.022	36.235	0.000
EXP	0.912	0.913	0.017	54.527	0.000
INTATTR	0.864	0.868	0.014	62.869	0.000
PERCON	0.880	0.613	42.273	0.021	0.983
PERVAL	0.946	0.947	0.005	182.440	0.000
PURIN	0.921	0.921	0.009	103.521	0.000

Composite reliability (rho_a) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.843	0.843	0.000	0.801	0.876
AWAR	0.793	0.796	0.004	0.740	0.829
EXP	0.912	0.913	0.002	0.865	0.933
INTATTR	0.864	0.868	0.004	0.829	0.885
PERCON	0.880	0.613	-0.267	-4.903	7.605
PERVAL	0.946	0.947	0.001	0.934	0.955
PURIN	0.921	0.921	0.000	0.901	0.937

Composite reliability (rho_a) - Confidence intervals

Zoom (107%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI	0.843	0.843	0.803	0.877
AWAR	0.793	0.796	0.751	0.838
EXP	0.912	0.913	0.881	0.940
INTATTR	0.864	0.868	0.838	0.893
PERCON	0.880	0.613	-6.042	5.982
PERVAL	0.946	0.947	0.937	0.957
PURIN	0.921	0.921	0.903	0.938

Discriminant validity - Cross loadings

Zoom (65%)

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	ATTI	AWAR	EMOPEVAL	ENVEX	ENVIPEVAL	EPISPEVAL	INTATTR	LEGETEX	PERCON	PURIN	SOCEX	SOCPEVAL
ATTI1	0.929	0.567	0.607	0.319	0.466	0.452	0.414	0.289	-0.084	0.715	0.315	0.417
ATTI2	0.930	0.517	0.641	0.363	0.464	0.490	0.409	0.271	-0.134	0.715	0.306	0.451
AWAR1	0.479	0.807	0.445	0.227	0.295	0.401	0.534	0.149	0.116	0.476	0.356	0.406
AWAR2	0.501	0.846	0.479	0.539	0.447	0.408	0.195	0.506	-0.083	0.417	0.466	0.374
AWAR3	0.486	0.862	0.479	0.524	0.407	0.442	0.312	0.534	-0.016	0.382	0.513	0.412
EMOPEVAL1	0.616	0.518	0.901	0.375	0.545	0.574	0.365	0.327	-0.055	0.525	0.318	0.566
EMOPEVAL2	0.642	0.533	0.923	0.357	0.589	0.604	0.379	0.298	-0.094	0.528	0.280	0.602
EMOPEVAL3	0.503	0.436	0.790	0.251	0.441	0.564	0.433	0.159	0.120	0.388	0.300	0.594
EMOPEVAL4	0.583	0.463	0.890	0.343	0.519	0.614	0.368	0.264	-0.096	0.492	0.276	0.608
ENVEX1	0.362	0.482	0.372	0.939	0.316	0.290	0.188	0.517	-0.029	0.265	0.616	0.275
ENVEX2	0.277	0.396	0.298	0.833	0.351	0.222	0.006	0.712	-0.113	0.165	0.492	0.197
ENVIPEVAL1	0.424	0.368	0.523	0.299	0.886	0.570	0.275	0.312	-0.045	0.306	0.240	0.475
ENVIPEVAL2	0.449	0.402	0.546	0.360	0.907	0.554	0.251	0.388	-0.063	0.368	0.299	0.486
ENVIPEVAL3	0.465	0.410	0.523	0.264	0.898	0.529	0.358	0.287	-0.060	0.365	0.235	0.525
ENVIPEVAL4	0.426	0.418	0.532	0.385	0.837	0.540	0.187	0.422	-0.063	0.272	0.320	0.496
EPISPEVAL1	0.418	0.386	0.575	0.241	0.540	0.854	0.411	0.220	0.038	0.321	0.308	0.607
EPISPEVAL2	0.446	0.429	0.584	0.309	0.601	0.817	0.313	0.347	-0.014	0.329	0.288	0.585
EPISPEVAL3	0.410	0.428	0.529	0.196	0.430	0.840	0.496	0.130	0.132	0.392	0.292	0.630
INTATTR1	0.393	0.369	0.401	0.051	0.284	0.458	0.892	-0.049	0.138	0.372	0.240	0.398
INTATTR2	0.380	0.375	0.357	0.171	0.249	0.397	0.854	0.058	0.074	0.346	0.226	0.370
INTATTR3	0.403	0.389	0.393	0.131	0.284	0.449	0.908	-0.006	0.087	0.378	0.262	0.342
LEGETEX1	0.276	0.447	0.293	0.538	0.346	0.287	0.027	0.887	0.004	0.190	0.474	0.228
LEGETEX2	0.242	0.384	0.235	0.595	0.333	0.175	0.004	0.854	-0.028	0.114	0.451	0.177
LEGETEX3	0.288	0.422	0.309	0.621	0.368	0.257	0.019	0.912	-0.092	0.181	0.475	0.218
LEGETEX4	0.181	0.197	0.116	0.487	0.273	0.126	-0.134	0.706	-0.152	0.069	0.300	0.087
PERCON1	-0.038	0.034	0.001	-0.014	0.026	0.106	0.137	0.017	0.860	-0.061	0.162	0.116
PERCON2	-0.152	-0.003	-0.071	-0.093	-0.116	0.032	0.080	-0.104	0.943	-0.093	0.106	0.069
PURIN2	0.732	0.496	0.532	0.246	0.345	0.399	0.393	0.155	-0.082	0.939	0.269	0.367
PURIN3	0.754	0.483	0.530	0.237	0.355	0.386	0.407	0.174	-0.088	0.938	0.278	0.368
SOCEX1	0.286	0.430	0.255	0.529	0.255	0.271	0.167	0.534	0.079	0.238	0.826	0.244
SOCEX2	0.281	0.459	0.299	0.526	0.223	0.301	0.273	0.372	0.181	0.239	0.871	0.302
SOCEX3	0.298	0.469	0.306	0.580	0.312	0.340	0.268	0.436	0.107	0.269	0.891	0.284
SOCPEVAL1	0.393	0.411	0.600	0.233	0.509	0.614	0.319	0.218	0.026	0.324	0.252	0.882
SOCPEVAL2	0.430	0.439	0.576	0.274	0.542	0.637	0.338	0.264	0.045	0.345	0.322	0.869
SOCPEVAL3	0.366	0.358	0.536	0.183	0.370	0.604	0.416	0.087	0.186	0.302	0.240	0.799
PURIN1	0.642	0.438	0.475	0.214	0.344	0.376	0.341	0.172	-0.075	0.894	0.253	0.318

Discriminant validity - Fornell-Larcker criterion

Zoom (75%)

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	ATTI	AWAR	EMOPEVAL	ENVEX	ENVIPEVAL	EPISPEVAL	INTATTR	LEGETEX	PERCON	PURIN	SOCEX	SOCPEVAL
ATTI	0.930											
AWAR	0.584	0.839										
EMOPEVAL	0.671	0.557	0.878									
ENVEX	0.367	0.500	0.382	0.888								
ENVIPEVAL	0.500	0.452	0.600	0.366	0.882							
EPISPEVAL	0.506	0.497	0.670	0.294	0.619	0.837						
INTATTR	0.443	0.427	0.434	0.131	0.308	0.492	0.885					
LEGETEX	0.302	0.455	0.305	0.659	0.394	0.270	-0.000	0.844				
PERCON	-0.117	0.013	-0.046	-0.068	-0.066	0.068	0.113	-0.062	0.902			
PURIN	0.769	0.512	0.556	0.252	0.376	0.419	0.413	0.180	-0.089	0.924		
SOCEX	0.334	0.525	0.333	0.633	0.307	0.353	0.275	0.517	0.141	0.289	0.863	
SOCPEVAL	0.467	0.475	0.671	0.273	0.561	0.727	0.418	0.227	0.096	0.381	0.321	0.851

Discriminant validity - Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) - Matrix

Zoom (82%)

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	ATTI	AWAR	EMOPEVAL	ENVEX	ENVIPEVAL	EPISPEVAL	INTATTR	LEGETEX	PERCON	PURIN	SOCEX	SOCPEVAL
ATTI												
AWAR	0.713											
EMOPEVAL	0.767	0.658										
ENVEX	0.453	0.659	0.452									
ENVIPEVAL	0.572	0.540	0.662	0.461								
EPISPEVAL	0.622	0.627	0.800	0.380	0.743							
INTATTR	0.520	0.502	0.500	0.169	0.343	0.589						
LEGETEX	0.340	0.544	0.314	0.859	0.444	0.310	0.088					
PERCON	0.129	0.106	0.119	0.096	0.093	0.111	0.146	0.128				
PURIN	0.875	0.595	0.607	0.291	0.409	0.489	0.464	0.183	0.101			
SOCEX	0.400	0.655	0.387	0.789	0.356	0.435	0.323	0.592	0.185	0.331		
SOCPEVAL	0.565	0.590	0.792	0.338	0.652	0.908	0.505	0.260	0.133	0.442	0.390	

Discriminant validity - Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) - Matrix

Zoom (110%)

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	ATTI	AWAR	EXPECT	INTATTR	PERCON	PERVAL	PURIN
ATTI							
AWAR	0.713						
EXPECT	0.431	0.679					
INTATTR	0.520	0.502	0.206				
PERCON	0.129	0.106	0.157	0.146			
PERVAL	0.716	0.676	0.469	0.528	0.126		
PURIN	0.875	0.595	0.287	0.464	0.101	0.550	

Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (145%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
AWAR <-> ATTI	0.713	0.712	-0.001	0.627	0.790
EMOPEVAL <-> ATTI	0.767	0.768	0.000	0.690	0.836
EMOPEVAL <-> AWAR	0.658	0.658	-0.001	0.565	0.743
ENVEX <-> ATTI	0.453	0.453	0.000	0.332	0.558
ENVEX <-> AWAR	0.659	0.660	0.001	0.549	0.757
ENVEX <-> EMOPEVAL	0.452	0.452	-0.001	0.333	0.556
ENVIPEVAL <-> ATTI	0.572	0.572	-0.000	0.470	0.661
ENVIPEVAL <-> AWAR	0.540	0.539	-0.001	0.431	0.639
ENVIPEVAL <-> EMOPEVAL	0.662	0.662	0.000	0.578	0.732
ENVIPEVAL <-> ENVEX	0.461	0.460	-0.000	0.339	0.569
EPISPEVAL <-> ATTI	0.622	0.622	-0.000	0.524	0.709
EPISPEVAL <-> AWAR	0.627	0.627	-0.001	0.521	0.725
EPISPEVAL <-> EMOPEVAL	0.800	0.801	0.001	0.725	0.865
EPISPEVAL <-> ENVEX	0.380	0.379	-0.001	0.259	0.499
EPISPEVAL <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.743	0.743	-0.000	0.657	0.822

Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (145%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
INTATTR <-> ATTI	0.520	0.521	0.000	0.425	0.605
INTATTR <-> AWAR	0.502	0.502	-0.000	0.408	0.585
INTATTR <-> EMOPEVAL	0.500	0.500	0.001	0.399	0.587
INTATTR <-> ENVEX	0.169	0.179	0.010	0.095	0.238
INTATTR <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.343	0.342	-0.001	0.240	0.436
INTATTR <-> EPISPEVAL	0.589	0.589	0.001	0.488	0.678
LEGETEX <-> ATTI	0.340	0.338	-0.002	0.226	0.451
LEGETEX <-> AWAR	0.544	0.546	0.002	0.449	0.630
LEGETEX <-> EMOPEVAL	0.314	0.315	0.001	0.210	0.413
LEGETEX <-> ENVEX	0.859	0.859	0.000	0.780	0.921
LEGETEX <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.444	0.442	-0.002	0.336	0.540
LEGETEX <-> EPISPEVAL	0.310	0.314	0.004	0.199	0.414
LEGETEX <-> INTATTR	0.088	0.107	0.019	0.043	0.111

Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (145%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PERCON <-> ATTI	0.129	0.142	0.013	0.057	0.224
PERCON <-> AWAR	0.106	0.125	0.019	0.044	0.147
PERCON <-> EMOPEVAL	0.119	0.130	0.011	0.073	0.168
PERCON <-> ENVEX	0.096	0.118	0.023	0.033	0.159
PERCON <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.093	0.109	0.016	0.035	0.141
PERCON <-> EPISPEVAL	0.111	0.132	0.021	0.044	0.172
PERCON <-> INTATTR	0.146	0.153	0.007	0.054	0.262
PERCON <-> LEGETEX	0.128	0.137	0.009	0.075	0.192
PURIN <-> ATTI	0.875	0.874	-0.000	0.825	0.916
PURIN <-> AWAR	0.595	0.594	-0.001	0.495	0.683
PURIN <-> EMOPEVAL	0.607	0.607	0.000	0.514	0.681
PURIN <-> ENVEX	0.291	0.291	0.000	0.169	0.406
PURIN <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.409	0.408	-0.001	0.305	0.507
PURIN <-> EPISPEVAL	0.489	0.489	0.000	0.383	0.587
PURIN <-> INTATTR	0.464	0.464	-0.000	0.363	0.552
PURIN <-> LEGETEX	0.183	0.184	0.001	0.083	0.292

Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (145%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURIN <-> PERCON	0.101	0.107	0.007	0.026	0.209
SOCEX <-> ATTI	0.400	0.400	0.000	0.279	0.512
SOCEX <-> AWAR	0.655	0.656	0.001	0.551	0.743
SOCEX <-> EMOPEVAL	0.387	0.387	-0.000	0.269	0.496
SOCEX <-> ENVEX	0.789	0.789	-0.000	0.691	0.876
SOCEX <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.356	0.354	-0.001	0.236	0.468
SOCEX <-> EPISPEVAL	0.435	0.436	0.000	0.304	0.546
SOCEX <-> INTATTR	0.323	0.324	0.001	0.215	0.432
SOCEX <-> LEGETEX	0.592	0.589	-0.002	0.489	0.681
SOCEX <-> PERCON	0.185	0.188	0.003	0.085	0.287
SOCEX <-> PURIN	0.331	0.331	0.001	0.209	0.438
SOCPEVAL <-> ATTI	0.565	0.564	-0.000	0.463	0.654
SOCPEVAL <-> AWAR	0.590	0.589	-0.001	0.475	0.694
SOCPEVAL <-> EMOPEVAL	0.792	0.793	0.000	0.717	0.858
SOCPEVAL <-> ENVEX	0.338	0.338	0.000	0.215	0.451
SOCPEVAL <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.652	0.651	-0.001	0.548	0.739

SOCPEVAL <-> EPISPEVAL	0.908	0.908	0.000	0.844	0.962
SOCPEVAL <-> INTATTR	0.505	0.505	0.000	0.398	0.598
SOCPEVAL <-> LEGETEX	0.260	0.260	-0.000	0.151	0.365
SOCPEVAL <-> PERCON	0.133	0.153	0.019	0.065	0.216
SOCPEVAL <-> PURIN	0.442	0.441	-0.001	0.333	0.539
SOCPEVAL <-> SOCEX	0.390	0.390	0.000	0.265	0.504

Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) - Confidence intervals

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
AWAR <-> ATTI	0.713	0.712	0.627	0.790
EMOPEVAL <-> ATTI	0.767	0.768	0.693	0.838
EMOPEVAL <-> AWAR	0.658	0.658	0.566	0.745
ENVEX <-> ATTI	0.453	0.453	0.336	0.561
ENVEX <-> AWAR	0.659	0.660	0.553	0.761
ENVEX <-> EMOPEVAL	0.452	0.452	0.335	0.559
ENVIPEVAL <-> ATTI	0.572	0.572	0.471	0.663
ENVIPEVAL <-> AWAR	0.540	0.539	0.432	0.639
ENVIPEVAL <-> EMOPEVAL	0.662	0.662	0.581	0.734
ENVIPEVAL <-> ENVEX	0.461	0.460	0.340	0.572
EPISPEVAL <-> ATTI	0.622	0.622	0.526	0.711
EPISPEVAL <-> AWAR	0.627	0.627	0.522	0.725
EPISPEVAL <-> EMOPEVAL	0.800	0.801	0.729	0.867
EPISPEVAL <-> ENVEX	0.380	0.379	0.257	0.497
EPISPEVAL <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.743	0.743	0.657	0.823

INTATTR <-> ATTI	0.520	0.521	0.428	0.608
INTATTR <-> AWAR	0.502	0.502	0.410	0.587
INTATTR <-> EMOPEVAL	0.500	0.500	0.405	0.589
INTATTR <-> ENVEX	0.169	0.179	0.110	0.262
INTATTR <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.343	0.342	0.242	0.438
INTATTR <-> EPISPEVAL	0.589	0.589	0.491	0.681
LEGETEX <-> ATTI	0.340	0.338	0.225	0.450
LEGETEX <-> AWAR	0.544	0.546	0.454	0.635
LEGETEX <-> EMOPEVAL	0.314	0.315	0.213	0.415
LEGETEX <-> ENVEX	0.859	0.859	0.785	0.923
LEGETEX <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.444	0.442	0.334	0.540
LEGETEX <-> EPISPEVAL	0.310	0.314	0.206	0.423
LEGETEX <-> INTATTR	0.088	0.107	0.068	0.158
PERCON <-> ATTI	0.129	0.142	0.065	0.243
PERCON <-> AWAR	0.106	0.125	0.068	0.190
PERCON <-> EMOPEVAL	0.119	0.130	0.083	0.191

PERCON <-> ENVEX	0.096	0.118	0.054	0.214
PERCON <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.093	0.109	0.054	0.178
PERCON <-> EPISPEVAL	0.111	0.132	0.067	0.226
PERCON <-> INTATTR	0.146	0.153	0.057	0.271
PERCON <-> LEGETEX	0.128	0.137	0.083	0.206
PURIN <-> ATTI	0.875	0.874	0.827	0.917
PURIN <-> AWAR	0.595	0.594	0.497	0.685
PURIN <-> EMOPEVAL	0.607	0.607	0.519	0.684
PURIN <-> ENVEX	0.291	0.291	0.170	0.408
PURIN <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.409	0.408	0.304	0.507
PURIN <-> EPISPEVAL	0.489	0.489	0.385	0.588
PURIN <-> INTATTR	0.464	0.464	0.368	0.554
PURIN <-> LEGETEX	0.183	0.184	0.084	0.294
PURIN <-> PERCON	0.101	0.107	0.028	0.216
SOCEX <-> ATTI	0.400	0.400	0.279	0.512

SOCEX <-> AWAR	0.655	0.656	0.554	0.746
SOCEX <-> EMOPEVAL	0.387	0.387	0.271	0.498
SOCEX <-> ENVEX	0.789	0.789	0.693	0.878
SOCEX <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.356	0.354	0.235	0.467
SOCEX <-> EPISPEVAL	0.435	0.436	0.311	0.551
SOCEX <-> INTATTR	0.323	0.324	0.215	0.432
SOCEX <-> LEGETEX	0.592	0.589	0.489	0.680
SOCEX <-> PERCON	0.185	0.188	0.089	0.292
SOCEX <-> PURIN	0.331	0.331	0.214	0.442
SOCPEVAL <-> ATTI	0.565	0.564	0.466	0.655
SOCPEVAL <-> AWAR	0.590	0.589	0.475	0.695
SOCPEVAL <-> EMOPEVAL	0.792	0.793	0.720	0.861
SOCPEVAL <-> ENVEX	0.338	0.338	0.217	0.453
SOCPEVAL <-> ENVIPEVAL	0.652	0.651	0.549	0.740
SOCPEVAL <-> EPISPEVAL	0.908	0.908	0.847	0.963
SOCPEVAL <-> INTATTR	0.505	0.505	0.403	0.601
SOCPEVAL <-> LEGETEX	0.260	0.260	0.152	0.366
SOCPEVAL <-> PERCON	0.133	0.153	0.080	0.257
SOCPEVAL <-> PURIN	0.442	0.441	0.334	0.540
SOCPEVAL <-> SOCEX	0.390	0.390	0.268	0.507

Model Fit

Model fit

[Zoom](#) (137%)

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.063	0.063
d_ULS	2.655	2.655
d_G	0.913	0.913
Chi-square	2,574.652	2,574.652
NFI	0.781	0.781

SRMR - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (155%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	95%	99%
Saturated model	0.063	0.032	0.035	0.046
Estimated model	0.063	0.032	0.035	0.046

d_ULS - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (155%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	95%	99%
Saturated model	2.654	0.683	0.814	1.408
Estimated model	2.654	0.683	0.814	1.408

d_G - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (155%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	95%	99%
Saturated model	0.913	0.629	0.684	0.844
Estimated model	0.913	0.629	0.684	0.844

Inner VIF

Collinearity statistics (VIF) - Inner model - Matrix

Zoom (82%)

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	ATTI	AWAR	EMOPEVAL	ENVEX	ENVIPEVAL	EPISPEVAL	INTATTR	LEGETEX	PERCON	PURIN	SOCEX	SOCPEVAL
ATTI										2.205		
AWAR										2.179		
EMOPEVAL										2.944		
ENVEX										2.380		
ENVIPEVAL										2.010		
EPISPEVAL										2.842		
INTATTR										1.632		
LEGETEX										2.089		
PERCON										1.134		
PURIN												
SOCEX										2.056		
SOCPEVAL										2.541		

R-square of the Model

R-square - Overview

Zoom

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURIN	0.613	0.603

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (102%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURIN	0.614	0.624	0.034	17.918	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURIN	0.614	0.624	0.010	0.528	0.668

R-square - Confidence intervals

Zoom

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURIN	0.614	0.624	0.554	0.688

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (102%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURIN	0.604	0.615	0.035	17.208	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURIN	0.604	0.615	0.011	0.516	0.660

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURIN	0.604	0.615	0.543	0.680

Structural Model

PERCON - PURINT

Inner model: Path coefficients and p values | Constructs: R-square | Outer model: P values | Highlight paths: off

Zoom (100%)

Outer model: P values | Inner model: Path coefficients and t values | Constructs: R-square | Highlight paths: off

Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values | Zoom (102%) | Copy to Excel | Copy to R

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
PERCON -> PURIN	-0.089	-0.098	0.053	1.674	0.094

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected | Zoom (107%) | Copy to Excel

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PERCON -> PURINT	-0.089	-0.098	-0.010	-0.159	0.113

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals | Zoom (102%) | Copy to Excel

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PERCON -> PURIN	-0.089	-0.098	-0.189	0.064

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURIN	0.008	0.006

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.008	0.012	0.009	0.862	0.389

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.008	0.012	0.005	0.001	0.024

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(150%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.008	0.012	0.002	0.036

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.006	0.010	0.009	0.620	0.536

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.006	0.010	0.005	-0.002	0.022

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.006	0.010	-0.001	0.034

f-square - Matrix

	PERCON	PURIN
PERCON		0.008
PURIN		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PERCON -> PURIN	0.008	0.013	0.009	0.836	0.403

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PERCON -> PURIN	0.008	-0.098	-0.106	-0.041	0.161

f-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PERCON -> PURIN	0.008	0.013	0.002	0.037

AWAR - PURIN

Outer model

P values

Inner model

Path coefficients and p values

Constructs

R-square

Highlight paths

off

Zoom (100%)

Outer model

P values

Inner model

Path coefficients and t values

Constructs

R-square

Highlight pa

off

Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (102%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
AWAR -> PURIN	0.512	0.514	0.041	12.573	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

Copy to

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
AWAR -> PURINT	0.512	0.514	0.002	0.427	0.588

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
AWAR -> PURINT	0.512	0.514	0.432	0.592

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURIN	0.262	0.261

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.262	0.266	0.042	6.280	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.262	0.266	0.003	0.182	0.345

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.262	0.266	0.187	0.350

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.261	0.264	0.042	6.228	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.261	0.264	0.003	0.181	0.344

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.261	0.264	0.185	0.349

f-square - Matrix

	AWAR	PURIN
AWAR		0.356
PURIN		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
AWAR -> PURINT	0.356	0.366	0.079	4.493	0.000

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
AWAR -> PURINT	0.356	0.514	0.158	0.359	0.359

f-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
AWAR -> PURINT	0.356	0.366	0.229	0.539

EXPECT - PURINT

Outer model

P values

Inner model

Path coefficients and p values

Constructs

R-square

Highlight paths

off

Zoom (100%)

Outer model

P values

Inner model

Path coefficients and t values

Constructs

R-square

High

off

Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (102%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
EXPEC -> PURINT	0.286	0.295	0.046	6.274	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

Copy

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
EXP -> PURINT	0.286	0.295	0.009	0.185	0.367

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
EXP -> PURINT	0.286	0.295	0.205	0.383

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURINT	0.082	0.080

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.082	0.089	0.027	3.027	0.002

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.082	0.089	0.008	0.034	0.134

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.082	0.089	0.042	0.147

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.080	0.087	0.027	2.945	0.003

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.080	0.087	0.008	0.032	0.133

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.080	0.087	0.040	0.145

f-square - Matrix

	EXPECT	PURIN
EXPECT		0.089
PURIN		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
EXPECT -> PURINT	0.089	0.099	0.033	2.689	0.007

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
EXP -> PURINT	0.089	0.295	0.206	0.112	0.112

f-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
EXP -> PURINT	0.089	0.099	0.044	0.172

Structural Model

LEGETEXP - PURINT

Constructs: R-square
 Inner model: Path coefficients and p values
 Outer model: P values
 Highlight paths: off
 Zoom (100%)

Constructs: R-square
 Inner model: Path coefficients and t values
 Outer model: P values
 Highlight paths: off
 Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values Zoom (110%)

[Copy to Excel](#) [Copy to R](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
LEGETEX -> PURINT	0.181	0.189	0.047	3.880	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
LEGETEX -> PURINT	0.181	0.189	0.007	0.092	0.268

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
LEGETEX -> PURINT	0.181	0.189	0.102	0.281

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURINT	0.033	0.031

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.033	0.038	0.018	1.846	0.065

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.033	0.038	0.005	0.008	0.072

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.033	0.038	0.011	0.079

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.031	0.036	0.018	1.721	0.085

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.031	0.036	0.005	0.006	0.070

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.031	0.036	0.008	0.077

f-square - Matrix

	LEGETEX	PURINT
LEGETEX		0.034
PURINT		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics ((O/STDEV))	P values
LEGETEX -> PURINT	0.034	0.040	0.020	1.737	0.082

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
LEGETEX -> PURINT	0.034	0.189	0.155	-0.142	-0.142

f-square - Confidence intervals

Zoom (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
LEGETEX -> PURINT	0.034	0.040	0.011	0.086

SOCEXP - PURINT

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and p values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and t values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values [Zoom \(110%\)](#) [Copy to Excel](#) [Copy to R](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
SOCEX -> PURINT	0.289	0.293	0.050	5.727	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected [Zoom \(107%\)](#) [Copy to E](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
SOCEX -> PURINT	0.289	0.293	0.004	0.181	0.380

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals [Zoom \(122%\)](#) [Copy to Excel](#) [Copy to](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
SOCEX -> PURINT	0.289	0.293	0.192	0.389

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURINT	0.083	0.081

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.083	0.089	0.030	2.822	0.005

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.083	0.089	0.005	0.033	0.144

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.083	0.089	0.037	0.152

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.081	0.087	0.030	2.747	0.006

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.081	0.087	0.005	0.031	0.143

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.081	0.087	0.035	0.150

f-square - Matrix

	PURINT	SOCEX
PURINT		
SOCEX	0.091	

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
SOCEX -> PURINT	0.091	0.098	0.036	2.512	0.012

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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Co

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
SOCEX -> PURINT	0.091	0.293	0.202	0.085	0.085

f-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
SOCEX -> PURINT	0.091	0.098	0.038	0.179

ENEXP - PURINT

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and p values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and t values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values [Zoom \(110%\)](#) [Copy to Excel](#) [Copy to R](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ENVEX -> PURINT	0.252	0.257	0.050	5.003	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected [Zoom \(107%\)](#) [Copy to R](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ENVEX -> PURINT	0.252	0.257	0.005	0.148	0.344

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals [Zoom \(122%\)](#) [Copy to Excel](#) [Copy to R](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ENVEX -> PURINT	0.252	0.257	0.159	0.355

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURINT	0.064	0.061

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.064	0.069	0.026	2.432	0.015

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.064	0.069	0.005	0.022	0.119

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.064	0.069	0.025	0.126

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.061	0.067	0.026	2.347	0.019

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.061	0.067	0.005	0.020	0.117

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.061	0.067	0.023	0.124

f-square - Matrix

	ENVEX	PURINT
ENVEX		0.068
PURINT		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ENVEX -> PURINT	0.068	0.075	0.031	2.210	0.027

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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Co

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ENVEX -> PURINT	0.068	0.257	0.189	0.077	0.077

f-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ENVEX -> PURINT	0.068	0.075	0.026	0.144

ATTI - PURINT

Outer model: P values | Inner model: Path coefficients and p values | Constructs: R-square | Highlight paths: off

Zoom (100%)

Outer model: P values | Inner model: Path coefficients and t values | Constructs: R-square | Highlight paths: off

Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values | Zoom (102%) | Copy to Excel | Copy to R

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI -> PURIN	0.770	0.770	0.023	33.669	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected | Zoom (107%) | Copy

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI -> PURINT	0.770	0.770	0.000	0.719	0.810

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals | Zoom (122%) | Copy to Excel | Cop

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI -> PURINT	0.770	0.770	0.722	0.812

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURIN	0.593	0.592

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.593	0.594	0.035	16.895	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.593	0.594	0.001	0.517	0.656

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.593	0.594	0.521	0.659

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.592	0.593	0.035	16.832	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.592	0.593	0.001	0.516	0.655

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.592	0.593	0.520	0.658

f-square - Matrix

	ATTI	PURIN
ATTI		1.457
PURIN		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ATTI -> PURINT	1.457	1.480	0.216	6.753	0.000

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI -> PURINT	1.457	0.770	-0.687	0.676	0.676

f-square - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ATTI -> PURINT	1.457	1.480	1.087	1.934

INTATTR - PURINT

Outer model: P values | Inner model: Path coefficients and p values | Constructs: R-square | Highlight paths: off

Zoom (100%)

Outer model: P values | Inner model: Path coefficients and t values | Constructs: R-square | Highlight paths: off

Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (102%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
INTATTR -> PURIN	0.413	0.415	0.042	9.898	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
INTATTR -> PURINT	0.413	0.415	0.002	0.321	0.489

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
INTATTR -> PURINT	0.413	0.415	0.330	0.496

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURIN	0.171	0.169

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.171	0.174	0.034	4.962	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.171	0.174	0.003	0.103	0.239

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.171	0.174	0.109	0.246

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.169	0.173	0.035	4.898	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.169	0.173	0.003	0.101	0.237

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.169	0.173	0.107	0.244

f-square - Matrix

	INTATTR	PURIN
INTATTR		0.206
PURIN		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
INTATTR -> PURINT	0.206	0.213	0.051	4.031	0.000

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
INTATTR -> PURINT	0.206	0.415	0.209	0.218	0.218

f-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
INTATTR -> PURINT	0.206	0.213	0.123	0.326

Structural Model

PERVAL - PURINT

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (90%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PERVAL -> PURIN	0.527	0.530	0.037	14.174	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

Copy to E

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PERVAL -> PURINT	0.527	0.530	0.003	0.446	0.593

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PERVAL -> PURINT	0.527	0.530	0.455	0.601

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURIN	0.278	0.276

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.278	0.283	0.039	7.069	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.278	0.283	0.005	0.199	0.351

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.278	0.283	0.207	0.361

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.276	0.281	0.039	7.013	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.276	0.281	0.005	0.197	0.350

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.276	0.281	0.205	0.359

f-square - Matrix

	PERVAL	PURIN
PERVAL		0.385
PURIN		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
PERVAL -> PURINT	0.385	0.398	0.078	4.956	0.000

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PERVAL -> PURINT	0.385	0.530	0.146	0.374	0.374

f-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PERVAL -> PURINT	0.385	0.398	0.261	0.565

Structural Model

EMOPEVAL - PURINT

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and p values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and t values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values Zoom (110%) Copy to Excel Copy to R

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
EMOPEVAL -> PURINT	0.556	0.557	0.039	14.276	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected Zoom (107%) Copy to Excel

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
EMOPEVAL -> PURINT	0.556	0.557	0.002	0.468	0.625

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals Zoom (122%) Copy to Excel Copy to R

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
EMOPEVAL -> PURINT	0.556	0.557	0.476	0.629

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURINT	0.309	0.307

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.309	0.312	0.043	7.159	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.309	0.312	0.003	0.219	0.390

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.309	0.312	0.227	0.396

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.307	0.310	0.043	7.107	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.307	0.310	0.003	0.217	0.389

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.307	0.310	0.225	0.394

f-square - Matrix

	EMOPEVAL	PURINT
EMOPEVAL		0.446
PURINT		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
EMOPEVAL -> PURINT	0.446	0.459	0.093	4.821	0.000

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
EMOPEVAL -> PURINT	0.446	0.557	0.111	0.388	0.388

f-square - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
EMOPEVAL -> PURINT	0.446	0.459	0.293	0.655

Structural Model

SOCPEVAL - PURINT

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and p values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and t values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values Zoom (110%) Copy to Excel Copy to R

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
SOCPEVAL -> PURINT	0.381	0.384	0.045	8.473	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected Zoom (107%) Copy to Excel

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
SOCPEVAL -> PURINT	0.381	0.384	0.002	0.286	0.465

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals Zoom (122%) Copy to Excel Copy to R

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
SOCPEVAL -> PURINT	0.381	0.384	0.292	0.470

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURINT	0.145	0.143

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.145	0.149	0.034	4.224	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.145	0.149	0.004	0.082	0.216

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.145	0.149	0.085	0.221

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom](#) (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.143	0.147	0.034	4.160	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom](#) (107%)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.143	0.147	0.004	0.080	0.214

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom](#) (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.143	0.147	0.083	0.219

f-square - Matrix

	PURINT	SOCPEVAL
PURINT		
SOCPEVAL	0.170	

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
SOCPEVAL -> PURINT	0.170	0.177	0.048	3.518	0.000

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
SOCPEVAL -> PURINT	0.170	0.384	0.214	0.151	0.151

f-square - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
SOCPEVAL -> PURINT	0.170	0.177	0.093	0.283

EPISPEVAL - PURINT

Constructs

R-square

Inner model

Path coefficients and p values

Outer model

P values

Highlight paths

off

Zoom (100%)

Constructs

R-square

Inner model

Path coefficients and t values

Outer model

P values

Highlight paths

off

Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O /STDEV)	P values
EPISPEVAL -> PURINT	0.419	0.421	0.045	9.371	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
EPISPEVAL -> PURINT	0.419	0.421	0.002	0.328	0.501

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
EPISPEVAL -> PURINT	0.419	0.421	0.333	0.506

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURINT	0.175	0.174

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.175	0.179	0.038	4.668	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.175	0.179	0.004	0.107	0.251

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

[Copy to Excel](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.175	0.179	0.111	0.256

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.174	0.178	0.038	4.609	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.174	0.178	0.004	0.105	0.249

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

[Copy to Excel](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.174	0.178	0.109	0.254

f-square - Matrix

	EPISPEVAL	PURINT
EPISPEVAL		0.213
PURINT		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
EPISPEVAL -> PURINT	0.213	0.221	0.057	3.741	0.000

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
EPISPEVAL -> PURINT	0.213	0.421	0.208	0.210	0.210

f-square - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
EPISPEVAL -> PURINT	0.213	0.221	0.125	0.343

ENVIPEVAL - PURINT

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and p values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Constructs R-square **Inner model** Path coefficients and t values **Outer model** P values **Highlight paths** off
 Zoom (100%)

Path coefficients - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values Zoom (110%) Copy to Excel Copy to R

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ENVIPEVAL -> PURINT	0.377	0.379	0.047	8.077	0.000

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals bias corrected Zoom (107%) Copy to Excel

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ENVIPEVAL -> PURINT	0.377	0.379	0.002	0.281	0.465

Path coefficients - Confidence intervals Zoom (122%) Copy to Excel Copy to R

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ENVIPEVAL -> PURINT	0.377	0.379	0.284	0.468

R-square - Overview

	R-square	R-square adjusted
PURINT	0.142	0.140

R-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.142	0.145	0.035	4.023	0.000

R-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.142	0.145	0.004	0.079	0.217

R-square - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.142	0.145	0.081	0.219

R-square adjusted - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

[Zoom \(110%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PURINT	0.140	0.144	0.035	3.961	0.000

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals bias corrected

[Zoom \(107%\)](#)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.140	0.144	0.004	0.077	0.215

R-square adjusted - Confidence intervals

[Zoom \(122%\)](#)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
PURINT	0.140	0.144	0.079	0.217

f-square - Matrix

	ENVIPEVAL	PURINT
ENVIPEVAL		0.165
PURINT		

f-square - Mean, STDEV, T values, p values

Zoom (110%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
ENVIPEVAL -> PURINT	0.165	0.172	0.049	3.358	0.001

f-square - Confidence intervals bias corrected

Zoom (107%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Bias	2.5%	97.5%
ENVIPEVAL -> PURINT	0.165	0.379	0.213	0.203	0.203

f-square - Confidence intervals

Zoom (122%)

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	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	2.5%	97.5%
ENVIPEVAL -> PURINT	0.165	0.172	0.088	0.281

MV prediction summary - Overview

Zoom (107%)

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	Q ² predict	PLS-SEM_RMSE	PLS-SEM_MAE	LM_RMSE	LM_MAE
PURIN2	0.538	1.182	0.897	1.220	0.921
PURIN3	0.564	1.211	0.903	1.234	0.939
PURIN1	0.401	1.302	0.982	1.348	1.010

MV prediction summary - PLS-SEM prediction error (descriptives)

Zoom (62%)

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	Mean	Median	Observed min	Observed max	Standard deviation	Excess kurtosis	Skewness	Number of observations used	Cramér-von Mises test statistic	Cramér-von Mises p value
PURIN2	0.002	0.051	-4.892	3.708	1.182	1.118	-0.400	4,530,000	2.169	0.000
PURIN3	0.002	0.118	-5.807	3.992	1.211	2.242	-0.676	4,530,000	4.882	0.000
PURIN1	0.002	0.145	-5.048	4.939	1.302	1.690	-0.463	4,530,000	4.779	0.000

CVPAT - PLS-SEM vs. Indicator average (IA)

Zoom (150%)

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	Average loss difference	t value	p value
PURIN	-1.552	9.352	0.000
Overall	-1.552	9.352	0.000

Appendix 6

One-way Analysis of Variance Test

Descriptives

PURIN	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Female	274	14.9234	4.75225	.28709	14.3582	15.4886	3.00	21.00
Male	173	14.4566	4.93618	.37529	13.7159	15.1974	3.00	21.00
Prefer not to answer	6	10.1667	4.99667	2.03988	4.9230	15.4103	5.00	18.00
Total	453	14.6821	4.84910	.22783	14.2344	15.1299	3.00	21.00

Tests of Homogeneity of Variances

PURIN		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
	Based on Median	.011	2	450	.989
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.011	2	434.368	.989
	Based on trimmed mean	.153	2	450	.858

ANOVA

PURIN	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	147.076	2	73.538	3.157	.043
Within Groups	10481.149	450	23.291		
Total	10628.225	452			

ANOVA Effect Sizes^{a,b}

PURIN		Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper
	Eta-squared	.014	.000	.040
	Epsilon-squared	.009	-.004	.035
	Omega-squared Fixed-effect	.009	-.004	.035
	Omega-squared Random-effect	.005	-.002	.018

a. Eta-squared and Epsilon-squared are estimated based on the fixed-effect model.

b. Negative but less biased estimates are retained, not rounded to zero.

Post Hoc Tests

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: PURIN

	(I) GenderN	(J) GenderN	Mean Difference (I- J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
LSD	Female	Male	.46671	.46866	.320	-.4543	1.3877
		Prefer not to answer	4.75669*	1.99171	.017	.8425	8.6709
	Male	Female	-.46671	.46866	.320	-1.3877	.4543
		Prefer not to answer	4.28998*	2.00413	.033	.3514	8.2286
	Prefer not to answer	Female	-4.75669*	1.99171	.017	-8.6709	-.8425
		Male	-4.28998*	2.00413	.033	-8.2286	-.3514
Hochberg	Female	Male	.46671	.46866	.685	-.6564	1.5898
		Prefer not to answer	4.75669	1.99171	.051	-.0162	9.5295
	Male	Female	-.46671	.46866	.685	-1.5898	.6564
		Prefer not to answer	4.28998	2.00413	.095	-.5126	9.0926
	Prefer not to answer	Female	-4.75669	1.99171	.051	-9.5295	.0162
		Male	-4.28998	2.00413	.095	-9.0926	.5126

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Homogeneous Subsets

		PURIN	
GenderN	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Hochberg ^{a,b}	Prefer not to answer	6	10.1667
	Male	173	14.4566
	Female	274	14.9234
	Sig.		1.000

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 17.036.

b. The group sizes are unequal. The harmonic mean of the group sizes is used. Type I error levels are not guaranteed.